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_ leading the future of learning

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_ Leading the Future of Learning

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Message Of Limassol

Leading The Future Of Learning

As we conclude the I-HE2024 conference, we find ourselves at the forefront of transformative shifts in education, driven by rapid advancements in digital technology, new pedagogical strategies, and an evolving understanding of learner needs. Throughout the sessions, we have explored these shifts through a variety of lenses, each contributing to a more holistic view of how education must adapt to remain relevant, inclusive, and impactful in the 21st century.

A recurring theme of the conference has been the significant **role of artificial intelligence (AI) and big data in revolutionising education**. As discussed in several sessions, AI presents both opportunities and challenges. On one hand, AI and learning analytics allow for personalised learning experiences, helping educators to identify specific learning needs, track student progress, and provide timely interventions. Tools like automated grading, real-time feedback, and adaptive learning systems are already reshaping how students engage with content. However, we must also be mindful of ethical concerns such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and equitable access to technology. It was clear from the discussions that embracing AI requires balancing innovation with transparency and responsibility.

Lifelong learning was highlighted in several sessions as a central theme of this conference. With the European Union's goal of 60% adult participation in lifelong learning by 2030, institutions must rethink how they deliver education beyond traditional degree programs. The rise of micro-credentials, as discussed in the panel on "Scaling Lifelong Learning through Digital Pathways", is crucial for offering flexible, accessible, and modular learning opportunities that cater to diverse learners. **Micro-credentials** not only provide tangible recognition for skills acquired but also create a more inclusive landscape for learners at different stages of their careers or life paths. These credentials were identified as key to bridging the gap between formal education and the constantly evolving demands of the labour market.

Another important takeaway from the conference was the need to **ensure that education remains accessible to all learners**, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds or with special needs. The session on "Inclusive Digital Learning Environments" reinforced the necessity of designing educational models that support accessibility, including the use of assistive technologies and inclusive pedagogies. Inclusive design, coupled with flexible learning pathways, will help reduce barriers and ensure that every learner, regardless of their background, can thrive in a digital-first educational system.

Personalised learning emerged as a focal point, particularly in discussions around tailoring education to individual needs while maintaining academic standards. Presenters highlighted how AI and learning analytics can help educators design more dynamic, responsive educational experiences that engage learners based on their unique strengths and weaknesses. Yet, as noted during the session "Balancing Personalisation with Standards in Higher Education", this personalisation must ensure that all learners reach the same core outcomes, even if the path they take is different. Maintaining a balance between personalisation and equity is critical to ensuring both high standards and inclusivity.

One of the most poignant discussions throughout the conference was the emphasis on mental wellbeing. The challenges faced by both students and staff in the context of online, open, and distance education were explored in depth during the session on "Mental Wellbeing in the Digital Age". Speakers brought attention to issues such as burnout, isolation, and the emotional toll of the digital divide. Addressing these challenges is essential not only for fostering student success but also for creating sustainable, supportive environments for educators. The strategies proposed, such as fostering a sense of community through online platforms and improving institutional support for both students and staff, were widely acknowledged as crucial for improving retention rates in digital learning.

Retention and Student Success

Closely linked to mental wellbeing was the critical issue of student retention, particularly in online and distance learning settings. The session on "Retention Strategies in Open and Distance Education" highlighted that dropout rates in these environments can be as high as 50%, with many learners struggling due to personal challenges, workload pressures, or a lack of engagement. The importance of offering flexible learning pathways, proactive support structures, and smaller, manageable study modules was repeatedly stressed as a means of keeping students motivated and on track. Institutions must focus on creating structured, engaging, and supportive experiences to reduce dropout rates and promote student success.

Looking Forward

The discussions at I-HE2024 have demonstrated that the future of learning will be defined by its ability to be flexible, inclusive, and learner-centric. As we continue to embrace digital transformation, it is clear that technology will play a vital role in creating more personalised and adaptive learning environments. However, we must ensure that this future is built on a foundation of equity, transparency, and mental wellbeing, ensuring that no learner is left behind. The integration of AI, micro-credentials, and lifelong learning pathways presents tremendous opportunities, but only if we align these innovations with policies and practices that put learners first.

As we leave this conference, **the call to action is clear**: we must lead the future of learning by fostering environments that are not only technologically advanced but also human-centred. By focusing on the holistic needs of learners and educators, we can build an educational system that is resilient, inclusive, and equipped to meet the challenges of tomorrow.

Prof. dr. Theo Bastiaens

President of EADTU

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Online, Blended and Synchronous Hybrid Education

Blending Traditional and Online Approaches for Soft Skills Development in Higher Education

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Abstract

Soft skills are increasingly recognized as essential for student success in both academic and professional settings. To enhance soft skills development, this paper explores an integrative approach that blends traditional teaching methods with innovative technologies such as e-learning platforms, augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and gamification. These blended teaching methods create engaging, interactive environments that foster active learning and skill acquisition. Using the European project D-ChallengHE as a case study, we present a systematic methodology for designing instructional materials to improve soft skills. Central to this approach are key European competence frameworks—DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp—that provide a structured foundation for competency-based learning. Supported by the ADDIE instructional design model, our approach offers a scalable solution to closing the gap between education and employability by preparing students with the soft skills needed for future career success.

Keywords: soft skills development, blended learning, e-learning platforms, competency frameworks, instructional design

1. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving global economy, employers increasingly prioritize soft skills—such as communication, teamwork, problem-solving, adaptability, and emotional intelligence—over purely technical expertise. These skills are crucial not only for success in the classroom but also for long-term career progression. Despite their importance, many higher education institutions struggle to adequately integrate soft skills into their curricula, leading to a growing gap between the competences developed in academic settings and those required in the workforce. This soft skills gap represents a critical challenge for teachers and employers, as students often graduate with strong technical knowledge but lack the interpersonal and cognitive skills necessary for professional success.

The significance of addressing this gap lies in preparing students academically and holistically for the demands of modern workplaces. While traditional educational methods—such as group projects, classroom discussions, and role-playing activities—have long been used to develop soft skills, they may not fully engage today’s tech-savvy students. This is where the integration of emerging technologies comes into play. Combining traditional pedagogical approaches with cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and gamification creates a more dynamic, interactive, and personalized learning experience. These technologies enhance student engagement, foster active learning, and provide practical scenarios where students can develop and apply soft skills in virtual and real-world environments.

Our paper explores how blending traditional and online teaching methods can effectively close the soft skills gap in higher education. The research specifically focuses on integrating e-learning platforms, gamification, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Augmented Reality (AR) into conventional teaching practices. Key questions driving this research include: How can these blended approaches enhance the acquisition of critical soft skills? To what extent do competency frameworks such as DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp provide a structured basis for developing soft skills in educational settings? Furthermore, how can the ADDIE instructional design model be employed to create educational materials that foster the acquisition of soft skills? Through the European project D-ChallengHE case study, this paper examines these blended learning methods' theoretical and practical applications in fostering essential skills for the modern workforce.

2. Literature Review

Technology integration into soft skills development has gained substantial attention in recent years, with various studies examining the impact of e-learning platforms, gamification, artificial intelligence, and augmented reality on student engagement and competency acquisition. Previous research has demonstrated the potential of these technologies to enhance interactive learning environments, thereby facilitating soft skills development. For example, Laurillard (2013) and Bates (2015) have shown how e-learning platforms can create flexible and adaptive learning experiences, allowing students to practice problem-solving, communication, and teamwork. Similarly, studies by Deterding et al. (2011) and Siemens and Baker (2012) highlight how gamification and AI-driven assessments can foster collaboration and critical thinking by offering real-time feedback and personalized learning paths.

However, many of these studies focus primarily on individual technologies and their isolated impact on skill development. They need an integrated or blended approach that combines traditional pedagogical methods with advanced technological tools. In contrast, this paper's approach emphasizes the fusion of traditional classroom teaching with cutting-edge technologies, such as AI, AR, and gamification, within the framework of structured competency models like DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp. This integrative approach fosters soft skills in a dynamic, technology-enabled environment and ensures alignment with well-established competency standards that guide the design and evaluation of learning experiences (Huang et al., 2019).

Unlike other methodologies, which may focus on technology-driven skill acquisition alone, our approach underscores the importance of blending these technologies with traditional teaching practices. By doing so, it addresses the limitations of both methods—ensuring the human element of teaching is preserved while leveraging the power of technological innovation to enhance active learning. This study also differentiates itself by employing the ADDIE model, which offers a systematic and iterative framework for instructional design, ensuring that the development of soft skills is embedded into the curriculum from analysis to evaluation (Bates, 2015).

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Soft Skills in Higher Education

Soft skills, frequently referred to as interpersonal or non-technical skills, are essential proficiencies that facilitate successful communication, environment adaptation, and problem-solving in various contexts. These abilities complement technical knowledge in higher education and help students be ready for the more dynamic and collaborative needs of the modern workforce and academic success. Collaboration, flexibility, and human-centered problem-solving are key in professional settings; therefore, soft skills like communication, teamwork, leadership, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence are vital (Robles, 2012).

The demand for soft skills in the labor market has steadily increased as industries recognize that technical expertise alone is insufficient for long-term success. Employers across sectors prioritize candidates who can effectively collaborate, manage conflicts, lead teams, and adapt to new challenges. As a result, higher education institutions are re-evaluating their curricula to ensure students develop these essential skills alongside their technical abilities. Traditional education methods often focus on rote memorization and individual performance and may not fully address the need for active engagement in situations that build these interpersonal competences (Andrews & Higson, 2008).

Even though their significance is acknowledged, teaching and evaluating soft skills can be more difficult and complex than teaching technical abilities. They need frequent feedback, reflective practices, and experiential learning to reach their full potential. To address these issues, universities are adding more case studies, collaborative projects, and problem-based learning to their curricula. To ensure that students are ready for both online and in-person professional situations, institutions are also investigating novel approaches to develop soft skills in virtual environments because of the growing usage of digital platforms in education (Jackson, 2010).

Not only is the inclusion of soft skills in higher education a response to the changing needs of the labor market, but it also acknowledges the importance of these talents for lifelong learning. Students' need for critical thinking, good communication, and teamwork increases as they encounter more challenging social, technological, and environmental issues. To ensure that students graduate from higher education institutions with a well-rounded skill set that can meet the demands of the modern world, it is their twin responsibility to promote both academic knowledge and these crucial soft skills (Jorre de St Jorre and Oliver, 2018).

3.2 Traditional and Technological Teaching Approaches

Traditional teaching methods, which mostly rely on in-person interactions, lectures, and textbook-based learning, have been replaced in the progression of education by a more dynamic and adaptable approach that integrates contemporary technologies. Conventional teaching methods are suitable for teaching the basics but could be better at developing soft skills like teamwork, communication, critical thinking, and flexibility. These methods frequently emphasise knowledge transmission, in which students take in information passively. This reduces the opportunity for active learning, problem-solving, or collaboration—critical for developing soft skills—in students (Laurillard, 2013).

Conversely, technology-based teaching methods present fresh chances to involve students in personalized, interactive, and hands-on learning. The advent of e-learning platforms, virtual simulations, gamified learning experiences, and AI-driven exams has transformed how students gain and apply knowledge. These technologies make Active learning environments possible, where students are urged to work together,

participate in conversations, solve problems, and get immediate feedback. Furthermore, technology-enabled learning settings are flexible, enabling students to access resources anytime and from any location. This promotes self-directed learning and adaptation, two essential soft skills (Bates, 2015).

By actively involving students in simulated real-world scenarios, technological technologies like AR and gamification encourage students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts. For instance, students participate in cooperative or competitive activities that foster leadership, teamwork, and decision-making through gamified learning experiences. Similarly, AR enables students to engage with virtual surroundings and items replicating real-world problems, forcing them to communicate, exercise critical thought, and adjust their action plans instantly. According to Deterding et al. (2011), immersive experiences offer a more practical approach to education, allowing students to hone their soft skills in ways that traditional techniques frequently cannot.

Technology-based methods come with difficulties, however. An over-reliance on technology risks undermining the human components of education, like empathy, interpersonal communication, and mentoring. Therefore, it is crucial to balance traditional and technological approaches to guarantee that students receive the one-on-one mentoring and interactive learning opportunities required to develop complete soft skills. The most successful teaching techniques frequently incorporate a blended learning model, in which technology is used to supplement conventional teaching techniques so that students can gain from both approaches' advantages (Graham, 2006).

4. Methodology

4.1 Frameworks for Competences Development

Competency frameworks are crucial when designing educational programs to improve students' abilities, knowledge, and attitudes. These frameworks offer a consistent method for identifying and assessing competences, which makes them especially essential in higher education, where the development of soft skills is of greatest importance (Panagiotakopoulos et al., 2024). We present four key European frameworks, DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp, that provide detailed guidelines for developing and evaluating competences associated with environmental sustainability, entrepreneurship, digital literacy, and life skills, respectively (Mulder, 2012).

It is commonly acknowledged that the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp) outlines the competences required to use digital technology efficiently. It addresses problem-solving, safety, digital content creation, communication and teamwork, and information and data literacy. DigComp offers a basis for incorporating digital tools into the learning process in developing soft skills, allowing students to master technical skills and effectively collaborate, think critically, and solve problems in digital environments (Carretero et al., 2017). Furthermore, DigComp has been widely recognized as a unique framework for students, teachers, instructional designers, and adult education providers (Lazarinis et al., 2024). It serves as a detailed guide for designing, assessing, and enhancing educational programs that align with the competences needed in today's digital age (Spyropoulou et al., 2024).

By placing a strong emphasis on creativity, innovation, and strategic thinking, the Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp) promotes an entrepreneurial attitude. This approach makes promoting initiative, self-efficacy, and the capacity for uncertainty navigation—skills essential to contemporary soft skills education—possible. Teachers can assist students in gaining the self-assurance and flexibility required for personal and professional development by implementing EntreComp (Lackéus, 2015).

A more detailed approach is taken by the Life Competence Framework (LifeComp), which focuses on social, emotional, and cognitive competences that support people's capacity to interact with others and prosper in various challenging contexts. Since LifeComp focuses on essential components of emotional intelligence and interpersonal abilities, including self-regulation, empathy, teamwork, and communication, it is especially pertinent to teaching soft skills (Sala et al., 2020).

Finally, the recently unveiled Green Competence Framework (GreenComp) recommends incorporating environmental sustainability into teaching. GreenComp emphasizes ecological awareness above all else, but it also strengthens soft skills like critical thinking, flexibility, and ethical responsibility—qualities that are becoming increasingly important in today's globalized, environmentally conscious workforce (Lozano et al., 2017).

4.2 ADDIE Model Application

Our study proposes and utilises the ADDIE instructional design approach to ensure the systematic and efficient development of educational materials to enhance soft skills. The acronym for the five essential phases of instructional design is ADDIE, which stands for Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. This model helps create curriculum in an organized and iterative manner, allowing teachers to carefully plan, design, and evaluate the learning experiences that promote the acquisition of soft skills (Branch, 2009).

Figure 1: ADDIE Model application steps

The following five steps of the ADDIE instructional design approach will be described: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation.

- Analysis

The ADDIE approach is built upon the analysis phase, which thoroughly assesses the target audience, learning objectives, and educational needs. Using the competency frameworks, the essential soft skills to be cultivated in this phase include communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and adaptability. The learning environment is also examined to ascertain whether conventional, digital, or blended approaches will best convey the material. The results of this phase direct the design and development procedures in later stages, guaranteeing

that the instructional materials are customized to fit the needs of students and institutional objectives (Gagne et al., 2005).

- Design

The plan for the instructional materials is created during the design process. This entails deciding on suitable teaching tactics, developing the course structure, and specifying precise learning objectives. At this point, combining conventional and technological methods improves involvement and engagement. A dynamic and engaging learning environment is produced by fusing traditional teaching techniques with technologies like gamification, AI-driven assessments, and e-learning platforms. Furthermore, learning objectives should be matched with the competences listed in DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp to guarantee that students meet academic requirements and acquire practical abilities for use in the real world (Reigeluth, 2013).

- Development

Creating instructional materials using the design blueprint is the primary goal of the development phase. This entails creating learning modules, evaluation tools, and multimedia content to aid in developing soft skills. To promote problem-solving and teamwork, for example, digital simulations, role-playing games, and cooperative projects are created. To guarantee a well-rounded learning experience, traditional materials—such as textbooks and in-person activities—and technology-based resources are developed per the blended approach. The content is regularly evaluated and improved throughout this stage to meet the learning objectives (Gibbons, 2013).

- Implementation

The delivery of the contents to the students in the classroom constitutes the implementation phase, which follows the development of the resources. Instructors, administrators, and IT staff must often coordinate during this phase to guarantee a seamless transition from development to real-world application. This phase involves implementing the blended learning strategy, which uses both digital and classroom-based learning resources. To gauge their proficiency in the targeted soft skills, students take part in tests, participate in various learning activities, and are introduced to the resources. Feedback from teachers and students is gathered regularly to find areas that need improvement or adjustment (Clark and Mayer, 2023).

- Evaluation

The efficacy of the instructional materials and the entire learning process are evaluated during the evaluation phase of the ADDIE paradigm. There are two stages of evaluation: formative and summative. Formative assessment is a continual process that gathers feedback to improve the materials throughout the design and development phases. Following implementation, a summative assessment is carried out to determine whether the learning objectives were satisfied and whether the students could acquire the desired soft skills. Data about students and teachers is gathered through surveys, interviews, and performance evaluations. The evaluation of this input yields information about the instructional materials' advantages and disadvantages and suggestions for future development (Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick, 2006).

5. Blending Traditional and Technological Approaches

5.1 Integration of E-learning Platforms

Because e-learning platforms offer dynamic, adaptable, and scalable learning environments, they have entirely changed the face of education. These platforms are beneficial for integrating into the development of soft skills because they let students interact with the material at their speed, work together on projects, and get immediate feedback. Developing problem-solving, collaboration, and communication, all depend on these abilities. Students with different learning styles and preferences can flourish in an inclusive atmosphere provided by the synchronous and asynchronous learning opportunities provided by e-learning platforms (Hrastinski, 2008).

Offering a vast range of multimedia tools, including interactive tests, discussion boards, video lectures, and virtual simulations, is one of the main benefits of e-learning platforms. These tools are intended to increase participation and offer various educational opportunities that promote the development of soft skills. For example, e-learning systems' role-playing exercises and group projects allow students to practice decision-making, leadership, and interpersonal communication in a safe yet dynamic environment. These platforms also help students enhance their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities by letting them go through difficulties, study case studies, and get quick feedback on how they did (Bates, 2019).

Another key feature of e-learning platforms is the capability to track student progress and personalize learning experiences. Through learning analytics, teachers can monitor students' interactions, assess their performance, and identify areas where additional support is needed. This data-driven approach ensures that educational content can be adapted to meet individual learning needs, making the process of soft skills development more effective and targeted. Furthermore, gamified elements within e-learning platforms—such as badges, leader boards, and rewards—motivate students to engage actively with the material and collaborate with their peers, reinforcing individual and group-oriented soft skills (Deterding et al., 2011).

E-learning platforms supplement traditional classroom training in a blended learning environment by allowing students to develop and apply soft skills in virtual situations. By integrating these platforms, educators may provide learning opportunities for students outside the classroom. Students will have constant access to digital content and interactive activities that will help them improve their abilities. Combining in-person and virtual instruction guarantees a thorough approach to developing soft skills, meeting the requirements of contemporary higher education and equipping students for the changing workforce expectations (Graham, 2006).

5.2 Gamification, Artificial Intelligence, and Augmented Reality

Incorporating cutting-edge technology like AR, AI, and gamification into higher education has completely changed how soft skills are taught in recent years. These technologies improve traditional teaching approaches by producing immersive, personalized, and interactive learning experiences that engage students more effectively and enable more profound skill development. With these resources, teachers may give students cutting-edge opportunities to practice the skills of leadership, communication, problem-solving, and adaptation—all of which are essential for success in both the classroom and the workplace (Garrison, 2016).

Applying game-design components to educational settings, such as leaderboards, point systems, challenges, and prizes, is known as gamification. Students are more likely to take initiative, interact with the material, and actively participate in group projects when learning feels like a game. Gamification encourages healthy rivalry and collaboration, which helps kids develop their resilience and social skills as they work toward specific objectives. Students can practice problem-solving and decision-making in a secure and controlled environment

by using role-playing games or challenge-based simulations, which can replicate real-life professional scenarios (Clark and Mayer, 2023).

Personalized learning and adaptive learning are made possible in large part by AI. Systems powered on AI can evaluate how pupils learn, spot knowledge gaps, and offer customized feedback and improvement suggestions. Soft skill development is made possible by this technology, which provides personalized learning routes that adjust to the needs and success of each learner. AI-driven chatbots mimic discussions, giving kids chances to practice speaking and listening. Simultaneously, by dynamically modifying task complexity based on performance, AI-driven evaluations might enhance critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Siemens & Baker, 2012).

By superimposing digital data over the natural environment, augmented reality (AR) adds a new level of complexity to hands-on learning by enabling students to engage with both virtual and real-world objects at the same time. Because AR creates immersive settings that require students to collaborate, make decisions, and solve complicated problems in real time, it can be instrumental in helping students build soft skills. For instance, students can practice negotiation, dispute resolution, and cooperation in a highly engaging and realistic setting using AR-based simulations of group discussions or team projects. These encounters encourage hands-on learning and a deeper understanding of the practical application of soft skills.

In a mixed-learning setting, gamification, AI, and AR integration provides a potent arsenal for improving soft skills. Beyond the limitations of conventional approaches, these technologies enable more individualized, captivating, and interactive learning experiences (Iatreli et al, 2024). By incorporating them into the curriculum, teachers can better prepare students for the demands of the modern workplace—where flexibility, teamwork, and communication are critical. According to Deterding et al. (2011), this technology-based strategy guarantees that students acquire the theoretical information required for their studies and the valuable soft skills to help them in their future employment.

6. Case Study: D-ChallengHE Project

6.1 Project Summary: D-ChallengHE and Its Impact on Digital Education

D-ChallengHE¹ is an innovative initiative designed to enhance the landscape of higher education (HE) by strategically integrating digital technologies—the project aimed to spotlight professors' and university staff's experiences and competences in digital fields. By disseminating best practices in online learning, the digitalization of educational content, and training for both online and blended learning, D-ChallengHE sought to facilitate a transformative educational environment that embraced the challenges and opportunities of the digital age.

One of the primary goals of D-ChallengHE was to establish a generative network that connected universities, research centers, training institutions, and enterprises. This collaborative framework was pivotal for fostering engagement in the ongoing digital transformation within higher education. By bringing together diverse stakeholders, the project shared insights, resources, and methodologies that drove innovation and improved the quality of educational experiences for students and faculty alike.

In addition to promoting collaboration, D-ChallengHE emphasized the importance of cultivating a digital culture within educational institutions. Recognizing the systemic complexity of digital technologies in the education system, the project advocated for a comprehensive understanding of how these technologies could

¹ <https://d-challenghe.unilink.it/>

enhance teaching and learning processes. This involved adopting new tools and platforms and fostering an environment that encouraged continuous learning and adaptation among educators and students.

Ultimately, D-ChallengHE aspired to create a robust framework for digital transformation in higher education, equipping institutions to better respond to the evolving needs of learners and the demands of the contemporary workforce. Through its multifaceted approach, the project empowered educators, enhanced digital competencies, and promoted a culture of innovation that aimed to drive the future of education in a digital world.

The purpose of this program was to assess the efficacy of a blended learning initiative created to improve the online teaching strategies employed by teachers in higher education. Blended learning integrates traditional face-to-face classroom procedures with online learning activities, allowing students to access content asynchronously while participating in real-time interactions. The ability to teach effectively online requires knowledge of various digital tools, including virtual classrooms, learning management systems, and collaborative tools, in addition to pedagogical strategies that maintain student engagement in an online setting. This entails creating varied learning paths, giving prompt feedback, and ensuring digital tools enhance human contact rather than take its place (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008).

E-learning standards denote a change from solely content-driven online education techniques by paying greater attention to the qualitative components of human connection. It emphasizes how crucial social and emotional learning components are, including empathy, teamwork, and the growth of interpersonal skills. An effective online education replicates the kinds of interpersonal interactions commonly observed in traditional classroom settings by providing opportunities for students to collaborate, solve issues, and have reflective conversations. In addition to acknowledging the diversity of students' experiences, human-centered e-learning promotes inclusivity and addresses problems like accessibility and digital equity. Teachers are urged to employ strategies that assist in replicating the depth of conventional classroom engagement in a virtual environment, such as group discussions, peer cooperation, and interactive simulations (Salmon, 2013).

Teachers must embrace both pedagogical and technological changes to facilitate excellent blended learning and online teaching. This includes active learning, where students are kept interested through engagement in discussion boards, group projects, or interactive tests. Another crucial element is scaffolding and feedback, where giving pupils regular, helpful feedback allows them to progressively expand their knowledge. Teaching with emotional intelligence is also essential; this involves identifying the emotional needs of students, creating a safe and encouraging environment, and being flexible when faced with obstacles. Additionally, digital literacy is critical for both teachers and students to ensure effective communication and engagement with the course material, as highlighted by Laurillard (2013).

6.2 Structure of the program

The D-ChallengHE program initiative highlights the importance of digital capabilities in the knowledge society. This is accomplished by creating higher education policies for EU member states that are in line with the Education and Training 2020 agenda and the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027. Three courses were available during the program: 1. Online teaching methodologies, 2. Soft and Communication Skills for Digital Teaching, 3. Use of AI in Education. The training program included assignments and synchronous and asynchronous learning, and participants from Italy, Slovenia, Romania, Lithuania, and Greece.

Why You Should Enroll

The Reasons Why Mastering Online Teaching is Important

Figure 3: D-ChallengHE Course delivery webpage

Course	Number of Learning Units	Asynchronous hours (self-learning)	Assignment hours (practical work/tasks, final assessment)	TOT hours
Soft and Communication Skills for Digital Teaching	4	14	8	22
AI and Online Teaching: Traps and Opportunities	6	13	8	21
Online Teaching Methodologies	7	12	7	19

Figure 4: Training Course Delivery Plan

➤ **1. Online teaching methodologies**

As part of integrating traditional and technological approaches for soft skills development, the "Online Teaching Methodologies" e-course offers an example of how digital tools and innovative methods can enhance teaching practices. Designed to support higher education instructors, the course provides them with the necessary skills to combine advanced technologies with appropriate pedagogical techniques for creating interactive and collaborative online learning environments. By developing these competences, educators can foster soft skills such as communication, problem-solving, and teamwork in virtual settings, complementing traditional methods.

Throughout the course, participants were introduced to innovative instructional activities designed specifically for online learning environments. These activities emphasized collaboration, decision-making, and problem-solving—critical elements of soft skills development. The course employed a blended approach, incorporating hands-on tasks and peer collaboration. Participants shared resources, engaged in peer evaluations, and applied course concepts to real-world teaching scenarios. This interactive and reflective process allowed participants to engage with both the content and their peers actively, mirroring the collaborative nature of soft skills acquisition.

➤ **2. Soft and Communication Skills for Digital Teaching**

The Soft and Communication Skills for Digital Teaching e-course provided participants with the necessary tools to develop essential soft skills and communication competences for effective digital teaching. Recognizing that more than subject matter expertise is needed for maintaining student engagement in virtual environments, the course emphasized the importance of adaptability, empathy, and clear communication. Participants learned how to create a supportive and inclusive atmosphere in digital classrooms, where traditional physical cues and face-to-face dynamics are often absent. This focus on interpersonal skills is aimed at helping educators foster student engagement, maintain attention, and build meaningful relationships in a virtual context.

Participants engaged in various activities throughout the course to improve their digital communication techniques and soft skills. They worked on practical tasks such as offering clear instructions, managing group projects, and leading online discussions—all while fostering emotional intelligence and empathy. The course also emphasized strategies for maintaining student motivation and engagement, which are crucial in digital environments where distractions are common. By the end of the course, participants had developed vital skills to create dynamic and supportive online learning environments that encourage collaboration, problem-solving, and effective communication among students.

➤ 3. Use of AI in Education

The Use of AI in Education e-course gave participants the knowledge and skills to effectively integrate AI into digital teaching environments. The course emphasized how AI-powered tools can enhance personalized learning, streamline lesson planning, and improve learning outcomes. Throughout the course, participants explored various AI technologies, such as adaptive learning systems and AI-driven assessments, that support the development of critical soft skills like problem-solving and decision-making. The course also covered the broader implications of AI in education, encouraging participants to critically evaluate the ethical considerations associated with AI usage, including data privacy and potential biases.

During the course, participants engaged in hands-on activities to familiarize themselves with AI tools and platforms. They learned to create AI-driven lesson plans, utilize AI for data-driven assessments, and apply AI to adapt instructional materials to meet students' individual learning needs. Discussions around the ethical challenges of AI, such as fairness and transparency, were central to the course, ensuring that participants could apply AI responsibly in their teaching. By the end of the course, participants were equipped with practical skills to implement AI-driven strategies in their virtual classrooms, ultimately enhancing student engagement and improving learning outcomes.

6.3 Evaluation of the E-course Online Teaching Methodologies

The evaluation focused exclusively on participants of the Online Teaching Methodologies e-course, utilizing quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Quantitative data was collected through post-course surveys using a 5-point Likert scale to assess participants' views on course relevance, quality, and knowledge gained. Qualitative data was gathered through open-ended survey questions and interviews, providing deeper insights into the participants' experiences and the course's impact on their teaching methods. Statistical analysis was applied to the quantitative data, while thematic analysis was used to identify key insights from the qualitative responses.

Of the 79 registered participants, 72 completed the course (91.13%). Feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with nearly 100% agreeing that the content was relevant, well-structured, and applicable to their teaching

needs. Participants also appreciated the clarity of instructions, balanced workload, and the interactive synchronous sessions. The course improved their knowledge of online teaching practices and was highly practical, with participants expressing satisfaction and willingness to recommend it to others. These responses highlight the course's effectiveness in enhancing educators' digital teaching competences (Lazarinis et al., 2024).

Figure 5. Responses to learning process quality questions

7. Conclusions and Future Work

In our paper we have thoroughly examined the integration of traditional and online teaching methods to address the growing gap in soft skills development within higher education. Soft skills like communication, teamwork, critical thinking, and adaptability have become essential for students to thrive in academic and professional environments. However, traditional teaching methods often fail to engage students or fully foster these crucial skills. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies such as e-learning platforms, augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and gamification, we demonstrated how these approaches can create a more dynamic and interactive learning environment that supports the development of technical and interpersonal competences. These technologies enhance student engagement and provide real-world scenarios where soft skills can be applied and refined.

The integration of European competency frameworks—DigComp, EntreComp, LifeComp, and GreenComp—further underscores the importance of aligning educational strategies with well-established standards to ensure skill development. Through the D-ChallengHE project case study, we showed how these frameworks can be effectively employed to design competency-based learning materials that address both academic knowledge and soft skills. The use of the ADDIE model in instructional design proved essential in developing a structured, iterative process for creating learning experiences that actively promote soft skills acquisition. Our findings suggest that these blended approaches enhance learning outcomes and provide a scalable, adaptable model that can be implemented in various educational settings to prepare students for the demands of a rapidly changing workforce.

Despite the promising results, further research is necessary to understand how emerging technologies can continuously enhance soft skills acquisition. Future work should focus on expanding the evaluation of these blended learning approaches to a broader range of institutions and geographic regions, ensuring the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, empirical studies with longitudinal data could offer more insights into the long-term impact of integrating such technologies in higher education. Continued innovation in

teaching methods and the exploration of cutting-edge technologies like virtual reality and machine learning will be critical in evolving this approach, ultimately leading to a more holistic and adaptive educational ecosystem that bridges the gap between academic training and employability.

As higher education systems worldwide continue to evolve, the urgency to adopt blended approaches that integrate both traditional methods and emerging technologies is paramount. By embracing these innovative strategies, institutions can better equip students with the essential soft skills they need to navigate the complex challenges of the future workforce and thrive in an increasingly competitive global economy.

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Incorporating Metaverse Technology into the Adult Distance Learning Process for Open Universities

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Abstract

Metaverse, an emerging form of the World Wide Web, emerged from the technological developments of Web 3.0 and is expected to transform distance education, which is provided by both conventional and open universities. The purpose of the study is to investigate Metaverse as a technology to support distance education, with special reference to the Hellenic Open University (HOU). Through the HOU case study, models of utilization and development of this technology for academic institutions are identified. At the same time, the user experience is investigated through the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) model and the usability of educational virtual worlds in Metaverse Spatial.io through the System Usability Scale (SUS) model. The findings reveal the attractiveness and usability of these environments in supporting the educational process. As a result, specific Metaverse utilization and deployment models for distance education are proposed, as well as a strategic framework for the transition of academic institutions, such as HOU, to Metaverse, with measurable indicators to evaluate the success of this transition. Research findings indicate that Metaverse can provide significant benefits to distance education by enhancing student interaction and immersion in virtual learning environments.

Keywords: metaverse, open universities, distance education, virtual worlds, user experience, usability.

1. Introduction

Ongoing advancements in digital and internet technologies together with their growing incorporation into education has brought new possibilities and challenges for academic institutions. Metaverse may well be considered one of the latest and most exciting areas within the digital environment that allows participants to create virtual three-dimensional worlds where students can comfortably learn in real-time without temporal-spatial constraints (Mystakidis, 2022). In terms of education, the Metaverse can provide new effective approaches to a combined and distance learning where communication, cooperation, and application of the gained knowledge can occur in the framework of virtual online multi-user environments (Wang et al., 2022). As the Metaverse encompasses a vast of various possibilities for teaching and learning processes, it can be implemented in setting of traditional universities as well as the open universities like the Hellenic Open University (HOU). Since HOU is based mainly on distance education, the Metaverse can improve the potential to support online learning and sharing new interactive ideas in more creative and dynamic ways to both learners and instructors.

The main focus of this research is the examination of models for applying the Metaverse in higher education institutions considering the suitability of its inclusion into the educational process. The study focused on how Metaverse can be integrated into the Hellenic Open University or used individually as part of distance

education. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to provide insight into the proposed use of Metaverse in HOU while evaluating its use. At the same time, HOU's transition model to the Metaverse was explored and strategic directions were determined. These strategies include integrating principles into existing educational environments as well as creating an independent learning process.

In the present research, a combination of two important tools for evaluating user experience in Metaverse were used in parallel: the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) (Schrepp et al., 2014) and the System Usability Scale (SUS) (Klug, 2017). Through their application, data was collected and analyzed from students of a higher education department to determine their satisfaction and overall experience of using virtual worlds developed on the Metaverse Spatial.io platform (Spatial, 2024).

To date, Metaverse is not widely implemented as a learning environment in the field of education (Cai et al., 2022). Unlike many other applications, which mainly deal with face-to-face or blended learning, this study is dedicated exclusively to Metaverse, with an emphasis on distance education in open universities. This is an innovation, as it is going to look at a still unexplored and new technology – that of the Metaverse – and its possible use in the field of distance education that institutions will offer in the future. This gives a broad framework that may suit other tertiary institutions that may wish to follow this path.

This research mainly contributes to the investigation of the upgrading of distance education offered by universities such as Hellenic Open University by adopting Metaverse technology. Until now, the technologies that support distance education use, for example, video conferencing facilities, forums, and educational content that is not immersive. Metaverse integration changes this paradigm by presenting teaching examples that build real virtual learning environments that more realistically replicate the face-to-face form of education. This enhances the educational practices implemented, enhancing and enabling the use of additional simulations and situations that would not be possible in a traditional distance learning platform. The proposed framework also explores the use of Metaverse from its pedagogical dimension. The proposed framework guarantees that Metaverse technologies will not be applied to impress but to enhance and enrich distance education.

The research questions of this study are:

1. What are the models of utilization and development of the Metaverse that can support and strengthen distance education in traditional and open-type academic institutions such as HOU.
2. What is the framework for the strategic transition of academic institutions such as HOU to the Metaverse and how can it be successfully implemented.
3. What are the students' opinions about the educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse, according to their experiences and the usability of the virtual worlds in the Metaverse.

This study is organized in the following sections: in section 2 there is the theoretical background with reference to open universities and the Metaverse. Section 3 includes the research methodology, section 4 the findings and recommendations, section 5 the discussion and section 6 the conclusions.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Open Universities

Open universities are another form of universities that use the internet to provide distance education. They seek to provide an opportunity for adults of different backgrounds and ages to gain academic qualifications. The beginnings of open universities can be traced back to the external study system of the University of

London which was established in the year 1858. Open universities have developed rapidly by making use of computer and internet technologies (Open university, 2024). In open universities, the internet is the central technology for the transmission of knowledge but also for the development of skills through e-learning. This method of education has become very important as the dynamics of the labor market evolves towards flexible and remote working relationships. It has been observed that costs incurred in distance education are usually lower than conventional methods because no physical infrastructure is required and most courses are delivered electronically (Harvard Extension School, 2024). New multimedia technologies make it possible to develop effective educational modules at low cost, while the scalability of digital platforms also has a positive effect on academic organizations because it allows teaching a large number of students, resulting in lower per capita costs. In addition, one of the main benefits is the ease of access, because students do not need to come to classes and can study whenever they want, as they want and according to their personal schedule and commitments. This feature is quite important in today's demanding work schedule. Last but not least, online education uses advanced technologies, including virtual reality (VR), thus providing a more tangible and realistic feel to the learning experience that can increase student interest and distance learning effectiveness.

2.2 Hellenic Open University

"The Hellenic Open University (HOU) as a public Higher Education Institution, was founded in 1992 and is based in Patras. Important peculiarities of the university are the participation of students in the costs of their studies and distance education. The institution's mission is to provide undergraduate and postgraduate education and training, with the development and utilization of appropriate educational material and teaching methods for distance education . The purposes of the HOU also specify scientific research and the development of technology and methodology in the conceptual framework of distance education. The offer of studies is made exclusively by the method of distance teaching." (Hellenic Open University, 2024).

2.2.1 Educational Portal HOU

To facilitate distance education, the Hellenic Open University has developed an online educational portal (<http://portal.eap.gr/>). This portal includes the required electronic services to support distance education and is used, among other things, for distance training of Group Counseling Meetings (Tele-GCM), which take place within the thematic units of the HOU. HOU students use this educational portal to participate in group advisory meetings, attend lectures, participate in discussions, and interact with their professors and fellow students without the need for physical presence (HOU, 2013). Through this portal, the educational process becomes more flexible and accessible to students located in different parts of Greece or abroad. The portal offers opportunities for synchronous education through live meetings, storage of material for asynchronous study (e.g. video lectures), interactive tools (such as chats, quizzes, etc.) to enhance participation. The educational portal is HOU's main tool for supporting students in distance education supported by world wide web technologies.

2.3 Metaverse: The future internet

The evolution of the World Wide Web from its inception to the current vision of a decentralized Internet—commonly referred to as Web 3.0—marks a major transformation in digital interaction, comprising three distinct phases: Web 1.0, Web 2.0, and Web 3.0 (Nath et al., 2014). Web 1.0 that provided limited interactivity through the presentation of static web pages and information sharing was prominent in the 1990s. On the other hand, Web 2.0 provided a participatory environment that enabled users to create their

own content. This development made the web more dynamic and empowered individuals to create and share information. Web 3.0 or Web3 is the third generation of the World Wide Web which, among other things, offers the Metaverse as the future form of the Internet (Magetos et al., 2024a). Web 3.0 is the architectural model of the next generation of the Internet that offers even more value to users compared to Web 2.0. As the Internet evolved into Web 3.0, researchers began to investigate decentralization and user dominance of information by incorporating technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence. This phase seeks to remove the challenges of current web generations, and seeks to develop a user-oriented web that respects privacy, security and data ownership (Magetos et al., 2024b).

Metaverse because of these developments, defines a future with improved social networking and interactive economy offering innovative applications in areas such as education, entertainment, commerce, as well as health (Duan et al., 2021). Metaverse, a term derived from “meta” (meaning beyond) and “universe”, are multi-user 3D environments where through Avatars, who represent our digital virtual selves, we communicate and collaborate either synchronously or asynchronously, both with each other and with the content of the virtual worlds, in an environment shaped by artificial intelligence (AI) (Chamola et al., 2024). In Metaverse, we can do the same things that one does online with a more immersive and interactive experience, in which we don't just participate, but realistically experience virtual reality. The Metaverse is alternatively a mix of virtual reality, augmented reality and physical reality. It is a virtual, digital, 3D universe that blurs the lines between real and virtual life. Users will be able to buy or exchange land, buildings and other digital assets that exist in the Metaverse and explore the "space" using Avatars, which are essentially us, since each avatar will constitute a replica of the user's real appearance (Dionisio et al., 2013).

The Metaverse can be distinguished into four main categories, which represent different forms and technologies for interacting with virtual and real worlds: *Virtual Worlds*, where people get together with “Avatars” as they interact in 3D formats (Mystakidis, 2022). *Augmented Reality*, which overlays a real world environment with computer generated images or data on to the user interface environment. *Mirror Worlds*, being virtual or real world images. These worlds are used to model actual places or data such as “smart cities” and digital replicas of structures and cities. *Lifelogging* to refer to the capturing and archiving of users’ lives and activities using data from the mobile devices or from social media. Within the application of Education, Virtual Worlds and Augmented Reality have the highest number of application since there is great possibility for their effectiveness in improving the delivery of education (Kye et al., 2021).

Metaverse is a multi-dimensional digital reality which is developed through integrating various today’s modern technologies to provide better and more effective user experience. Some of the supporting technologies include Cloud and Edge Computing that offer the platform where data collected is processed and to allow a user access to rich content from any device (Mozumder et al., 2022). Edge Computing minimizes latency which means real time execution is more feasible at. Blockchain have brought security and transparency to transactions and the ownership of products through NFTs, and smart contracts bring automated agreements (Lnenicka et al., 2024). AI is prerequisite for the implementation of realistic virtual environments, effective 3D content for education, personalized learning, and constant data processing and translating. IoT links the physical with the virtual world where real physical objects are interfaced with virtual interactions; future technologies like 6G offer higher speeds improving real time interconnectivity. Sonic graphics using sophisticated game engines such as the Unreal Engine as well as the Unity engine, plus AR/VR devices provide an actual imitation of the environment, and interactive quality.

The devices used to enter the Metaverse (Park & Kim, 2022) are of varying levels of immersion, cost, and interaction capabilities. *Limited immersion* using computers that provide interaction with virtual environments using a screen (Desktop Virtual Worlds). While the overall experience is in a 3D virtual environment, input and output are performed strictly by keyboard, mouse or touch screen. *Mid-level immersion* with AR gear, with devices like HoloLens, which help provide a view of both the real and virtual worlds. The level is higher than the previous one which means a user is immersed to a greater extent. *Full immersion* with the help of VR headsets (such as Meta Quest, HTC Vive, Sony PlayStation VR, Valve Index) that immerse users in fully virtual worlds and interactions are made through control inputs and the sense of presence is highly felt. *High immersion* with other systems that include the concept of touch and mobility to make people almost feel like they are interacting with virtual realities (Lnenicka et al., 2024).

2.4 Metaverse in education

Virtual worlds in the form of the Metaverse hold great promise in the educational process, providing students and teachers with a platform to work in an environment that is fully customizable to meet various educational requirements. Virtual tours of the Metaverse allow students to experience immersive learning environments in an interactive and exploratory way. The Metaverse removes physical boundaries. Wherever we are as students, we can enter immersive environments for any number of reasons. Metaverse applications can transform e-learning (Chen, 2024), providing learners with a virtual place to browse, collaborate, and interact with other learners. Advances in virtual reality technology have been instrumental in paving the way for the Metaverse in education, with the continuous innovation and improvement of virtual reality equipment and applications greatly increasing the ability to create immersive and interactive virtual environments (Tlili et al., 2022). These advancements include high-resolution audio, realistic graphics, motion tracking, and haptic feedback, all of which contribute to a more authentic and engaging learning experience in the Metaverse. The educational Metaverse can be conceptualized as the incorporation of intelligent education within the cloud, where teachers and students, through their digital avatars. Virtual worlds in Metaverse offer several benefits in the educational field. Virtual worlds allow users to perform tasks that would be difficult or impossible in the real world, either due to cost, time constraints, or geographic barriers. The enduring nature of virtual worlds provides fertile ground for the development and maintenance of social interactions. Through them, students build relationships, exchange ideas, and collaborate on projects, cultivating skills necessary for their future careers. One of the major advantages of virtual worlds is their flexibility. They can be easily configured and adapted, considering the individual needs and learning styles of learners (Kaddoura & Hussein, 2023).

The Metaverse is being realized as an innovative platform for the Open and Distance Learning institutions. The University Terbuka in Indonesia has been in the process of designing a Metaverse framework that creates a framework for governance and educational action (Firman et al., 2022). The use of VR in teaching and learning was established in China to enhance the learning achievement and participation among students as revealed in the study by Yuan et al. (2023) a case of English programs within an open university. In the University of Panama there have been some attempts to pilot the use of open source Metaverse teaching technologies in electronics for e-learning (Vernaza et al., 2012). It has cost efficiency for universities, improvement of the students' performance, and improve access for distance learning students (Auer & Tsiatsos, 2018). Metaverse is set to become the new paradigm of education and virtual learning; as of now, many universities established Metaverse-based programs – the so-called metaversities (Elgamal, 2022).

These developments suggest that the Metaverse has the potential to revolutionize open university education by providing immersive, engaging, and accessible learning experiences.

3. Research Methodology

The present study was based on the literature review, focusing on Metaverse technology and online distance education delivery systems implemented in both traditional and open universities. In the present study, an attempt was made to identify scientific articles pertaining to the study through the Google Scholar search tool by entering the keywords “Metaverse”, “education”, “distance education” and “open universities”. The choice of the articles for the analysis concerned the empirical articles published in the scientific journals after the year 2021. Besides, the research was devoted to the analysis of the European Union’s policies in the perspective of creating and supporting Virtual Worlds in the context of Metaverse and searching for guidelines and strategies that could contribute in enhancement of distance education in open universities. The HOU was chosen as a case study in which the authors have extensive educational experience. At the same time, a quantitative survey was conducted on students of a university department of Informatics in traditional university, in order to record their user experience and level of satisfaction with Metaverse, using the UEQ and the SUS, when using virtual educational worlds.

Usability is defined by ISO 9241-11 as “*the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use*” (Kaya et al., 2019). Measuring usability is a crucial step in assessing a system's acceptability and efficacy. Usability is a way to assess or gauge a system's or product's ability to accomplish a certain task in an efficient manner when utilized by users in a particular scenario. The appearance, features, and user interface design of a system are the primary factors that determine its usability. In addition to being assessed through the completion of activities, usability is also impacted by human factors. The ease of use and effectiveness of a product's interaction with a user are referred to as its "usability."

The *User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)* is an evaluation tool used to measure user experience (User Experience-UX) in various interactive systems such as software, websites and digital platforms. The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) (ueq-online.org) allows the collection of data on how users perceive and experience a system while using it. This questionnaire is structured with 26 items distributed in six dimensions: *Attractiveness, Efficiency, Perspicuity, Dependability, Stimulation, Novelty*.

Users are asked to respond to a set of opposite word pairs (e.g, “simple–complex,” “boring–interesting”), using a seven-point scale. This allows responses to be compared and quantitative data to be extracted for each dimension. UEQ can be applied to many different platforms and systems, both for prototype evaluations and for products already in use, allowing researchers to understand user perception in real-world usage conditions. The questionnaire is available in several languages, which makes it ideal for surveys with an international audience. UEQ is particularly useful for comparing different systems or measuring the improvement of user experience after system upgrades or changes. To process the data, a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet specially designed by the developers of the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) was used to thoroughly examine user experience profiles. The data were converted from the original Likert scale, from 1 to 7 to a scale of -3 to 3. A response of 1 on the questionnaire was converted to -3, while the highest score of 7 was converted to 3, and so on.

The *System Usability Scale (SUS)* is another usability evaluation tool used to measure the ease of use of various systems and products, such as software, websites and digital applications. Developed in 1986 by John Brooke (1996), it is one of the most widely used and versatile usability evaluation tools. It consists of 10 questions with a 5-point scale, where users rate the usability of the system (from "Strongly agree" to "Strongly disagree"). It has been the most widely used standardized usability questionnaire for years, with over 15,000 papers citing it. It has been demonstrated to be reliable even with small sample sizes. Questions alternate between positive and negative wording to avoid biasing user responses. SUS provides an overall score from 0 to 100, which allows usability to be evaluated: scores above 68 are considered acceptable, while higher values indicate very good usability. It is fast, simple to use and widely used to provide reliable and comparable data. Although the SUS is a general tool, it measures essential dimensions of usability, such as ease of understanding and ease of use of a system, efficiency, and user satisfaction (Lewis, 2018). The processing of the data of this scale was done with the online tool (<https://sus.tools>) which is the most complete solution for the development of the system usability scale. It allows the creation of the questionnaires as well as the analysis, statistical processing and interpretation of the results.

3.1 Study Group

In this study, students of the Informatics department of a traditional university participated, with the total sample consisting of 75 male and 25 female students, aged 18-23. The students were extensively informed about the objectives of the research and, in order to gain the necessary knowledge about the virtual worlds, they attended live information sessions under the guidance of the researcher. In addition, they were provided with asynchronous learning materials to facilitate their independent study. As part of the research, students navigated virtual worlds, which were developed specifically for the needs of the study. At the same time, they were invited to actively participate in the development of suitable virtual worlds through the spatial.io platform, with the aim of acquiring broader knowledge. The total duration of the research was four months, with the final result including the development of 112 virtual worlds, the product of the active participation of the students.

3.2 Data Collection Tool

The data collection tool in the present study included the use of two questionnaires, which were distributed to the students through the Google Forms platform. The first questionnaire was based on the structure of the UQE (User Experience Questionnaire), while the second followed the structure of the SUS (System Usability Scale). Students were asked to complete questionnaires after completing the development of the virtual worlds in order to capture their experiences and perception of both the usability and experience of using the virtual worlds on the Metaverse Spatial.io platform. The virtual worlds were implemented for research needs on the Metaverse Spatial.io platform leveraging a variant of the ADDIE instructional design model for developing educational virtual worlds in Metaverse (M-ADDIE). ADDIE is an instructional design model that can be adapted to various educational settings. Its name comes from the initials of the five main phases of the design cycle: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation (Spatioti et al., 2022).

4. Findings and Proposals

The present study, focusing on the utilization of the metaverse in the educational environment of the Hellenic Open University (HOU), presents two proposed utilization models, and three models of metaverse deployment which are analyzed in the next section. Research findings, based on the UEQ and SUS

questionnaires, regarding the virtual worlds of the metaverse are also analyzed. Finally, this article presents a strategic framework for the gradual transition of the HOU to the metaverse environment, which aims to enhance interactivity, personalization and the overall student learning experience.

4.1 Metaverse Utilization Model 1

The first Metaverse usage model at the Hellenic Open University (HOU) could be a combination model. In this model, existing infrastructures that support distance education could be enriched with complementary and supportive virtual reality (VR) and 3D virtual world technologies from Metaverse (Fig. 1), to meet educational needs that traditional platforms they cannot fully cover. For example, the existing HOU education portal mainly supports asynchronous and modern distance education, without providing the necessary immersion capabilities for experiential learning. Metaverse, on the other hand, could offer for example simulations of historical events (e.g. participation in virtual battles or explorations of ancient civilizations), virtual laboratories for scientific experiments, as well as simulations of professional scenarios through secure virtual environments created by the computer and without them it would not be possible to represent them (e.g. virtual clinics for medical or psychology students, simulation of nuclear power plants, journey to the bowels of the earth).

Figure 1. Metaverse Utilization Model 1.

4.2 Metaverse Utilization Model 2

The second model of Metaverse in HOU could rely solely on Metaverse platforms, bypassing the traditional platforms that HOU now uses. While these platforms allow students to participate in educational activities through digital environments (e.g. forums, webinars), Metaverse and Web 3.0 platforms provide active and experiential participation, where the user feels alive and interacts with the virtual environment. . In this context, students will not be limited to watching or simply participating through traditional digital tools, but will have the opportunity to fully experience learning in immersive 3D multi-user virtual worlds. For example, students could simultaneously use their avatars to walk on the surface of the Moon in a simulated educational world, exploring the environment as if they were there. Metaverse platforms can offer full immersion in virtual environments, where the user does not just observe the content, but becomes a part of it, participating in dynamic experiences such as exploring space worlds or interacting with 3D objects in real time and in a safe way.

4.3 Metaverse Deployment Models

The most likely Metaverse deployment models (European Commission, 2024), which would be suitable for the HOU or other type of universities, fall into three categories:

1. *Public or Corporate Model:* This model is being developed by large companies that are global leaders in Metaverse technologies, such as Meta, Microsoft, Google, and others. The platforms and infrastructures of the Metaverse are managed by these companies, providing access to users through centrally controlled systems. This model is characterized by central control, with these companies providing the necessary tools, applications, and infrastructure to users through cloud computing and other online services.
2. *Private Model:* In the private model, the Metaverse is developed within educational institutions or through state infrastructures. Educational institutions fully manage and control the technological infrastructure and virtual environments. The private model is based on the development and management of the Metaverse by the educational institutions themselves or public bodies, such as the Ministries of Education. For example, in Greece, the Ministry of Education could undertake the implementation of platforms through GRNET (National Infrastructures for Research and Technology), providing academic communities with secure and reliable access to virtual reality educational environments.
3. *Hybrid Model:* The hybrid model combines elements from both the public and private Metaverse. Thus, there is a collaboration between public entities and private companies, ensuring the use of innovative technologies on a broader scale, while maintaining control by public or educational organizations. In this case, essential parts of the technological infrastructure (e.g., computing power, networks, databases) may belong to companies, while applications and virtual worlds are developed and managed by educational institutions or user communities.

4.4 Proposal for the strategic transition of the HOU to the Metaverse

The introduction and use of the metaverse in HOU requires strategic planning that takes into account the dimensions of education, organization and technology. The proposed framework for the implementation of this initiative consists of several stages (Fig. 2). *The initial stage is about the vision and defining the strategic goals of the company.* On this, the vision will be to use Metaverse launch a new kind of learning environment. Concrete aims consist in enhancing the quality of distance education, in engaging students more effectively, and in introducing the students with new technologies. The achievement of such objectives could be measured with the help of various indicators such as increasing the students' satisfaction (through questionnaires), or increasing the educational results (measuring pass rates and overall pass scores).

Next, an analysis of *student and faculty needs* is required to identify areas where the metaverse can provide added value. This is followed by an *assessment of available technologies*, such as virtual and augmented reality (VR, AR), to determine which tools are appropriate for the needs of the HOU. Key performance at this stage may mean shortening the time taken to adapt to new technologies and enhancing the rates of students using the virtual environment.

Figure 2. Suggested Metaverse transition framework.

The other element in the framework is the *flexibility of the content of education* that is delivered to learners. Some of the existing material needs to be resourced in a suitable format for metaverse technologies, and more material needs to be created that is designed for immersive technologies. Furthermore, it is necessary to involve exciting work-shops, simulations and other forms of practical-oriented learning into the instructional design. Rather, established and newly designed objects, marked as sequence and tentative activity designs (e.g., simulations and virtual workshops), have to be assessed with parameters such as student engagement accruing or meeting educational goals by means of new practice (e.g., actualizing courses or projects by IT metaverse).

Preservice education, as well as *professional development for teaching staff*, are the other important areas. The implementation of training seminars and workshops is suggested in order to let teachers get acquainted with the new technologies. Here, KPIs could include the percentage of teachers participating in educational programs and the improvement of teachers' use of technologies (eg number of integrated virtual activities). In terms of *technical infrastructure*, the HOU should ensure the availability of the necessary resources, such as fast internet connections, VR/AR equipment and virtual worlds hosting platforms. In addition, cooperation with technological companies is considered necessary for the acquisition of know-how and the development of pilot applications. Regarding infrastructure adaptation, the assessment could be based on indicators such as the availability and speed of access to new technologies (eg VR/AR equipment) and the use of partnerships with technology companies to acquire specialized knowledge.

The next step concerns the *development and evaluation of pilot programs*. It is proposed to implement pilot courses or modules in selected curricula, in which the use of the metaverse will be tested. The collection of data from students and faculty will help evaluate the performance and acceptance of the technology, while with KPIs such as increasing active participation in pilot modules and improving the educational experience.

In the light of the pilot applications, the framework suggests reconsidering and fleshing out the strategy and further *large-scale actualization* of the metaverse in the HOU. There will be a gradual infusion of technology into learning and teaching across curriculum with more and more activities.

Last but not the least, in order to understand lessons of *educational outcomes* in achieving the Strategic Plan, its implementation and sustainability would require an ongoing assessment activities. Student and professors feedback will enhance the flow of feedback on the methods and technologies used in the process. And at the same time, the dissemination of good practices and experiences to be gained will further enhance the position of HOU as a new approach educational institution, nationally and internationally. Last of all, the general extent and *growth of the use* of the metaverse can be assessed by means of quantitative criteria like, for instance, the number of curricula that use virtual worlds and the performance of students enrolled on the

programs. Ongoing evaluation of educational performance indicators will improve the specific educational process, with effectiveness indicators like general satisfaction and learning objectives effectively achieved.

The preferred development model of Metaverse for the Hellenic Open University (HOU) would be a hybrid model of cooperation with leading technology companies. Under this model, the companies would provide the technological infrastructure and tools necessary to develop the virtual worlds, while HOU would undertake the complete organization and management of the virtual environments, as well as the protection and management of the students' personal data. Add in, during the first part of the transition to Metaverse the suggested model will be a blend model where the Metaverse technologies are integrated with the existing technologies in the field of education portal at HOU. Such an approach will occur in stages to foster the adoption of innovative virtual environments while keeping the continuity of distance learning through traditional technologies.

During the current transition stage, the students, as well as instructors, will be able to use Metaverse and its virtual worlds mostly via computers, rather than requiring use of expensive devices, like VR headsets. However, with concerns to learning environments, fully immersive technologies should, where possible, be piloted for those specific education applications that benefit from immersion.

4.5 Results of Empirical Research

The participating students in the research were 100 and their demographic data were as follows: 75% were male and the remaining 25% were female, all students of the computer science department of the traditional university. 67% were in their second year of study and 90% of them were 20-25 years old. 96% of them accessed the pilot virtual worlds via computer, while 4% via smartphone.

4.5.1 User Experience Results

The analysis of the results based on the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) shows that the pilot educational virtual world in Metaverse Spatial.io received a positive evaluation in all evaluation dimensions. The results of the analysis using the UEQ method obtained an average scale of Attractiveness=1.637, Perspicuity=1.531, Efficiency=1.515, Dependability=1.343, Stimulation=1.410 and Novelty=1.479. Figure 3 shows the overall mean of the different dimensions of user experience.

Figure 3. UEQ benchmark diagram.

Considering the reference points of the various variables of the scale, the Attractiveness dimension emerged as the most important dimension while the Dependability was the least important. These results explain that the pilot virtual world in Spatial.io according to the UEQ scale has a positive user experience value because all scales show a mean value greater than 0.8. In the Attractiveness dimension, students found the platform pleasant and attractive to use.

In the Perspicuity dimension, a positive score indicates that the majority of students had no difficulties understanding and using the system. In the Efficiency dimension, students felt that they could perform the necessary actions efficiently and effortlessly.

The Dependability dimension was also rated positively, suggesting that the system worked stably without unforeseen problems, while the Stimulation dimension showed that students found using the platform interesting and fun. Finally, the Novelty dimension received a relatively positive rating, indicating that students found the user experience novel. Comparison with the benchmark showed that all scale values fall into the Good category. However, none of the scale values fall into the Excellent category which corresponds to the top 10% of results, so there is still room for improvement.

4.5.2 Virtual Worlds Usability Results

Analysis of the SUS scale results for virtual worlds on the Spatial.io platform shows an overall score of 74.63, which is considered "Good" by SUS standards (Fig. 4). The standard deviation of the responses is 18.55, which indicates that there is some variation in the opinions of the participants, but not too much. The descriptive rating of the score is "Good", meaning that users were generally satisfied with the ease of use of the platform. The overall score corresponds to a B on the grammar scale, indicating that the platform performs quite well. The acceptability of the platform is characterized as "Acceptable", without serious usability problems. The platform is in the third quartile, meaning its results are above 50% of usual performance.

Figure 4. Virtual Worlds usability diagram.

The overall conclusiveness is 100%, which means that the research results are considered complete and representative. Overall, the survey is judged to be complete and representative, indicating that users are generally satisfied with the usability of the virtual worlds in Spatial.io, but there is considerable room for improvement.

5. Discussion

Metaverse is seen as the future third-generation Web and enables a number of positive effects on education, including real-life simulations that are particularly useful in fields based on experiential education, such as medicine and engineering. Virtual learning environments in the Metaverse are able to enhance the learning of complex concepts since they create learning environments in which multiple senses are used simultaneously (Chen, 2024). The provision of asynchronous learning and the availability of educational material without geographical and time constraints are beneficial for working adults. The possibility of remote collaboration sharpens the interaction of students with other students and teachers and fosters social learning that helps to create communities of practice as well as to acquire effective collaboration skills.

Open and traditional universities can use Metaverse to create fully or partially virtual campuses that include virtual libraries, virtual labs, and virtual student support centers. Such virtual infrastructures can somehow help students in areas such as advising and providing learning resources.

In order to effectively exploit the metaverse, a combination of technological, educational and organizational infrastructure is required. To do this, high-speed and reliable connections are required for both students and faculty—especially to engage in immersive experiences like VR and AR. Existing distance systems of educational institutions should be able to integrate specialized metaverse platforms such as Spatial.io, Mozilla Hubs or similar, which host virtual worlds, so that the capabilities of the metaverse work seamlessly in academic environments (Kye et al., 2021). Courses should be developed that take advantage of the possibilities in the virtual environment, such as laboratory simulations, group work or virtual classrooms. It is necessary to have technical support for students and teachers to guide them in the use of the equipment and the virtual environment which should be available in real time. Universities should partner with companies that provide Metaverse expertise (such as VR/AR software development, virtual worlds creation companies) to develop corresponding pilot programs. As Metaverse involves the creation and management of personal data and virtual spaces, universities should ensure privacy and data security by adopting appropriate security strategies and protocols. All students should have access to the metaverse, including students with special needs. This means adapting equipment, technology and platforms to ensure universal and inclusive access.

Metaverse is highly technology-based and, for example, requires VR or AR equipment that may not be affordable for all students. The lack of this equipment or limited access to it can widen the gap between students. It is also possible that some of the adult students find it difficult to deal with such VR/AR technologies because their training in the new ways of using the technology is insufficient and this, in some ways, hinders their participation. Virtual platforms may not be fully compatible with each other, making integration and collaboration between different education systems difficult. The need for standards that will ensure ease of use and data transfer is great.

However, the positive impact of immersion and interactivity as Metaverse promises in the learning environment of adult learning remains uncertain. Concerns are growing as to whether the learner will benefit from this mode of delivery in the same way as when learning through conventional methods.

Creating virtual spaces and hardware specifically for Metaverse can be very expensive, and the university will need a sufficient number of specialized staff, necessary technology support, and ongoing investment in the system for expansion or maintenance. The transition to virtual platforms as the main or supporting learning technology affects the physical and mental health of students. Challenges that may require attention include: social isolation and over-reliance on cyberspace experiences. The integration of Metaverse will also cause changes in administrative structures and processes. For example, it will bring about reorganization of educational processes, modification of learning management systems to adapt to the new virtual platforms. The absence of a transition strategy can lead to confusion or inconsistency in learning and teaching. Until there is a clear framework for how Metaverse will be implemented in the education system, how success will be measured and how this will affect the learning environment, open universities will face major challenges in integrating Metaverse technology into their environment.

6. Conclusions-Limitations-Future actions

Research findings show that Metaverse can provide significant benefits to distance education by enhancing student interaction and immersion in virtual learning worlds, but the transition to Metaverse environments must be well-planned to produce the expected results. Evaluation through the UEQ and SUS tools showed that the educational virtual worlds are engaging, enjoyable and easy to use, suggesting that Metaverse can be successfully integrated into educational institutions. However, this study has several limitations. First, there is a lack of generalizability of the results because convenience sampling was used and because a small number of women participated. Also, the survey did not involve adults of various ages who are usually students in the HOU, but Generation Z students who study computer science and are therefore familiar with new technologies and similar platforms, such as Roblox or Fortnite, which are considered the precursors to the Metaverse. In our future research, our goal is to study the acceptance of Metaverse also by HOU students in order to have a more complete age distribution and a more valid picture.

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Introducing a holistic digital pedagogical framework for university educators

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Abstract

The abrupt shift to technology-enhanced teaching, accelerated by the global pandemic, developed a sense of uncertainty amongst academics as to whether they are integrating technology correctly in their pedagogies. The online teaching mode had various educators ill-prepared, and many felt that they did not consist of the necessary technological-pedagogical knowledge to deliver content effectively. In the global south, digital exclusion is often viewed as a major problem amongst students, both in terms of internet access and digital fluency. However, university educators are often under-emphasised in the digital exclusion debate. During a qualitative study, seven university educators in a particular faculty were interviewed to determine their experiences of applying a digital pedagogy. It was found that a clearly defined digital pedagogy lacked. In this paper I draw on some of these experiences and introduce a hybrid framework based on a) *productive pedagogies* and b) *technological, pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK)*.

Key words: digital pedagogy, technology, university educators, teaching

1. Introduction

The rapid integration of technology has brought about radical transformation in higher education institutions. Services and job opportunities are becoming more dependent on having access to and proficiency with digital platforms. This implies that university educators have no other choice but to integrate technology in their pedagogies. However, for some the adoption thereof did not come easy. Most university educators tend to be self-taught or peer taught. Given the difficulties that come with using innovative technologies in the classroom, make teaching with technology even more complex as more and more AI tools find their way to the classroom. Practically speaking, some of the technologies discussed in the literature include certain intrinsic characteristics that make simple applications of them challenging for both students and educators. Therefore, an in-depth understanding amongst university educators of how to use technology effectively in teaching and learning processes is required for the successful integration thereof.

Some university educators' technology skills tend to be limited to what is in their home and work environment. Although most of them use technology every day, the types of technology they use might not be as up to date as their students, nor even their teaching requirements, need them to be. In this paper I discuss a case at a university in South Africa, where seven university educators were interviewed to determine what their lived experiences regarding the integration of technology as part of their pedagogy were. Another objective was to investigate what pedagogies they were employing in the digital age. However, the lack of a clear digital pedagogy was found amongst most of the participants. It was also clear that technological skills alone are not the defining factor for an effective digital pedagogy. In this context, I introduce a holistic framework that emphasises the junction of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge referred to as Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) (Koehler, 2006). TPCK can be improved even more, though, the incorporation of Productive Pedagogies (QSRLS, 2002), a paradigm that emphasises the value of social interaction, higher-order thinking, and active engagement in teaching and learning. In order to promote more meaningful educational experiences, this paper advocates for the hybridisation of productive pedagogies and TPCK, in developing a holistic and effective digital pedagogy. I divide this paper into four sections. Firstly, I present a brief literature review, secondly, I discuss the methodology which shall be followed by some main findings. Lastly, I introduce the proposed framework and explore some implications for higher education institutions.

2. Literature review

2.1 The need for a holistic digital pedagogy

When technology's potential was first explored, some educators were rather excited about it. Many prescient remarks were made about how the computer will take the place of the educator which caused some opposition to using technology in the classroom (Citizens Advice Scotland, 2018). After the initial wave of critical reaction subsided, educators began to look at the possibilities of new technologies in the classroom. The transition to more autonomous, student-led inquiry models of learning has been accelerated by technology during the global pandemic. These days, in a post-pandemic era, educators take on the position of an e-moderator or co-collaborator. Technology in the modern classroom does more than just serving as a tool; it transforms both what and how students learn. The use of a computer in a classroom doesn't automatically translate into effective learning; instead, educators must understand how to utilise technology wisely, comprehend the theories of learning that underpin the practice, and choose the best equipment to achieve their goals for student learning (Falloon, 2020).

In order to improve educational outcomes in the light of the 4IR and 5IR, a holistic yet substantive digital pedagogy is required. The latter can be seen as the integration and application of using digital tools, resources, and technologies into teaching and learning processes. It includes the deliberate and intentional application of technology to enhance and support educational methods, encourage participation, enable active learning, and

build necessary digital literacy. In order to fully utilise the affordances of digital tools and platforms, a digital pedagogy entails rethinking teaching strategies, curriculum design, and assessment procedures. It goes beyond merely putting technology in the classroom.

Fundamentally, learner-centered approaches—in which students are empowered to actively participate in their own learning—are the focus of a digital pedagogy. This could entail giving students the chance to work together on projects via online platforms, connect with multimedia materials to study difficult subjects, or take part in interactive and virtual simulations (Coker, 2019). Additionally, a digital pedagogy encourages individualised learning experiences by giving teachers the tools to differentiate education, adjust learning systems, and provide data-driven insights to customise training to each student's needs and preferences. It therefore acknowledges differences, while at the same time embracing diversity. However, from the study that was conducted with seven university educators, it appears that the lack of a theoretical framework underpinning their pedagogy in the digital space created various challenges. Next, I will briefly discuss the methodology.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

A qualitative study framed in the interpretive paradigm was conducted with seven university educators teaching at a university in South Africa. The aim of the study was to determine what effective pedagogies they have adopted in the digital age, especially three years post the pandemic. First ethical clearance and informed consent were obtained before the empirical research commenced. Gephart (2018:34) defines interpretive research as "experimental studies that methodically develop scientific theories and concepts (knowledge) as 'second order' interpretations predicated on inductive and abductive analysis of members' real common sense or 'first order' concepts and actions and meanings." The interpretive paradigm prioritises participant accounts of knowledge from various angles so that the researcher can make meaning of patterns and draw conclusions. For this research, the case study approach was selected since it enables a thorough examination of the phenomenon under investigation.

3.2 Sampling

In this study purposive sampling was used. Purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Cresswell, 2018). Participants were collected based on two criteria: 1) they had to teach longer than five years at a university and 2) they had to teach during and post the pandemic.

Participants	James	Kelly	Shaun	Amy	Shaun	Lucy	Kyle
Number of years teaching at a university	25	10	8	12	15	6	13
Highest qualification	PhD	PhD	PhD	PhD	PhD	Master's	Master's

3.3 Data collection

In-person semi-structured interviews coupled with focus groups were conducted over a period of three weeks to gain a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of the participants' digital pedagogies.

3.4 Data analysis

Data was first transcribed and secondly analysed by using NVivo software. Thematic analysis was applied to arrive at main themes. Throughout the study ethics was adhered to by maintaining confidentiality and protecting the participants' names and identity. Pseudonyms were used.

4. Results: Main themes

Although the participants agreed that technology is needed and should be integrated in teaching and learning as far as possible, they did not omit mentioning the various challenges and barriers they have experienced during and post the pandemic. Due to scope and space, I could not include all the themes and excerpts from transcripts, but have tabled some of the main ones below:

Table 1: Excerpts from transcripts.

Themes	James	Kelly	Shaun	Amy	Shaun	Lucy	Kyle
Inadequate preparation time to master tools and learning platform	<i>"I have always used some sort of technology before COVID19 but getting to know the learning management system in such a short period of time was a nightmare."</i>	<i>"I felt that more could have been done to prepare us. I was totally overwhelmed and am still not sure whether I am optimally applying the tools and devices correctly."</i>	<i>"Every month a new tool comes out. Students know more than us on how to use them. Luckily, I am a fast learner myself, but I know of a few older colleagues who really struggled."</i>	<i>"I understand that we had to adapt fast, but I felt that it is a disservice to students if academics are not well prepared on using the latest tools and technology."</i>	<i>"What can I say? Such is life! We have to adapt, however, perhaps more time and proper training would have been appreciated."</i>	<i>"I am tech savvy and learned rather quickly. I was just not sure as to whether I am teaching or whether the tool is teaching!"</i>	<i>I knew it would happen sooner than later. Technology is here to stay. But although we are educators it does not mean that we know much about technology in teaching."</i>
Time-consuming	<i>"It takes hours and days to get my course material ready for the online platform."</i>	<i>"I have to say, and my husband can attest to it that I work day and night including weekends to adjust my content for the online classroom."</i>	<i>"This is not fair. We already spend so much time on creating course material, and now re-creating it for the online and hybrid classroom!"</i>	<i>"We are not getting paid extra for all the time that goes into planning and re-designing courses."</i>	<i>"I don't know whether I should be in academia anymore. The amount of time spent on teaching and learning is getting ridiculous."</i>	<i>"It takes a lot of time, but I also learn a lot in the process. I think I need more tutors and TA's to assist me."</i>	<i>"The university should budget for more teaching assistants to help us with this. I teach 5 courses and translating these to the online platform is not a joke!"</i>
Fear of technology substituting the educator	<i>"At some point I wasn't feeling that I</i>	<i>"I wasn't sure what my role is now that</i>	<i>"There was a time when I was wondering:</i>	<i>"I think we just need to figure out how to get</i>	<i>"Tech-nology is taking over everything.</i>	<i>"I need workshops on my role in this tech-</i>	<i>Technology fails us a lot. Especially</i>

	<i>am teaching. It felt like technology has taken over my role."</i>	<i>we have ChatGPT and online tools that mark assessments."</i>	<i>am I still needed? The students seem to enjoy the technology more than listening to my voice!"</i>	<i>the balance between our role and that of technology. Currently it is unclear."</i>	<i>In a few years' time there won't be a need for lecturers anymore."</i>	<i>driven society. I feel that students and technology get along much better."</i>	<i>with our energy crisis in South Africa. How do they expect us to embrace 4IR and 5IR if we don't even have power?"</i>
Lack of pedagogical knowledge when using technology	<i>"I have no idea what I am doing. Currently I just teach as before the pandemic with some tech tools but not sure if I am doing it right."</i>	<i>"I did not even have sufficient knowledge of pedagogy before Covid, less during the pandemic and now it feels the little that I knew is irrelevant."</i>	<i>"Oh dear, don't even start with me on educational terms like pedagogy. No idea!"</i>	<i>"Am I the only one not knowing what I am doing? Please help!"</i>	<i>"I am not afraid to admit that I need help. I have little knowledge on pedagogy, and this is unfair towards the students."</i>	<i>"I think I am on the right track, but I need someone with educational knowledge to assess my pedagogy."</i>	<i>"Do we need pedagogy when we have technology? I don't think so!"</i>
Feeling disconnected from students	<i>"Of course, I felt alienated from my students. Talking to a screen is just not the same as in person teaching."</i>	<i>"To be honest I hate the online world. The connection is just not the same. You cannot pick up on body language."</i>	<i>"I think students feel more isolated in the online space than they / we want to admit. In-person connection is crucial in teaching. What about those coming from different countries, religions and socio-economic backgrounds, how can we find a real connection</i>	<i>"Technology should not take over teaching. Teaching should be done in close proximity of humans not algorithms."</i>	<i>"I miss my students when we're in an online class. It is just not the same. It is similar to having a long-distance relationship and we know 80% of those never work out!"</i>	<i>"I agree the connection is lost, but I think we need to find the connection in the virtual world. Why can we find it on social media but not in teaching online?"</i>	<i>"We need to find a balance. We sit with a diverse mixture of students in our class. Technology can't do justice to this. Teaching technical, and practical stuff online is a waste of time and not teaching, but rather demonstrating."</i>

			<i>with them through technology?"</i>				
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5. Discussion

As can be seen in the above table, one can concur that participants have scant knowledge on pedagogy let alone a digital pedagogy. There could be various reasons for this. It could be that they have limited knowledge on educational theory and didactics. It could also be that it might not be that important to them. Whatever the reasons, it is clear that a framework for developing a substantive digital pedagogy is required in order to enhance the learning experience and address some of the challenges mentioned. I therefore propose the holistic framework of productive pedagogies and the TPCK.

5.1 Productive Pedagogies

Productive Pedagogies were coined in Queensland, Australia, by the Department of Education, Training, and Employment in response to the need for an all-encompassing method of instruction that goes beyond the simple transfer of knowledge and instead encourages meaningful learning experiences and active student participation. Productive Pedagogies is a framework that provides educators with a thorough methodology to improve student engagement, encourage critical thinking, and develop a better comprehension of the subject matter. It is based on research regarding effective teaching and learning approaches (QSRLS, 2002). It is imperative that university educators gain insight into the effective implementation of Productive Pedagogies to maximise student learning outcomes and foster a conducive learning environment supportive of academic success. Furthermore, Productive Pedagogies places a strong emphasis on creating dynamic, interactive learning environments that maximise student engagement, improve topic understanding, and encourage the development of higher-order thinking skills (Hayes, Mills, Christie and Lingard, 2020).

The Productive Pedagogies framework comprises four main interconnected domains, each of which plays a crucial role in shaping effective teaching practices and optimising student learning outcomes:

Intellectual Quality: This domain emphasises the importance of challenging students intellectually by providing them with opportunities to engage in complex tasks, analyse information critically, and apply knowledge creatively. Intellectual quality encourages deep understanding and promotes higher-order thinking skills such as problem-solving, analysis, and synthesis (QSRLS, 2002).

Connectedness: Connectedness underscores the significance of making meaningful connections between students' prior knowledge, experiences, and the content being taught. It emphasises the integration of new information with existing knowledge frameworks and the relevance of learning to students' lives, interests, and aspirations (QSRLS, 2002).

Supportive Classroom Environment: A supportive classroom environment is characterised by positive relationships, mutual respect, and a sense of belonging among students and between students and teachers. It provides a safe and inclusive space where students feel comfortable taking risks, asking questions, and expressing their ideas freely (QSRLS, 2002).

Recognition of Difference: This principle acknowledges and respects the diversity of students' backgrounds, abilities, learning styles, and cultural identities. It emphasises the importance of differentiated instruction, inclusive practices, and culturally responsive teaching strategies to meet the needs of all learners effectively (QSRLS, 2002).

Teachers may build dynamic, inclusive learning environments that encourage critical inquiry, active engagement, and academic excellence by incorporating these four into their pedagogy. A student-centered approach to

teaching, where the emphasis is on creating meaningful learning experiences that enable students to become autonomous and lifelong learners, is encouraged by this framework (QSRLS, 2002).

Figure 1: The Productive Pedagogies Framework. Adapted from the Queensland School Reform Longitudinal Study (QSRLS, 2002).

5.2 Technology Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK)

A crucial framework in the field of education, Technology Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) synthesises the junction of technology knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge. In this paper I briefly discuss the theoretical foundations of this framework. This paper attempts to clarify the significance of TPCK in assisting educators in effectively integrating technology into their instructional practices and improving student learning outcomes. The TPCK framework views pedagogical knowledge (PK) as the "how" that explains how the educator will make the content more accessible (via direct instruction, inquiry, group discussion, debate, modeling, etc.) and content knowledge (CK) as the "what" that is the subject matter (arts, English, mathematics, science, etc.) that teachers teach (Koehler, 2006). Technological knowledge (TK) is then used as the "partner" to answer the question of what instruments (simulations, smart boards, projects, multimedia, etc.) will be used to help the students better understand the material. By highlighting the types of knowledge that exist at the intersections between these three primary forms, Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), and Technological Knowledge—the TPCK framework goes beyond viewing these three knowledge bases in isolation. Researchers contend that learning to be sensitive to the dynamic, transactional link between various components of knowledge placed in particular settings is necessary for the effective integration of technology into pedagogies and for the pedagogical use of technology for particular subject matter.

Figure 2: The technological pedagogical content knowledge framework (TPCK). Adapted from Koehler (2006).

6. Hybridising Productive Pedagogies and TPCK: Some implications for higher education

Figure 3: The hybridisation of Productive Pedagogies and TPCK: A holistic framework for a digital pedagogy.

The four domains of Productive Pedagogies (connectedness, supportive classroom environment and engagement with difference) are paramount for university educators to understand. Elsewhere I have argued that new e-learning places and spaces (splaces) should be created in this digital era (Ontong and Waghid, 2021 & Ontong, 2022). In these new unfamiliar splaces in which we currently teach and learn, students find themselves entrenched in the integrated social-ecological-political-psychological and virtual dimensions of their learning. Therefore, educators need to acknowledge that creating conducive splaces of connectedness are paramount not only for enhancing the learning experience but also in the co-production on new knowledge and identity formation.

Therefore, I also propose flexible learning as a teaching style in this new digital age. Flexible learning at convenient times and across geographic boundaries is made possible by technology (learning anywhere, anytime). It is thus imperative that university educators equip themselves with knowledge on the latest technology devices, software and tools, the latest content and knowledge in their discipline and the essence of productive pedagogies. By doing this, they could maximise the teaching and learning experience and assist

students in reaching the learning outcomes. While Productive Pedagogies and TPCK are paramount in developing a digital pedagogy suitable for the current dispensation, the student learning experience is about a lot more than the educator getting the design of assessment tasks right and providing students with useful feedback. Learning is a complex process in which different students and learning groups adopt a variety of motivational and cognitive regulation strategies as part of their learning. And, in the context of distance, online and distributed educational settings, which are characterised by the separation of students from educators in time and space, these variables take on new meanings, and a new level of importance. An understanding of the Productive Pedagogies framework coupled with the TPCK will be useful for university educators to develop their own digital pedagogy and personal philosophy. In this sense the framework serves as a mere supportive ‘tool’ to inform a digital pedagogy.

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Online Education among Police Studies students: How to embrace their interest (course design, pedagogical approaches).

A case study from the Open University of Cyprus

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Abstract

Background: Police studies education at the Open University of Cyprus prepares students for police involvement positions by developing criminal, international, EU law and methodological skills. Police studies is a first-year Bachelor's degree that has been addressed to Cypriot Police officers. As a full time degree lasts 3 years otherwise as part time 4 years. Cypriot Police has given incentives to Police officers in order to attend this course and ameliorate their position. It includes a range of mandatory and selective courses one of which is the one I have been teaching.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the online education on the distance course 'Police / Law & Cultural Heritage' where I have been teaching since 2015 at the Open University of Cyprus. More than 150 Cypriot Police officers have been taught this course. Initially the teaching of this course has been based on blended learning or hybrid learning which is 'the combination of traditional face-to-face and computer-mediated instruction' (Hadizadeh & Kanik, 2022: 42). This 'hybrid learning can help to realize the advantages of both methods for providing flexible education' (Pramila-Savukoski et al., 2023: 1920). This type of blended learning was based on two hybrid teleconferences plus 4 teleconferences. Gradually and mainly 'the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a digital transformation of universities within a short time, which would typically take years in normal circumstances' (Hadizadeh & Kanik, 2022: 41). The Open University of Cyprus has responded all in once to the COVID-19 pandemic challenge as it has been well prepared for this total shift all through the years from hybrid learning to online teaching. As it is going to be presented later on, the Open University of Cyprus has always had the appropriate technology to support distance teaching as it is a University that is based on distance learning including a platform with synchronous technologies and asynchronous capabilities. Therefore we will argue that there was the appropriate planning accompanied with the necessary technological and social infrastructure.

Objectives: The main research question of this presentation is how to embrace Police officers student's interest, which is the most appropriate course design that meets their needs. Moreover what kind of pedagogical approaches are being chosen in order to achieve the best outcomes. Furthermore is it possible to activate students with the existing digital tools? (Haarala-Muhonen & others, 2023).

Methods: This study is based on the qualitative and quantitative findings of teaching students for this course. An effective online teaching is assessed from the results of the evaluation of the students in the end of each academic semester which is possible through a questionnaire, suggestions from the students and lastly but not least the continuous pedagogical training.

Findings: This paper offers a general overview of this shift from hybrid teaching of this course to online teaching and online exams.

Originality /value: Its aim is to value the existing online teaching of this course and its future transition to a course open to other students.

Keywords: police, law, cultural heritage, art law, national law, international, EU law, art trade, online education, hybrid education, face-to-face education, distance learning.

Introduction

The teaching of the distance course ‘Police / Law & Cultural Heritage’ dates back to 2015. More than 150 Cypriot Police officers have been taught this course. It has started initially as a ‘blended hybrid model’ teaching course (Constantinou, 2023: 75) turning to a fully online course (Haarala-Muhonen, et al, 2023). The main hypothesis is that it is possible to activate Police officers’ students interest through the appropriate technological and social infrastructure. I will argue that there are challenges but they are able to be coped with.

This paper is based on the presentation of the involved students, the selected study guide, what kind of teaching methods and exams have been selected, the role of student evaluation, continuous training.

Main Body

‘Learning to teach online is not learning to teach all over again. As we design online courses and even hybridize face-to-face settings, remember that you possess a wealth of knowledge, experience, and expertise that will guide you in developing robust, pedagogically sound learning environments that facilitate meaningful learning for both students and teachers. Use that experience. Rely on that expertise. Reach out to other educators and ask for help. Above all, talk to your students and keep cultivating those relationships’ (Itow, 2020: 451). The distance course ‘Police / Law & Cultural Heritage’ is addressed to Cypriot Police officers that are faced with working and family engagements. It is a challenge to achieve the most effective online teaching that will inspire mature students and encourage them to problematize focusing on students’ needs and course goals (Itow, 2020). Lifelong learning has at its scope ‘to enable people, at any stage of their lives, to take part in stimulating learning experiences’ (Raes et al, 2018: 270). Mature students return to education and make their best in learning process. ‘Lifelong learners often cannot attend traditional classroom instruction because of family or work commitments. Within this context, digital technologies are often proposed as a possible answer to change the educational landscapes and make it more flexible and accessible for a larger group of

learners' (Cain in Raes et al 2018: 270). This freedom and flexibility enables access to education in real time with other students and teachers no matter job and family commitments and obligations (Passyn & Wright).

The guide of this course has been based on providing a synchronous online teaching that will be able to engage students' enthusiasm to learn and attend their lessons. This course has initially started on the basis of hybrid teaching then with covid era has turned to a fully online course. In 2015 there were scheduled two hybrid teleconferences plus 4 teleconferences. The hybrid teleconferences gave to remote students the opportunity to contribute to classroom discussions together with the face-to-face attendees.

There are diverse pedagogical practices and use of digital tools in online teaching either blended or fully online course that the Open University of Cyprus has tried to initiate through a common pedagogical training. 'Pedagogical training plays a key role in how teachers approach their teaching and use digital tools in an online environment' (Haarala-Muhonen, 2023: 8). 'University teachers are a very heterogenous group in both their pedagogical and digital skills' (Haarala-Muhonen, 2023: 1). The scheduled Distance Learning Certificate of the Open University of Cyprus together with the long-term training and personal support on digital and pedagogical tools has offered a great variety of skills in order to cope with the after pandemic needs in turning to full online teaching. In general in online teaching, it is vital for teachers to be trained on new technologies and pedagogical skills in order to be able to cope with the growing demand and developments in online teaching. Open University of Cyprus offers a sufficient pedagogically and technologically training and support. Prior to the beginning of each teleconference an audio set up is made.

Digital tools such as Moodle learning platform and Blackboard Collaborate are used in teaching 'Police / Law & Cultural Heritage'. The asynchronous part of the course is delivered through Moodle platform where the material is placed on, discussion takes place in forums where students have the ability to prepare before they take part which may indicate a lack of spontaneity (Flynn-Wilson, & Reynolds, 2021). At the discussion forum students are able to discuss, exchange opinions etc which diminishes distance bringing them closer. The platform (with the asynchronous activities) is enriched more specifically with primary and secondary mandatory material and readings (always corresponding to the limitations of copyright), web links, videos, Panopto videos, interactive exercises (such as wiki, quizzes, polls, chat room, questionnaire etc.), teleconferences (at the synchronous part). Activating students through polls, quizzes can solve the engagement problem (Raes et al 2018: 285). 'The platform gives access to the sources that teachers are using during lectures (e.g. Power point slides or annotations made on the digital whiteboard)' (Raes et al, 2018: 271). Blackboard Collaborate constitutes the virtual synchronous course delivery tool where students and their teacher meet on a virtual classroom which enables at its best an interaction and a 'sense of community' (Flynn-Wilson & Reynolds, 2021: 47). The scheduled interactive lectures which include 4 teleconferences of 45 minutes plus 2 teleconferences of 3 hours each have as their aim to increase student participation

engagement. Once the teleconference takes place I turn on the camera, display the presentation slides with the lecture notes starting the lecture and the discussion with the students. These teleconferences are recorded which make them available to be studied later on by students whenever they want. The main aim of this course is not only to deliver theoretical skills on protecting cultural heritage but also in activating Police Officer students in how to use the acquired knowledge in their everyday working life. That is why it is given priority to quantitative research through in situ research visits and by posing empirical research exercises. Bringing theory into practice is the key to success and activation of the students something that is obvious the yearly evaluation scheme. The contact and discussion with students is achieved through the forum which enables the teacher and students to interact and solve problems and discuss current issues related to the course. The face-to-face exams have turned with COVID-19 pandemic to fully online exam either written as it is the case in this course or by using Proctorio.

Transferring a face-to-face course into a digital format was not an issue for the course I am teaching since it has been operated as a hybrid one since 2015. The main advantage of a full online course is that offers flexibility to its students that give them the opportunity to attend recorded lectures and relevant resources on their own time. The main challenge is to try to 'reframe human interactions in online courses which is necessary for effective online teaching' (Basdogan & Birdwell, 2023: 431). The negative aspects of online teaching is the lack of eye contact and a 'lower sense of social presence in online discussion groups' (Basdogan & Birdwell, 2023: 429), the lack of socialization and face-to-face interactions (Hadizadeh & Kanik, 2022). Of course it is difficult to achieve engagement of the remote students at the same extent as those attending in the traditional way. Hybrid or full online learning requires more self-discipline from students (Raes et al 2018). I always try to increase students' involvement during teleconferences by making the lesson more interesting, asking them oral questions and getting them involved. Last but not least student evaluation plays a great role in ameliorating online teaching.

As we talk the course 'Police / Law & Cultural Heritage' will be renamed to 'Policing/ Law and Crime against Cultural Heritage' opening to other students and not only Cypriot Police officers.

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Supporting Inclusive Tourism Professionals via Curricula For Accessible Tourism Manager and Frontline Staff: the In-tour Courses

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Abstract

Accessibility in tourism is a social right which concerns all citizens. It is often limited to a certain group of people, but it should be seen in a more holistic approach. The "INclusive TOURism professions - European curricula for accessible tourism manager and frontline staff (In-Tour)" project, which concluded in 2023, aimed to address gaps in the European educational system concerning knowledge and competences in Inclusive - Accessible Tourism. The study conducted, enhanced the existing evidence on skills requirements, ensuring professional profiles met current and future industry demands, culminating in the release of occupational profiles for Inclusive Tourism Manager (ITM) and Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff (ITFS), specifying skill gaps by connecting demand with representatives of tourism industries and entrepreneurs, analysing good practices especially for customers with specific access requirements. This marked a significant advancement in supporting Vocational Education and Training (VET) within the tourism sector, crucial for achieving inclusive tourism.

In-Tour defined European Curricula in the accessible tourism sector at EQF levels 5, 6, and 7, designed a flexible, modular training path for both Curricula, and delivered them through pilot courses in Greece, Germany and Italy. The Curricula serving as a European reference model implementable in each EU Member State, tested through 5 local pilots incorporating work-based learning. This paper presents the curricula as well as the methodology for developing and providing the Greek pilot courses for the "Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff (ITFS)" (EQF-level 5) and the "Inclusive Manager in Tourism (ITM)" (EQF-level 6), based on a blended distance learning format. Each course attracted more than 42 participants from the tourism sector, supported by the Training & Lifelong Learning Centre (KEDIVIM) of the Hellenic Open University (HOU).

The curricula prioritize learning outcomes linked to core competences across various levels, emphasizing practical application of knowledge in work settings for both managerial and frontline staff. The educational design followed a methodology supporting open and distance e-learning, with teaching primarily through asynchronous study and activities to ensure learner autonomy. Synchronous learning was also conducted based on educational needs. In-Tour aimed to create a model and methodology that could be replicated and spread among other European Universities and VET providers. Developed collaboratively with stakeholders from VET, the tourism industry, and accessibility experts, the curricula feature a framework structured around competences, knowledge, and skills. Each curriculum includes numerous learning outcomes connected to core competences, with ITM comprising 259 and ITFS 112 learning outcomes. Personal and transversal

competences emphasizing responsibility and autonomy were delineated, facilitating learners' understanding and application of knowledge. Additionally, the paper assesses the results of the evaluation and impact analysis, identifying both the potential benefits and drawbacks of the In-Tour pilot courses. These findings will aid in the development of an "accessible and inclusive product," ensuring that all visitors have equitable access to travel opportunities. By training professionals to accommodate diverse access needs, In-Tour contributed to a more inclusive society, enabling them to provide accessible services. Its success supported ongoing professional development and fostered a more welcoming tourism environment.

Keywords: inclusive tourism manager, frontline staff, curricula, training, blended courses, methodology, results.

1. Introduction

In 2023, as Covid restrictions were lifted, tourism numbers rebounded in many regions. The pandemic exposed the fragility of mass tourism, prompting a shift towards more responsible, sustainable, and resilient tourism practices. Today's focus is on enhancing the quality of tourism offers and experiences, benefiting local communities and promoting sustainable development. Accessible tourism is seen as a model for future quality tourism, supporting sustainable businesses, destinations, and communities while providing inclusive and quality experiences for all.

Accessible Tourism, also known as "Access Tourism," "Universal Tourism," "Inclusive Tourism," and "Barrier-free Tourism" in countries like Japan, is tourism and travel that accommodates everyone, including individuals with disabilities such as mobility, hearing, sight, cognitive, intellectual, and psychosocial disabilities, as well as older adults and those with temporary disabilities (Takayama Declaration, 2009). Accessible tourism enables people with access requirements, including mobility, vision, hearing and cognitive dimensions of access, to function independently and with equity and dignity through the delivery of universally designed tourism products, services and environments. This definition is inclusive of all people including those travelling with children in prams, people with disabilities and seniors (Darcy & Dickson, 2009, p. 34). Accessible Tourism is achieved through a collaborative Universal Design process involving stakeholders. This approach ensures that visitors with various access requirements, including mobility, vision, hearing, and cognitive needs, can function independently and equitably by providing accessible products, services, and environments.

The general demand for accessibility in Europe alone exceeded 120 million people in 2005, more than 27 per cent of the European population at the time. It is estimated that by the end of 2025 this demand will reach an approximated 160 million people. An analysis of the accessible tourism market size shows that 70 per cent of the population demanding accessibility have both the financial as well as the physical capabilities to travel, generating potential revenues of €88.6 billion by 2025. This represents a 65 per cent growth rate (2.56 per cent CAGR) from 2005. With the ageing of the baby boomer generation and their accompanying burden of disease, future disability rates are expected to increase. It is forecast that 35 per cent of the population in developed countries will be at least 60 years old in 2050. This demographic containing a greater proportion of seniors, unlike past generations, is seeking an active and adventurous experience for their post work lives, and tourism is seen as an important component of their quest for life experiences. In the post-Covid tourism landscape, the industry is increasingly prioritizing quality over quantity.

Evidence suggests there is substantial volume in the accessible tourism market, however an analysis of available information demonstrates that only a very small percentage of the market addresses the needs for

accessible tourism (Buhalis et al., 2005). It has been estimated that over 25 per cent of European citizens do not take holidays due to perceived barriers to accessible travel (Bowtell, 2015). The European Commission reports a need for better education and training in accessible tourism. While there is sufficient provision of tourism graduates, there is a lack of courses focused on accessibility, particularly in adult or continuing education. There is also a need for improved interaction between higher education institutions and the tourism industry.

In In-Tour project, the desk and field research identified specific tourism sector occupations and their training requirements using an Inclusive Tourism Service Design Methodology, which analysed customer journeys of individuals with disabilities. The study highlighted 27 management and 37 frontline staff occupations that require knowledge and skills in accessibility. These roles span customer service, facility management, marketing, transportation, accommodation, hospitality, food and beverage, and tourist activities, emphasizing the necessity for specialized training in accessible tourism.

1.1 Inclusive Tourism Manager Professional Profile

The Inclusive Tourism Manager (ITM) is a professional managing a business, a specific department or a local service, connected to the tourism industry and its inclusiveness. The ITM has a comprehensive knowledge of access requirements and is able to optimize all the resources within the context in which operates (from hotels to amusement parks, from restaurants to museums, etc.), realising an accessible physical/digital environment and being also capable to identify adequate training programmes for the internal staff. The ITM plans and applies intra-corporate procedures, structures and marketing strategies to ensure the provision of a physical/digital accessible environment, products and services for all customers. “Accessible Tourism” or “Inclusive Tourism” is not defined by ESCO as a specific sector within the service occupations. The IN-TOUR research has identified 26 managerial occupations that would benefit from training in inclusive/accessible tourism.

Table 1: For each Key Activity a list of competences is mapped for ITM.

KEY ACTIVITY	Competences
KA1: Analyse customers’ needs to provide accessible and inclusive environments, services, information and communication.	M.CC1.1 Identifying and collecting users’ needs, including accessibility requirements, by either collecting proper information through a direct interaction with the users or through secondary data. M.CC1.2 Identifying and collecting relevant market needs, opportunities and trends in the respective field of tourism also in terms of accessibility. M.CC.1.3 Identify the main development prospects and opportunities for the specific enterprise with respect to inclusive tourism. M.CC.1.4 Analysing the collected data regarding users’ needs, to develop creative and purposeful ideas for accessible and inclusive environments, services, information and communication.
KA2: Design, plan and implement overall accessible environments, services, information and communication, both physical and virtual.	M.CC2.1 Defining physical and virtual accessibility requirements, policies and strategies for the specific tourism offers. M.CC2.2 Developing a plan for the implementation according to previously defined accessibility policies and strategies with evidence of priorities and objectives to be achieved. M.CC2.3 Identifying and setting the proper actions and resources to support the implementation of the plan M.CC2.4. Identifying, implementing and evaluating an intra-organisational accessibility framework to improve the services.

<p>KA3: Monitor, assess and maintain the quality of the tourism offers in terms of accessibility and inclusiveness.</p>	<p>M.CC.3.1 Defining and keeping updated a monitoring plan to assess the quality and accessibility of the delivered tourism services according to the regulatory framework and quality standards. M.CC.3.2 Analysing the collected data to assess the quality and accessibility of the delivered tourism services according to the monitoring plan. M.CC.3.3 Tuning the accessibility policies and strategies according to the findings from monitoring activities and with the financial capabilities. M.CC.3.4 Ability to cope with situations marked by uncertainty, ambiguity & risk and develop purposeful solutions.</p>
<p>KA4: Manage human resources.</p>	<p>M.CC4.1 Managing human resources to build a team supporting an accessible and inclusive tourism experience for the respective field of tourism. M.CC4.2 Evaluate staff performance and identify skill gaps to be addressed through Continuing Professional Development (CPD) with a particular reference to accessibility issue and digital gaps. M.CC4.3. Recruiting personnel and schedule personnel shifts according to the staff performance and business development plan.</p>
<p>KA5 Communicate, interact and collaborate with customers and other stakeholders.</p>	<p>M.CC5.1 Creating a supportive and effective communication environment, using the most appropriate means of communication to understand and be understood. M.CC5.2 Communicating and interacting proficiently with customers, suppliers and interprofessional team. M.CC5.3 Designing, Implementing, and evaluating measures that minimize everyday digital and physical barriers to data collection, management and archiving. M.CC5.4 Managing digital safety. M.CC5.5 Interacting through digital technologies.</p>

2.1 Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff Profile

The Inclusive Tourism Front-line Staff professional (ITFS) is a practitioner of the tourism sector who interacts directly with customers (virtually or in presence) by providing suitable services according to their specific access requirements. These services may include communications and information, physical assistance, use of equipment, food and beverage services, accommodation, guiding, transportation and/or other tourist services. The ITFS professional has knowledge and understanding of how to cater for customers with a wide range of specific access requirements, thus ensuring - as far as possible - safe, equitable and independent conditions for all customers. The IN-TOUR project has identified 37 Front-line staff occupations that would benefit from training in inclusive/accessible tourism.

Table 2: For each Key Activity a list of competences is mapped for ITFS.

KEY ACTIVITY	Competences
<p>KA1: Understand customers’ access requirements, priorities, and requests and share them with the stakeholders involved in the service provision</p>	<p>CC1. Collecting information about customers’ access requirements, priorities, and specific requests, both directly and indirectly, and identifying relevant accessibility measures in order to provide a personalised service. CC2. Identifying other possible stakeholders involved in the service provision, who should be informed about customers’ access</p>

	requirements, priorities, and specific requests and share with them the relevant information in order to ensure a personalised service.
KA2: Interact effectively with customers and their companions	CC3. Using appropriate communication methods, styles according to the customers' attitude, culture and the purpose of communication. CC4. Enacting customer-oriented behaviours, guided by situational awareness and ability to adapt, in order to provide increased service performance and customer satisfaction.
KA3: Customise the service delivery to meet customers' specific access requirements	CC5. Delivering the service addressing the identified customer's access requirements, priorities and specific requests, collaborating with other service providers if needed. CC6. Analysing the service provision in order to identify new opportunities for improvement and to plan efficient use of resources for managing multiple requests.
KA4: Use available technologies or devices (including customers' own devices) to support the delivery of services	CC7. Using the available technologies/devices to support the personalised service and guiding the customer and their companions to use them safely and correctly. CC8. Responsibly searching, evaluating and managing data, information and digital content to support the delivery of services

Based on the analysis of the ITM and ITFS competencies the following accessibility-related knowledge, skills and competencies can be understood as the core set for both clusters. Following ESCO subdivision, it is indicated whether they represent a knowledge or a skill to be acquired:

1. Disability awareness
2. Understanding and knowledge of specific access requirements and accessibility for the entire customer service chain
3. Awareness and/or specific knowledge on food preparation protocols and provision of special diets meals
4. Skills for communicating and interacting with persons with disabilities and /or other specific access requirements
5. Empathy
6. Speaking English and preferably other foreign language(s), according to the specific location requirements
7. Managing and handling complaints and/or unforeseen situations in relation to customers with disabilities and/or other specific access requirements
8. Awareness and/or specific knowledge on food preparation protocols and provision of special diets meals
9. Knowledge of the entire accessible offer (facility, services and policy)
10. Awareness of existing emergency and evacuation plan and procedures
11. Web accessibility awareness and /or training on internationally recognised guidelines and standards for web/digital accessibility
12. Knowledge of food intolerances, allergens and ingredients for special diet meals
13. Networking / cooperating with other stakeholders who provide accessible offers and services
14. Knowledge of the general legal framework and national policies on accessibility

15. Sign language skills - different specific sign language to be defined for each case (only necessary for specific customers)
16. Skills in assisting people with specific access requirements and use of assistive equipment
17. Specific knowledge about plants and criteria for plant's selection in relation to persons with disabilities and/ or allergies (allergens, poisonous, rooting systems, trimming etc).
18. Knowledge of special cleaning materials, procedures, and tools for rooms regarding different allergies.

From the examination of ESCO occupations, essential skills, competencies, and knowledge have been identified for 27 Inclusive Tourism Manager profiles and 37 Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff profiles. These skills encompass a broad range of training content due to the diverse roles within the tourism sector. The profiles fall into two clusters: Managerial and Frontline Staff, which is crucial for designing training curricula for both groups.

Both clusters require complementary skills in accessibility and inclusion to serve tourists with disabilities or specific access needs. There is significant overlap in competencies between managers and frontline staff, particularly in disability awareness and customer service skills, such as interpersonal and communication abilities. Accessibility knowledge and skills are seen as additional to the general skills required for these occupations and can also be provided through continuing professional development (CPD) courses for upskilling. It is emphasized that there are multiple managerial and frontline roles in tourism, each necessitating tailored accessibility training to fit specific professional duties.

2. Description of the ITM Pilot Course

The ITM pilot course covers the needs of executives/managers working in the wider tourism sector, with the necessary knowledge, digital and transferable skills to provide quality accessible tourism services to the seniors, to people with disabilities, families with small children and other population groups with specific access requirements. This course is addressed to the needs of the manager who works or would like to work in the field of tourism, in order to provide services in accessible tourism or tourism for all. This course covers the needs of managers for developing skills in digital services and accessible tourism. The course targets the needs of graduates of Departments of Tourism, Departments of Business Administration or related departments, senior executives or owners in businesses or institutions of the tourism sector.

ITM learners would gain the following proficiencies and competencies:

1. Designing sustainable solutions.
2. Identifying and analyzing tourism market needs.
3. Designing frameworks, policies, and strategies for accessibility in tourism.
4. Using financial planning principles, managing project risks, and leading a team to implement accessibility frameworks.
5. Effective digital communication.

The ITM course included learning material, additional material, quizzes, cases studies for ten (10) modules:

Module 1 Data Management & Analytics

Module 2 Communication Strategies

Module 3 Human Resource Strategy

Module 4 Market research & Consumer Behaviour

Module 5 Quality evaluation, organization/operation monitoring & impact assessment

Module 6 Project management

Module 7 Decision making & change management.

Module 8 Designing sustainable solutions & digital content

Module 9 Strategies and Technologies for accessible tourism

Module 10 Strategic Development through innovation

Upon completing the ITM course, learners are able to:

- Identify and apply techniques for customer support and service tailored to accessibility needs.
- Describe at least two methods for ensuring digital security, data protection, and effective data management.
- Identify accessibility requirements and standards for effective communication with customers, colleagues, and stakeholders.
- Describe technologies, devices, and tools that support accessible and personalized services.
- Understand and differentiate the values created when providing inclusive tourism services.
- Recognize and apply different quality standards and guidelines relevant to the tourism sector and accessible tourism.
- Describe the basic elements of project management and financial planning.
- Use at least two technologically accessible solutions to enhance services and products.
- Develop a financial roadmap for creating accessible and inclusive environments, services, information, and communication.
- Create digital solutions and policies for the accessible tourism sector.
- Apply various tools to forecast and plan human resource needs.
- Demonstrate different patterns of behavior and expertise in digital environments.
- Assess staff skills and the level of inclusivity within a company.
- Determine priorities, allocate resources, and reassign tasks effectively as an inclusive tourism manager.
- Exhibit leadership, teamwork, and interpersonal skills in managing teams.
- Distinguish between professional and inter-professional communication.
- Evaluate and enhance supervisory actions and decisions to improve the work environment and staff employability.
- Anticipate needs, priorities, opportunities, and market trends in the tourism industry.
- Propose effective approaches to raise public awareness of accessible and inclusive tourism.

The course, lasting 8 months and totaling 550 hours (22 ECTS credits), was designed for Managers of the Tourism Industry seeking to enhance their knowledge and skills in providing quality accessible services. It was at an EQF6 educational level and conducted in Greek. The pilot course was offered free of charge, targeting graduates from Tourism, Business Administration, or related departments who are senior executives or business owners in the tourism sector. It was open to learners across Greece.

3. Description of the ITFS Pilot Course

The ITFS pilot course covers the needs of covers the needs of frontline staff working in the wider tourism sector with the necessary knowledge, digital and transferable skills to provide quality accessible tourism services to seniors, to people with disabilities, families with small children and other population groups with specific access requirements. This course is addressed ddressed to the needs of frontline staff who work or would like to work in the tourism sector, in order to provide services in accessible tourism or tourism for all. The course targets the needs of Graduate students or graduates of Tourism departments, departments of Business

Administration or related departments, graduates of programs of Vocational Training Institutes - IEK with emphasis on Tourism, employees in companies belonging to the tourism sectorl.

ITFS learners would gain the following proficiencies and competencies:

1. Gain competence in providing services that meet specific access requirements of clients.
2. Develop skills in searching, evaluating, and managing data and digital content to support service provision.
3. Learn to use available technologies and tools to support personalized services.

The ITFS course included learning material, additional material, quizzes, cases studies for ten (10) modules:

Module 1 Data Management & Analytics

Module 2 Social Justice, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

Module 3 Digital Technology interaction

Module 4 Stakeholders Identification, Assessment and Management

Module 5 Assistive & Personalization Technology

Module 6 Business Process Analysis

Module 7 Service Request Management

Module 8 Communication Techniques & Collaboration Skills

Module 9 Insight-driven marketing

Module 10 Customer-oriented behaviors

Upon completing the ITFS course, learners are able to:

- Identify basic principles of inclusive communication based on customer access requirements.
- Recognize at least two factors affecting intercultural communication.
- Differentiate between active/passive and verbal/non-verbal/paralanguage communication methods.
- Identify useful information to collaborate with other stakeholders.
- Identify accessible technologies/devices to facilitate service.
- Develop digital skills related to accessible and inclusive tourism.
- Adapt resources to provide accessible customer service.
- Apply problem-solving techniques to address technology-related issues in service delivery.
- Implement methods to protect devices and digital content.
- Provide personalized services in collaboration with stakeholders.
- Ensure reliability and privacy in service provision.
- Protect personal data and manage it securely in digital environments.
- Develop welcoming and pleasant communication with customers based on trust and understanding of accessibility requirements.
- Apply communication methods and tools to meet specific customer accessibility needs.
- Develop communication and collaboration skills for personalized service.
- Demonstrate autonomy and empathy in providing appropriate services based on clients' specific needs.
- Deliver effective, efficient, and inclusive services based on social justice, diversity, equality, and inclusion.
- Reflect on and resolve issues arising from customer interactions.
- Apply a flexible approach to resolving problems and queries.

The ITFS course, lasting 8 months and totaling 500 hours (20 ECTS credits), was designed for frontline staff working in the wider tourism sector seeking to enhance their knowledge and skills in providing quality accessible services. It was at an EQF5 educational level and conducted in Greek. The pilot course was offered free of charge, targeting senior students or graduates of Tourism Departments, Business Administration Departments or related departments, graduates of VET programmes with a focus on Tourism, who work in businesses that fall within the Tourism sector. It was open to learners across Greece.

4. Implementation of the Greek Pilot Courses

Both courses were promoted through the Hellenic Open University, DAISy Research Group, and Training & Lifelong Learning Centre (KEDIVIM) websites, as well as on their social media platforms. It was also advertised through targeted emails to relevant stakeholders and tourism VET providers. Applications were submitted online and selected based on the evaluation of the application forms, educational and professional background, and IT and study competencies.

The full-time courses used a range of educational materials, including open resources (e-books, papers), videos, and original content created by the academic manager. Each module was managed by designated tutors and included compulsory and additional (optional) materials. The materials were available online in digital format, with options for local storage and printing. Learners could also upload assignments for evaluation. After the course ended, materials remained accessible through the e-learning platform developed by the DAISy research group of Hellenic Open University (<https://learning.in-tour.eu>).

The courses' design incorporated open and distance e-learning methodologies, featuring asynchronous study and activities to promote learner autonomy, with supplementary synchronous sessions as needed. The primary mode of instruction was distance learning, supported by both synchronous and asynchronous methods. In addition to the scheduled lessons, tutors could engage with learners through written communication, such as messages, announcements, or forum discussions on the platform. They also interacted verbally during the regular online Zoom sessions, which occurred once or twice a week. The two Greek pilot courses included practical assignments that learners completed at their workplace. These assignments were submitted on the e-learning platform and assessed by tutors.

To earn ECTS credits, learners needed to complete all modules and self-assessment tests with at least 75% overall accuracy and practical assignments with at least 70% overall accuracy. Learners received a 'Certificate of Continuing Education' and an 'Annex to the Certificate,' detailing the course duration, teaching method, ECTS credits, and module titles. Certificates were signed by the Scientific Director, President, and Director of the Training & Lifelong Learning Centre. In the case of unsuccessful completion, learners received a 'Certificate of Attendance.'

5. Teachers' Evaluation of Greek ITM and ITFS Pilot Courses

The three teachers involved in the pilot courses were familiar with the concept but had not previously taught similar topics. They found the provided materials very helpful, though one wished for more details. In addition to the IN-TOUR materials, they developed their own resources. The teachers rated the support from IN-TOUR project representatives highly (4.6/5), noting excellent cooperation and prompt responses to issues. They agreed that the student workload was appropriate, the skills taught were practical, and the learning outcomes aligned with the average learner's achievements. Overall, they felt the learning outcomes were verifiable, accessible, and consistent with the course content, and that the assessments accurately reflected the qualification level.

6. Learners' Evaluation of Greek ITM and ITFS Pilot Courses

Concerning the evaluation of the Greek ITM pilot course, out of 44 participants, seven (7) engaged in the first evaluation round. Only one was unfamiliar with Inclusive Tourism, while others had varying degrees of prior exposure. Most respondents were enthusiastic about learning more about the subject. Twenty-five participants completed the second questionnaire, rating the pilot course an average of 4.36 out of 5. Most participants (22 out of 25) found the workload appropriate. Those with prior knowledge of Inclusive Tourism (23 out of 25) felt this background helped them manage the course content effectively. Feedback on the teachers was positive, with 23 out of 25 participants recognizing their competence. However, 10 participants were not convinced of the relevance of Inclusive Tourism, and fifteen (15) had no strong opinion on this aspect.

The accessibility and quality of training materials were generally well-received. Participants (22 out of 25) found the course easy to navigate and appreciated the logical module organization (23 out of 25). Learning outcomes were clear to most (23 out of 25). A few suggested improvements for the materials and teaching approach. Seventeen (17) participants found Work-Based Learning (WBL) beneficial for understanding Inclusive Tourism, and fifteen (15) felt there was sufficient time to cover relevant content. Eighteen (18) participants agreed on the importance of Inclusive Tourism for practitioners. Assessments were viewed as well-aligned with course content and learning outcomes. Participants felt well-prepared for the assessments, which were deemed appropriately challenging. Some requested feedback sessions for their assessments.

Concerning the evaluation of the Greek ITFS pilot course, feedback from both questionnaires reflects a positive assessment of this pilot course. Participants appreciated the course content, found the assessments appropriate, and highly valued the work-based learning (WBL) component. They noted that the workload was manageable, the training materials were accessible, and the teachers demonstrated competence. The course successfully highlighted the significance of Inclusive Tourism and equipped participants with relevant skills for their tourism careers. Assessments were considered appropriately challenging, though some participants suggested incorporating feedback sessions. Participants engaged in Work-Based Learning (WBL) through various methods, including class discussions, assignments, interactions with hotel entrepreneurs, and accommodation visits. Most participants strongly agreed that WBL deepened their understanding of Inclusive Tourism and that there was sufficient time to cover relevant content. They acknowledged the importance of Inclusive Tourism for practitioners and felt that the program enhanced their awareness of the needs of individuals with disabilities.

The consensus was that diversity and inclusion are becoming increasingly vital in the tourism industry. Feedback indicated that the course workload was manageable, suggesting an effective design that prevented participants from feeling overwhelmed. The training materials were deemed accessible and current, with additional resources, such as scientific journal articles, providing valuable in-depth knowledge. Overall, the course design and materials effectively supported the participants' learning experience. In summary, the ITFS course successfully conveyed the importance of Inclusive Tourism, with teachers playing a crucial role in delivering content and supporting participants throughout their learning journey.

7. Impact of the Greek ITM and ITFS Pilot Courses

The feedback was predominantly positive, with 17 of the 25 participants in ITM course strongly agreeing that their awareness of Inclusive Tourism issues had significantly increased. Nineteen participants felt they gained valuable new knowledge beneficial for their future careers in tourism, while five reported acquiring new skills relevant to their work. Overall, ITM participants rated their experience with the IN-TOUR pilot course highly. They found the course materials and organization to be of high quality and appreciated the expertise of the

instructors. The work-based learning (WBL) component and assessments were well-received, enhancing the overall learning experience. The ITM course successfully improved participants' understanding of Inclusive Tourism and provided them with useful skills and knowledge for their careers.

The IFS course participants provided overwhelmingly positive feedback on the teachers' competence and their effectiveness in delivering the Inclusive Tourism modules. This feedback underscores the teachers' essential role in enhancing the learning experience and guiding participants. It also suggests that the teachers successfully communicated the importance and relevance of Inclusive Tourism. The strong consensus among participants about the significance of Inclusive Tourism for industry professionals reflects its growing recognition within the field. The ITFS course appears to have significantly raised participants' awareness and understanding of this importance. Participants also praised the course for equipping them with new skills and knowledge applicable to their work. This further highlights the practical value and relevance of the course content. Overall, the feedback indicates that the ITFS course effectively conveyed the importance of Inclusive Tourism, with teachers playing a crucial role in delivering content and supporting the participants' learning journey.

8. Recommendation for optimization of the Greek pilot courses

This section outlines key areas for improvement in future iterations of the Greek ITM and ITFS pilot courses, focusing on target audience, curriculum development, multidisciplinary collaboration, and flexible learning options. To enhance the course, incorporating more visual and multimedia resources, such as videos on inclusivity and accessibility, is recommended. The pilot courses in Greece primarily addressed the needs of tourism staff, managers, and professionals. However, the lengthy duration of the courses, spanning over 6.5 months from December to June or July, contributed to higher dropout rates.

In the ITM course, 45 initially expressed interest, 43 enrolled, but only 21 completed, with 15 passing. In the ITFS course, 43 enrolled, but only 16 completed, with 14 passing. The tourism season, starting in April, limited participants' ability to complete the course on time. Hellenic Open University (HOU) is committed to maintaining the ITM and ITFS courses through its Lifelong Learning Center (KEDIVIM) beyond the In-Tour project. The courses, which have proven successful, will continue as part of HOU's offerings. Certificates for tourism professionals will support their ongoing success. HOU is dedicated to ensuring these courses' sustainability with financial backing.

The In-Tour e-learning platform, developed by the DAISy research group at HOU, features Open Educational Resources and adheres to WCAG standards for accessibility. HOU and DAISy will work to ensure the platform's long-term sustainability. Future courses should enhance interdisciplinary collaboration by involving external experts, such as accessibility specialists, sociologists, and cultural anthropologists. Their insights will enrich the course content and materials. Offering hands-on experiences, internships, or field trips to inclusive tourism destinations is crucial. Practical exposure helps learners apply theoretical knowledge in real-world settings. The Greek pilot courses included practical training within participants' work environments.

Inviting guest lecturers and industry experts to share their knowledge and experiences will provide diverse perspectives and valuable industry connections. Implementing regular assessments and feedback mechanisms, including surveys and evaluations from students and industry professionals, will help gauge and improve course effectiveness. Facilitating networking with industry stakeholders through events, guest speaker series, or networking sessions will help students build valuable connections in the inclusive tourism sector. Incorporating these recommendations will help create a more comprehensive and impactful inclusive tourism manager course, better preparing learners for the field's challenges and opportunities.

9. Conclusions

Accessibility is still not seen as a game changer by all destinations despite a market of 1.3 billion people with significant disability in 2023, and 1 in 6 persons expected to reach the age of 65 by 2050. In Europe alone, "baby boomers" already account for over one third of the EU population and 70% of the EU citizens with disability have financial means to travel. Experts in the field discussed how best to cater to this growing market and offer tourism experiences in the spirit of the Universal Design, so they can be enjoyed by all people, with or without disabilities. Debates also centred on the importance of social inclusivity and accessibility for sustainable tourism and the huge economic benefits the sector can reap by putting better access measures in place.

The comprehensive analysis of the Greek pilot courses for Inclusive Tourism Manager (ITM) and Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff (ITFS) within the In-Tour project has yielded valuable insights that can inform future curriculum and instructional improvements. Key findings indicate notable differences in learner demographics, needs, and expectations across the courses. Overall, participant feedback from the surveys was positive, with high ratings for course content, appropriate assessments, and the Work-Based Learning (WBL) component. Participants found the workload manageable, appreciated the accessibility of training materials, and praised the instructors' competence. The course effectively conveyed the importance of Inclusive Tourism and equipped participants with relevant skills and knowledge for their future roles in the tourism industry. The In-Tour e-learning platform adhered to specific web accessibility standards to accommodate learners with accessibility needs. Additional tailored accommodations included extensions for assessments and deadlines, technical support, and the use of assistive technologies during lessons and exams.

Both the Inclusive Tourism Frontline Staff (ITFS) and Inclusive Tourism Manager (ITM) curricula are structured similarly, with the assessment addressing both unless specified otherwise. The curricula are modular, with learning outcomes grouped into Areas of Learning (AoLs) related to knowledge and skills, aligned with core competencies mapped to the profiles of ITM and ITFS. This modular approach allows for easy adaptation and implementation in various contexts, offering flexibility and customization possibilities for teachers and staff. Personal and transversal competences are also included to support national or regional adaptation and implementation. Taking the list of Inclusive Tourism occupations identified, the ESCO database was used as the source for identifying the complete lists of knowledge, competences and skills attributed to each occupational profile.

The modular structure's functionality has been demonstrated in pilot trainings, which showcased flexibility by distributing content through different teaching modalities and selecting specific modules for practical assignments in Work-Based Learning (WBL). The curricula's adaptability is further highlighted by its successful organization around different key areas. Positive student feedback and feedback loops confirm the curricula's support for creating modular course designs, although more guidance is needed for new staff or those unfamiliar with ECVET and EQF systems.

To enhance future iterations of the courses and maintain relevance in the evolving field of Inclusive Tourism, the following recommendations are made:

- Diversify Learning Resources: Introduce multimedia and interactive resources such as videos, simulations, and case studies to cater to different learning styles.
- Regular Feedback Mechanism: Implement a structured system for continuous feedback from participants and instructors to improve course effectiveness.

- Industry Collaboration: Strengthen ties with the tourism industry to keep the courses aligned with current trends. Incorporate guest lectures, industry projects, and internships to enhance real-world relevance.
- Incorporate Technology Trends: Integrate emerging technologies and tools relevant to the tourism sector to enrich the learning experience.
- Tailor Content for Diverse Audiences: Customize course content to address the diverse backgrounds and needs of participants, considering factors such as age, experience level, and cultural background.
- Promote Collaboration Among Participants: Encourage group projects, forums, and collaborative assignments to enhance peer-to-peer learning and networking.
- Continuous Professional Development for Instructors: Offer ongoing training and development opportunities to keep instructors updated on the latest developments in inclusive tourism.
- Expand Practical Components: Increase hands-on experiences such as field trips, case studies, and real-world projects to bridge theory and practice.
- Accessibility Audits: Conduct regular audits of course materials and the e-learning platform to ensure they remain inclusive and comply with the latest accessibility standards.
- Evaluate and Refine Assessment Methods: Review and refine assessments to accurately measure participants' understanding and application of inclusive tourism concepts, using a mix of practical assignments and exams.
- Flexibility in Learning Paths: Provide flexible learning paths to accommodate different learning speeds and preferences, offering optional modules or specific areas of focus within the broader course.
- Promote Lifelong Learning: Emphasize the importance of continued learning and professional development beyond course completion, providing resources and guidance for participants to stay engaged with industry advancements.

By implementing these recommendations, future courses can better meet participants' needs and prepare them for the challenges and opportunities in the inclusive tourism sector. Through training, managers and staff need to understand the importance and value of access and inclusion, in order to make any accessibility improvements in facilities and services.

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Teaching design courses at a distance: A case of cultural collaboration between a Design Course and a Museum

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Abstract

How can a design course be taught in distance, and furthermore, what kind of applications could occur in the context of the course? How can distant learners in a design course gain a feeling of community and avoid feeling detached from their design peers? This paper presents a case study of a multilevel collaboration between the Thematic Unit *Graphic Design* of the Master Program *Graphic Arts and Multimedia* of the Hellenic Open University, and the Archaeological Museum of Patras.

Keywords: Archeological Museum, Mycenaic Artefacts, Design, Education, Distant Learning, Design Projects, Student Show, Homer, Epic Poetry, Motion Typography

1. Introduction

Since 2017 and for two years, until the covid-19 pandemic postponed all cultural exhibitions, the activities of the Archaeological Museum of Patras stood for many years as an inspiration for the assignments of the course of Graphic Design at the Hellenic Open University's Master in Graphic Arts and Multimedia. At the same period, the Museum offered its exhibits as subjects of contemplation for our students. The bilateral collaboration among professors, curators, and students provided a common goal, and lead not only to the obvious projects of posters and printing material design, but also to the synthesis and mise-en-scene of sensitive motion type animations. These could also be viewed as augmented reality animations, which the user could activate through her smart phone and watch over the original exhibits per se. Thus, new interpretations would emerge, occurring from the overlay of animated audiovisual content over precious archeological objects. These motion typography design outputs from the assignments, were to be seen alongside exhibits (via AR) and eventually were shown as projections on a central wall of the museum in a final student's design exhibition.

The goal of these assignments was to provoke an out of the box approach of contemporary design, which should be disseminated not only to the direct students, but also to larger parts of the society. The Archaeological Museum of Patras (Fig1, right), with its unique collection, its innovative architecture and openminded staff gave Distant learning students in a Design course, the opportunity to design for the society of visitors as well as to expand this audience via the special events which took place on the spot. (Fig.1, Fig.2).

The gain of this cooperation was multilevel: The students and their tutors were inspired and motivated by this important museum and its exhibits. The whole Thematic Unit came up with an Augmented Reality (AR) App, powered by HP Reveal. The motion type animations became interactive and tangible, narrative audiovisual

compositions overlaid to antique scalp and objects. The students' works were presented to a larger audience while the museum's exhibits took an augmented dimension.

The thematics related to the Museum actions every year, have provided a clear motivation for the project and gave the group momentum and a sense of purpose in their assignments, something to look forward to, and at the end a feeling of pride and belonging to the academic group.

The cooperation started in the academic year 2017, resulting in an exhibition with selected students works stemming from thematic assignments, such as posters and visual material relating to the museums planned events for that year. By mid May the course assignments are completed, and students are preparing for their term exams, therefore making May a good timing for the show to take place. The cooperation was similarly fruitful on the following years, with shows in 2018 and 2019, at the International Museum Day, annually celebrated in May 18th. For the shows, the School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design and the Hellenic Open University released related press kits, with attribution to the students whose work was selected for the show, and jointly co-organised an opening and a closing party each year (Fig.1). The opening and closing events provided an opportunity for students and tutors alike to travel for a short city break, in order to see the show and also meet in person (Fig.2), at the end of the year's remote online learning academic experience.

The exercise was repeated again in the academic year 2024, nevertheless in the post Covid area, for a number of reasons, it has become more constrained to plan an exhibition in the Museum itself. Yet the course keeps this practice alive, by striving to exhibit in other venues and occasions, and is used as best practice for motivating remote design students towards a common goal, and related student work is to be presented in Crete in 18-19 October 2024 as part of the Chania Film Festival.

Figure 1: Poster of HOU student exhibition 2018 (left) at the Patras Archeological Museum (right)

2. Design courses at the School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design, HOU

2.1 Hellenic Open University: Design courses via distance learning

The School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design, of the Hellenic Open University, offers a course on Graphic Arts and Multimedia: a two year, 120 ECTS master course, offered online, to aprox. 60 distance learners per year. Students are primarily over the age of 30, that also work, have families and other obligations, as is often the case with Open Education Institutes. The Hellenic Open University, is an open and distance learning University, with its organizational premises based in Patras, Greece.

The Master of Arts “Graphic Arts – Multimedia” provides specialized knowledge in the broader scientific and modern cognitive subject of Graphic Arts Technology and Multimedia. The course combines knowledge: a) in the field of arts and visual creation, communication design and creative design for print and electronic media with the help of visual communication, b) in the broader scientific and technological field of graphic arts, publishing, printing, typography and packaging, and with the study of the fields of design of web applications, interactive design systems and interface design. The MA Programme of Studies aims to offer students the opportunity to cultivate their creativity and acquire knowledge and skills in the creative design of printed and electronic media, in the administrative, managerial, technological and production processes of graphic arts, publishing, printing, design and production of packaging, as well as in the design and development of multimedia applications and web applications with emphasis on the study of interactive systems and applications.

The course is taught via four Thematic Units. One of the Thematic Units is Graphic Design, that aims to cultivate students’ creativity in visual communication via design projects assignments, in print and digital media alike. Assignments are selected every year, following the course curriculum, taking into considerations synergies, events and design competitions whereby the students can participate in with their work, if they wish so. One such synergy has been achieved with a memorandum of cooperation with the Patras Archeological Museum, as the Museum and the Hellenic Open University and both located in Patras city, in western Greece.

Figure 2: HOU Graphic Arts Multimedia, Student Show 2019 at the Patras Archeological Museum

2.1 Challenges in Teaching Design in Open and Distance Learning

Teaching a Design course via Distance Learning, at an Open University structure can be a challenge both for students and professors, due to the asynchronous and individual characteristics of tuition. In traditional Design courses it is expected for students to work synchronously together in situ, often in a Studio class, to evolve their design thinking skills while working on project assignments. Design Studio is a primary teaching method used in Design, Architecture and Art classes, to this date. In the Design Studio, students gather and work together in situ, so as to engage hands-on on project assignments where they learn design skills, exchange,

test and evolve their ideas, and receive feedback from their peers and tutors. In the Studio students learn to produce a high ratio of Ideas, and address the design problem from different perspectives, thus enhancing the design brief. Iteratively they develop their ideas into a specific solution (through testing and consensus).

Teaching a Design course with distance learning, in the Hellenic Open University, poses the challenge of students not being exchanging ideas in situ. In addition, distance learners have difficulties to feel as part of the academic community. In the Master of Arts Graphic Arts-Multimedia, tutors tried to remedy this by arranging an in situ activity or event on a voluntary basis, in different cities in Greece where students would possibly visit. In addition to efforts encouraging face to face encounters with the courses academic community, attempts are also made to replicate the design studio experience virtually, via Social media, as reported in (Fotaris et al, 2015).

(Croft et al 2010) examines the experiences of distance learning students at UWE, and in particular addresses exploring collaborative study issues and student isolation. Their recommendations include: clarify expectations by providing service level agreements; motivate by ensuring 'staging points'; utilise student generated content within the material; have a human centered writing approach in the course material; and introducing mechanisms to provide insight to other students perspectives on course material. Along these lines, and the latter points in particular, the Graphic Arts Multimedia MA approach to design assignments that incorporate museum curatorial perspectives, discussed here, provides students with a shared common goal and the opportunity to discuss design perspectives. Students' selected projects are also discussed in the lectures, acting as student generated content – case studies for the MA course discussion.

As part of these efforts to enhance the experience of distance learners, and provide common goals and experiences that promote the feeling of belonging to an academic community, while enriching the learning assignments, the School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design -via the course director and tutor- and Patras Archeological Museum – via a curator - have formed a collaboration, and the two organisations have established a memorandum of cooperation.

3. The Archeological Museum of Patras

3.1 Homer's role in Cultural diplomacy

The influence of Homeric Epics, in terms of Cultural Diplomacy, has been enormous. Homer was the so called 'influencer' of the ancient and modern world, from the 8th century BC to the present. Bearing in mind that the best way to create awareness about Cultural Heritage is to "make Heritage part of the educational process", the cooperating bodies such as the Archaeological Museum of Patras and the School of Applied Arts - Hellenic Open University, formed a connective educational Art-Net, a cultural network that ended with a pop-up exhibition held in The Archaeological Museum of Patras for the celebration of ICOM's International Museum Day 2019. Design students created animated typography videos using Homer's verses, as they relate to certain museum artifacts, thus providing a contemporary multimedia interpretation of the Homeric verse. This collaboration highlighted the crucial need of cooperation among Cultural and Educational Organizations in order to promote new methodological approaches aiming to attract young public and even evolve in terms of professional development. How is the Homeric world verified through the findings of the Archaeological Museum of Patras? What are the traditions surrounding death and burial and how can everyday life in the "world" of Homer be accessible to the public through alternative educational networks?

The assignments have focused on specific exhibits of the Museum of Patras of the Mycenaean and Geometric times, in comparison to the Homeric epics, which, regardless of the actual time of their writing, testify to the customs of an Achaean society that constantly evolved. More specifically, this presentation attempts to combine three scientific fields: Archaeology, Museum Education and Informatics. Despite the complexity of the sciences, having as case study the ancient artefacts of the Archaeological Museum of Patras this presentation attempts to decode the use of ancient objects (weapons, jewelry, pottery) which constitute an ideal landscape observation of behavior and identity of artists and the general population to which they belong.

In the present study we did not attempt to refer to issues concerning the poetic genius, the originality and the realistic representation of the Homeric Epics, which have been the subject of controversy especially from the 18th century onwards. Homer is considered as an intellectual. In the Epics, reality coexists with the imagination at specified rates and in a predetermined historical context which is supposed to belong to the period of prehistoric times and specifically, to the Mycenaean. In fact, it reflects elements of the 8th century (the geometric era), in which he lived.

3.2 The mycenaic Collection, at the Archeological museum of Patras

The exhibits of the museum that could inspire the student assignment were selected carefully from the museum collection, and indicated in the student assignment brief. The artefacts, gobblets, craters, arrowheads, among others (i.e. Fig.3) were presented in the student assignment brief, along with Indicative references to Homeric epics, related to military equipment (swords, spears, arrows, helmets, leggings), (see *Odyssey*, Rhapsody χ , 326-327). Specific Homeric verses were marked and given as part of the student assignments, for creating motion typography representation of the Homeric text (Fig.4).

The selections curated and given as student assignments, from the the mycenaic collection, at the Archeological museum of Patras, are described in detail below in this section.

The mycenaic collection: Private Life Section of the Archaeological Museum exhibits objects related to daily life and the occupations of the inhabitants that come from settlements and cemeteries in the periods under study. Among them household utensils, tools, toiletries, jewelry and other small items are exposed. The section of *Public Life* includes -among others- representative samples of the military equipment, while the *Necropolis*, through its objects and information material, offers information about the typical funeral rites and the afterlife. The data related to the exhibits may not be sufficient on their own, however, their role is distinct when their final valuation includes data related to their location (e.g. in tombs) and their – occasionally- ostentatious (in situ) placement.

Especially the study of exhibits relating to offerings, (as already known from the *Odyssey*, Rhapsody α , 290-292), highlights the participation of the living in burial rites with customary behaviors, from which conclusions emerge for the society of the periods under study. From the study of the offerings themselves, conclusions regarding the external contacts of the settlements under study and the commercial circulation of the goods can emerge.

In all the vessels, the gobblets, the pre-eminent drinking vessel of the Mycenaean, have a primary role. Homer makes clear references to this vessel, the use of which is characteristic of high prestige persons (see cup of Nestor, *Iliad*, Rhapsody Λ , 632-635). In the Collection of the Museum of Patras, the type of the vase is represented indicatively in Private Life Collection (Showcase 5 in the museum). Three Vessels (no 5, 10, 11) coming from the Mycenaean cemetery of Voudeni, had their surface covered with thin sheets of tin imitating

silver vessels. The type is also represented in Public Life Collection (Museum Showcase 48) with three other vessels (no. 2, 3, 4 of the showcase), of similar origin and material. Vases made of valuable materials are also testified in the Odyssey, declaring the prestige of their owners.

In general, in Homeric Epics, small or large-scale symposium is recorded as a process repeated by Homeric heroes on any occasion securing their own status as heroes. Already in the LH IIIC period the goblets are abandoned and we have the emergence of vessels that incorporate the activities of mixing, drinking and eating. The presence of the goblets supported the power of the "ἄναξ" and their abolition and the use of different and more common vessels, symbolized a more noble relationship and cooperation between the participants. Other vessels used in similar gatherings which are exhibited in the museum of Patras and at the same time are mentioned in the Homeric epics are (among others) the cups, the oinochoae and the craters. The Collection of the Museum of Patras presents a representative typology of cups, which are indicatively mentioned in Showcase 5 (Private Life Collection): no7 tripod cup with elevated handle from Kallithea (14th century B.C); no15 cup from Clauss with fish decoration inside (14th century B.C).

In the Museum of Patras and specifically in the Public Life Collection, weapons are exhibited in groups which are often accompanied by jewelry or cosmetics such as razors and hairpins, reminiscent of Homer's characterization of the Achaeans. Characteristic is the set of finds that accompanied the male burial of the chamber tomb B in Spentzes, Kallithea, in Showcase 52 (12th/early 11th century B.C). It includes a knife, a razor, tweezers, the Naue II type sword, the spearhead, the boar tusks of a boar tusk helmet lining, among others. Equally representative is the set of objects that accompanied burial II of chamber tomb A. The group of offerings is consisted of a spearhead, a sword, the helmet lamina, and a pair of bronze greaves. Echoes of burials with weapons from the Mycenaean period reach the end of the 8th century. At this period the spear and the sword are the main weapons and specifically the sword is an evolution of the well-known type of Naue II, which is now made of iron. The weaponry of this period is also comprised of knives and spearheads.

Figure 3: Mycenaic Arrows and ceramics from the museum showcases.

Figure 4: Motion typography snapshot presenting a view on the Homeric verses, (the verse was about the army throwing arrows, and, in turn, related to the arrowhead artefacts of the museum).

4. Cooperation of the Archeological Museum of Patras and the Open University School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design

Bearing in mind that the best way to create awareness about Cultural Heritage is to "make Heritage part of the educational process", the cooperating bodies such as the Archaeological Museum of Patras and the School of Applied Arts - Hellenic Open University, formed a connective educational Art-Net, a Heritage Educational Hub, a cultural network that ended with a pop-up exhibition held in The Archaeological Museum of Patras for the celebration of ICOM's International Museum Day 2019. The importance of creating an educational program was based on new approaches. Our Heritage Educational Hub was focused on this new philosophy; HEH was about reforming museum into an intellectual, pleasant and creative interactive cell outlining the importance of Homeric Epics through educational, formal or non-formal procedures and to present an interdisciplinary educational Cultural Network Project, combining Archaeology, Museology and Applied Arts. The interdisciplinary approach and creative methodology of Homeric's Epics and museum artifacts promotes new methods that facilitate students to understand the multiplicity of museum artifacts in order to formulate alternative interpretations and gain knowledge.

The mission of the educational project with the engagement of postgraduate students of the Hellenic Open University was to use its Mycenaean collection and the Homeric Epics as a tool of knowledge and pleasure. It was about reforming museum into a creative Heritage Hub by stimulating active participation and interaction together with the use of animation typography.

The postgraduate students of the School of Applied Arts were given the option to select carefully chosen exhibits of the Mycenaean collection of the Archaeological Museum by the curator and the archaeologist, accompanied with the text of the Homeric Epics and under the supervision of their Professor according to the questioning "How is the Homeric world verified through the findings of the Archaeological Museum of Patras", in order to animate the lyric text of Homer, Iliad and Odyssey by creating an animated video and visualize the museum artifact.

The archaic lyric poetry of Homer is one of the most famous poetry of all times. It is a narrative storytelling of heroes and their deeds with the purpose to teach morals and beliefs to society. Homer, as Plato said, has been the great Educator of all people. Homer's Iliad and Odyssey is a vital text that demonstrates common values and beliefs, enriches our memory and stimulates our mind. The Epics are influential texts that have inspired every citizen of the world. The educational project was an exploratory, experiential and interdisciplinary approach through the Epics of Homer, Odyssey and Iliad through the more contemporary translation of the Greek philologist and writer Dr Dimitris Maronitis.

It is by all means an influential poetry, a vital text, with a strong impact through all ages. Bearing in mind that new characteristics have to be defined when developing museum programs for the near future, the relationship between heritage, museums and educational context is reconsidered, with the emerging notion of what we can call the 'expanded museum'. In this context, we curated this creative hub for heritage focusing increasingly on the intergenerational dialogue in a society. Museums are changing, the world is changing, and societies are changing. Museums adjust to their important role as cultural and educational actors.

The main thematic context comprised Mycenaean artifacts of the three permanent exhibition collections of the Archaeological Museum of Patras such as Private Life, Public Life and Necropolis, towards to a holistic museum strategy that addressed issues such as interpreting value, learning, creativeness, inclusivity, interaction and innovation. Homer is not only a pioneer but had a modern perspective in illustrating the Archaic and Greek World. Taking into consideration that the Museum is an environment of non-formal education in

which we accept that each person learns differently, emphasis was placed on different interpretive means to satisfy each different audience through a holistic and experiential approach to meet modern requirements related to the public.

Figure 5: A snapshot of a student motion typography of the Homeric Verse, in Youtube

Students from the master course of the School of Applied Arts, Hellenic Open University were given the chance to be creative combining artifacts and lyric poetry highlighting the importance of everyday life and afterlife customs of the ancient Greek World.

Moreover, students created animated typography videos using Homer’s verses (Fig. 5, 6), related to certain museum artifacts (Fig. 3, 4), thus providing a contemporary multimedia interpretation of the Homeric verse. This collaboration highlighted the crucial need of cooperation among Cultural and Educational Organizations in order to promote new methodological approaches aiming to attract young public and even evolve in terms of professional development. The interdisciplinary approach and creative use of Homeric verses promotes methods that facilitate the student to understand the multiplicity of museum objects and to formulate alternative interpretations, hypotheses, conclusions and ultimately knowledge. Museums and other cultural sites have a great comparative advantage as informal educational spaces with tangible and intangible depictions of history.

On the occasion of the celebration of International Museum Day in 2019, the animated videos were presented at the Archaeological Museum (Fig 7, 8). Every 18th of May since 1977, the global museum community is coming together to celebrate around the world. Thousands of activities and events are being organized to celebrate museums as incomparable places of knowledge, inspiration and creativity. In 2019, the topic proposed by ICOM was “Museums as Cultural Hubs: The Future of Tradition”. The topic in itself was a statement on the important role museums play in the future of our societies. “They give meaning to our past, and they make it meaningful today – a solid path upon which we can build our future. As a result, while preserving their core missions, such as collecting and exhibiting, museums have come to realize that they can be agents of educational and social change. Today, they are more aware of this than ever before.”

However, this celebration was not only about museums – it was also about tangible and intangible heritage. It was about strengthening the bonds that tie them together and establishing new ones. It was a celebration of our collective memory, our histories and our traditions. It was a big occasion to learn about what unites us . During that celebration the whole educational project was presented as small scale pop up exhibition .

The whole action was based on the philosophy of open access and the need to develop synergies and partnerships with other communities. The didactic and museological approach of this educational project was designed to fulfill those goals and based on the principles of modern museology that relate mainly to the multiplicity of museum exhibitions and objects and the mental, social and epistemological dimensions of knowledge. The main rationale for this cooperation was the outlining of the importance of creating educational programs based on new approaches and methods, of building synergies and cultural nets with museum and all communities and artists by bearing always in mind the needs and desires of every target group

Figure 6: Snapshots of Motion Type animations of the Homeric verse.

Figure 7: Motion type projected in Patras Archaeological Museum, next to the Mycenae rooms with exhibits.

5. Conclusions

Museums, like the Archaeological Museum of Patras, are not static repositories of artifacts but active educational hubs that shape the identities of future global citizens. The collaboration described in this paper illustrates how remote design education can successfully integrate cultural heritage into its curriculum through the use of innovative technologies like AR. The project not only enhanced students' learning experiences but also opened up new avenues for public engagement with cultural heritage. The success of this collaboration suggests that similar partnerships between museums and academic institutions could be a valuable model for distance learning in design fields. By linking student projects with museum collections, students are motivated and inspired, and they gain a deeper sense of purpose and community despite the challenges of remote education. The ongoing success of this project shows the potential for design education to adapt to and thrive in a digital, globalized world.

Surveys of visitors have long shown the necessity of readdressing interpretation of the exhibits. Linking the exhibits with student projects has been based on the philosophy that a museum needs to open up, at national and international level, be inspired by its collection and be connected with its audience via contemporary narratives or visual forms. Museums have the potential to offer different presentation of Heritage perspectives and a variety of context in order to meet the needs of students and encourage their active participation. The museum should strive to create the proper state of mind to students so that they would want to actively engage with the collections and exhibits. Thus, remote design student's motivation and creativity is ensured. Cultural Heritage, in association with contemporary forms of visualization and narrative, can become a "space" that teaches cultural diversity and democracy and shape the Citizens of the World.

The gain of this cooperation was multilevel: The students as well as their tutors were inspired and motivated by this important museum and its exhibits. The whole Thematic Unit came up with an Augmented Reality (AR) App, powered by HP Reveal. The motion type animations became interactive and tangible, narrative audiovisual compositions overlaid to antique scalps and objects. The students' works were presented to a larger audience while the museum's exhibits took an augmented dimension.

The thematics related to the Museum actions every year, have provided a clear motivation for the project and gave the group momentum and a sense of purpose in their assignments, something to look forward to, and at the end a feeling of pride and belonging to the academic group.

The exercise was repeated again in the academic year 2024, nevertheless in the post Covid area, for a number of reasons, it has become more constrained to plan an exhibition in the Archeological Museum of Patras. Nevertheless, such assignments, joined with other associations, purposeful and targeted to actual events, have proven a worthy practice for the Graphic Arts Multimedia course. The association with other events around Greece has led to design us in 2024 to present game concepts from students, related to Cretan mythology, which are exhibited in Crete, Greece, in the course of Chania film festival, in October 2024.

All students whose work are selected are proud to be a part of such events, although remote, they gain a feeling of purpose and community. They also perceive their association with the Hellenic Open University for their studies as reciprocal, as they get exposed online (Fig. 5), GTP51 – (MA GRAPHIC ARTS MULTIMEDIA, HELLENIC OPEN UNIVERSITY. *YouTube*). as well as in public events and exhibitions (Fig. 7, 8). They also get from the School of Applied Arts and sustainable Design a certificate of participation. Some make a point of meeting in person with their tutors and peers by coming to the opening of the events. Moreover such events, via word of mouth of the students and press releases, are promoting the work of the HOU Graphic Design - Multimedia course to the broader community.

Even though the majority of the students and tutors may never see the exhibition in person, due to time and location constraints of adult distant learners of the Hellenic Open University, they gain a feeling of pride and assertiveness for their work, asserted by the exhibition space status and its extensive presentation in press releases, and they gain a feeling of joy from their studies.

Last but not least, the need to promote new methodological approaches aiming to attract young public, points at the need for cooperation among Cultural and Educational Organizations. Design students as content creators can act as a contemporary view, modernizing and re-appropriating the museum narratives, addressing them with fresh and varied idiosyncratic stylistic approaches, and coevolve in terms of professional development.

Figure 8: HOU Student Poster and booklets in show at a Patras Archaeological Museum.

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We would like to thank the students of the School of Applied Arts at the Hellenic Open University and their tutors, who participated in the cooperation with the Archeological Museum of Patras through their projects, as well as the museum direction, alongside with its curators and personnel who made such events possible.

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Asynchronous, virtual teaching of physical experiments in hydraulics: a paradigm in practice

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Abstract

This paper presents the development and implementation of an innovative educational approach for teaching hydraulic experiments remotely, addressing challenges posed by equipment limitations, distance learning (DL), and exceptional circumstances like pandemics or exclusion. A case study is presented, focusing on an e-textbook created for asynchronous, virtual teaching of hydraulic experiments. The e-textbook features multimedia content, including videos and photos of 18 typical hydraulic phenomena, along with theoretical analysis, exercise instructions, and measurement tools. The e-textbook is designed to support undergraduate civil engineering students studying fluid mechanics and hydraulics, combining theoretical and hands-on learning. It allows students to observe and analyze hydraulic phenomena remotely, improving their understanding of complex engineering problems and motivating further research. The material is structured into four main parts, covering foundational knowledge and key topics in hydrostatics, pressure hydraulics, and free surface hydraulics. The multimedia content was produced using the infrastructure of the Hydraulics Laboratory at the University of West Attica and was successfully used during the COVID-19 pandemic when in-person labs were unavailable. The project was supported by a national grant and continues to serve as the primary textbook for the "Experimental Hydraulics" course, complementing other courses in fluid mechanics and hydraulics. In summary, the initiative modernizes hydraulic engineering education by integrating digital tools to enhance remote learning, ensuring continuity in education during disruptions like the pandemic.

Keywords: distance learning, asynchronous teaching, hydraulics laboratory.

1. Introduction and State-of the-art

The conventional approach to educating students typically involves in-class presentations of subject matter, analysis and solution of standard problems, and overviews of applications and paradigms. This "theory" approach generally relies on in-class delivery of material, utilizing a range of teaching aids such as blackboards, whiteboards, interactive monitors, or projectors. However, conducting physical experiments in a laboratory setting offers significant advantages, particularly for engineering and technology subjects. These benefits include hands-on experience in analyzing and observing physical models, taking measurements, understanding length and time scales, and gaining a tangible, three-dimensional perspective.

Unfortunately, access to laboratory resources is not always feasible. Factors such as limited budgets, resource constraints, distance learning (DL) setups, or extraordinary situations like pandemics, major outages, or other catastrophic events can limit or prevent lab access. Furthermore, students with physical disabilities may face additional challenges in accessing traditional lab settings. Holmberg and Bakshi (1982) highlight the critical role of laboratory work, discussing the strengths and limitations of both conventional and home-study lab activities. They also explore five alternatives to traditional labs and identify three areas needing improvement for effective distance lab experiences, based on the technology available in the 1980s.

A viable solution to these limitations is the development of asynchronous, virtual educational materials for lab experiments, such as multimedia repositories or e-textbooks. Two landmark resources in creating visual educational materials for fluid mechanics merit special mention.

The first, *Illustrated Experiments in Fluid Mechanics: The NCFMF Book of Film Notes* by Ascher Shapiro, published in 1972, is a classic work developed by the National Committee for Fluid Mechanics Films (NCFMF) with support from the National Science Foundation. Created to accompany a series of educational films produced at MIT, the book offers a rich, visual exploration of fluid mechanics concepts. Shapiro's guide presents experiments that demonstrate key fluid mechanics phenomena with explanations, diagrams, and photographic sequences of principles like flow visualization, vorticity, laminar and turbulent flows, and boundary layers. By combining theoretical discussions with visual examples, this tool has been instrumental in helping students bridge the gap between abstract equations and observable flow phenomena.

The second resource, *An Album of Fluid Motion* by Milton Van Dyke (1982), captures the aesthetic and scientific beauty of fluid dynamics through a collection of high-quality photographs. The book presents a broad spectrum of fluid mechanics phenomena—laminar and turbulent flows, boundary layers, shock waves, and vortices—accompanied by minimal text to allow the images to communicate concepts on their own. Van Dyke's album serves as an invaluable educational tool, revealing theoretical insights through direct observation and inspiring students and researchers with visually accessible representations of complex dynamics.

While these works offer comprehensive and visually engaging presentations of fluid mechanics principles, they cannot substitute laboratory exercises. Students cannot interact with these resources to take measurements or directly engage with the content, as they might in a lab.

Another paradigm for laboratory activity in DL is presented by Santiago *et al.* (2022) who introduce students to wastewater treatment using an advanced oxidation process.

In our case study, we present the development of an e-textbook for asynchronous learning of hydraulic experiments in a DL setting. This e-textbook features video-recorded laboratory experiments in hydraulics, presenting 18 typical hydraulic phenomena alongside theoretical analyses and exercise instructions. The content is accessible through hyperlinks, allowing students to observe phenomena, take measurements on their screens, and analyze data to understand physical properties.

The goal of this e-textbook is to provide an alternative, virtual laboratory experience. By integrating theoretical explanations with multimedia content—including videos and photographs of real experiments—the e-textbook offers a virtual approximation of in-lab activities. This format enables students to engage with hydraulic experiments, make measurements, and analyze collected data as though they were physically present in the lab.

2. History and implementation

Between 2010 and 2015, multimedia content was created at the Hydraulics Lab of the Technological Educational Institute of Athens (TEI Athens), a higher education institution that later merged with the TEI of Piraeus to form the University of West Attica in 2018. The four-year curriculum offered by the Department of Civil Infrastructure Engineering (CIE) at TEI Athens combined theoretical and laboratory-based instruction. Generally, each four-hour weekly theory class was supported by a two-hour laboratory session, which involved small projects where students observed, measured, and analyzed relevant phenomena. Following a

major refurbishment, the Hydraulics Lab was fully operational, and students, organized in small groups of 6–8, participated in these two-hour weekly lab sessions across several hydraulics courses (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Physical lab sessions at CIE/TEI Athens.

To expand lab access through electronic classes (e-class), key experiments, particularly those that allowed for visual observation and video documentation, were recorded. This initiative was part of the project “Open Academic Courses at TEI Athens,” funded by the European Union’s (EU) European Social Fund (ESF) and national resources under the Operational Program “Education and Life-Long Learning.” This project aimed to develop open and distance-access course material. As part of this initiative, the lab materials were restructured into “exercise packages” that combined fundamental theoretical analyses with multimedia content (photos and videos), charts, and guidelines for data measurement, analysis, and calculations of key hydraulic variables, along with interpretative notes for student observations.

During the COVID-19 restrictions from 2020 to 2022, online courses were the only viable option to sustain educational activities, which posed significant challenges for lab-based courses. However, as multimedia materials were already organized in exercise packages, the "*Experimental Hydraulics*" course (course code CE0843 in the five-year Civil Engineering curriculum, <https://civ.uniwa.gr/en/courses/undergraduate/>) was adapted for remote learning. Students could observe actual hydraulic phenomena through videos and take measurements on their home monitors. This adaptation worked smoothly, requiring only minor editorial adjustments to the packages. Both instruction and assessment (exams) were conducted through a mix of synchronous and asynchronous methods.

In the post-COVID period (2021–2023), the multimedia materials were further refined and compiled into an e-textbook, with support from the Kallipos+ project. The e-textbook is currently undergoing final proofing to ensure editorial consistency and compliance with the Kallipos+ project book series standards.

It is noteworthy that, following the merger of TEI Athens and TEI Piraeus to form the University of West Attica, the Hydraulics Lab at TEI Athens was dismantled, transported, and reassembled at a new location on

Campus 2 (Ancient Olive Grove), which temporarily halted physical lab operations until early 2024. However, the "*Experimental Hydraulics*" course continued uninterrupted in the same distance-learning format. Since mid-2024, the e-textbook has been enriched with new exercise packages as additional lab equipment is installed (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Laboratory reproduction of hydraulic phenomena along a six-meter flume at the new Hydraulics Lab, Campus 2. These sessions support theoretical instruction by illustrating fundamental concepts in open-channel flow.

3. The e-textbook

The e-textbook (Figure 3) is organized into four main parts, comprising 21 chapters in total. Part 1 covers foundational knowledge and methodological tools essential for designing and conducting experiments, including dimensional analysis, metrology, and curve fitting. Parts 2 through 4 are devoted to Hydrostatics (Part 2), Pressure Hydraulics (Part 3), and Free Surface Flow Hydraulics (Part 4). Each chapter represents a laboratory exercise or “lab work package” that includes theoretical analysis, multimedia materials (videos, photos, illustrations), step-by-step instructions for conducting the lab exercise, guidance on measurement-taking, pre-formatted data tables, calculations of key hydraulic variables, and prompts for reflection, conclusions, and practical insights. In the following we will present a selection of lab exercises:

Figure 3: The cover page of the e-text book.

Lab Exercise 3.2 involves using the classical free-sinking ball method to evaluate the viscosity of thick liquids (see Figure 4, http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v0502_Stokes_4balls.mp4). Students observe steel balls of various diameters sinking freely in different liquids (e.g., machine oil, glycerine, liquid soap) and, using the ruler and timer visible in the video, record position and time measurements directly on their screens. They plot these measurements, apply least-squares fitting to determine the sinking velocity, and calculate the fluid’s viscosity using Stokes’ law.

Figure 4: The free-sinking ball experiment. Left: video example. Right: typical measurements of ball velocities in various viscous liquids, with least-squares fitting applied.

Figure 5: Experimental setups for measuring surface wave celerity at different water depths (left: 18 mm, right: 75 mm).

Lab Exercise 4.4 explores the basic phenomenology of shallow water waves, providing videos for students to calculate wave propagation velocity (celerity). Figure 5 illustrates experiments for two water depths, one for 18 mm (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1402_Celerity_y018mmC.mp4) and the other for 75 mm, (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1402_Celerity_y075mmC.mp4), in a 6-meter-long flume. Using a stopwatch or video timer, students measure the time a wave travels a 5-meter distance, indicated by two white bands.

Lab Exercise 4.5 demonstrates hydraulic jump phenomenology in flumes of different dimensions. In Figure 6, students observe how a hydraulic jump’s position can be controlled upstream, e.g. by adjusting a sluice gate

(http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1501_HydraulicJump_UpstrContrC.mp4) or downstream, e.g. by a weir (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1502_F6m_HydrJump_DwnstrQContrC_480.mp4) by changing its height. Students measure pre- and post-jump depths to estimate flowrate and hydraulic energy loss, and create charts comparing hydraulic jump characteristics.

Lab Exercise 4.6 covers flow past a sluice gate (Figure 7). Students observe flow structure and measure flow characteristics (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1601_sluicegate_jumpC.mp4) with rulers mounted on the flume wall. The support video, on the right, provides a visualization of flow lines, (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1602_streaklines_sluicegate.mp4) allowing students to verify that sluice gate flow results in minimal hydraulic energy loss.

Figure 6: Studying hydraulic jumps in different flume setups. Control via upstream sluice gate and downstream weir.

Figure 7: Flow past a sluice gate and formation of hydraulic jump. Left: video appropriate for taking measurements. Right: flow line visualization to confirm minimal energy loss.

Lab Exercise 4.10 presents flow over a smooth-crested weir (Figure 8). Students examine the flow structure and measure various geometric characteristics using rulers as indicated on the video on the left (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1901_SmoothWeir_JumpC.mp4). The video on the right (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v1903_streaklines_smoothweir_MOV_0579.mp4) includes flow line visualization, highlighting hydraulic energy loss across the weir.

Figure 8: Flow over a smooth crested weir. Left: video appropriate for measurements. Right: flow line visualization to indicate energy loss.

Figure 9: Flow over a bed bump. Taking of measurements is possible using the ruler and the background orthogonal frame grid. Left: snapshot showing supercritical flow. Right: snapshot showing the transformation of supercritical flow into subcritical flow resulting in a hydraulic jump.

Figure 10: Flow over a bed bump. Left: snapshot appropriate for measurements. Right: geometric analysis of the flow structure at the left.

Lab Exercise 4.11 examines flow over a short bed bump (bump-flow), with videos capturing both supercritical flow and the transition from super- to subcritical flow with a mild hydraulic jump, see Figure 9

(http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/v2004_sharpbump_sub_sup_jumpComsdr.mp4). Students take measurements from snapshots (Figure 10) and apply geometric analysis to estimate the flowrate.

More videos are available at the web page of the Hydraulics Lab, Dept. of Civil Engineering, University of West Attica (http://users.uniwa.gr/marval/HydroLab/index_en.html)

4. Conclusions

The development and implementation of digital educational material compatible with distance learning (DL) frameworks enables asynchronous, virtual teaching of hydraulic experiments. This educational resource, an e-textbook, integrates video-recorded laboratory experiments in hydraulics, along with theoretical analyses and step-by-step exercise instructions. The e-textbook's innovation lies in offering students direct access to multimedia content that allows them to observe hydraulic phenomena, take measurements directly on their screens, and analyze these measurements to deepen their understanding of the physical principles involved. All multimedia content can be accessed via hyperlinks for easy download.

Designed for use in undergraduate civil engineering programs, the e-textbook supports both in-class and DL teaching in fluid mechanics and hydraulics. Its objective is to enhance students' skills in addressing hydraulic engineering challenges by blending theoretical concepts with empirical, hands-on learning. The multimedia content also boosts students' engagement, encouraging interest in research and advanced studies. Moreover, it enables students to critically evaluate real-world hydraulic phenomena, empowering them to form well-reasoned conclusions when managing, operating, or redesigning hydraulic systems.

The e-textbook's digital format, combined with detailed theoretical analysis, provides an accessible, effective alternative to hands-on lab work. This approach enables remote laboratory practice in cases where lab equipment is unavailable, allowing students to prepare thoroughly and perform actual experiments more effectively when resources are available. Additionally, it enhances the efficiency of training by enabling more complex project work.

The multimedia material was produced with the infrastructure of the Hydraulics Laboratory at the University of West Attica, finalized before the lab's relocation and the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. During the pandemic restrictions, the "*Experimental Hydraulics*" course transitioned to an online DL format, using this multimedia material for the first time as a "virtual realization" of laboratory exercises. Students could remotely observe hydraulic phenomena through video and take measurements from their screens, ensuring continuity of practical learning despite physical limitations.

This initiative modernizes hydraulic engineering education by leveraging digital tools to enrich learning and maintain educational consistency. In recent years, particularly post-COVID, the e-textbook has served as the primary textbook for the course "Experimental Hydraulics" and a supplementary reference for courses in fluid mechanics and hydraulics.

The e-textbook aims to:

- Enhance students' ability to tackle hydraulic engineering problems through a blend of theoretical and empirical training.
- Help students critically analyze field-observed hydraulic phenomena and draw substantiated conclusions, particularly regarding hydraulic system operation, management, or redesign.
- Spark educational interest and motivate students to pursue research projects in postgraduate studies.

As complementary study material, this e-textbook provides significant advantages. When lab resources are accessible, it prepares students to manage in-person experiments effectively or undertake complex projects,

thus improving training outcomes. In situations lacking lab equipment, it facilitates effective remote DL education, ensuring students continue to develop key skills.

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Innovative Knowledge Transfer from Higher to Primary Education; Teaching philosophy with "Sofia@School" method

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Abstract

One of the most significant challenges facing Higher Education in Greece is the persistent decline in student's ability for critical thinking. This is evidenced by the findings of the PISA 2025, which indicate that Greek schools are among the lowest-performing. Children lack the capacity to think rationally and coherently. The younger generation is exposed to information without the capacity to evaluate its content. They do not learn how to transform information into knowledge.

This is the objective of the innovative programme for teaching philosophy in Primary Schools, "Sofia@School", which has been approved and funded by The Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) and is already being implemented in public and private schools in Athens and the Periphery in 270 students of 4th and 5th grade.

The programme comprises ten lessons in Logic and Ethics. It is based on the use of a triptych of innovative means: animation, gamification and digital game-based learning. "Sofia@School" employs a step-by-step familiarisation process, encouraging children to participate in the educational process through play and entertainment.

Philosophy is not approached historically, preaching what great philosophers of the past may have said, but rather as a problem solving method. "Sofia@School" is an innovative online, cloud-based digital tool, which transfers knowledge from higher education Humanities to Primary Level. In addition, it serves as an interconnection Hub for different levels of education, facilitating the formation and coordination of digital communities.

Keywords: philosophy for children, logic, ethics, animation, gamification.

1. Introduction

The prevalence of irrational or absurd views, populism, conspiracy theories, and fabricated fake news is a significant challenge facing Greek society. Concurrently, scientific research (e.g. PISA studies) indicate that students in secondary education demonstrate a deficiency in comprehension and discourse structure. These characteristics were further exacerbated during the economic crisis and the subsequent two-year period of the pandemic.

It is self-evident that enhancing the quality of the educational system is a crucial step in overcoming this challenging situation. In particular, the teaching of philosophy could play a dynamic role in this project. However, the common issue that unites the majority of proposed reforms is that they concentrate on universities. In contrast, significant reforms necessitate a foundation in primary education (Scholl et al., 2014: 253).

This approach cultivates abilities, knowledge, and capabilities related to the child's intellectual, moral, social, and cultural development. These capabilities pertain to the child's intellectual, moral, social, and cultural

development (Love, 2016), extending beyond the family unit to encompass the broader social and cultural milieu. Conversely, they encompass the child's cognitive, emotional, and social skills (Scholl et al., 2014). The introduction of young students to an understanding of the constitutive principles of philosophy, which fosters children's innate reflection on issues that touch on key philosophical concepts (Fard et al., 2016), could contribute to a deeper change that, in the medium term, might be able to alter the unpleasant picture. This research hypothesis gave rise to the development of the Philosophy Teaching Programme in Primary Education, entitled "Sofia@School".

The Programme has been implemented by the Philosophy-Politics-Economics Laboratory of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (www.pplab.gr) with funding from the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) in the thematic section "Research & Innovation Hubs in Education". The research and implementation team that was responsible for the organisation and creation of the entire project included the following: Professor George N. Politis, Dr. Panagiota Vassi, Dr. Alkiviadis K. Gounaris, Dr. Panagiotis Perros, Vassiliki Baka, Panagiotis Dedes, Dimitra Vagena, Zacharoula Theodorou, Vassilis Tsakiroglou, Theodora Markantonatou.

The thorough planning, implementation and evaluation of the project took 24 months (2021-2023). Through the Programme, the teaching of Philosophy in Primary Education has been implemented for the first time in Greece on such a large scale (private and public schools both in Athens and in the Periphery).

2. The Project

The programme is comprised of eleven modular lessons, each covering a specific introductory topic related to the innovative teaching of philosophy at the primary school level. The programme makes use of innovative media, including original animation, gamification, and digital game-based learning.

A significant aspect of the design is the central character, "Sofia," the little owl, who serves as the mascot and has been adapted for use in a multitude of graphic and digital applications (Figure 1). In Greek mythology, the little owl is associated with Athena, the goddess of wisdom. As a result of this association, the bird is frequently referred to as the "owl of Athena" and is a timeless symbol of knowledge and wisdom. Apparently, Sofia means wisdom in Greek.

Figure 1: "Sofia" the little owl of Athena, the goddess of wisdom, mascot of the programme

By popularizing the disciplines of Logic and Ethics in new ways and communicating them to students through the enhancement of research, interactive and experiential practices, the programme teaches children to think critically, to doubt creatively and to evaluate beliefs and values in a critical manner. It establishes a physical hub between the NKUA and five primary schools and approximately 270 of their students and a corresponding digital hub, which is an open access and interconnection platform (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Creating & orchestrating digital communities

Sound knowledge is a prerequisite for progress and creation. Currently, expert knowledge of programming code is a prerequisite for any creative endeavor aimed at transforming research knowledge into innovation. However, it is philosophy that "clears away the rubbish that lies in the way to knowledge," as John Locke famously stated (Locke, 1976: 9-10). The application of logic and the consideration of human values serve to guarantee that efforts to innovate do not represent a manifestation of simplistic technocratic superiority. It is not sufficient for children and, subsequently, young people to merely possess knowledge; they must also be able to operate machines in a manner that aligns with human ideals and the public interest. In conclusion, the objective of the programme is to establish a preliminary connection between accelerated technological advancement and the principles of reason and ethics. The integration of philosophical tenets enables children to develop the capacity to discern the most appropriate course of action amidst the overwhelming amount of data present in the modern era.

The emphasis on logic does not impinge upon children's capacity for imagination, which is a remarkable faculty of the human mind. However, it does serve to enhance one's capacity to resist the absurd. Logic is a prerequisite for and a tool of clear thinking. The cultivation of logic facilitates the development of several positive attributes in children, including flexibility, open-mindedness, logical reasoning, fairness, honesty, wisdom, and curiosity. Additionally, it enhances their language skills, ability to engage in discourse, sociability, and tolerance of divergent perspectives (Pritchard, 1992).

A study conducted by the U.K. Department for Education revealed that the introduction of philosophical concepts in primary education fosters children's capacity to discern and resist manipulation and indoctrination (Bonnell, Copestake, Kerr, Passy, Reed, Salter, Sarwar & Sheikh, 2010:122-130). Children who have been exposed to the study of philosophy demonstrate an understanding that there are numerous ways of thinking, being, and living, as well as approaches to the world (Hobbs, 2018).

The programme does not seek to impose a particular moral code upon the children, nor does it attempt to instruct them in the rules they should follow in their lives. Nevertheless, the objective is to assist them in

comprehending that a fundamental condition for harmonious social coexistence is the acknowledgment of a comprehensive framework of regulations. It elucidates the necessity of establishing rules that resonate with the fundamental principles of each group of people as a prerequisite for eudaimonia (Aristotle, 1962: 1099a 23-28). In this sense, the capacity for rational judgment is understood as a prerequisite for the possibility of attaining happiness (Politis, 2014: 10).

3. The Method

One of the most crucial competencies that an educational system can impart upon its students is the capacity to differentiate between simple information and meaningful knowledge. This capacity is of particular significance in the contemporary era, given the advent of universal digitization of knowledge. Given its status as a cognitive discipline, it is reasonable to conclude that philosophy could play a pivotal role in fostering this essential capacity, particularly when taught to younger students (4th and 5th grade). This is because the formation of deductive thought is a gradual process occurring during the cognitive stage in which the child is capable of discovering the "possible-possible," engaging in productive reasoning, and employing combinatorial thinking.

Philosophy could therefore be an effective means of fostering this essential capacity, particularly when taught to younger students. The teaching of philosophy could make use of new educational tools offered by the rapidly developing digital technology, as well as the newest applications of artificial intelligence, with the aim of cultivating children's ability to distinguish between fact and opinion, between a valid proposition and a simple expression of emotion (Politis et al, 2022a).

Digital education can be broadly defined as the innovative use of digital media and technologies in teaching and learning (<https://www.ed.ac.uk/institute-academic-development/learning-teaching/staff/digital-ed/what-is-digital-education>). The basic assumption is that the use of digital educational media, such as multimedia materials (educational video, audiovisual material, etc.), digital applications, digital learning games, etc., can be particularly effective in the teaching of Philosophy, as it will not only make it easily accessible to all, but, at the same time, it will help to enrich it and make it more direct and widely understood. Digital educational tools, such as original animation and gamification, help to simplify the basic elements of Philosophy, thus making its constitutive principles easier to understand for young students (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Presenting Sofia@School in Athens Science Festival 2023

The use of audiovisual material with original short animations can convey information, knowledge and events to students in a short, concise, yet direct and easy to understand way. As a result of this practice, children have no difficulty understanding the basic principles of philosophy and, most importantly, do not see the class as

just another hour of information overload to be memorized and analyzed. It is imperative to note, that the goal of teaching philosophy in primary school is not to "teach children philosophy", but to enable them to use philosophical thinking in a way that will benefit them not only in their academic performance, but also in their lives in general, both at school and in society at large.

The process of digital game-based learning is enriched through interactive digital applications, which exploit a number of possibilities offered by artificial intelligence. Digital games address a wide range of learners with different educational needs and learning abilities (<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/digital-game-based-learning-dgbl/7628>); they make learning attractive to more types of learners than traditional teaching, thus facilitating the participation of more learners in the learning process.

It is a given that not all students retain the information provided by the course in the same way or at the same speed. The integration of digital technology into the educational process allows teachers to differentiate instruction and modify information in such a way that the lesson can be adapted to the individual learning abilities of the students. At the same time, it facilitates the overall understanding of the subject matter and allows students to process information at their own pace (<https://drexel.edu/soe/resources/student-teaching/advice/how-to-use-technology-in-the-classroom/>).

"Sofia@School" was designed as a self-paced learning method. Digital learning tools largely involve students in the learning process, whether they study individually or in groups. In fact, it is argued that digital game-based learning is one of the most applicable and effective methods to educate students belonging to the younger generation, also called the 'game generation' (Prensky, 2007).

The lesson is 'gamified' in a manner that incorporates elements of play and is enhanced with the objective of fostering engagement and active participation. This approach is believed to resonate with children, who tend to feel more at ease in a playful setting. (<https://www.trueeducationpartnerships.com/schools/gamification-in-education/>). Furthermore, evidence indicates that entertaining students during the educational process is not only harmless but also beneficial, as it relaxes and motivates them, thereby enhancing their willingness to learn. Concurrently, it facilitates optimal brain function. The aforementioned factors contribute not only to enhanced comprehension but also to receptivity to novel knowledge. This element is especially conducive to the learning process, particularly with regard to the introduction to the fundamental principles of Philosophy, let alone when addressed to primary school students (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Students following "Sofia@School" in Athens Science Festival 2023

It is important to note that gamification should not be confused with commercial digital games. It is evident that the objective is not to provide formal entertainment for children. Rather, as previously stated, the intention is to motivate learning and encourage active participation in the educational process. Consequently, digital learning games are frequently designated as 'serious games'. The defining characteristic of serious games is the presence of specific rules, which are designed with the objective of facilitating the development of particular cognitive, emotional, and social skills. A 'serious digital game', although situated outside the recreational context, is technologically analogous to typical games. This is because, based on artificial intelligence and utilizing the tools provided by digital technology, it employs 3D graphics, virtual reality, technical simulation, and so forth.

Concurrently, however, in terms of pedagogical design, a serious game focuses on exploration, problem-solving strategies and skill development. Digital game-based learning has been successfully used in recent years in various business sectors in the training of employees. The main reason for the success of their use is common and, of course, none other than the fact that workers can have fun during their training (Prensky, 2007).

The evidence presented above demonstrates that the incorporation of digital educational media in the teaching of Philosophy not only enhances the richness and accessibility of the course content but also facilitates the development of a range of skills, both cognitive and non-cognitive, in students. As research from Harvard University confirms, this type of practice not only encourages active participation and minimises resistance to innovative ideas, thereby capturing students' attention, but also stimulates mechanisms for deeper learning and understanding of the subject matter. (Randel et al., 1992; Philpot et al., 2003).

Furthermore, the utilization of digital educational media facilitates the advancement of students' critical and rational thinking abilities. Digital games assist students in attaining proficiency in crucial skills and abilities, including critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and digital literacy (Johnson et al., 2012). The integration of gamification in education has enhanced creativity and imagination, while also helping students to improve their strategic thinking, memory, concentration, reflexes, and dexterity abilities.

In addition, digital games designed specifically for primary education help students to improve their academic progress and gain a positive attitude towards the educational process (Lin et al, 2013). In the light of the above, it is clear that the use of digital educational media contributes both to the intellectual cultivation of children and to the shaping of their character and the building of their personality, as it contributes to the development of numerous cognitive and non-cognitive skills, resulting in the strengthening of their rational thinking and critical faculties.

By definition, the teaching of Philosophy also contributes to these objectives. With the use of appropriate digital media, the beneficial effects of teaching Philosophy at primary school are multiplied - and vice versa: the benefits that students can generally gain during the educational process from the use of digital educational media and from the use of the possibilities provided by artificial intelligence, in terms of enriching the course, are enhanced during the teaching of Philosophy. Therefore, it is reasonable to argue that the use of digital educational media benefits children in multiple ways and equips them with skills and abilities that will be useful in many areas of their lives.

A philosophy course that utilizes appropriate digital educational media is not so much focused on the instructor as it is on the learner (Prensky, 2007). Making the learner the center of the educational process is, of course, a matter of perse. This element becomes even more important in the teaching of Philosophy, because it serves to develop the rational thinking, critical faculties and creativity of young students.

"Sofia@School" was designed as an interactive, playful learning experience, with extensive use of multimedia. It combines digital technology and innovative means: original animations, gamification, digital game-based learning, and processes of step-by-step familiarization with complex philosophical concepts of Logic and Ethics.

These means encourage the active participation of students. They capture their attention while stimulating mechanisms for deeper learning and understanding. "Sofia@School" teaches children to think, to question creatively, and to critically evaluate beliefs and values (Politis et al, 2022b).

The "Sofia@School" method is divided into two major sections: The first one is "Educate the Students" and the second is "Train the Trainers" (Figure 5).

Figure 5: "Sofia@School" - The Method

Train the Trainers

During the Train the Trainers phase, the participating schools' teachers receive a brief training in teaching each lesson and handling digital media from a team of specialized staff from the University of Athens. The participating teachers are provided with a comprehensive schedule for each lesson, digital presentations, portable notes, and all other necessary materials to ensure the consistent and effective delivery of the lesson and facilitation of the interactive dialogue. Upon completion of the Train the Trainers module, the participating teachers are awarded certification as "Sofia@School" trainers.

Educate the Students

The programme employs a blended learning approach, integrating both face-to-face and distance learning modalities. The face-to-face unit is subdivided into three phases. Prior to the implementation of the solution, the solution itself, and subsequent to its implementation.

Each lesson commences with the formulation of the problem, which is conveyed through an animated video in which Sofia poses a philosophical question in a manner that is both thought-provoking and entertaining. Subsequently, in accordance with the prescribed curriculum, the teacher presents a PowerPoint demonstration and initiates a series of activities within the "Pre-Solution" phase.

The incorporation of diverse exercises, such as riddle games, fosters engagement among children, who are then presented with the opportunity to influence the outcome of the game. The students are gradually guided towards the solution following interactive dialogue. Upon attaining the solution, the subsequent activities designated as "Post-Solution" are initiated. The objective of these activities is to reinforce the solution and facilitate its comprehensive understanding.

The lesson continues at home, in accordance with the principles of self-paced learning. The platform (www.mysofia.gr) is online, cloud based and it facilitates parental involvement and interaction through asynchronous distance learning.

Upon accessing the platform, students can view the lesson summary, presentation slides, animated video, access bibliography (documentation and references), and participate in a gamified quiz. In each exercise, specific points are assigned for correct answers (and also for effort, so that no student receives a zero score). An aggregate scoreboard is created, and upon completion of all lessons, each student is awarded a badge according to the points they have accumulated (Figure 6).

Figure 6: www.mysofia.gr homepage

4. Results

4.1 Evaluation Methodology

Upon completion of the research phase of the "Sofia@School" programme, an evaluation was conducted in accordance with the pre-established criteria, methodology, and timeline. This evaluation was designed to capture the opinions of the participants from the collaborating schools: Athens College, Psychico College, Geitonas School, Ekpaideytiria Bougas, University of Athens Experimental School.

Quantitative and Qualitative Evaluation Tools were designed, consisting of anonymous questionnaires tailored to the target audience (parents, teachers, instructors, 4th-grade students, and 5th-grade students). The purpose of the evaluation was to assess specific data through a structured research study.

The students were designated as the experimental group, while the instructors, who were responsible for implementing the "Sofia@School" research programme, were assigned as the control group.

The questionnaires were designed to capture:

- The percentage that proves the shift in the philosophical thinking of the children as a result of teaching Logic and Ethics.
- The evaluation of each organizational aspect of the programme, concerning parents, instructors who taught the programme, class teachers, and students, in relation to:
 - Their level of satisfaction with the programme
 - The management and logistical infrastructure of the school where the programme was implemented (as previously designed by the PPE Lab).
 - The management of learning and the organization of the children
 - The impact of the programme's lessons on the children's social, emotional, and cognitive development

- Finally, participants were asked to share their overall impressions of their engagement with the programme (overall impact).

4.2 Indicative Results

The average value describing the shift in the philosophical thinking cross all classes that participated in the programme was found to be **12.9935%**. This percentage reflects the overall change observed in children's philosophical thinking as a result of the programme. In terms of quantitative outcomes, the Programme yielded a statistically significant improvement in the level of critical thinking among 4th Grade children, with an increase of **16.44%** (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Shift in the philosophical thinking by class

The overall shift in the philosophical thinking excluding lowest and highest value was found to be 13,43% whereas the average value across all classes was found to be 12,99% (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Overall shift in the philosophical thinking excluding lowest and highest value:

At the qualitative level, the Programme has been observed to facilitate an improvement in the capacity to construct logical and well-founded arguments, to make sound and accurate judgements, and to comprehend the necessity of established regulations as a foundation for individual autonomy.

In the global environment where children are bombarded with information that teachers find challenging to transform into knowledge, "Sofia@School" does not introduce new information. Conversely, it enables children to adopt a mode of thinking that allows them to distinguish between authoritative knowledge and subjective opinion.

5. Conclusions

The "Sofia@School" project has established an interconnection Hub between Higher Education and Primary levels. The digital platform www.mysofia.gr, developed by the research team of the Philosophy, Politics, Economics of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, has enabled the formation of digital communities engaging students, school teachers, parents, university professors and researchers.

The programme has been proven to be effective. Pilot implementation and the use of assessment tools revealed that "Sofia@School" achieved a positive change of 16.44% in the critical thinking levels of 4th grade students. The research findings indicate a measurable improvement in children's critical and creative thinking, along with the adoption of rational problem-solving strategies.

Highlighting the differences between hypothesis and proof, thesis and argument, cultivates resilience to misleading. Children develop the ability to make the right choices from the vast amount of information available. The programme has demonstrated that children can understand concepts that may initially seem complex and challenging for their age when they are presented in a simple, clear, and understandable way.

The incorporation of state-of-the-art technology and modern pedagogical approaches (namely animation, gamification, digital game-based learning, step by step procedures for gradual familiarisation, self regulated learning), enables the introduction of children to philosophical thinking in an effective manner.

Various "philosophy for/with children" methods developed in the 1970s tried to meet the needs of young learners and made a significant impact. Nevertheless, half a century later, these methods have only been adopted by a limited number of educational institutions and have not succeeded in introducing philosophical concepts into primary education.

The reason for this is that they necessitate the presence of highly proficient educators who can be considered as a sort of "miniature Socrates". This is precisely what the "Sofia@School" initiative addresses and constitutes a key aspect of its innovation. In contrast to the traditional approach of assuming that teachers are miniature versions of Socrates, this method focuses on the role of the teacher as a successful facilitator. This is achieved through the use of a fully standardised and certified format, which is designed to enhance the effectiveness of the teaching process.

Figure 9: "Sofia@School", Graduation Day!

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Chat GPT, Generative AI, and Large Language Models (LLM)

AI Chatbots in Radiography Education: A Tool for Improving Mathematical Confidence and Physics Understanding

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Abstract

Traditionally, many radiography students feel somewhat unsure about their mathematical skills needed to handle the radiation physics topics. They frequently ask for help or tutoring for the calculations. This paper examines how the use of AI chatbots, which have recently become publicly available, affects students' need for guidance, the completion of exercises, and learning outcomes within the radiography program at Tampere University of Applied Sciences (Finland). Artificial Intelligence has significantly impacted education by enhancing personalized learning and automating administrative tasks, thereby transforming traditional educational methods.

Radiography nurses need to understand the principles of radiation physics to ensure not only their safety but also the safety of patients. Knowledge of radiation dosages, exposure limits, and protective measures helps prevent unnecessary radiation exposure at the same time ensuring that images are clear and detailed, which is essential for accurate diagnosis and effective treatment planning. The understanding of how imaging machines (X-rays, CT scanners, and MRI) work and the physics behind them enables radiography nurses to better understand the imaging process and aspects that could potentially reduce image quality. Also simple troubleshooting and managing minor technical issues becomes more efficient. However, radiation physics is not an easy topic due to the interplay of mathematical principles and abstract concepts. To help the radiography students to grasp the fundamentals of radiation physics, a foundation in specific mathematical skills (geometry and trigonometry involving mostly spheres, circles, and triangles) and physics concepts (energy, motion, force, oscillations and waves) is necessary. The initial part of our course is designed to prepare students with these essential skills needed for understanding radiation physics and the results presented in this paper describe this part, not the radiation physics itself.

Previously, the mathematics and physics skill level of 2023 cohort was assessed through an at-home, self-paced combined mathematics and basic physics exam, with three attempts allowed. The assessments were automatically graded and featured randomly generated questions for each attempt. The setup was changed for the 2024 cohort, and they are now encouraged to utilize AI tools such as ChatGPT or Copilot for learning support when they practice at home, before taking a proctored exam via Moodle in a classroom setting. This study aims to compare the learning outcomes and learning experiences of the two groups, particularly focusing on the students' perceptions and usage of AI tools like ChatGPT in their learning process. All data will only be available by fall 2024 and not yet at the time of writing this abstract, the results will be detailed in the final publication and presentation at the conference. This research highlights the potential shifts in educational strategies through the integration of AI, promoting a more interactive and supported learning environment. Through this comparative analysis, we aim to highlight both the challenges and opportunities presented by the integration of advanced technologies (AI chatbots) in educational setup.

Keywords: please add your keywords without capitals here, separated by commas.

1. Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has rapidly transformed traditional learning environments, offering new opportunities for personalized learning and automated support. In recent years, AI-driven tools such as chatbots and digital assistants have become more accessible, providing students with real-time assistance in various subjects (Data & analytics, 2023; Tan, 2023). European Commission report gives many examples and ideas about using AI and data in education (European commission, 2022). While the use of AI in education has been explored in disciplines such as language learning and programming, its potential in fields that require a solid understanding of mathematics and physics, such as radiography, remains underexplored.

Radiography students must master complex topics, including radiation physics, to ensure the safety of both patients and themselves when handling imaging equipment such as X-rays and CT scanners. However, many students often feel underprepared for the mathematical and physical principles required in this field (Ingrassia, 2021). This has led to an increased demand for supplementary resources and tutoring to aid their understanding. In response, educators have begun experimenting with AI-based learning assistants, such as ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini, and Photomath, to help the students' independent study at home when the instructor is not available for answering questions. Also, by using the AI tools, students can get instant answers to their questions even in the classroom when the instructor is busy helping other students.

This study focuses on the impact of AI-driven learning assistants on radiography students at Tampere University of Applied Sciences. Specifically, it examines how these tools influence students' learning experiences, engagement with course material, and overall performance in the mathematics and physics components of the radiography program. By comparing the 2023 cohort, which did not have access to AI tools, with the 2024 cohort, which was encouraged to use them, this research aims to provide insights into the effectiveness of AI in supporting the learning of technical subjects and identify potential areas for improvement.

The findings of this study contribute to the ongoing discussion on how AI can be leveraged to enhance learning outcomes in higher education, particularly in courses where students struggle with the abstract and mathematical nature of the subject matter. The integration of AI into educational practices holds the promise of offering personalized support, reducing students' reliance on one-on-one tutoring, and fostering more independent learning habits.

2. “Mathematics, Physics, and Radiation Physics” course

2.1 Course structure

“Mathematics, Physics, and Radiation Physics” is a mandatory part of the radiography curriculum at Tampere University of Applied Sciences, designed to provide students with a solid understanding of the essential mathematical, physical, and radiation physics concepts that underpin their professional practice. The course is structured into two main sections, each worth 2 ECTS credits: Mathematics and Physics, and Radiation Physics and Imaging Devices. The primary goal is to prepare students for their roles as radiographers, particularly in terms of the safe and effective use of imaging technologies like X-rays and ultrasound and prepare them to understand, measure and record patient doses.

The mathematics section of the course focuses on the fundamental mathematical skills necessary for calculations in clinical practice, including percentages, proportional reasoning, equation solving, and understanding basic functions, such as the exponential and logarithmic functions in relation to radiation

physics. The physics section covers general principles such as mechanics, wave motion, electricity, and magnetism, all of which are important for understanding the operation of radiographic devices and ensuring safe practices with electrical medical equipment.

In the second part of the course, students study radiation physics and the operation of diagnostic imaging devices and the physics behind their principles of operation. Topics include the properties and generation of X-ray radiation, atomic structure, and oscillations and waves for ultrasound imaging, as well as the specific functionality of X-ray and ultrasound machines. Understanding radiation safety, including the relevant units and measurement methods is a key outcome of this section.

In the earlier (2023) cohort, the assessment of the mathematics and physics section (2 ects) consisted of an automatically scored Moodle exam, in which the initial values were randomized and the questions had a few different versions. The students took the exam at home, and they had three attempts, with the highest score being retained. There was a 3.5 h time limit for each attempt. Due to the emergence of AI chatbots, for the 2024 cohort the assessment method was changed: the previous automatically scored Moodle exam worked now as “practicing exam” for the students and it had no limit in the number of attempts but still had the time limit of 3 h for each attempt. In 2024 the graded exam was taken supervised in the classroom. It was still done in Moodle and had similar questions as the practicing exam. This way, the students were encouraged to learn the topics – with or without the help of AI assistant tools – but they could not use AI in the actual graded exam.

2.2 AI assistant tools

In the 2024 course, AI tools such as Photomath, ChatGPT, and Copilot were introduced to the students and their use was encouraged to support students in their learning process. Short instructional videos were provided to help the students start using the tools. Photomath was recommended for solving mathematical problems, providing step-by-step solutions to help students grasp fundamental concepts. ChatGPT and Copilot helped in explaining complex physics topics and in solving mathematical problems. These tools were promoted mainly for independent study at home but also for in-class support, enabling students to receive real-time feedback and guidance, even when the instructor was not immediately available.

Figure 1. Photomath app showing step-by-step solutions and explanations for mathematical problems.

Photomath is a mobile application designed to assist students with solving mathematical problems by providing step-by-step solutions and explanations. By simply scanning a math problem with their phone, students can receive instant feedback, allowing them to better understand the underlying concepts and the steps in the calculation. Photomath can be particularly helpful for students who struggle with basic arithmetic,

equations, percentages, and proportional reasoning. Figure 1 illustrates the use of the Photomath app. In this example, a user takes a photo of a handwritten equation, which is then processed by the app. Photomath instantly recognizes the equation and proceeds to solve it. The app not only provides the final solution, but also breaks down the process, explaining each step in detail. This feature is particularly beneficial for students, as it helps them understand the logic behind each mathematical operation, promoting deeper learning instead of merely providing the answer.

3. Methodos

The learning experiences and learning outcomes of two cohorts of students taking this course are investigated. In 2023 altogether 68 students took this course and in 2024 the number of students was 73. To assess the impact of AI-driven tools such as Photomath, ChatGPT, and Copilot on student learning in the Mathematics, Physics, and Radiation Physics course, a survey was conducted using an online form hosted on Microsoft Forms. The survey was distributed to the 2024 cohort at mid-course, after the mathematics and physics section. The aim was to gather students' experiences, their engagement with AI tools, and the perceived benefits.

The survey utilized a combination of multiple-choice questions, Likert scale ratings, and open-ended questions to capture both quantitative and qualitative feedback. Multiple-choice questions covered topics such as how often students used AI tools, which tools they found most useful, and in which areas of learning they felt the tools had the greatest impact. Likert scale questions asked participants to rate the effectiveness of the tools in helping them understand specific mathematical or physical concepts, and whether using AI tools improved their confidence in independently solving problems. The open-ended questions provided an opportunity for students to share their personal experiences and opinions on how the tools had influenced their learning. They were invited to elaborate on any challenges they encountered while using AI, as well as suggestions for improving the integration of such tools in future iterations of the course.

Data from the survey was anonymized to protect student identities, and the results were analyzed to identify trends and patterns in how the use of AI tools influenced learning outcomes. The findings were then compared to the performance and feedback from the 2023 cohort, which did not have access to AI tools, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the AI tools' impact on student performance and engagement.

Learning outcomes of the two cohorts were compared using two sets of data: final grades of the mathematics and physics sections and the results of automatically scored Moodle exam. For the 2023 cohort, the Moodle exam was part of the course's formal assessment, whereas for the 2024 cohort, it was used as a practice exam. Moodle log data was used to investigate how much time the students spent on the Moodle exam.

4. Results

The results of the survey question *"Which AI-based learning tools have you used in the math and/or physics studies?"* are shown in Figure 2 and they indicate varying levels of engagement with AI tools. The number of responses was 59 (81 % of the 2024 cohort students). Photomath emerged as the most used tool, with 64 % of students reporting that they relied on it for solving mathematical problems. Its popularity can be attributed to its user-friendly interface and ability to break down mathematical processes into step-by-step solutions. ChatGPT was also widely used, with approximately 47 % of respondents indicating that they had utilized it during their studies. ChatGPT's strength lies in its versatility; it provided students with detailed explanations of complex physics concepts, supported independent problem-solving, and answered questions in real-time, offering a valuable resource both during classroom activities and independent study sessions. Using ChatGPT in generating exercises and their stepwise solutions was also encouraged in the beginning of the course.

Copilot is the default AI chatbot at Tampere University of Applied Sciences. However, its usage was not especially encouraged, since in previous study (Suhonen. 2024) it was found to lose in some aspects to ChatGPT in physics learning. Therefore, only a few students used it during the course. Other AI tools, such as Google Gemini, saw much lower levels of adoption, with only a small percentage of students indicating they had used them. This may reflect student's lack of confidence in these tools or the fact that they are less familiar to students.

Interestingly, around 19 % of students reported that they did not use any AI tools during their studies. This could suggest several factors, including a preference for traditional learning methods, lack of awareness about the availability or potential benefits of AI tools, or discomfort with integrating technology into their study habits. In open-ended questions, some of these students reported that they actively decided against using AI-driven learning assistants due to concerns about their potential negative aspects: lack of royalties or proper recognition for content creators and possibility of biased or inaccurate information being provided by AI models.

Figure 2. The answer distribution to the question about AI learning tools usage.

Students were also asked to rate the helpfulness of three AI tools - Photomath, ChatGPT, and Copilot - in supporting their learning. The responses are shown in Figure 3. Photomath emerged as the most positively rated tool, with 39 % of students strongly agreeing and 20 % agreeing that it was helpful in their studies. This suggests that Photomath's ability to break down mathematical problems into step-by-step solutions made it highly effective for students struggling with mathematical concepts, such as equation solving.

ChatGPT also received favorable responses, with 29 % of students strongly agreeing and 15 % agreeing that it was helpful. Its versatility in explaining both physics and mathematical concepts likely contributed to this positive reception, as it provided students with instant feedback and detailed explanations during their independent study. The same applies to Copilot, which had only a few users and therefore the percentages appear to be low.

It is particularly noteworthy that none of the students expressed negative opinions about the AI tools they had used. The figure 3 indicates that only a few students remained neutral and no one selected "Disagree" or "Strongly Disagree" for any of the AI tools. This absence of negative feedback suggests that the integration of AI tools into the Mathematics, Physics, and Radiation Physics course was at least unobtrusive, and in many cases, beneficial. This lack of negative feedback further reinforces the value of AI tools in supporting students, offering personalized assistance without introducing new frustrations or hindrances in the learning process.

These findings highlight that while AI tools like Photomath and ChatGPT have clear benefits in enhancing student understanding, not all AI tools are perceived as equally valuable. Photomath and ChatGPT, with their problem-solving and explanatory capabilities, were particularly well-suited for the mathematical and technical demands of the course, whereas Copilot's utility in this specific academic context remains limited. Future iterations of the course may benefit from further refinement in the selection and integration of AI tools based on student needs and the nature of the content.

Figure 3. The perceived helpfulness of three AI tools - Photomath, ChatGPT, and Copilot - in supporting student learning. Data represents those students, who used AI tools.

Table 1 shows students’ perception of the usefulness of AI-tools in different tasks. In addition to choosing from the list, they could also give their own point of view, but there were no new themes in their answers and they are included in the categories shown in the table. The majority of students (44 responses) indicated that the AI tools clarified difficult concepts or calculations, highlighting their role as an effective supplementary resource for tackling challenging material. Additionally, 16 students reported that these tools sped up task solving, demonstrating their usefulness in enhancing efficiency during problem-solving in exercises. A further 15 students stated that the tools provided new learning opportunities, indicating that the AI platforms introduced methods or perspectives that were otherwise unavailable. Only 7 students felt that the tools did not bring significant benefits to their learning, suggesting that while the overall impact was positive, a small minority of students did not find the tools particularly transformative. These results affirm the generally favorable reception of AI tools, particularly in helping students grasp complex concepts and improve their learning efficiency.

Table 1. Students’ perception of the usefulness of AI-tools in different tasks

<i>The AI tool helped me in the following:</i>		
Clarified difficult concepts or calculations.	44	
Sped up task solving.	16	
Provided new learning opportunities.	15	
Did not bring significant benefit.	7	

These results demonstrate that while Photomath and ChatGPT have been successfully integrated into the students' learning processes, a significant portion of the cohort either did not engage with AI tools or may

benefit from additional guidance on how these tools can enhance their learning outcomes. As the use of AI in education grows, understanding why some students opt out of using these tools will be crucial for improving their accessibility and effectiveness in future iterations of the course.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of final grades of the mathematics and physics section of the course for the 2023 (blue bars) and 2024 (green bars) cohorts. The grades, ranging from 0 to 5 on the x-axis, represent the following: 0 is a failing grade, while 5 is the highest possible grade. The y-axis shows the percentage of students in each grade category.

Figure 4. The distribution of final grades of the mathematics and physics section of the course for 2023 cohort (67 students) and 2024 cohort (60 students).

In the 2023 cohort, the largest portion of students (over 30%) received a grade of 2, with the majority of students concentrated in grades 2 and 3. Fewer students achieved the top grades of 4 or 5, and less than 5% failed the course with a grade of 0. The 2024 cohort, on the other hand, displayed a shift toward higher grades. About 30% of the students earned the top grade of 5, with a more balanced distribution across grades 2, 3, and 5. Overall, this comparison suggests a slight improvement in student outcomes between the 2023 and 2024 cohorts, with the 2024 cohort having a higher proportion of students achieving top grades, particularly grade 5. To test this, a two-sample t-test assuming unequal variances was conducted to compare the final grade distributions between the 2023 and 2024 cohorts. The test compared the mean grades of the two cohorts, with the 2023 cohort having a mean of 2.84 (variance 1.90, n=67) and the 2024 cohort a mean of 3.1 (variance 2.19, n=60). The t-test shows a p-value of 0.30, which is above the commonly used significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis—that there is no significant difference between the mean grades of the two cohorts—cannot be rejected. This suggests that while the 2024 cohort shows a slightly higher mean grade, the difference is not statistically significant, and it may be attributable to random variation. Anyhow, at least the change of assessment from non-proctored to proctored did not drop the learning outcomes.

To get further insight into the student studying and learning, the time they spent on automatically scored Moodle exam and the points they got were analyzed for both cohorts. For the 2023 cohort the data consists of graded Moodle exam only and for the 2024 cohort, the points refer to real, proctored, classroom exam and the time to practicing with Moodle exam. The results are grouped and categorized according to the exam points: 0.0-6.0, 6.1-9.0, 9.1-12.0, 12.1-15.0 and 15.1-18 and the average points and average time spent are for each category is presented. The maximum number of points was 18. The data is show in Table 2 and in Figure 5. In the figure, the bubble size corresponds to the number of students. According to the data, in both cohorts,

there is a correlation between the time spent and the points gathered. This is no surprise – only by practicing and studying it is possible to learn. The large exam time for the lowest category in 2024 cohort is likely due to the fact that the students opened the exam and left it open for maximum time (3 h). This could explain the long time yet small points for the 2024 cohort’s lowest scoring students. On the other hand, the students with best points in 2024 cohort spent even more than six hours in the practice exam – on average. This is remarkably long time and shows that this kind of practice exam works well in learning and preparing for the real exam.

Table 2. Students’ exam points and the total time spent for the 2023 and 2024 cohorts presented grouped according to the points gathered.

Point Category	2023 cohort			2024 cohort		
	Students	Average	Average time	Students	Average Points	Average time (min)
0.0 - 6.0	1	4,8	126	6	3,6	173
6.1 - 9.0	6	8,0	148	10	7,7	147
9.1 - 12.0	24	11,0	167	17	10,9	182
12.1 - 15.0	22	13,7	171	23	13,6	313
15.1 - 18.0	15	17,1	183	11	17,1	373

Figure 5. The correlation between points gathered and time spent in the automatically scored Moodle exam (2023) or practice exam (2024). The bubble size corresponds to the number of students.

To gather insights on improving the integration of AI assistants in the course, students were asked open-ended questions such as how to improve the course arrangements to better support students' learning and what suggestions they had for the future use of AI assistants. This approach encouraged reflective feedback on both the course structure and the application of AI tools. Student responses to open-ended questions gave some helpful ideas of which here are a few picks:

"I liked that AI assistants were introduced in Moodle, and they were also mentioned in the first class. Perhaps the threshold for using them could be lowered further by adding an example sentence in Moodle on how to ask ChatGPT to complete exercises on a specific topic."

"Encouraging their (AI tools) use was a very positive surprise. In my previous studies, AI was not used at all and was rather seen in a negative light. Emphasizing its useful side is, in my opinion, only a good thing, and this should be actively done in the future as well."

5. Conclusions

The integration of AI chatbots into radiography education, particularly in the areas of mathematics and physics, has demonstrated benefits in enhancing students' independent studying. Tools such as Photomath and ChatGPT, by providing instant feedback and step-by-step guidance, have improved students' ability to tackle challenging mathematical problems and grasp complex physics concepts. Notably, none of the students who utilized AI tools provided negative feedback about their experience. This absence of criticism suggests that AI tools are well-received and effectively support learning without introducing frustration or confusion, making them a valuable resource for independent study.

The comparison of learning outcomes between the 2023 and 2024 cohorts, though not statistically significant, indicates a positive trend in the performance of the cohort exposed to AI tools. The integration of AI did not negatively affect learning outcomes despite the shift from non-proctored to proctored exams, suggesting that AI enhances independent learning without compromising assessment integrity. However, some students struggled to effectively utilize these tools, highlighting the need for better integration strategies and further research on optimizing AI's role in supporting diverse learning preferences.

As AI continues to evolve, its role in education will likely expand, offering increasingly personalized and effective learning experiences. Further exploration into the long-term impact of AI on technical subjects, like radiation physics, will be essential to fully harness its potential in radiography and beyond.

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Generative AI and academic integrity - a contradiction?

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Abstract

The integration of Generative AI (GenAI) into higher education has sparked extensive discussions within the scientific community. These discussions cover both opportunities, as well as challenges and barriers (Michel-Villarreal et al., 2023). Most of these publications assume that GenAI will fundamentally transform the academic world. As change processes are inherently associated with uncertainty, it is not surprising that the use of GenAI in higher education institutions (HEIs) is seen not only positively but also critically.

One concern relates to academic integrity. Assuming that GenAI is understood as “production of previously unseen synthetic content, in any form and to support any task, through generative modeling” (García-Peñalvo & Vázquez-Ingelmo, 2023), text-generating AI systems in particular appear capable of undermining academic integrity. After all, individual paragraphs up to entire essays can now be automatically generated using a simple prompt and presented as original work. Additionally, neither individuals nor software systems are currently able to reliably detect such plagiarized content (Alexander et al., 2023). Assuming that current deficiencies of GenAI, such as hallucinated content or fabricated citations, will be largely remedied in the future, GenAI could indeed pose a threat to academic integrity.

However, proving or disproving this assumption remains a challenge. Although there seems to be a “perceived” consensus within academia regarding the concepts of “academic integrity”, “good scientific practice” and “plagiarism”, universal definitions for these terms are lacking (Perkins, 2023). Therefore, a clarification of terms is paramount. Additionally, the question remains open as to whether AI-generated texts have a work character from both a linguistic (de Beaugrande & Dressler, 1981) and legal (Hugenholtz & Quintais, 2021) perspective. Consequently, it remains unclear whether authorship and/or copyright can be claimed for such texts (and if so, by whom). This is closely related to the question of originality. For example, it should be discussed whether an AI-generated text based on multiple intellectually challenging prompts can be understood and evaluated as the personal achievement of the individual who formulated the prompts. This in turn raises the question of whether new criteria are needed for the assessment of academic performance. Particularly, in written works, the product, i.e., the finished text, is currently mainly evaluated. However, a more targeted approach would involve evaluating the creation process (Liu, 2023), potentially incorporating elements such as brainstorming using chatbots or text generation through intentional prompting.

The understanding of scientific achievement and academic integrity is rooted in a tradition that often spans centuries. It is therefore not surprising that GenAI is perceived as a disruption. While most HEIs have recognized that banning GenAI is not an option, many opt to avoid it, for example, by proposing alternative examination methods whose tasks current AI systems cannot (yet) solve (Farhat, 2023). Not least, this approach is often motivated by the desire to safeguard academic integrity. But what if it made more sense to integrate the use of GenAI into the domain of academic integrity? This contribution, adopting an interdisciplinary approach, delves into the necessary prerequisites and potential solutions for resolving the (apparent) contradiction between GenAI and academic integrity.

Keywords: academic integrity, academic misconduct, GenAI, authorship, copyright, plagiarism, good scientific practice, intellectual creation, value the process

1. Introduction

The relationship between Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) and academic integrity represents a critical area of concern for Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs). The emergence of advanced GenAI technology, embodied by systems like ChatGPT, has led to a reassessment of fundamental concepts of authorship, originality, and responsibility in academic writing. This has resulted in complex questions about the definition of academic integrity and the recognition of potential threats and challenges posed by GenAI. Consequently, there is an urgent need to scrutinize the essential terms and concepts in this area to shed light on the relationship between GenAI and academic integrity.

This contribution delves deeply into the complex interplay between GenAI and academic integrity, beginning with a careful analysis of the relevant terminology. After a thorough consideration of the technological intricacies of GenAI, the functioning and capabilities of GenAI in text production are explained. Moreover, the definitions of academic integrity, academic misconduct, and plagiarism are scrutinized, and the central ethical principles and implications in the context of GenAI are discussed. The prevailing understanding of academic integrity is critically examined, and the diverse impacts of GenAI on scholarly practice are highlighted to pave the way for a comprehensive examination of the challenges and opportunities arising from the integration of GenAI into academic writing.

Diverse challenges that GenAI presents to academic integrity are described. The nuances of AI-generated text production are outlined and the implications for authorship, originality, and accountability in academic writing are explored. Furthermore, the ethical concerns surrounding the lack of transparency in AI systems, data privacy, and bias are discussed, advocating for a reassessment of academic integrity in the context of GenAI. The essential characteristics of a text and the transformation of a text into a scholarly work are examined, challenging conventional notions of authorship and originality in the academic writing process. The role of GenAI in text production and the implications for authorship is analyzed, addressing complex questions surrounding the creation of academic works in collaboration between humans and AI.

Amidst the uncertainties and challenges arising from the integration of GenAI into academic writing, the paper advocates for a gradual reassessment of policies on academic misconduct. It introduces a novel model that defines the use of GenAI as an integral part of the academic writing process, subject to specific prerequisites and a redefined understanding of academic integrity. This innovative approach aims to harmonize the use of GenAI with the principles of academic integrity, while promoting responsible collaboration between humans and AI, and fostering a new academic mindset.

The concluding section of the paper reflects on the transformative potential of the proposed model and recognizes the complexities and limitations associated with the integration of GenAI into academic writing. It highlights the urgent need for further research and comprehensive considerations on the multifaceted impacts of GenAI on academic integrity, authorship, and scholarly practice.

In essence, this paper aims to provide a nuanced and interdisciplinary exploration of the complex interplay between GenAI and academic integrity, offering a thought-provoking perspective that advocates for a progressive realignment of principles of academic integrity in light of advancing AI technology.

2. Analysis of terms

To approach the inquiry of whether GenAI and academic integrity are in conflict, an examination of the relevant terminology is requisite. GenAI has become widely recognized in public discourse following the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022. Yet, the understanding of its technological functioning varies significantly, as do the expectations associated with GenAI systems. Technologically speaking, GenAI represents a suite of technologies crafted to create various content types—such as text, images, or audio—drawing on patterns discerned from substantial datasets. This creation process predominantly employs deep learning methods, especially neural networks, which furnish AI with the capability to mimic human-like interactions or outputs. The efficacy of such models is dependent on the quality and quantity of the training data. Core to GenAI, Large Language Models (LLMs) and their embedded machine learning algorithms empower sophisticated text generation, contextual comprehension, and application versatility (Euchner, 2023).

Based on their literature mapping, García-Peñalvo & Vázquez-Ingelmo (2023) define GenAI as "the production of previously unseen synthetic content, in any form and to support any task, through generative modeling." Notably, the AI research domain often reserves the term "generative AI" for complex models that produce high-quality, convincingly human-like artifacts. Conversely, the general public interprets "generative AI" as the AI-driven creation of specific content.

With the advent of AI, a prevalent trend is the anthropomorphic portrayal of GenAI applications, particularly chatbots. This trend predicates the ascription of content creation to human agency rather than acknowledging mechanistic or algorithmic origins (Mendoza, 2024). However, the reality posits that content springs not from someone (i.e. a person) but from something (i.e. an algorithm, a device, a probability). Notably, this circumstance (amongst others) has raised complex questions regarding the definition of academic integrity, academic misconduct and plagiarism with the introduction of generative AI in HEIs (Barnett, 2023).

Perkins (2023) notes that while there is a general understanding within academia of what constitutes academic integrity, there is no universally accepted definition of the term. Macfarlane et al. (2014) point out, that the term "is widely used as a proxy for the conduct of students, notably in relation to plagiarism and cheating". However, the foundational ethos of academic integrity, as articulated by the International Center for Academic Integrity (2021), encompasses honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility, and courage—all values in direct antithesis to the essence of plagiarism. Consolidating various interpretations, Yeo (2023) characterizes plagiarism as the unauthorized appropriation of another's work, encompassing both text and the underlying ideas. Thus, plagiarism manifests as academic misconduct, which Fanelli (2013) describes as "any omission or misrepresentation of the information necessary and sufficient to evaluate the validity and significance of research." While plagiarism should be differentiated from academic ghostwriting—the act of commissioning and presenting someone else's writing under one's own name (Jamieson & Moore Howard, 2019)—both cases fall within the ambit of academic fraud.

The conclusions drawn from this terminological scrutiny suggest that HEIs generally maintain a lucid conception of academic integrity and identify misbehaviors contravening it. This comprehension is anchored in the core ethical tenets of scholarly practice, which are further refined and instantiated by each institution's distinct guidelines. Upholding academic integrity acts as a seminal criterion in the appraisal of scholarly merit (Kreiman & Maunsell, 2011) and applies to students and researchers alike. Notwithstanding, these standards have traditionally only recognized human beings as the creators of academic works. The increasingly prevalent deployment of GenAI institutes a re-examination at multiple levels. With the debate over whether, how, and for whom the use of a text-generating AI application establishes authorship of the generated text as a starting

point, the subsequent chapters will address the anticipated threats and challenges presented by GenAI. Then, approaches for a rearticulated perspective on academic integrity will be proposed.

3. GenAI as a threat to academic integrity

Long-standing research interest in artificial intelligence (AI) has spanned several decades (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019); however, HEIs only recently regarded GenAI as a potential threat to academic integrity after ChatGPT and akin GenAI applications gained popularity. The reasons for such apprehension are manifold. On one side, GenAI can acilitates traditional forms of academic misconduct while also introducing new facets through AI. These challenges encompass diminished originality and creativity, plagiarism issues, and breaches of ethical standards. On the other side, GenAI provokes further questions about academic compliance, such as the credibility of AI-generated texts and the data origins employed for training Large Language Models (LLMs).

Utilization of GenAI for text production assumes the output is from a machine, algorithm, or software based on an LLM rather than primarily from human effort. A human merely instigates this process with a command or prompt, and subsequently, the AI rapidly generates the text (Yeo, 2023). This delegation of text generation to AI (Eke, 2023) theoretically enables academic manuscripts to be solely and entirely authored by AI. In such scenarios, the current assumption is that scholarly work is devoid of self-directed effort, lacking individual authorship. Such a lack of an independent writing process conflicts with academic integrity standards and thus is deemed academic misconduct. Using AI-generated text in one's work without proper attribution is considered plagiarism (Lim et al., 2023), an action that equally infringes upon academic integrity.

Consequently, AI-produced texts necessitate labeling. Nevertheless, labeling is fraught with the issue that algorithms and LLMs underpinning most GenAI applications are neither transparent nor comprehensible. Hence, texts produced via prompts cannot be verified, even with a disclosed prompt, as the same application might generate diverse outputs from identical prompts. Despite attempts at standardizing labels for AI-generated texts, exemplified by proposals from the American Psychological Association (APA) (McAdoo, 2024), citations of AI-generated texts cannot be traced in the same manner as conventional literature citations.

Such forms of academic misconduct predate the prevalence of GenAI. Yet the current academic quandary lies in the challenge that AI-generated texts cannot be reliably identified by either humans or software (Alexander et al., 2023; Fleckenstein et al., 2024), hampering proper sanctioning for their misuse. Fabricated facts and literature citations might imply AI-involvement, but they offer neither conclusive proof nor allow one to ascertain the extent of AI-contributed text. AI-assisted texts, similar to ghostwriting, elude easy detection but are notably quicker and less expensive to generate. Educators and editors tasked with ensuring text quality, including adherence to scientific ethical norms, face a formidable challenge in detecting AI assistance. Thus, the major threat to academic integrity is not only the possibility of AI-based text generation but, more critically, the insufficient detection of such generated content.

Moreover, GenAI elicits ethical concerns perceived as threats to academic integrity, encompassing the inappropriate management of accountability, data privacy, and bias concerns (Akkaş et al., 2024). With GenAI systems often managed by enterprises beyond public scrutiny and lacking transparency, these systems function as enigmatic "black boxes." The datasets training the LLMs, the mechanisms of text generation, and potential biases infused within texts remain obscured (UNESCO, 2023). These issues cannot be entirely mitigated, even when the person responsible for text generation exercises the utmost care. Unless AI applications are developed and operated independently, copyright violations and plagiarism cannot be fully excluded due to the unknown nature of the training data used.

In the realm of GenAI application, the adherence to the scientific duty of care as mandated by academic integrity is pivotal. GenAI tends to fabricate fictional bibliographic references (Walters & Wilder, 2023). Even as advanced GenAI applications like ChatGPT demonstrate a capacity for crafting plausible academic essays, the peril of generated content built upon hallucinated facts remains (Alkaissi & McFarlane, 2023). These fabricated citations and facts are indicative of academic integrity violations, signifying that the user failed to validate the AI-sourced information, thus failing to meet the responsibility of adhering to scientific standards in text production.

Therefore, AI's role in scientific writing is viewed with skepticism due to its potential to undermine academic integrity. HEIs often anchor to prevailing standards, sometimes applying inconsistent rationale: AI-generated texts, for instance, can be judged for containing elements of "plagiarism" (implying authorship), while simultaneously these texts may be denied originality (precluding claims of individual authorial ownership). Given the opportunities and challenges associated with GenAI, it is essential to question to what extent and by whom authorship and intellectual property of an AI-generated text can be claimed, and what implications this might have for the definition of academic integrity.

4. GenAI as a challenge in crafting own work

Authoring scholarly papers is a cornerstone activity in academia, pertinent both to students and those engaged in education and research. Such texts serve to document advancements in knowledge, experiences, or disseminate scientific theories and findings. Authors of academic writings are committed to a scientific ethos, which is anchored in the tenets of academic integrity. A text, particularly in this context, is characterized by its origination from individuals, infused with their unique thoughts and deductions, and in which excerpts from other works are duly acknowledged through literature citations. When these principles are rigorously respected, authors create original works, thereby meriting claim to their authorship.

Prior to the widespread availability of GenAI tools, textual creation within academia was an exclusively human endeavor. Despite the presence of academic infringements such as plagiarism or ghostwriting, even the works illicitly presented as original were composed by humans. However, with the infiltration of tools like ChatGPT, CoPilot, or Gemini into academic institutions, this can no longer be taken for granted.

As previously underscored, AI-generated texts not explicitly identified as such are often considered a form of covert plagiarism by most HEIs, which is challenging to detect. To prevent associated cheating, avoidance strategies are often recommended. Assignments and exams should be set in such a way that they cannot be solved by GenAI. Yet, this perspective fails to address the crux of the matter: on one side, because the capabilities of GenAI are rapidly evolving, and tasks immune to GenAI today may likely be solved by these tools in the future. On the other side, as AI may become an embedded component of the academic writing landscape, adhering to conventional or anachronistic standards of academic integrity may prove illogical.

A more viable approach is elucidating methods by which AI-generated texts can be assimilated into one's writing process without compromising academic integrity. To navigate this approach, several critical questions warrant attention:

- What are the defining traits of a text, and how does one transform a text into a scholarly work?
- How is authorship constituted?
- What role can or should GenAI assume in the process of text production?

At first glance, the initial two questions seem quite easy to answer, given the ingrained conventions of scientific writing familiar to academia. However, upon closer scrutiny, it becomes apparent that even before the ubiquity of GenAI, unequivocal responses were elusive. The involvement of GenAI now increases complexity, meriting a comprehensive reevaluation of these questions. For this purpose, the subsequent discussion will incorporate philosophical, linguistic, and legal approaches and perspectives.

4.1 From text to work

The inquiry into what characterizes a text has long been a topic of exploration in the fields of philosophy of language and linguistics (Lycan, 2008). Within text linguistics, the seven standards posited by de Beaugrande & Dressler (1981) serve as a robust framework for delineating textuality. These established standards governing textual communication include cohesion, coherence, intentionality, acceptability, informativity, situationality, and intertextuality.

Cohesion signifies the linguistic ties within a text, achieved through cohesive devices like pronouns, conjunctions, and lexical repetition, which bridge sentences and ideas on a surface level. Coherence refers to the logical and semantic consistency of a text, where ideas and concepts unfold in a structured, intelligible manner, making the overall message accessible and comprehensible. Both are text-centered notions. Modern GenAI applications can generate text that satisfies both cohesion and coherence (e.g., in English), rendering these standards insufficient to differentiate AI-generated from human-produced texts.

Intentionality pertains to the purpose behind a text. It reflects the idea that a text is created with a specific goal or purpose by its author, for example, report on the outcome of an experiment or explain a scientific theory. The intention of the author should be discernible to the recipient, at least to a substantial degree. Texts generated by GenAI lack inherent intention as their text generation stems solely from algorithms and LLMs, initiated by a prompt, which in turn is done by a human.

Acceptability refers to the receiver's (reader or listener's) recognition of a text as being appropriate and useful. It indicates that the text meets the reader's expectations and fulfills its communicative function. Acceptability can relate to the author's intention but does not necessarily have to. Acceptance refers both to the cohesion and coherence of the text and to its content. If a text is grammatically and semantically sound, its relevance judgment lies with the recipient. Whether it is an ai-generated text or not, however, is not relevant.

Informativity measures the novelty or unpredictability of information conveyed by a text, where equilibrium is key—too much or too little novelty can compromise a text's impact and reception. Situationality pertains to the context in which a text occurs, including the situation or environment that influences the text's meaning and relevance. The situational context plays a crucial role in how the text is interpreted. Here too, the text's origin, whether human or AI, bears no significance.

Intertextuality refers to the interconnections between a given text and other texts, recognizing influence and comprehension through references, citations, or shared norms and genres. AI-generated texts are based on the quality of the training data of their LLM, to which they naturally also refer. Their intertextuality is therefore only as good as the underlying models. But it is not much different for humans. They also refer to their individual knowledge and personal experience. However, GenAI applications (currently) tend to misrepresent or fabricate facts and references. Although this can lead to incorrect claims, it does not contradict the text linguistic standard of intertextuality.

Six of the seven standards can apply to AI-generated texts, with intentionality being contentious, as AI lacks living attributes and thus cannot have intentions. Nevertheless, it necessitates discussion if the intentionality of an AI-produced text is derived from the prompting human. If this view is embraced, then it must be acknowledged that AI-generated texts are indeed texts in the linguistic sense.

The subsequent question is what transforms a text into a work. References to the Berne Convention, EU copyright law, and corresponding jurisprudence clarify this (Hugenholtz & Quintais, 2021). To qualify as a work, four prerequisites must be met: production within a literary, scientific, or artistic domain; human intellectual effort; originality/creativity; and expression. GenAI applications undoubtedly satisfy the first criterion by their ability to generate archetypical texts.

The creation of a work mandates human intellectual effort, leading to the presumption that a work can only be created by humans. Albeit, tools like cameras can play legitimate roles in creating works. If a GenAI application is deemed a tool, then its employment in authoring a work becomes feasible, particularly since AI-assisted output generally pairs with human intervention at some juncture. The crux is to ascertain whether and to what extent human participation in the AI-assisted process is ample to warrant consideration as an intellectual creation.

Originality and creativity are indispensable for a work. Originality implies that the work is created independently and in a creative form. For written works, this involves free choices in wording, structure, and phrasing. Hugenholtz & Quintais (2021) split the creative process into conception, execution, and redaction. The conception phase involves ideation, where AI may offer assistance through ideas or insights, but the principal conceptual work is human-driven. During the execution phase, the concept materializes, with AI possibly aiding in varying degrees, from drafting to fully writing based on a prompt. It's imperative that text production remain a creative endeavor, thus necessitating human input. Redaction involves the refinement of the output, where AI may aid with language polishing or translation, yet choices of the degree of use rest with human discretion.

The fourth prerequisite, expression, asserts that a work's creation must be intentional, inferring that creativity must “express” itself in the final product. The potential to create a written work with AI's help also wrestles with the scope of AI's support. GenAI systems that are easily accessible and often commercial prevent, as non-transparent entities, predictability in their output. Humans cannot precisely control their text production or predict the result. However, the conception and redaction stages predominantly involve human effort, indicating that an AI-assisted text might indeed qualify as a work.

In conclusion, texts aided by AI can be considered both as texts and as works. The determining factor lies in the extent and manner of AI integration in the text production process. Ultimately, the pivotal debate revolves around the rightful claimant to authorship of a text—a question that will be explored in the ensuing subsection.

4.2 Claiming authorship

In European copyright law, the concept of authorship is intimately tied to the act of creating a work, with the stipulation that the author must be a human being. When examined through the lens of academic integrity, this principle underscores that the creator of a written work is entitled to claim authorship. Such a claim substantiates that the written work is a product of independent achievement.

In the academic sphere, it is now a prevalent practice for research articles to be collaboratively produced and disseminated by several contributors. These collaborators each make distinct contributions to a publication,

necessitating a determination of which contributions warrant (co-)authorship rights. Livingston (2016) offers a causal framework for understanding authorship: “S authors some work, W, just in case S intentionally performs actions A1-An,” and identifies delivering an original utterance as the minimal requisite act among these actions.

Osborne & Holland (2009), in their analysis of widely recognized guidelines for determining authorship in scientific publications, identify several contributory actions that can establish authorship. These actions span a spectrum from the conception or design stage to data collection and analysis, including data interpretation and drafting significant parts of the manuscript. Authorship is established by a “substantial contribution”, potentially encompassing one or more of the aforementioned actions. Hence, individuals can lay claim to authorship even without personally writing sections of the text, a finding also substantiated by research from Pruschak (2021). Those who fall short of making a substantial contribution are more appropriately recognized in the acknowledgments.

Many who have collaborated on a scientific paper will recognize that authorship often becomes a contentious issue. The criteria for what constitutes a significant contribution are not universally fixed; they vary based on factors such as the academic discipline, the parties involved, and their shared scientific principles. As Livingston (2016) articulates: “Authorship is one thing, honest and valuable authorship is something more.” Despite the variable standards for authorship, the notion that only a human can be recognized as an author has been a constant. However, with GenAI now in the picture, a pivotal question emerges: Can an AI system also be regarded as the author of a text and thereby bring forth a work?

4.3 GenAI: a new type of tool

It is widely accepted that GenAI applications are capable of producing texts that adhere to the foundational text-linguistic criteria for a text. Whether such texts qualify as a work is at least worth discussing. However, authorship cannot be ascribed to AI. On one hand, this would necessitate the capacity for intentional action—an attribute that is (at least presently) beyond the reach of AI technology. On the other hand, to attribute participation in text production, particularly during the conception and/or execution phases, AI would need to function independently (Ginsburg & Budiardjo, 2019). Current AI systems fail to meet this criterion as well, functioning solely to execute tasks as dictated by a human, typically via a prompt.

Yet, GenAI surpasses the role of a mere tool. Traditional software like word processors serve simply as instruments for humans to articulate their own thoughts. Conversely, the output of GenAI applications is shaped not solely by the input prompt but also by the training data and the configuration of the deployed algorithms. The influence of these elements means that GenAI can indeed produce value, and the creative process cannot be exclusively steered or predicted by human operators.

Consequently, GenAI applications exist in a unique category, neither solely as tools for human facilitation nor as generators of completely arbitrary (non-original due to the absence of creative decision-making) outcomes (Gervais, 2020). They also lack the capacity to yield results without human input. This leads to the conclusion that texts produced with the assistance of GenAI represent an amalgamation of human and artificial intelligence. Yet, pivotal questions linger: can individuals who utilize GenAI to create texts legitimately claim authorship, and do these texts uphold the traditional principles of academic integrity? From a legal standpoint, clarifying who qualifies as the copyright holder for these texts remains an essential task.

In accordance with European copyright law, copyright holders must be natural persons; thus, AI is precluded from holding copyright. The AI-generated text is the culmination of complex processes, potentially attributing

copyright to various individuals in roles ranging from copyright owners of the training data to the technical developers of AI applications, algorithm programmers, and—considering US copyright law—corporations that distribute GenAI services. The legitimacy of these claims is a matter that courts will ultimately need to resolve. Yet, authorship, as earlier delineated, cannot be readily inferred for these individuals and entities.

Moreover, users of GenAI applications do not automatically acquire copyright ownership of the resultant text (Gervais, 2020). In the conception phase, users define the subject or the content essence of the text. In the execution phase, the tangible text emerges, with AI mechanisms determining the specific crafting of the text from the generalized concept. The user's eligibility for copyright hinges on whether a substantial personal contribution to the text's creation has been made. As stated by Ginsburg & Budiardjo (2019): "To satisfy the execution requirement, the person claiming authorship must be responsible for controlling the basic steps that will lead to the manifestation of the key expressive elements of the work." (Gervais, 2020) argues that if a user cannot exert the necessary control and responsibility over the generated text, it lacks copyright and should be deemed public domain. Texts that emerge from a collaboration between humans and AI "should be treated as any other case where someone has reused material from the public domain to create a new work: The public domain material must be filtered out".

This viewpoint, however, does not contemplate the current reality that AI-generated texts can evolve through iterative collaborations between humans and AI. A text produced by an AI in response to a prompt can be refined, specified, or corrected through subsequent prompts. Thus, humans guide—even if not fully control—the execution process. Additionally, during the redaction phase, humans are tasked with rewriting and enhancing AI-generated texts. Identifying and attributing the portions of the text that are original AI creations can undoubtedly pose problems for both the recipients and the users of the GenAI application.

Deciding if the independent contribution of a GenAI user is substantial enough to merit (proxy) authorship of the text must be judged on a case-by-case basis (parallel to how courts resolve copyright claims). However, it's still ambiguous as to who is qualified to make this assessment and by what standards. At HEIs, there's an understandable level of uncertainty on this front, often leading to the classification of GenAI-generated texts as cheating and academic fraud under prevailing standards. Nevertheless, a more progressive perspective would entail recognizing the use of GenAI as an integral part of academic writing and re-evaluating the definition of academic misconduct accordingly.

5. GenAI as an opportunity for academic misconduct reassessment

Academic misconduct is routinely equated with plagiarism (Roig, 2015), wherein the explicit attribution of external ideas, data, and text incorporated into one's work is a cornerstone of adhering to commendable scientific practice. This acknowledgment is necessary not just for ethical reasons, but also to distinguish and evaluate the extent of an academic work's original contribution. This is true for both student essays and professional research papers.

As previously discussed, the extent to which texts produced with GenAI's help represent an independent accomplishment of the GenAI user is ambiguous. Consequently, it's indeterminable whether employing GenAI in academic writing comprises academic misconduct. This uncertainty is also reflected in a study by Duah & McGivern (2024), where "participants universally defined traditional classifications of academic misconduct but were unable to provide clear definitions where the use of GenAI was included for writing summative assessments." Therefore, the study's authors argue that HEIs need to reassess their academic misconduct policies. Lim et al. (2023) suggest a broader approach, advocating for a comprehensive reevaluation of academic misconduct criteria, rather than merely detailing acceptable uses of GenAI in guidelines. Akkaş et al.

(2024) call for a clarification of the boundaries between “AI assistance” and “AI ghostwriting.” Meanwhile, Barnett (2023) indicates that “universities are forced to reconsider their definitions of academic integrity”.

However, proposing these changes is less challenging than implementing them due to the significant transformation required, one that challenges the very roots of the traditional notion of academic work. Thus, what follows is an initial approach to the foundational contemplations instrumental to this transformative process.

Embracing GenAI as a component of academic writing, rather than forbidding or avoiding its usage, necessitates specific prerequisites: Individuals utilizing GenAI must substantially contribute during the conceptual and executional stages of the writing process and engage in a thorough editing procedure of the AI-assisted content. The emerging text must be sufficiently original, reflecting the person's intent. Any claim to authorship demands full responsibility for the text; it involves verifying the accuracy of AI-sourced sections, especially in relation to potential factual errors or fabricated citations. To the fullest extent, responsibility encompasses addressing any biases inherent in the LLMs that power the GenAI tools. Finally, persons generating ai-aided texts must scrutinize AI-generated content as rigorously as they would traditional sources.

Under these guidelines, it is likely that most AI-generated passages would be further modified, corrected, and expanded before being used. Hence, those rare sections that might be integrated unchanged into the final text should not be considered plagiarism, nor do they necessitate citation, as they typically constitute sentence fragments or subcomponents of a paragraph. In this context, the outline provided by Liu (2023), which plots the relationship between human and AI contributions, is instructive. If a piece of academic work possesses substantial human input, it does not represent academic misconduct. Concerns regarding academic integrity only emerge when the human contribution to the shared human-AI creation is low.

Figure 1: Forms of human AI co-creation (Liu, 2023).

To clarify: This proposal is not a green light to present substantial portions of AI-generated text as one's scholarly work. Those who rely on GenAI applications to write an essay through a single prompt and claim the output as their own work are guilty of academic fraud (as depicted in the lower right quadrant in figure 1). However, individuals leveraging GenAI to aid the writing process, who also make substantial contributions and takes responsibility for the resulting output, should not (any longer) be accused of academic misconduct.

It is imperative that the principles of academic integrity, particularly responsibility and honesty, be reevaluated in light of the above considerations. The insufficiency in detecting AI-generated texts (Katsamakos et al., 2024) currently casts a shadow over academic integrity. If responsible human-AI collaboration is no longer classified as academic misconduct, the need for detection diminishes. Nonetheless, equipping authors—students in particular—with the necessary understanding and competencies to effectively engage with GenAI is crucial. This encompasses comprehending how GenAI systems operate, recognizing their capabilities and boundaries, and acquiring the proficiency to utilize these technologies (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

In continental European higher education, academic performance—and potential academic misconduct—is typically judged by the final product. Yet, the competencies for effective GenAI engagement are improved during the writing process. A progressive approach involves introducing students to this process incrementally and evaluating their skill development. Liu (2023) proposes an array of assessment criteria, such as proficiency in crafting AI prompts, critical analysis of AI-generated suggestions, revision techniques, informational and digital literacy, thorough documentation, reflection on the co-creative process, and ethical reflection. These benchmarks not only assist in monitoring student progress but also can serve to measure the quality and quantity of human performance in any co-created text with AI.

Thus, improving the skills of students, educators, and scientists in AI usage is arguably more vital than detailed guidelines dictating the use of GenAI tools, especially as such directives would necessitate continual updates to keep pace with technological advancements. During the learning phase of AI application, documenting each step of the writing procedure allows assessors to identify and correct mistakes. This pedagogical approach should be executed in specific courses, focusing on how AI is utilized in the writing process rather than if it is used. Following this foundational learning, attributing AI-assisted text parts should no longer be a mandatory, provided the conditions outlined above are satisfied.

Understanding GenAI application use as a core component of the academic writing process signifies a paradigm shift that demands an evolution in academic mindset. This adaptation reimagines these applications not as something to be sanctioned, but as an intrinsic aspect of writing competence. Under this new paradigm, academic misconduct and academic integrity are not diluted; instead, they are meaningfully expanded.

6. Conclusion and limitations

The advent of GenAI text generation has triggered in a period of uncertainty within HEIs. The initial reaction has been to either categorize AI-generated texts under plagiarism or to insist on precise attributing of such texts. However, creators of these texts and their evaluators soon confront formidable challenges. The main issues include the near-impossibility of reproducing AI-generated texts, inadequate detection capabilities, and the rise of texts crafted through iterative collaboration between humans and AI.

This paper employs an interdisciplinary approach to examine whether AI-generated texts can be considered a "work" from linguistic, legal, and ethical standpoints and outlines the conditions necessary to claim authorship over such works. Subsequently, a model is introduced, framing the use of AI applications as an integral element of the writing process, contingent upon satisfying certain conditions. Key among these conditions is that AI users must act with intention, contribute substantial to the text's conception and execution, and accept full responsibility for the collaboratively produced text. HEIs are encouraged to instruct the requisite skills for this process early and centrally, potentially within scientific writing courses.

Despite its potentially provocative implications, applying the model described herein could harmonize GenAI usage with academic integrity principles. However, this adaptation must be viewed within the broader,

dynamic complexities confronting HEIs when integrating GenAI use. Strategic considerations and decisions currently have to be made almost exclusively on the basis of interpretations and assumptions. This even applies to copyright issues, as there are still no definitive supreme court verdicts on copyright matters.

The model outlined also encounters certain limitations. Gauging whether GenAI application users contribute substantially to text production varies by factors such as the scientific field involved. For instance, in humanities and language studies, the very act of writing is deemed a distinctive criterion. The parameters for evaluating the independent contribution of humans in the co-creative process remain inadequately defined. Moreover, the responsibility of assessing such texts and the expertise required for evaluators are yet to be determined. Additionally, further research into how GenAI impacts the writing process's quality is warranted. Presently, findings are mixed; for example, Doshi & Hauser (2024) state that GenAI amplifies individual author creativity, while but - collectively speaking - leads to a homogenization of text production.

In conclusion, this paper serves as a call to explore how GenAI integration should be approached in the realm of academic integrity, rather than whether it should be integrated at all. In closing, the study by Yusuf (2024) poses a thought-provoking point, indicating that societies more adept at navigating uncertainties are more inclined to perceive AI utilization as an opportunity rather than academic misconduct.

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Higher education students using GenAI tools to design websites

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Abstract

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools have the potential to revolutionize education. However, there is limited research of empirical studies on university students' uses and experiences with GenAI tools. This study investigates the views of university students regarding Wix AI and ChatGPT after they have used these tools for website design and development. The students evaluated the user experience, and the quality of both Wix AI and ChatGPT as well as of their responses. They mostly appreciated ChatGPT's easy-of-use, fast and useful responses. They also believed that both tools are interesting and helpful. However, they disliked their unoriginal and occasionally inaccurate, fabricated responses. Furthermore, they highlighted more advantages, disadvantages, opportunities, obstacles, and risks associated with using Wix AI and ChatGPT for website design and development. Finally, the study provides recommendations to students, GenAI developers, and educational institutions with regards to the use of GenAI tools in education.

Keywords: authentic assessments, ChatGPT, ease-of-use, evaluation, generative artificial intelligence, GenAI, higher education, project-based learning, quality, user experience, Wix, Wix AI.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is advancing at a fast pace causing extensive changes in higher education (Hwang & Chang, 2023; Wu & Yu, 2024). A special area of interest is how to combine generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools into educational practices (Lam et al., 2023). These powerful tools can produce content like code, text and other multimedia materials enabling educational experiences that can enhance personalized learning. GenAI is an emerging technology that can revolutionize education (Adeshola & Adepoju, 2023; Rejeb et al., 2024). Students consider GenAI tools as an attractive assistant that can provide personalized learning support, writing help, and research support (Chan & Hu, 2023). In art education, GenAI fosters creative thinking through prompt writing and iteration, motivating students to explore and revise their ideas. Students using generative AI tools as study aids showed improved students' outcomes (Gupta et al., 2024; Hutson & Cotroneo, 2023). Additionally, these tools can empower students to become critical thinkers by using AI to comprehend texts, aggregate knowledge, and understand genre conventions across various disciplines (Steele, 2023). Despite concerns about accuracy, privacy, and ethical issues, the integration of GenAI in education offers promising opportunities for enhanced learning experiences and outcomes across various disciplines.

The main aim of this study is to examine the effective incorporation of GenAI tools within the higher education landscape. Although several previous studies suggested the integration of GenAI into teaching and learning, the perceptions of students towards utilizing these tools in classrooms remain ambiguous (Lam et al., 2023; Rejeb et al., 2024). Moreover, few studies investigated the actual use of GenAI tools by higher education students (Economides & Perifanou, 2024; Rejeb et al., 2024; Vargas-Murillo et al., 2024). Actually, there is limited research on real cases that describe the actual use of GenAI tools by students (Das & J.V., 2024; Kasneci

et al., 2023; Montenegro-Rueda et al., 2023). More specifically, there is not any study to investigate university students using and evaluating two such GenAI tools, Wix AI (Wix, 2024) and ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2024).

Wix is a user-friendly online platform offering customized templates for website creation without any need for coding (Wix, 2024). Wix AI, launched in March 2024, is an evolution of Wix's previous AI tool called Wix ADI (Artificial Design Intelligence) which was first released in 2016. Users without prior coding knowledge can use a conversational interface to create customized websites. However, Wix AI has been critiqued for potential limitations in creative customization. Over-reliance on templates can lead to website homogenization with regards to design aesthetics. ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI and released in November 2022 (OpenAI, 2024), utilizes the Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) model to understand human language and respond to users by providing ideas and multimedia content. However, its responses are not always accurate (Das & J.V., 2024; Dwivedi et al., 2023). Combining Wix AI and ChatGPT can support users in design and development of websites.

In addition to the limited research on the actual use of GenAI by university students, there is limited research particularly on the use of GenAI tools for website design and development. Large language models were proposed to non-technical users to create websites from natural language specifications (Calò & De Russis, 2023). The method employs prompt engineering to generate websites without coding knowledge. A study on AI integration in web design and user experience (UX) education revealed positive student perceptions (Lively et al., 2023). Most participants found AI beneficial, with high usage rates for text and image-based AI content generation. The majority incorporated AI into their final projects, believing it improved their work. Students appreciated AI's time-saving aspects and its potential for ideation, content creation as well as suggesting creative solutions and assisting with coding. Another study examined the feasibility of generative AI tools in web development tasks such as brainstorming, design, and coding at beginner and advanced levels (York, 2023). A systematic literature review on automatic website generation concluded that artificial intelligence is revolutionizing web user interface design and development, offering rapid prototyping and easy-to-build website solutions (Kaluarachchi & Wickramasinghe, 2023). AI-powered tools can translate sketches into functional code and assess design quality automatically. However, there is not any study to investigate university students using Wix AI and ChatGPT for website design and development. Furthermore, there is not any study to evaluate and compare Wix AI and ChatGPT from the user point of view. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the university students' evaluations of Wix AI and ChatGPT?

RQ2: At what extend university students use Wix AI and ChatGPT during the implementation of their projects?

RQ3: What are the university students' views on the advantages, challenges, and risks of using Wix AI and ChatGPT?

RQ4: What are the university students' recommendations for using Wix AI and ChatGPT?

The next sections describe the study's methodology, results, discussions, and conclusions.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods research design, using both quantitative and qualitative methods in order to comprehensively understand students' experiences using GenAI tools for their class projects. Combining data from students' responses to close and open-ended questions, students' presentation as well as focus groups discussions can enhance the validity of the findings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). By combining quantitative and qualitative data, this study aims to provide a holistic view of students' perceptions, practice, and experiences.

2.2 Context and Participants

This study investigates the use of ChatGPT by college students in an "E-Commerce and Digital Marketing" course that is based on project-based learning and authentic assessment. Project-based learning (PBL) is a student-centered instructional strategy (Bell, 2010; Kokotsaki et al., 2016) that involves students in authentic and real-world projects. Based on constructivist ideas, PBL emphasizes the unique needs and experiences of individual learners (Von Glasersfeld, 2012). Students work on personalized projects by investigating and evaluating relevant information and resources, and producing concrete outcomes (Economides & Perifanou, 2024). Also, PBL can develop students' intrinsic motivation and self-regulated learning (Kokotsaki et al., 2016).

In authentic assessment (AA) students implement assignments that are meaningful and relevant to the workplace or real-world, practical situations (Sokhanvar et al., 2020). It replicates or resembles tasks faced by professionals in the workplace and students have to apply their knowledge and skills to solve practical problems, develop artefacts, or perform tasks that mimic those of the workplace (Villarroel et al., 2017). Also, it can enhance students' engagement in learning as well as their satisfaction (Sokhanvar et al., 2021). More specifically, it can enhance students' problem-solving skills (Darma et al., 2018; Ukobizaba et al., 2021) and critical thinking skills (Gedera, 2023; Ifelebuegu, 2023; Schultz et al., 2022; Sokhanvar et al., 2020).

The study involved a group of 14 students (9 female and 5 male) enrolled in an elective course on "E-Commerce and Digital Marketing" in the Department of Economics, at the University of Macedonia, Thessaloniki, Greece, during the spring semester of 2024. Eleven students were under 22 years old and three students were between 23 and 27 years old. Most students had previously completed two or three additional introductory informatics courses. The course is designed to incorporate project-based learning and authentic assessment as a primary pedagogical approach. Using Wix, students have to design and develop a website by also exploiting Wix AI and other generative AI tools such as ChatGPT. The students voluntarily participated in the study, and informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. Thirteen (13) students have used both Wix AI and ChatGPT, while one more student used only Wix AI. In addition to Wix AI and ChatGPT, students used more tools such as MS Copilot, Google Gemini, Canva, WriteSonic, Simplified, Synthesia, Pixlr, Gencraft, Quillbot, Paraphrase Online, Rewrite AI, AISpline, Looka, Diagramming AI, Easy-Peasy AI, Squarespace, etc.

Initially, each student had to consider and select a specific and creative digital business idea that they would explore in order to build a relevant website. This digital business idea could be the digital makeover of an already-existing company or a brand-new digital business (online store, online platform, mobile app, etc.). The student had to make an argument for why their digital business idea was a good and novel one, as well as for what market share it targeted, who their competitors were (specifically, similar businesses), what their idea's advantages and disadvantages were relative to those of their competitors, and what unique and novel features their digital business needed to have in order to compete. In order to evaluate the internal and external

elements that could have an impact on the success of their digital business idea, the student had also to perform a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis.

Then students had to use Wix to design and develop a website related to their digital business idea. The Wix AI website builder can help the users to: refine business name and logo; choose colors; create content; create visuals and video; do search engine optimization (SEO); add AI-powered product recommendations; create customer service chatbots, and more. In parallel, students could use other GenAI tools such as ChatGPT to select business name and logo, create an outline, select options, create content, summarize text, promote the website, etc.

After the creation of their websites, students had to answer a questionnaire with close and open-ended questions. Furthermore, they had to prepare a presentation of all steps of their project and their website design and development. Following the students' presentations to class, they participated in focus group discussions about their experiences on using Wix AI and ChatGPT for the design and development of their websites. So, students followed these steps: 1) develop their website idea; 2) design their website; 3) develop their website; 4) present all steps of their work and their final website; 5) answer a questionnaire; 7) participate in class discussions.

2.3 Data Collection

Data were collected through multiple sources to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the students' experiences: i) online questionnaire; ii) projects' presentations; iii) class discussions, and iv) students' reports.

A structured online survey was administered to students in order to gather quantitative and qualitative data on their perceptions of generative AI tools. The survey included both closed-form questions (e.g., Likert-scale items) as well open-ended questions (Denscombe, 2017). During the presentations of their websites and the focus groups discussions in class, students described how they implemented the various parts of their websites and how they used GenAI at the various stages of their websites' design and development. Specifically, they highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of Wix AI and ChatGPT, their potential opportunities for education and work, the issues that they faced and how they solved any problems. Finally, the researchers collected more data when reading the students' reports that include all the steps in developing students' websites as well as their interactions with the GenAI tools.

2.4 Data Analysis

This mixed methods study utilized both qualitative and quantitative analysis. Regarding quantitative analysis, descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize quantitative data from students' responses to the closed form question of the survey. Regarding qualitative analysis, thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was utilized to identify common themes and patterns in student responses to the open-ended questions of the survey and the focus groups discussions in class. These qualitative data were transcribed and analysed to recognize repeating themes and patterns related to students' views and experiences with GenAI.

3. Quantitative Results

A questionnaire was developed in order students evaluate the free versions of Wix AI and ChatGPT. This questionnaire consists of demographics questions, closed form questions and open-ended questions. In order to evaluate these AI tools, the questionnaire included the user experience – lite (UX-Lite) scale (Lewis & Sauro, 2024), self-developed questions to evaluate the quality of the AI tool itself as a system, and self-developed questions to evaluate the quality of the responses of the AI tool (Table 1).

The quality of the AI tool itself was evaluated with respect to being: i) quick to generate responses, ii) interesting, iii) helpful, iv) enjoying and fun to use, and v) satisfying. The quality of the responses of the AI tool was evaluated with respect to their: i) usefulness, ii) accuracy, iii) completeness, iv) relevance, and v) up-to-datedness (recentness, currentness). The responses to each question correspond to a 5-point Likert scale as follows: 1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neither agree nor disagree; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree (Table 1). The comparative analysis of Wix AI and ChatGPT in the context of website design and development reveals distinct advantages and potential drawbacks associated with each tool.

Table 1: Evaluation of Wix AI and ChatGPT.

Evaluation of the AI Tool	Wix AI		ChatGPT	
	Mean	SDT	Mean	SDT
User Experience of the AI Tool				
I thought this AI Tool was easy to use	3.93	0.73	4.62	0.65
The capabilities of this AI tool meet my requirements	3.57	0.85	3.85	0.69
Quality of the AI Tool				
I think this AI Tool generates responses quickly without any delays	4.14	0.95	4.54	0.52
I think this AI Tool is interesting	4.21	0.7	4.46	0.66
I think this AI Tool can help me with the assignment (task, work, project) and improve my performance	4.29	0.73	4.38	0.65
I enjoy using this AI Tool and I have fun	3.64	0.63	3.77	0.93
I am satisfied with the overall experience of using this AI Tool	3.79	0.97	3.92	0.86
Quality of the AI Tool's Responses				
I think the responses of this AI Tool are useful for completing my assignment (task, work, project)	3.57	1.09	4	0.58
I think the responses of this AI Tool to be accurate and correct without any errors and inconsistencies	2.79	0.97	2.77	0.93
I think the responses of this AI Tool to be complete and comprehensive without any duplications or repetitions	3.14	0.77	3	0.71
I think the responses of this AI Tool to be relevant and appropriate to the prompt	3.36	0.74	3.85	0.69
I think the responses of this AI Tool to be current and up-to-date	3.57	0.76	3.77	0.83

Students give the highest score (Mean= 4.62) to ChatGPT's easy-of-use (Table 1). In addition, they rate both tools high (Mean above 4) with respect to generating responses quickly without any delays, interesting, as well as help with the assignment (task, work, project) and improving their performance. Students believe that it is easier to use ChatGPT (Mean= 4.62) than Wix AI (Mean=3.93). Actually, 92.3% of students using ChatGPT versus 71.4% of students using Wix AI agree or strongly agree that the tool was easy to use. Regarding the speed of the tools, students believe that ChatGPT (Mean= 4.54) is faster than Wix AI (Mean= 4.14). Actually, all students (100%) using ChatGPT versus 78.6% of students using Wix AI agree or strongly agree that the tool generates responses quickly without any delays. Also, students believe that ChatGPT (Mean = 4.46) is more interesting than Wix AI (Mean= 4.21). Indeed, 92.3% of students using ChatGPT versus 85.7% of users using Wix AI agree or strongly agree that the tool is interesting. Similarly, students believe that ChatGPT (Mean = 4.38) is more helpful than Wix AI (Mean= 4.29). In fact, 92.3% of students using ChatGPT versus 85.8% of users using Wix AI agree or strongly agree that the tool can help them with the assignment (task, work, project) and improve their performance. Also, students believe that ChatGPT (Mean= 4) is more useful than Wix AI (Mean= 3.57). Indeed, 84.6% of students using ChatGPT versus 64.3% of students using Wix AI agree or strongly agree that the responses of the tool are useful for completing their assignment (task, work, project). Table 1 presents

the means and standard deviations of students' responses to the close-ended questions about Wix AI and ChatGPT.

Regarding the quality of the tools' responses, students believe that ChatGPT (Mean= 3.85) provides responses that are more relevant and appropriate to their prompts than Wix AI's responses (Mean= 3.36). In fact, 69.2% of students using ChatGPT agree or strongly agree versus 50% of students using Wix AI agree that the responses of the tool are relevant and appropriate to the prompt. On the other hand, students give low scores to the responses' accuracy of both Wix AI (Mean= 2.79) and ChatGPT (Mean= 2.77). More specifically, 28.6% of students using Wix AI and 38.5% of students using ChatGPT disagree or strongly disagree that the tool responses are accurate and correct without any errors and inconsistencies.

Regarding the number of prompts that students ask the tools, seven (7) students asked ten (10) or more prompts to each GenAI tool (Figure 1, Figure 2). Actually, three students asked dozens of prompts to the tools. However, there were several students who did not take advantage of the tools' affordances. There were seven (7) students who asked less than ten prompts to Wix AI or ChatGPT. Actually, one student did not ask any question to ChatGPT. Reasons for some students' reservedness and caution to use these tools will be discussed in the next section based on the analysis of their answers to the open-ended questions.

Figure 1: Number of prompts to Wix AI given by students

Figure 2: Number of prompts to ChatGPT given by students

Another interesting result is that students did not use the exact responses of ChatGPT in their project as they were given by ChatGPT but they modified them at an average rate of 48% (Figure 3). Interestingly, four students modified ChatGPT’s responses at 60% and two students at 80%.

Figure 3. To what extent have you modified (changed) ChatGPT's responses?

Finally, students stated that their website design and development was based at an average rate of 42% on the responses of ChatGPT and the rest was based on Wix, Wix AI, Internet resources, etc. (Figure 4). Interestingly, three students stated that their work was based at 60% on ChatGPT responses and one student at 80%. Thus, students were mostly inspired by the responses of ChatGPT and they applied them after modifying them.

Figure 4. What percentage of your work is based on ChatGPT responses (the remaining percentage is based on Wix, Wix AI, Internet resources)?

4. Qualitative Results

Qualitative data from students’ answers to open-ended questions and focus groups discussions are categorized and analysed in the following subsections. Students have used GenAI tools during all four phases of their project workflow: 1) Project Initiation, 2) Project Planning, 3) Project Development, and 4) Project Evaluation phases (Table 2). They have used Wix AI and ChatGPT mostly during the 3rd phase of Project Development.

Table 2: Phases of Project’s Workflow and Prompt Examples.

Phases	Description	Prompt example
1) Project Initiation	Defining the project’s objectives, goals, and deliverables.	“Recommend me some innovative ideas for my website?”
2) Project Planning	Planning the activities, timelines, milestones.	“What should I do next?”

3) Project Development	Designing and creating the website; Monitoring project's progress; Making adjustments.	<i>"On the website we provide a modern psychometric test which detects the inclinations and skills of the clients. The test is very quick and easy to be completed. It is also weighted with respect to Greek students and adults. After completing it, the client discusses the results with the professionals. Provide a full description of this service."</i>
4) Project Evaluation	Reflecting with regard to the whole project lifecycle; Creating a Presentation about their work; Making the presentation; Evaluating their work.	<i>"How would you improve the cancellation policy?"</i>

4.1 Advantages of Wix AI and ChatGPT

Students highlighted several advantages of using Wix AI for website design and development. They mostly appreciated the easiness of using Wix AI to create websites. Also, they liked that Wix AI can provide immediate answers and useful resources, suggest various options such as customizable templates and functions, easily create text, combine complex photos, and save time in developing their websites. For example, a student was impressed by *"Wix AI's ability to suggest templates as a basis for further website editing"* and another student liked that *"Almost at every step there was an AI function, which reduced the construction time of the site by a lot"*.

Almost all students praised the ease of use of ChatGPT. They appreciated that it quickly provides instant, relevant, and detailed answers without unnecessary information to any question (at any language, subject, complexity, difficulty, etc.) saving time and energy. They underlined that it is a useful tool helping them in various tasks such as explaining complex terms, topics, and concepts. They valued that it generates human-like text without grammatical and syntactical errors, summarizes long text, and creates ideas and advice on any topic even for personal or professional development. In addition, they liked that it can organize and guide (provide a plan) the user to complete the work as well as suggest the sequence of steps to follow for solving a problem or implementing a project. Finally, they enjoy using it. For example, a student valued that *"ChatGPT quickly and easily provides you with ideas and useful information for work. It helped me to formulate in a formal style the texts in my work without grammatical and syntactical errors. It also contributed to the creation of summaries of long texts. In each step of the work, it directed me as to the next steps to follow and more generally in creating a plan to complete the work. Finally, on a more general level in learning, ChatGPT helps me to better understand terms and concepts through its detailed answers"*.

4.2 Disadvantages of Wix AI and ChatGPT

On the other hand, students pointed out several disadvantages of Wix AI for website design and development. They did not like that sometimes Wix AI is slow, provides inaccurate or fabricated as well as trivial, ordinary, unimaginative, and unoriginal responses. Also, they were not pleased by its inability to completely understand all of their questions. In addition, they did not like the quality of the generated text as well as the images that are irrelevant to the prompt and need a lot of refinement. For example, several students mentioned *"Very slow response"*, *"Loading between pages is slow"*, *"it was very slow and crashed often"*. They also worried about the generated text, e.g., *"Wix AI's original text production probably lags behind that of humans or other AI programs (e.g., ChatGPT)"*.

Students pointed out several disadvantages of using ChatGPT. They mostly underlined that sometimes ChatGPT did not understand their prompt and it requires clarifications and detailed input. So, they need to revise their prompt several times in order to get appropriate answers. For example, a student mentioned that *“Many times, to understand the question exactly, it needed two or three more revisions”*. Also, they did not like that it does not always give accurate, current, relevant, targeted, precise, and clear answers without so much chatter.

4.3 Opportunities and Suggestions for using Wix AI and ChatGPT

Students identified several opportunities Wix AI offers for learning and work such as effective writing, easy web design without the need for coding, building professional websites quickly, managing and promoting websites, and increasing their *“confidence in handling other AI tools”* for future AI-powered work. They mentioned that *“It opens your mind and shows you things you hadn't thought to include in your work.”* The students suggested to use Wix AI in education for getting *“familiar with AI tools, web design and digital marketing”*, providing ideas and knowledge, create websites, promote students' work, *“share business ideas and business proposals”*. They also suggested it for *“creating and selling websites, consulting and training services for businesses and individuals as well as website management by professionals”*. Finally, they proposed universities to offer training, such as seminars and workshops, to both educators and students on using Wix AI to easily create websites. For example, educators can create educational websites for supporting their courses.

Students valued ChatGPT as a useful tool for learning and work opportunities such as explaining difficult concepts and specialized terms of any subject; gaining knowledge, ideas, and advice; writing, editing, and translating text; developing scenarios and simulations; helping with exams preparation and doing research as well as foreign language learning and practice. To integrate ChatGPT in education, students recommended training both teachers and students on how to effectively use it. For example, a student suggested that *“Teachers can use it to create [educational] material and presentations, plan and organize their lessons and tasks, as well as find ideas to make the lesson more interactive and interesting for students”*. Students can use it as a virtual tutor to answer any question and expand their knowledge on any issue that interest them. Finally, ChatGPT could be integrated into online learning platforms for broader use.

4.4 Obstacles, Risks and Coping Difficulties using Wix AI and ChatGPT

Students recognized several obstacles and risks associated with using Wix AI. They were seriously concerned about their dependency on Wix AI and not developing their own knowledge and skills in creating websites. This over-reliance on Wix AI, due to the convenience that it provides, may limit their creativity and skills development, and eventually, they may become unable to develop websites without using AI. Also, the risks include the doubt about the correctness, validity and reliability of the content produced. They also worried about Wix AI providing identical responses to different users. By not providing creative and unique responses, the websites will tend to look similar and be identical without any differentiation. For example, a student was concerned that *“Maybe because some designs are automatically generated to look similar to other sites using the same tool. This can affect the uniqueness of the site”*. In addition, they were anxious about security and privacy risks such as personal data leaked. Furthermore, they would like that Wix AI provides more free features for educational usage, multilingual support, better community support (FAQ, chats, etc.), and higher speed. Finally, they suggested users' training on using AI tools and cybersecurity. They advised using strong passwords to access Wix. They also recommended users to check and confirm the validity of AI responses.

Additionally, students highlighted several obstacles and risks associated with ChatGPT use. Key obstacles included its inaccurate and fabricated answers as well as the no differentiation of its answers to similar

prompts. They stated that the answers of ChatGPT are almost fixed, standardized without any innovation. They were afraid that using ChatGPT the learners' imagination, creativity, critical thinking, judgment, and motivation for learning and personal development will decrease and the students' outputs will become uniform and identical losing any personal taste and touch. Also, ChatGPT unsuccessfully imitates the human-like writing and it can be detected by several AI text detectors.

They also see risks of misinformation, plagiarism, and exam cheating. A student suggested that *"These obstacles and risks could be reduced through the continuous updating and improvement of ChatGPT, the additional control of users for the accuracy and validity of the text, and the taking of measures by the state and educational institutions to prevent them from being deceived"*. Also, they would like that ChatGPT provides a collaborative environment for multiple users working at the same time on a shared task. They suggested that ChatGPT responses include valid citations to the original sources of information so that the user can assess their reliability. Finally, they recommended training students on critical thinking and misinformation detection in order to distinguish between reliable and unreliable sources of information.

5. Discussion

Wix AI exploits GenAI to facilitate the ease and quick design and development of websites by users without any need for coding. Through a conversational interface, Wix AI provides ready-to-use templates and automated features that facilitate the website design process. On the other hand, ChatGPT operates as an interactive assistant that provides ideas, explanations, and human-like content to student prompts about any topic.

Wix AI facilitated the website creation by enabling students to select customized templates. There was no needs for students to have prior website design or coding knowledge. Wix AI asked a few questions about the student's business or personal preferences and generated a website that could fit their needs. It allowed students to create websites quickly offering modern and aesthetically pleasing designs. Its interface is simple and straightforward, allowing students to easily follow instructions and make minor adjustments, if needed. While Wix AI simplified the website design, it raised students' concerns about the potential homogenization of website design, as reliance on predefined templates may result in less original, creative, and diverse designs. Some students found it limiting if they wanted a fully unique and original design. Wix AI allowed for a certain degree of personalization by integrating business branding elements such as logos and color schemes.

One of ChatGPT's strongest points was its ease of use, speed, and time-saving capabilities. Many students enjoyed interacting with ChatGPT due to its conversational ability, which made it feel fun and engaging. ChatGPT enabled students to explore various design prompts and ideas, fostering a more personalized approach to their projects. They appreciated that responses were generally clear, well-structured, and easy to understand. Students liked ChatGPT's ability to generate quickly creative content. However, some students found that ChatGPT can become repetitive or overly verbose in certain cases. It sometimes provided generic answers or added unnecessary details. Also, there were concerns about the accuracy of its responses and the potential that students may over-rely on it. Students reported occasional fabricated or outdated information, especially if they would like the latest, up-to-date facts. Therefore, it is important to improve the model's accuracy and contextual understanding as well as educate users on its effective and responsible use.

Based on the results of the previous sections, this study makes the following recommendations to GenAI users:

- Exploit GenAI for personalized learning.
- Decompose problem in steps and use GenAI for help in each step.

- Provide clear, detailed and focused prompts to GenAI to get more accurate results.
- Revise prompts to guide GenAI to your requirements.
- Verify GenAI's responses using reliable and authoritative sources.
- Use GenAI as a learning aid, but not as a substitute for doing assignments.
- Be aware of GenAI's limitations, especially regarding current events.
- Take training on the effective and responsible use of various GenAI tools.
- Develop skills in creating effective prompts to get more accurate and relevant responses.
- Cultivate creativity, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving skills.

In addition, recommendations to GenAI tools' developers follow:

- Implement real-time information updates to improve the timeliness of GenAI's knowledge.
- Enhance GenAI's ability to understand complex and vague prompts.
- Develop features that encourage critical thinking, such as providing multiple perspectives on topics.
- Continue to improve the GenAI's ability to generate creative, diverse and differentiated responses.
- Validate the generated content, cite sources of information, detect and correct inaccuracies.
- Provide more free functionalities for educational purposes.
- Provide explanations on how the GenAI's responses come out.

Correspondingly, recommendations to educational institutes follow:

- Integrate the customized and responsible use of GenAI in courses of various subjects.
- Provide training on GenAI for students, faculty, and staff.
- Develop policies and guidelines for responsible and ethical use of GenAI.
- Foster collaboration and partnerships between students, faculty, educational institutes, and companies.

6. Conclusions and Future Research

During a project-based "E-Commerce and Digital Marketing" course, students used Wix AI and ChatGPT for helping them to design and develop websites. They used these GenAI tools for generating business ideas, SWOT analysis, website designs, content (e.g., business names, logos, page titles, headings, keywords, page meta descriptions, products' descriptions, services' descriptions, personnel descriptions, blogs, emails, social media posts, customer support, cancellation policies, FAQ), images, and more. Then students evaluated Wix AI and ChatGPT with respect to several evaluation criteria and expressed their views about these GenAI tools answering closed and open-ended questions and participating in focus groups discussions in class.

In order to evaluate the use of Wix AI and ChatGPT, this study proposed evaluation criteria with respect to user experience and quality of both the GenAI tool and its responses (Table 1). These evaluation criteria are crucial for students' adopting and using these tools. Based on the students' answers to these evaluation criteria, their answers to open-ended questions, their projects' presentations in class, and their views during focus groups discussions, this study provides the following conclusions.

Wix AI is easy to use, time saving and great for beginners in website design and development. It allows for quick website creation offering ready-to-use templates and design (Wix, 2024). However, it provides limited customization options that may lead to uniform and uncreative website design. ChatGPT is a user-friendly and time-saving tool giving fast (Hasanein & Sobaih, 2023; Kayalı et al., 2023; Yilmaz & Yilmaz, 2023), helpful, and

human-like responses in any language (Das & J.V., 2024). However, it has not access to real-time data or the latest information (OpenAI, 2024) and occasionally it gives inaccurate (Das & J.V, 2024; Dwivedi et al., 2023), superficial or repetitive responses. Depending exclusively on GenAI tools could lead to unimaginative outputs. So, it is needed careful management about how GenAI tools are employed in the creative process. GenAI tools should be positioned as powerful assistants that augment human knowledge and skills rather than replace them.

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Monitoring of Teachers' Digital Professional Development: A Revised Model

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Abstract

The Digital Competency Training Assessment Model (DCTAM) has been developed in response to the growing need to improve teachers' digital professional development by monitoring it for further support and transfer of digital competences. It is based on Guskey's (2002) model and introduces four new evaluation levels - trainee characteristics, training characteristics, sustainability of practice and learner characteristics - to complement Guskey's original five levels. The structure of the revised model was statistically tested using empirical data collected in the context of a large-scale curriculum reform in digital education. The results showed that delays in implementation affect the sustainability of new practices, that less favourable immediate reactions do not necessarily lead to less learning, and that organisational conditions are likely to moderate the relationship between immediate reactions and behavioural change. These findings highlight the need to look beyond participants' initial reactions when evaluating digital education training programmes. Future research should explore innovative measurement methods that combine subjective and objective assessments. Equally important is the development of user-friendly digital tools for consistent programme monitoring to ensure that trainers can efficiently implement this model, such as digitaltrainingcompanion.ch.

Keywords: digital education, digital competences, teacher professional development, monitoring, evaluation, assessment frameworks, large-scale assessment, data science

1. Introduction

Many countries around the world are implementing reforms to integrate digital education into their curricula. While the main goal is to improve students' digital literacy, such reforms often start by strengthening teachers' digital competence (Valverde-Berrocoso et al., 2021). Improving teachers' digital competence is a major challenge. First, it requires teachers to quickly master the use of digital technologies for educational purposes, an area unfamiliar to many. Secondly, it requires the translation of this training into robust pedagogical practices within a limited timeframe. As a result, these unique aspects place significant pressure on teachers. (Fernández-Batanero et al., 2021). Despite substantial investment in curriculum reform, limited uptake of new

content has been observed in several countries, including the UK (Sentance & Csizmadia, 2017; The Royal Society, 2012; The Royal Society, 2017), France (Roche, 2019) and Japan (Ohashi, 2017). These findings show that the expected outcomes for the students, depend on a variety of organisational and personal factors that influence a teacher's propensity to apply what they have learned during training. Therefore, evaluation of training programmes is essential to ensure that they meet their objectives and allow for adaptation where necessary (Guskey, 2002).

While ongoing evaluation of training is widely seen as beneficial by advocates and practitioners, this type of evaluation is still rarely carried out (Benson-Armer, Otto & van Dam, 2015; Goodall et al., 2005). When it is the case, they often only measure participant satisfaction at the end of the training (Kim et al., 2020). A similar observation can be made in digital education training (King, 2014). In a review of 20 studies on the integration of technology into teaching practice, Gaytan & McEwen (2010) found that most evaluations did not go beyond measuring participants' perceptions and focused on tangential elements such as logistics and satisfaction with the training. These authors recommend that evaluation of professional development (PD) activities should also focus on student learning. King (2014) also highlights that the lack of appropriate expertise hampers attempts to conduct long-term monitoring of digital education programmes. Such deficiencies can lead to inadequate evaluation processes that fail to accurately assess the impact and success of these programmes, thereby limiting their potential.

To address this gap, this paper identifies key predictors to facilitate a comprehensive monitoring of teachers' PD based on relevant research on large-scale training programs evaluation in digital education.

2. Professional development evaluation: state of the art

Various frameworks in the literature outline key criteria for evaluating PD programs. The best known is Kirkpatrick's model (Kirkpatrick, 1959) and its four levels: reaction (measuring participant satisfaction), learning (content acquisition), behaviour (behavioural change) and results (intended outcomes). These levels reflect the effectiveness of the training activity. Given this limitation, Guskey (2000, 2016) proposed a model based on Kirkpatrick's and other related models but tailored to education (Table 1).

Guskey's model retains the levels of reaction (participants' reactions), learning (participants' learning) and behaviour (participants' use of new knowledge and skills). An additional level ("organisation support & change") is inserted between the levels of participants' learning and participants' use of new knowledge and skills. Kirkpatrick's fourth level is refined as student learning outcomes, focusing only on student learning outcomes and changes in attitudes and behaviour.

3. Enhancing Guskey's model

3.1 Limitations of Guskey's model

Although Guskey's model outlines the different levels for evaluating PD programmes in digital education, it does not detail the specific predictors to be measured at each level. The literature helps to circumscribe the most relevant predictors for evaluating these levels. Many studies highlight the key role of trainees and training variables in immediate reactions (e.g. Kim et al., 2020). In addition, Guskey's model does not address criteria that support participants' sustained use of new knowledge and skills.

Table 1: Comparison between the levels of Kirkpatrick's (1959) and related models and those of Guskey's (2000) model.

Levels of Kirkpatrick's and related models	Levels of Guskey's model
1. Reaction <i>Participants' satisfaction</i>	1. Participants' reactions <i>Participants' satisfaction</i>
2. Learning <i>Participants' acquisition of knowledge and skills</i>	2. Participants' learning <i>Participants' acquisition of knowledge and skills</i>
3. Behaviour <i>Participants' concrete use of knowledge and skills</i>	3. Organisation support & change <i>Organisational shift to support participants' change</i>
4. Results <i>Concrete impact on productivity</i>	4. Participants' use of new knowledge and skills <i>Participants' concrete use of knowledge and skills</i>
5. Return of investment <i>Rentability of the action (benefit-cost / cost)</i>	5. Student learning outcomes <i>Concrete impact on students' outcomes</i>

This model is also unidirectional and nested, implying that success at one level is usually necessary for success at higher levels' (Guskey, 2016). Therefore, success at level 1 (participant reaction) is assumed to be the main cause of success at level 2 (participant learning) and so on. However, this assumption can be challenged, as levels 1 and 2 can have a bidirectional relationship, with neither necessarily causing the other. Moreover, specific variables that influence the gap between training and actual application of the training content. In Guskey's model, while participants' use of new knowledge and skills is seen as a result of organisation support & change, level 3 could instead be seen as a moderating variable of the relationship between levels 1 and 2 and level 4, i.e. organisational conditions would not determine but moderate the likelihood that a given level of reaction and learning would be translated into effective behaviour in the field.

3.2 Additions and modifications made to Guskey's model

Taking all the above into account, the limitations identified in Guskey's model have been extended with levels and predictors from the digital education literature, and a new structure between these levels, supported by empirical evidence, has been introduced (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Digital Competency Training Assessment Model (DCTAM): A revised theoretical model for evaluation of digital education training. The numbers indicate studies that attest relationships between predictors.

3.3 Additions derived from the previous studies

Trainee and training characteristics

Level 1 of Guskey's model (participants' reactions) appears to be moderated by external variables (Davis, 1989). On the one hand, research on structural relationships between these external variables and participants' reactions in large sample studies suggests that both trainee and training characteristics influence these reactions. For example, trainee characteristics include pre-training motivation, which includes motivation to learn and apply the acquired knowledge (Kim et al., 2020; Devos & Dumay, 2006). In the context of technology acceptance, trainee characteristics also cover attitudes towards technology - one's evaluation of the technology or specific related behaviour (Zhang, Aikman & Sun, 2008), subjective norms - perceptions of significant others' beliefs about the behaviour in question (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977), and computer self-efficacy (Scherer, Siddiq & Tondeur, 2019).

Training or situational characteristics (Kim et al., 2020), on the other hand, encompass aspects such as perceived trainer performance. This refers to the trainer's ability to engage the audience, manage time, and the suitability of their teaching methods (Giangreco et al., 2009, Ludwikowska, 2021). It also includes the settings of the learning space, such as the condition of the classroom or the arrangement of instructional tools (Kim et al., 2020). In addition, Devos & Dumay (2006) also describe transfer training variables related to the characteristics and relevance of the training programme. These variables range from pre-training elements such as enrolment modalities - voluntary vs. mandatory, pedagogical approaches - alignment between what is learnt in training and what is done in the workplace, and utility/relevance of the training to the job.

Therefore, when evaluating learner characteristics prior to digital training, several predictors could be considered: pre-training motivation, attitudes towards technology, perceived social expectations (formerly referred to as 'subjective norms'), the type of enrolment (voluntary or compulsory) and digital self-efficacy.

Sustainability conditions

Level 4 of Guskey's model (Organization support & change) does not adequately address the sustained use of new knowledge and skills over time. Klingner et al. (2001) highlighted several factors that influence educators' commitment to the ongoing use of new training content. These factors include the perception that students both learn from and enjoy the new content, and the ability to fit the new training content into their existing teaching practices. Cèbe and Goigoux (2018) suggested that the success of new educational practices hinges on two primary factors: 1) their alignment with educators' existing practices and 2) the educators' perception of the efficiency of their intervention. This perceived efficiency is determined by weighing the perceived benefits against the potential disadvantages of implementing new resources. The benefits include student progress following the introduction of new materials and an increased sense of educator self-efficacy (Guskey, 2000). Conversely, potential drawbacks could include cognitive and emotional strain or an increased workload. Specifically, the Sustainable Adoption of Digital Education model shows that the sustainability of new content adoption is predicted by both the usefulness of teaching this new content and the ease associated with its implementation. The study also shows that adequate support within schools, a critical organisational condition, has a significant impact on sustainability. Therefore, compatibility with prior practices and perceived efficiency of new practices emerge as important predictors of the sustainability of teachers' practices.

Students' characteristics

Finally, existing research suggests that student learning outcomes cannot be fully attributed to the implementation of new knowledge and skills. For instance, a study on 109 vocational trainees (Barboutidis & Stiakakis, 2023) found that variables such as age, specialisation, possession and use of smartphone and computer, education level and internet use moderate several digital competence areas. Additionally, other

research emphasises the role of technology-related stereotypes, such as prevailing computer science biases and prior technology familiarity, especially home exposure, in shaping student outcomes in digital education (e.g., Master et al., 2017).

Therefore, when evaluating students' characteristics that moderate the relationship between behavioural change and student learning outcomes, the following predictors should be considered: age, specialisation, level of education, use of digital tools, technology-related stereotypes.

4. The Present study

4.1 Research questions and hypotheses

The study tests the validity of the suggested additions and structural modifications depicted in the revised model (Figure 1). Based on the previous literature, the following hypotheses guides this study:

- *Hypothesis 1*: The sustainability of the new practices is influenced by the delay of implementation.
- *Hypothesis 2*: Unlike in Guskey's model where favourable immediate reactions are prerequisites for successful participants' learning, it is assumed that low scores in immediate reactions do not necessarily lead to low scores in participants' learning.
- *Hypothesis 3*: Organisational conditions moderate the relationship between immediate reactions/participants' learning and behavioural changes.

4.2 Method

Research context and participants

This study is part of a broader initiative to introduce digital education as a new subject in Swiss schools. This initiative introduced a new curriculum in Computer Science, Information and Communication Technology, and Digital Citizenship, facilitated through a research-practice partnership. Within this project, teachers participated in a continuous education program, equipping them with new technology-related knowledge and digital competencies. They then applied this competence in their classrooms. The initiative was set to impact 12,000 teachers and 130,000 students, spanning from pre-K to high school. The digital competences provided during the training program were drawn from the official Digital Competence Framework for French-speaking Switzerland and Ticino, developed in 2021 based on DigCompEdu (Conférence intercantonale de l'instruction publique de la Suisse romande et du Tessin, 2021).

Procedure and material

Two samples of teachers were studied for this research. The first sample consisted of 205 teachers instructing grades K-5 to K-7 (Sample 1), and the second comprised 259 teachers from grades K-8 to K-10 (Sample 2). Each group participated in two sets of four-day training sessions. These sessions were structured as a series of workshops spread across multiple days. At the conclusion of each session, participants completed a comprehensive questionnaire. This survey assessed multiple aspects of the training: immediate reactions, perceived learning outcomes, perceptions of organisational support for classroom implementation, and actual application of training content and transfer of digital competencies. Table 2 offers a detailed breakdown of daily training activities and attendance figures.

Table 2: Workshops conducted each day of the training, and the total number of participants (N) involved.

	Day 1		Day 2		Day 3		Day 4	
	Workshops	N	Workshops	N	Workshops	N	Workshops	N
Sample 1	- Internet research:	257	- Orchestration	211	- Robotics	181	- Rights & data - Concept 360	205

	copyrights and sources - Pages with students - Pages for preparing lessons		- Scratch - Presentation tools, uses, media and society		- Reflective analysis of media		- Retroactions	
Sample 2	- Introduction to digital tools for teachers - Media literacy - Practical application	259	- Sociological model of the EduNum reform - Basic concept in computer science: from information to data - Sociology of media - Data and rights - Creating a video in class	276	- Digital support for accessibility - AI, challenges for education - Digital and sustainability	288	- Cybersecurity: from concepts to best practices - Prevention: construction and use of the digital charter - Video games: immersion in adolescent culture	239

Measures

Table 3 summarises the assessment levels and the indicators for each sample. It should be noted that not all predictors were assessed on each training day.

Table 3: Measurement of the predictors in each level of interest by day of training for sample 1 and 2.

Levels	Sample 1	Sample 2
Immediate reactions	Perceived interest Perceived usefulness Self-efficacy	Perceived interest Perceived usefulness Perceived ease of use Self-efficacy Behavioural intention
Learning	-	Knowledge Digital competencies
Organisational conditions	-	-
Behavioural changes	-	-
Immediate reactions	Perceived interest Self-efficacy Behavioural intention	Perceived interest Perceived usefulness Perceived ease of use Self-efficacy Behavioural intention
Learning	-	Knowledge Digital competencies
Organisational conditions	Material resources Temporal resources Technological-pedagogical support	-
Behavioural changes	Actual use of training content	Transfer of digital competencies
Immediate reactions	Perceived interest Self-efficacy Behavioural intention	Perceived interest Perceived usefulness Perceived ease of use Self-efficacy Behavioural intention
Learning	-	Knowledge Digital competencies
Organisational conditions	Material resources Temporal resources Technical and/or pedagogical support	Material resources Temporal resources Leadership and peer support Technological-pedagogical support
Behavioural changes	Actual use of training content	Transfer of digital competencies
Immediate reactions	Perceived interest Self-efficacy Behavioural intention	Perceived interest Perceived usefulness Perceived ease of use Self-efficacy

		Behavioural intention
Learning	Digital competencies	Knowledge Digital competencies
Organisational conditions	Temporal resources Technological-pedagogical support	-
Behavioural changes	Actual use of training content	Transfer of digital competencies

All predictors except behaviour change, which was measured with a multiple-choice question, were measured on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree) by rating each workshop topic using a suggested question. For instance, to measure the perceived interest and usefulness the following questions were asked: "I found the following workshop 'Copyright and Sources' interesting/useful"; the self-efficacy: "I feel capable of implementing elements of the following workshop 'Internet Research' with my students"; the behaviour change: "I intend to conduct the following workshop 'Scratch' with my students"; the organisational conditions: "Do you need the following elements to do your job as a teacher?" with 3 options.

In Sample 1, learning was assessed after day 4 of the training with a 7-point Likert scale from 1 (not at all acquired) to 7 (fully acquired) by answering 3-8 questions related to the knowledge acquired on the day of the training (e.g., "At the end of the day, I know how to effectively protect sensitive digital content") and 8 questions related to the acquisition of digital competences (e.g., "The digital practice of being able to define the phenomenon of video games and its influence on society, especially on young people, is now clear to me"). In Sample 2, learning was assessed in a similar way to Sample 1, but already after day 1 of the training and covering 13 topics for knowledge and 9 areas of digital skills. In addition, after day 3 and day 4 of the training, the perceived transfer of digital skills was measured using a 7-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree) by rating the question: "I have implemented these digital skills in my teaching" with 19 options (e.g. "I have implemented working with different digital environments, including open source solutions, in my teaching. ").

Data analysis

To ensure data accuracy and anonymity while linking participants from session to session, self-generated identification codes were used. They consist of generating a code based on bits of information people can provide with a high consistency over time. For example, the self-generated identification (O1FKM02) code could be made up of the month of birth (01), the gender assigned at birth (F), the first letter of the second name (K), the first letter of the mother's name (M) and the number of older siblings (02).

Further on, data from different training days were merged using self-generated identification codes. However, their use inevitably resulted in data loss due to the lack of matching codes provided by an individual on two different days (Audette, Hammond & Rochester, 2020). For example, to test Hypothesis 2, data on immediate reactions and participant learning were collected on the same day (e.g., D3), while organisational conditions and behavioural changes were measured on the following training day (in this case, D4). Thus, the number of participants who used identical self-generated codes on both D3 and D4 was smaller compared to the number of participants who provided data for D3 and D4 independently. Each test performed explicitly details the specific number of participants used in its corresponding analytical procedure.

Results

Hypothesis 1: To show the impact of the delay of implementation, i.e., to demonstrate that those who adopt early in the training program tend to continue to adopt most consistently afterward, Sample 1 was divided into two subgroups: participants who implemented the activities before the next training day (about two months later) and those who did not. The adoption rate for each activity was then recalculated for the following day (D+1) and, when data were available, for the subsequent day (D+2) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Adoption rates at D+1 and D+2 among participants implementing activities before the next day of training or delaying adoption.

In Figure 2, it is apparent that the adoption rate for participants at D+1 consistently reveals higher levels for those who embraced the training content before the next training day. Furthermore, the adoption rate experiences an additional increase for certain activities at D+2 among participants in the first subgroup. Table 4 confirms the results observed for most of the activities. Therefore, we can validate Hypothesis 1.

Table 4: Results for Chi-square of independence tests for Hypothesis 1.

Activities	Tests	Conclusion
Classroom orchestration and tablet use	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 6.96, p = <.01, w = 0.27$	H1 supported
Scratch	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 21.24, p = <.001, w = 0.48$	H1 supported
Presentation tools: uses, media and society	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 3.28, p = >.05, w = 0.18$	H1 not supported
Internet research: copyrights and sources	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 9.80, p = <.01, w = 0.32$ D+2: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 2.46, p = >.05, w = 0.16$	H1 partially supported
Pages with students	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 3.95, p = <.05, w = 0.20$ D+2: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 18.52, p = <.001, w = 0.45$	H1 supported
Pages for preparing lessons	D+1: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 13.16, p = <.001, w = 0.38$ D+2: $\chi^2 (1, 91) = 13.00, p = <.001, w = 0.37$	H1 supported

Hypothesis 2: The relationship between immediate reactions and participant learning was examined using bivariate distributions. In Sample 1, scores for *Perceived Interest*, *Self-efficacy*, and *Behavioural Intention* were averaged to create an *Immediate Reactions* measure. Similarly, perceived learning scores from the digital competencies training were averaged. For Sample 2, this method was expanded to include the predictors *Perceived Usefulness* and *Perceived Ease of Use*. These distributions were then segmented into four quadrants, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Bivariate distributions of the relationship between Immediate reactions and Participant learning.

Note. Spearman correlations were used. 1-β: post-hoc power. Purple crosses: lower scores (< 4) in immediate reaction and lower scores (< 4) in participant learning, Blue squares: lower scores (< 4) in immediate reactions and higher scores (>= 4) in participant learning, Green triangles: higher scores (>= 4) in immediate reactions and lower scores (< 4) in participant learning, Red circles: higher score (>= 4) in immediate reactions and higher scores (>= 4) in participant learning.

Visually, there is a strong positive correlation between Immediate reactions and Participants' learning. Higher scores in Immediate reactions are typically associated with higher scores in Participants' learning. However, contrary to Guskey's model—which suggests that favourable immediate responses are a fundamental precondition for successful learning—a subset of participants (blue squares in the left corner) shows significant acquisition of the knowledge and digital competencies even when their immediate reactions fall below neutral. To statistically validate this observation, Chi-Square goodness-of-fit tests were employed. The observed distribution of scores in the four quadrants was compared against a theoretical distribution based on Guskey's model assumption (H1): high scores (>= 4) in Immediate reactions should imply high scores (>= 4) in Participants' learning. Conversely, high scores (>= 4) in Immediate reactions should not correspond with low scores (< 4) in Participants' learning. The results of these tests are detailed in Table 5. The tests indicate that the presence of participants with lower scores in immediate reactions but higher scores in learning is not just a result of random chance. This evidence supports the validation of Hypothesis 2.

Table 5: Results of Chi-square goodness-of-fit tests for hypothesis 2.

Sample	Test	Conclusion
Sample 1 - D4 N=203	$\chi^2 (3, 203) = 332.75, p = <.001, w = 1.28$	H2 supported
Sample 2 - D1 N=257	$\chi^2 (3, 257) = 2434.3, p = <.001, w = 3.07$	H2 supported
Sample 2 - D2 N=273	$\chi^2 (3, 273) = 203.54, p = <.001, w = 0.86$	H2 supported

Sample 2 - D3 N=288	$\chi^2 (3, 288) = 5098.3, p = <.001, w = 4.21$	H2 supported
Sample 2 - D4 N=239	$\chi^2 (3, 239) = 4142.5, p = <.001, w = 4.16$	H2 supported

Hypothesis 3: Moderation analyses were conducted to identify whether Organisational conditions moderate the relationship between Immediate reactions/Participants' learning and Behavioural changes (Figure 4). Data from two consecutive days were consolidated for this analysis. The first day provided metrics on Immediate reactions and Participant learning, while the next day contributed information about Organisational conditions and Behavioural changes. For Sample 1, the focus was on the shifts between D2 to D3 and D3 to D4. In contrast, for the Sample 2, the analysis centred on the transition from D2 to D3, and both Immediate reactions and Participants' learning were included. Drawing from the methodology of Hypothesis 2, scores from various predictors were averaged to produce unified metrics for Immediate reactions, Participants' learning, and Organisational conditions.

Figure 4: Moderation Analysis of Organisational conditions on the relationship between Immediate Reactions/Participant Learning and Adoption.

Note. Spearman correlations were used. For sample 1, Adoption refers to the number of different training activities implemented later in the classroom. For sample 2, Adoption refers to the degree of agreement regarding the implementation of the digital skills learned during training in their teaching from 1 - Not agree at all to 7 - Fully agree. For Sample 1 and 2, Immediate reactions and Participants learning refers to the degree of agreement from 1 - Not agree at all to 7 - Fully agree. Hinderer conditions measure the extent to which participants require specific organisational conditions, while facilitating conditions measure the degree to which participants possess certain organisational conditions.

For Sample 1, it is evident that, as Organisational conditions become more hinderer, the positive correlation between Immediate reactions and the Actual use of training content (number of activities carried out in the classroom) decreases. This indicates a moderating effect of Organisational conditions on the relationship between Immediate reactions and Behavioural changes. For Sample 2, there is a positive correlation between

Immediate reactions and the Transfer of digital skills in the classroom for both Immediate reactions and Participants' learning. Yet, the moderating effect of Organisational conditions here is either mild or negligible. Table 6 provides a detailed overview of the analyses carried out to test Hypothesis 3. The results confirm a moderation effect of Organisational conditions on the relationship between Immediate reactions and Behavioural changes for Sample 1, but not for Sample 2. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is only partially validated.

Table 6: Results of interaction effects of moderation analyses for hypothesis 3.

Sample	Tests	Conclusion
Sample 1 - Transition between D2 and D3 Immediate reactions	There was a significant negative interaction effect between Immediate reactions and Hindering conditions on the outcome variable ($b = -0.14$, $SE = 0.05$, $t(123) = -3.02$, $p = .003$, $\eta^2 = .07$).	H3 supported
Sample 1 - Transition between D3 and D4 Immediate reactions	There was a significant negative interaction effect between Immediate reactions and Hindering conditions on the outcome variable ($b = -0.11$, $SE = 0.05$, $t(110) = -2.10$, $p = .03$, $\eta^2 = .04$).	H3 supported
Sample 2 - Transition between D2 and D3 Immediate reactions	There was a non-significant negative interaction effect between Immediate reactions and Facilitating conditions on the outcome variable ($b = 0.07$, $SE = 0.11$, $t(98) = 0.70$, $p > .05$, $\eta^2 = .002$).	H3 not supported
Sample 2 - Transition between D2 and D3 Participants learning	There was a non-significant negative interaction effect between Participants learning and Facilitating conditions on the outcome variable ($b = 0.04$, $SE = 0.09$, $t(98) = -0.64$, $p > .05$, $\eta^2 = .005$).	H3 not supported

5. Discussion

In the field of education, Guskey's model allows for comprehensive evaluation of the training process. However, while the mode outlines levels for evaluating a PD program, it lacks specificity regarding the predictors to assess at each level. By taking this model as a starting point, we identified predictors that align with the various levels of Guskey's model. Additionally, our research highlighted the significance of incorporating four additional levels, along with their specific predictors, which Guskey's model does not include. These additional levels encompass training characteristics, trainee characteristics, sustainability conditions and student characteristics.

First, we demonstrated that considering the delay of implementation serves as a crucial indicator of sustainability. Specifically, if trainees adopted the activities covered in the training before the subsequent training day, it strongly indicated their likelihood to continue implementing this activity in their classroom in the future. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring adoption at multiple intervals and directing the support offered by instructional coaches towards those trainees who do not implement within a short timeframe.

Second, while we discovered a robust correlation between participants' learning and their immediate reactions across two separate samples, it became clear that positive participants' reactions are not always a precondition for effective learning. Remarkably, we consistently noticed a significant number of participants who expressed below-neutral immediate reactions but indicated above-neutral knowledge and skills acquisition. These findings highlight the importance of evaluating both aspects to fully understand the training outcomes. Consequently, our revised model situates immediate reactions and learning on the same tier, treating them as separate outputs of the training.

Finally, we also investigated whether high scores in organisational conditions were a necessity for participants' behavioural changes. We hypothesised that organisational conditions might exhibit a moderating effect. Our results in this context were more varied. In Sample 1, where the dependent variable was the diversity of

training activities later implemented in the classroom, a pronounced moderating effect of organisational conditions was observed on the relationship between adoption and participants' reactions. Even with positive participants' reactions, the magnitude of adoption was influenced by the degree to which the organisational conditions enabled it. However, this relationship wasn't strictly binary. Even with lower scores, some level of adoption persisted, but it completely halted when organisational conditions were significantly unfavourable (+1 SD).

6. Limitations and future perspectives

The empirical evidence presented here has some limitations that could be addressed in future research. Firstly, while we aimed to measure all predictors from literature consistently, logistical needs in the training sessions sometimes took precedence, resulting in not every predictor being measured daily. This reality restricted our ability to perform comprehensive analyses, leaving certain aspects of our theoretical model unconfirmed. Secondly, our approach to ensuring participant anonymity led to a significant drop in participation rates. We used self-generated identification codes for privacy, but this led to a 30-50% decrease in participation between sessions, thereby affecting the study's methodological rigour. Lastly, our analyses mainly centred on the novel features of the proposed revised model rather than thoroughly replicating findings from Guskey's model or extensively examining the new levels we introduced. Although the DCTAM presented in this study offers a new perspective on evaluation of PD in digital education, the following areas require further exploration.

6.1 Subjective vs. objective measurements

While the current study has identified key predictors for evaluating digital education training programs, the effective measurement of these predictors, especially on a large scale, presents a substantial challenge. Future research could explore innovative methods for reliably and efficiently measuring these predictors at scale. In our study, we mainly used self-reported measures. These are especially apt for capturing subjective information that influences participants' future actions. While objective measures may better gauge acquired knowledge, self-reported confidence in learning can more predictably indicate later adoption, even though it might not always reflect the true depth of understanding. However, measuring behavioural changes necessitates more objective metrics. Maderick et al. (2016) found that pre-service teachers consistently overestimate their abilities when self-assessing. This overestimation is concerning because it suggests that trainees might be less competent after PD than their scores, based solely on their self-reports, would indicate. Nonetheless, it remains a challenge for trainers to objectively assess participants' digital competence implementation, especially on a large scale. External observation can be prohibitively time-consuming or even unfeasible. A potential solution is for trainers to operate with more specificity. By constructing test items rooted in tables of specifications, as discussed by Fives & DiDonato-Bernes (2013), trainers can provide teachers a clearer structure for self-assessment and develop specific test items matching their learning goals in digital competence acquisition.

6.2 Enhancing monitoring with data science and advanced digital tools

To facilitate the utilisation of such models, the development of digital tools leveraging data science is crucial. While tools tailored for each level of the model exist, there is a need for platforms that allow a holistic evaluation of training programs. In addition, data collection often requires both assessment creation and data processing. These are two labour-intensive processes that demand advanced expertise in psychometrics, data analysis, and visualisation to ensure that data collection effectively aids decision-making. However, trainers often lack these skills. Interestingly, recent advancements regarding generative AI models offer unprecedented opportunities for simplifying the construction of assessments. For example, to assess participants' learning, trainers could provide certain information about their training, such as the knowledge and skills covered in

each workshop and the desired skill level. This information could be input into a generative AI model, leading to the automated creation of multiple-choice questionnaires, which trainers can then tweak if necessary. This method could save trainers significant time while ensuring a consistent quality of assessments.

By providing user-friendly visualisation tools for feedback and negating the need for deep statistical knowledge, trainers can be better equipped to make proactive, real-time decisions based on data. This capability aids in pinpointing and addressing areas that need support, streamlining communication with instructional coaches. Thus, a web application (digitaltrainingcompanion.ch) integrating these features to empower trainers to effectively manage and enhance their digital competency training programs was developed.

7. Conclusions

This study builds upon Guskey's model of teacher PD evaluation, adapting it for the context of digital teacher training. Specific predictors for each level were introduced, as were additional ones based on empirical findings. Insights from a large-scale digital education reform were used to refine this model to align it more closely with field observations. The data indicated that the prompt integration of training content in the classroom had a pronounced effect on the continuation of learned activities. Furthermore, the research informs a revised model to aid trainers in selecting the most relevant predictors for comprehensive programme evaluation. Thus, this research offers essential perspectives for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders in digital education. The incorporation of the insights and recommendations presented here can significantly enhance the efficacy of digital competence training, fostering the integration of digital competences among educators.

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Diversity and Inclusion in Open and Online Education

Differentiated Teaching, Digital Tools and Inclusion: Teachers' Views and Practices in Primary schools: a Case Study

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Abstract

The educational reality very often fails to meet the needs of a large portion of students as well as the challenges of a constantly changing reality. This has the consequence that a large number of students are faced with school failure or unable to function in the context of a complex but also constantly changing society and reality in general. The demands of the times for inclusion and equality of opportunity so that all students have the opportunities to develop according to their particular potential and abilities has led schools to adopt and create mixed-ability classrooms and inclusive practices. This assumes that (a) there will be appropriate differentiation of instruction that will respond to a range of differences in students' learning readiness, interests, and learning styles, and that (b) teachers will be able to respond to the diversity of students. This differentiation of teaching within the framework of the theory of knowledge construction can contribute to reducing the phenomenon of school failure and improving learning. However, the questions that arise in the context of the school and especially regarding condition (b) are: (1) How do teachers perceive the concept of differentiated instruction? (2) How do they try to implement it? (3) Do they think that the differentiated approach can contribute to the improvement of teaching and learning? (4) How they embrace digital tools for differentiating students' learning. In our research we will follow a qualitative approach which include the examination of the research questions through a focus group and semi-structured interviews with teachers who apply differentiated teaching practices in the context of inclusion. The views and concerns that will be submitted in this pilot research will be the trigger for a broader quantitative approach in order to highlight the issues faced by teachers in their efforts to apply the differentiated method as well as ways to support them.

Keywords: differentiated instruction, inclusion, teachers' views, digital tools, qualitative methodology

1. INTRODUCTION

Undoubtedly diversity in educational context and, in general, is an undeniable phenomenon and differences between students are integral in classroom environments (Belfi et al., 2012). This becomes more obvious in urban environments where there is often a mixed and versatile student population regarding sociocultural backgrounds, home environments, languages etc. These factors nonetheless influence the quality of life and the dynamics of power and privilege (Gaikhorst, 2014; Matsko & Hammerness, 2014).

Because the 21st century is characterized by innovative ways to communication, dissemination and accumulation of information, education is called for to respond to two requests which initially seem contradictory: a) to effectively and comprehensively transmit the ever-increasing and evolving acquired knowledge, as well as the method of acquiring it, so the students will have the skill bases they will need in the future, and b) to spot and record the reference points that will help to not to become overwhelmed by the abundance of information that flows in private and public space – much of which are ephemeral – and contribute to maintaining the continuous development of themselves as individuals and

societies. Education, that is, shows people a picture of the world and at the same time it provides the compass that will help them navigate safely into it (UNESCO, 2002: 125). To achieve this, education must reinforce the following forms of learning, which are regarded as the pillars of knowledge: a) to learn how to learn, that is, how to acquire the tools of understanding this world in the broadest sense, b) to teach them (the students) how to act, so that they are productive in their space, c) teach them how to live with others, and d) to teach them how to exist, that is knowledge that results from the two previous ones. All four pillars are considered as a single whole, because they have many common points.

This exercises a demand on teachers to develop and expand the abilities of the students by accepting and recognizing that students have different ways of learning and responding to instruction (Gay, 2018; Tomlinson, 2014).

Differentiated instruction (DI) is a thorough teaching approach that intends to increase the learning outcomes of all students in the classroom and minimize the achievement gap (Gheysens et al., 2020; Griful -Freixenet et al., 2020; Steenbergen-Hu et al., 2016). However, the most important role, concerning its function and realization of differentiated teaching is held by the teacher. His/her role must be valued as a resource (Benjamin, 2006:59). In this context the teacher becomes more of a facilitator, activity planner and evaluator than a teacher (Theroux, 2004).

While most teachers agree with the obvious advantages of DI in meeting student needs, its actual the extend to which teachers engage in practice with it, is considered to be, as research has shown, a major challenge and remains critical (Suprayogi et al., 2017). It is common knowledge that teachers often need additional preparation and practice to be enabled for implementing DI in their classrooms (Dixon et al., 2014). It has been argued that there has been an increase in efforts aimed at developing and monitoring programs to effectively prepare and equip teachers for this task (Parsons et al., 2018). Even though the growing body of literature on DI offers some starting points, there is still no consensus on how to effectively prepare and professionalize teachers for DI (Bondie et al., 2019; Deunk et al., 2018; Smets, 2019). The present review study aims to uncover and describe what the literature tells us about teacher preparation and training programs targeted at improving teachers' competence for tailoring their education to the diverse learning needs of students. In our small scale research which attempts to investigate how teachers perceive and implement differentiated instruction with embracing digital technology the assumptions were that (a) there will be appropriate differentiation of instruction that will respond to a range of differences in students' learning readiness, interests, and learning styles, and that (b) teachers will be able to respond to the diversity of students aided also by the use of digital tools.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Creating an Inclusive environment

Sociocultural framing of learning which perceives learning as a socially situated process, influenced by cultural, historical, and contextual factors has been greatly underlined by educational research as it offers a broader, more contextualized understanding of how people learn (Wells 1999). This perspective, rooted in the work of scholars like Lev Vygotsky and Jerome Bruner, emphasizes the role of social interaction, cultural tools, and community in shaping individual learning experiences. More specifically, learning is viewed as a process that occurs through interaction with others, particularly more knowledgeable individuals (e.g., teachers, peers, or community members). This understanding has shifted the focus from individual cognition to the social nature of learning such as collaborative learning, peer

interactions, and the role of teacher-student relationships (Vygotsky,1978). The main idea is that learning is not only about acquiring universal knowledge, but it is also deeply embedded in specific cultural and historical contexts. This has led to an increased focus on culturally relevant pedagogy and understanding how students' cultural backgrounds shape their learning experiences. Teachers and researchers should pay more attention to the diverse cultural backgrounds of learners and how these influence their engagement with the curriculum, their motivations, and their learning outcomes. Teaching should be grounded in students' cultural contexts to promote meaningful learning experiences. (Ladson-Billings, 1995).

Also Vygotsky emphasized that learning is mediated by cultural tools such as language, symbols, and artifacts. This perspective has led educational researchers to focus on how tools and resources (e.g., language, technology, and physical objects) facilitate learning and cognitive development. As a consequence the use of cultural tools in classrooms—such as books, digital technologies, and language—has become a key focus of educational research, particularly regarding how these tools can be used to support learning in diverse contexts (Cole, 1996). An other dimension is the concept of *scaffolding*, introduced by Jerome Bruner, which refers to the support provided by a more knowledgeable other to help learners perform tasks they cannot complete independently.

Over time, as learners gain competence, the support is gradually withdrawn, a process known as *fading*. Therefore the provision of effective scaffolding promotes independent learning. Furthermore learning is inherently social and context-dependent. Learning occurs in communities of practice, where individuals participate in authentic activities and share experiences with others.the design of learning environments that encourage collaboration, real-world problem-solving, promotes the development of professional communities among educators and students (Lave & Wenger,1991). As a consequence sociocultural theories have encouraged the development of curriculum and instructional strategies that are more inclusive and responsive to the needs of diverse student populations. Instruction is increasingly viewed as a dynamic, interactive process that involves dialogue, negotiation, and adaptation to students' backgrounds and needs (Rogoff, 2003). Finally the sociocultural perspective also emphasizes how learning contributes to identity formation. It highlights the role of social and cultural contexts in shaping how learners view themselves and their place in the world (Holland, Lachicotte, Skinner & Cain, 1998). As it rightfully has been argued, a crucial factor for such a theoretical perspective is a teacher who is capable of creating a safe and supportive classroom environment which encourages the inclusive nature of learning (Hattie 2010; Navarro et al. 2016). This calls for the fact that inclusion is seen as process that increases participation and reduces exclusion (Booth and Ainscow 1998). As it has been pointed out (Qvortrup and Qvortrup, 2018:806) there are several components that inclusive schools and classrooms consist of: (1) All staff supporting a clear school-wide vision and focus on all children.(2) All children are valued members in the classroom and are educated together (in comparison to traditional “pull-out” methods).(3) Comprehensive support for not only all children but also teachers.(4) An approach supporting collaborative teams(5) Flexible curricula reflected in quality instruction and evidence-based approaches(6) Supportive leadership and shared decision making(7) Focus on teachers' professional development. Furthermore a key factor for inclusive learning environment is taking into consideration the variety of the student populations and implementing DI in a way that all pupils can develop socially, emotionally and academically as well (Evertson & Weinstein 2006; Hattie & Anderman 2013; Santangelo & Tomlinson 2012). In this heterogeneous student populations we also include students with disabilities or special education needs

that must be accommodated in an ordinary classroom environment, as it is the example of the primary education classes in Norway (Johler & Krumsvik, 2022).

3. Differentiated Instruction

The term “*differentiated instruction*” refers to a systematic approach to planning the totality of instruction for students with different learning needs. For appropriate teaching planning, emphasis is placed on two main axes: the student and the analytical program. With regard to the first axis, the students, we distinguish three sub-components : (a) their readiness or otherwise the level of performance, (b) their interests and (c) the particular way in which they learn (learning profile). The second axis, the curriculum comprises content and instruction.

More specifically Tomlinson and Imbeau (2010:11) do not view DI as a set of strategies but rather as a “*demographically necessary, ethically focused, pedagogically informed, and empirically tested way of thinking*” (11). Tomlinson (2001) frames differentiated instruction in four categories: Content: the knowledge, understanding and skills students should master. Process: the activities students use to understand and make sense of the contents. Product: the method the students use to demonstrate understanding of key ideas, transfer of knowledge and application of skills. Affect: how students’ emotions and feelings influence their motivation and learning.

Actually DI links on-going research on learning with everyday teaching. For example, it is research-documented that learning improves in an environment where knowledge is well organized, close to the level that students are already achieving (Howard, 1994), where students they are actively involved in learning and feel safe (Brandt, 1998). Moreover DI comprises a number of quality characteristics which render it a unique approach for all levels of learning and instruction. More analytically DI according to Tomlinson (2001) is : (a) Proactive. The teacher proactively plans differentiation to address a variety of learning needs—as opposed to adjusting a lesson plan when it becomes clear that it’s not working for some students, (b) More qualitative than quantitative. DI involves adjusting the quality of an assignment to match student needs—not varying the quantity of work. For example, a struggling reader may need additional support for reading and writing a book report. An advanced student who has mastered one math skill, instead of doing more assignments that are too easy for him, can practice another skill, (c) Rooted in assessment. Since addressing student individual needs is at the core of DI, teachers look for every opportunity to get to know their students better—through conversations with students, classroom discussions, student work, observation, and formal assessment. Then, teachers design and modify learning experiences based on assessment findings. Each student's progress is measured, at least in part, from where that student begins, (d) Provides multiple approaches to content, process, product, and affect/learning environment. At the core of DI is the modification of four elements—content (what students learn), process (how do students make sense of the information and ideas), product (how they show what they’ve learned) and affect/learning environment (the climate or tone in the classroom). This modification is based on assessment of student differences in readiness, interest, and learning profile, (e) Student centered. All students participate in respectful work—work that is challenging, meaningful, interesting, and engaging. Tasks are based on students’ prior knowledge and are designed with the level of challenge appropriate for the student. The teacher primarily coordinates time, space, and activities, rather than provides information. Pacing varies based on students’ needs. The goal is to help students become self-reliant learners and to share the responsibility for their learning, (f) is a blend of whole-class, group, and individual instruction. The teacher uses a variety of instructional strategies to help target instruction to students’ needs. Students

work in a variety of group configurations, as well as independently. Flexible grouping is evident, (g) “Organic.” Teaching constantly evolves through collaboration between students and teachers, which includes setting class and individual goals. Teachers monitor how learning fits the student and make adjustments, where necessary.

4. Educational Technologies

The influence of digital technologies on means of instruction, pedagogical practices, and classroom dynamics has been transformative, reshaping how education is delivered and experienced by both teachers and students. Digital tools and platforms have introduced new possibilities for teaching, learning, and interaction in the classroom, making it more dynamic, flexible, and student-centered. The classroom environment is becoming gradually more and more digitally oriented, and this inevitably has impacts on the means of instruction, pedagogical practices, and classroom dynamics (Harper and Milman 2016; Goodwine al. 2015). The capability of digital technologies in supporting differentiated instruction has appeared in many studies (e.g. Baron et al. 2019; Haymon and Wilson 2020).

Digital technologies enable teachers to integrate multimedia resources like videos, podcasts, interactive simulations, and animations into their lessons. These resources cater to various learning styles and can make complex concepts more understandable and engaging. For example Interactive whiteboards, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) allow for immersive learning experiences that traditional teaching methods cannot provide. The use of Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle, Google Classroom, and Canvas has revolutionized how assignments are distributed, assessed, and graded. They also facilitate collaborative learning among students through discussion forums and shared projects (Gee, 2003; Mayer, 2009). Moreover, digital technologies have facilitated the rise of blended and flipped classroom models. In a blended learning environment, face-to-face instruction is combined with online content, allowing for a more flexible learning experience. In flipped classrooms, traditional lecture-based instruction is replaced by students accessing content online at home, while class time is devoted to discussions, problem-solving, and interactive activities. In general, digital tools have altered classroom dynamics by enabling real-time collaboration among students, even outside the classroom. Tools like Google Docs, Microsoft Teams, and Padlet allow students to co-create documents, share ideas, and provide peer feedback in a seamless manner. This increases student interaction and collaboration, fostering a more communicative and cooperative classroom environment (Johnson & Stanne, 2000).

Also, technology enables the customization of learning experiences to meet the diverse needs of students. Through data analytics and adaptive learning technologies, instructional content can be tailored to the individual progress of each student, offering personalized paths for mastery of skills and concepts (Bishop & Verleger, 2013; Holmes, Bialik & Fadel, 2019). As it has been demonstrated by Harper and Milman (2016) one-to-one digital technologies have triggered an increase of collaborative learning, differentiated instruction and variation. One-to-one technologies were found to be used to differentiate particularly in interdisciplinary contexts and as a supplement to the curricula. On many occasions, teachers have also realized that applying digital technologies has increased motivation and engagement in their classrooms, detected during the implementation phase and does not always last (Bebell and Kay 2010; Hur & Oh 2012). In their research, Harper and Milman (2016) mentioned great variation in actual pupil achievement, and they traced some positive effects on achievement.

However, while digital technologies offer substantial benefits, they also introduce challenges, such as the digital divide (unequal access to technology), concerns about screen time, and the need for teacher professional development to effectively integrate technology into teaching. Additionally, the overuse of technology can sometimes lead to disengagement or distractions, requiring teachers to find a balance in its application (Selwyn, 2016).

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Approach to Data Collection

In our study we used the thematic analysis approach, a method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns (themes) within data” (Braun and Clarke, 2006:79) in an open-ended way. It is a fundamentally question-driven approach that depends on clearly articulated lines of inquiry to frame the scholar’s interpretation of the data (Lochmiller, 2021). Codes are considered to be, “a word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language-based or visual data” (Saldaña, 2015:4). Thematic analysis is adaptable to a wide range of research questions, data types, and theoretical frameworks. It can be applied across diverse disciplines (such as psychology, education, sociology, health studies, etc.) and is equally effective for both small-scale studies and larger, more complex research projects. As a method helps researchers identify and interpret patterns or themes that are central to the research questions. It provides rich, detailed insights into the data, making it possible to explore the meanings, experiences, and perceptions of participants. It is especially effective in understanding complex phenomena or lived experiences (Guest, MacQueen, & Namey, 2012) .

5.2 Interview Process and Participants

Participant interviews occurred in their place of work on a prearranged and mutually agreed day. Some of them were taken via phone. Interviews were semi-structured; a guide provided a loose structure within which to explore the topics of interest. The central question was: “How do you understand differentiated instruction regarding its implementation, outcomes and use of digital tools” Where appropriate, the interviewer prompted participants to expand on relevant and interesting responses.

We employed purposeful sampling, which is commonly used in qualitative research because it allows researchers to select participants who are most likely to provide rich, relevant, and diverse insights into the phenomenon being studied. This strategy ensures that the sample is directly aligned with the research objectives and the specific questions the study aims to answer. The goal of qualitative research is often to explore meaning, context, and depth rather than to generalize findings to a larger population. Purposive sampling facilitates this by prioritizing participants who can provide in-depth and varied perspectives that directly contribute to the research aims (Patton, 2002; Suri, 2011; Bernard, 2006). Therefore we selected 19 people (twelve women and seven men) working in urban school environments. They were all on permanent contracts and their working experience varied between 15-20 years. The study took place in the island of Rhodes in Greece during the school year 2023-24.

5.3 Data Analysis

After transcribing the interviews we started coding the data manually. A code is a label that describes a segment of data. These can be descriptive or interpretative, depending on the approach. In our case it was descriptive. We grouped related codes to form themes.

Themes are broader patterns in the data that capture something significant about the research question. This step often involves examining how different codes work together to form a narrative or larger idea. The next step was reviewing and refining the themes. This involved checking whether the themes accurately represent the data and whether the data within the themes form a coherent pattern. It was essential to ensure that the themes are distinct from one another and capture the key points of the data (Nowell, Norris, White & Moules, 2017). Once the themes were refined, we defined and named each theme. This was done by reviewing the data within each theme and ensuring that the theme captures the essence of what it represents (Clarke & Braun, 2013).

6. RESULTS

The analysis and the coding procedure produced four distinct themes:

(a) “Broad Conceptualization”

The majority of the participants (13/19) managed to perceive to a varied degree the main components of Differentiated Instruction (DI):

P2(woman): “DI the way I see it is a teaching approach that takes into consideration the students’ individual differences.....which means that the teachers must adapt their teaching in order to accommodate for the needs, interests and learning style of each student”

P4(woman): “DI is a combination of individualized approach, conventional teaching, and cooperative teaching which has as a compass each student’s needs and abilities. We have to discover how each student learns and give him/her the appropriate instruction

P10(man): “DI is paying attention to the learning needs of a particular student and the effort to integrate him/her in the classroom environment and make him/her feel emotionally safe.....”

P14(man): “DI is teaching methodology which focuses on students with special needs/difficulties..... The abilities of these students are taken into consideration and relevant activities are organized”

(b) “Possible outcomes”

Again most of the participants (16/19) managed to mention, to a lesser or greater extent the, contribution of the DI to the learning process:

P6(woman): “.....since emphasis is put on each students interests and strong points, then his/her participation is enhancedtakes a more energetic stance and cooperates both with his/her classmates and teacher”

P19(man): “through DI all students can get involved in the learning process and the chasm that exists among students with varying cognitive level and needs could be minimized”

(c) “Vague Implementation”

The majority of the participants didn’t mention more than a couple of instructional strategies relevant to DI. Moreover, one third of them 6/19 seem to make use of digital tools to facilitate the learning process.

P1(woman): “.....I just create flexible teams...the more advanced students don’t lose their interest, whereas the less advanced ones profit from the cooperation”

P3(man): "...my students work in small teams in order to feel more emotionally safe"

P17(woman): "...I just adapt the level of the material to the characteristics of each student or team..."

P8 (woman): "...I adapt my material to the learning needs of each student.."

P9(man): "...I use interactive board and I try to create new material with the students and not stick to the schoolbooks.... So students become more interested and get actively involved"

- P11(woman): "... I give exercises of graded difficulty to my students on a daily base.....and I use various digital tools for creating stories quizzes, like Kahoot, Nearpod, Edpuzzle, Quizizz.."

- P13(man): ".....Apart from working in small flexible teams, I also use a variety of digital tools like, Google Classroom, Kahoot, Quizizz....is a great tool for differentiated instruction. It is similar to Kahoot, but offers even more possibilities to personalize the educational process

P16(man): "...initially I try to do a basic profiling and evaluate each students needscreate flexible teams ..I adapt the content process.. Employ various instructional strategies ..like graphic organizers, differentiated homework, independent inquiry, alternative evaluation..I also use didital tools like Google Classroom , Edpuzzleand Quizizz which permits students to complete quizzes at their ownpace, which helps to differentiate according to individual needs and the time it takes each to understand the content ..."

- (d) **"Difficulties"**

Almost all of them mentioned a number of difficulties concerning the implementation of DI in the educational context they worked like: in-flexible curricula, lack of time, a lot of material in various subjects that had to be taught, lack of appropriate training, lack of digital equipment and knowledge of appropriate platforms for the production of tailor-made learning material, etc.

P7(woman): "even if we try to make a DI lesson adapted to the specific characteristics of our mixed abilities classes, this cant be applied to every single subject.... We have neither the time nor the knowledge of all instruction strategies....or digital tools....etc"

P19(man): "...in order to realized a class based on DI with would be much better if we had an one-to-one device (eg.tablet) and preferably a variety of digital tools to work with.....along with the permission to make our choices concerning the choice of the teaching material and the extend that has to be taught.....we cant teach everything in depth and still function according to the principles od DI"

- P18(woman) " ...I really don't understand how DI can work given the fact that there has to be a kind of on-going evaluation and reflection...couldn't the trainers or mendors prepare model lessons, invite them in our class to implement them an show us how all this works? ...if it works at all .."

7. DISCUSSION

Differentiation in the classroom is not just a strategy for adjusting teaching methods during a lesson; it must be integrated into every phase of the instructional process—from planning to evaluation. When we talk about differentiating content, processes, and products for students, it's essential to remember that this should be a continuous, dynamic process that

permeates the entire teaching cycle. Despite the fact that the majority of the participants perceive to various degrees the concept of differentiated instruction they seem to understand that it is a set of pedagogical principles not just guidelines and when is implemented lesson planning and evaluation cannot be excluded from the whole process and thus, apart from involving content, processes and products for pupils, this has to take into consideration planning the whole unit (lesson period) and evaluate student progress as well (van Geel et al.,2019).

Teachers often see DI as an effective tool for boosting student achievement, particularly for students who struggle in traditional classroom settings. By providing targeted support and varying the level of challenge, teachers find that students are more likely to experience success in their learning, whether through scaffolding, enrichment, or flexible grouping. Studies have shown that DI can lead to improved academic performance, especially when teachers actively monitor and adjust instruction based on formative assessments (Subban, 2006). However teachers need to consider each pupils' readiness to learn, personal interest and generic learning profile in order to be able to differentiate instruction efficiently (Tomlinson & Imbeau 2010).

Our findings, concerning implementation and the problems teachers have to deal with, seem to be consistent with the results of other researchers. Undoubtedly differentiating instruction, whether or not digital technologies are involved, is widely recognized as a difficult task. Research has highlighted several obstacles that prevent teachers from effectively implementing differentiated instruction in their teaching practices, including insufficient resources and time, personal beliefs, and a lack of training, competence, and collaboration (Brighton et al., 2005; Gudmundsdottir, Loftsgarden, & Ottestad, 2014; Bondie, Dahnke, & Zusho, 2019). Despite thorough planning, teachers often find themselves having to think quickly and make decisions on the spot throughout the day, constantly selecting from a wide range of potential responses.

According to Bondie, Dahnke, and Zusho (2019), the volume of decisions teachers must make can become overwhelming, leading them to simplify their approach by offering fewer options in their differentiated instruction. Specifically, digital technologies often intimidate teachers, and their concerns about technical failures and losing control have prevented them from fully embracing these tools, even though they recognize their value and potential for enhancing differentiated instruction (Krumsvik et al., 2013; Spiteri & Chang Rundgren, 2020).

8. Concluding Remarks

The objective of this paper was to explore how teachers perceive and understand differentiated instruction (DI) in the context of its implementation, outcomes, and the integration of digital tools within a primary school classroom. Through an analysis of the responses provided by the informants, it became clear that many teachers who are attempting or have already attempted to implement DI view it more as a set of instructional strategies or tools—something practical to guide their teaching—rather than as a holistic pedagogical philosophy or set of guiding principles. This suggests that, while teachers may acknowledge the value of DI, they often approach it in a more instrumental way, focusing on its immediate benefits rather than understanding its deeper, transformative role in shaping their teaching practices.

Moreover, several barriers to effective implementation of DI emerged from the analysis. Time constraints were highlighted as a significant challenge, with teachers often feeling that the demands of planning and managing differentiated instruction are overwhelming within the typical school schedule. The issue of insufficient resources, particularly digital tools and technologies, also stood out as a major hurdle. Teachers expressed concern over their ability to effectively integrate digital resources into their lessons, citing a lack of access to appropriate technology as a barrier to fully realizing the potential of DI.

Additionally, teachers noted the inflexibility of curricula and the constraints imposed by the prescribed subject material as another factor that limits the full adoption of DI. In many cases, teachers felt that the standardized nature of the curriculum left little room for the kind of individualized teaching that DI encourages. This tension between the prescribed curriculum and the need for flexibility in teaching was identified as an ongoing challenge that must be addressed in order to make DI more feasible and effective.

Finally, the paper emphasizes the need for extensive teacher training and professional development if DI is to be applied successfully in the classroom. Teachers must be provided with not only the knowledge and skills to implement DI, but also opportunities for ongoing reflection on their practices. Such training should focus not just on the "how" of differentiation, but also on the "why," helping educators to view DI as a comprehensive pedagogical approach rather than just a set of techniques. Continuous professional reflection and development are crucial for ensuring that DI becomes a meaningful and sustainable practice in schools.

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ADHD Lived Experience and how it has informed my practice in Higher Education

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In 2021, when embarking on her own Professional Doctorate, Jo Strang came to the self-realisation that she had an ADHD brain and therefore needed different considerations and approaches as a student. Jo works as a Health and Social Care Lecturer at the Open University, involved in online learning design and delivery of modules. On publishing her personal journey as a student on the PhD Place webpage, she realised the positive impact of adults sharing their late diagnoses and what it can mean as a learner. In this presentation Jo will share what her personal learning and reflections have meant for how she approaches learning design.

Keyword: adhd, neurodiversity, higher education, online learning, learning design, time management.

1. Introduction

In 2021 I began my Professional Doctorate, whilst also working fulltime for the Open University, UK. Although initially excited by the new venture, I quickly found myself overwhelmed by the requirement to study again and distracted, I began to scroll through Facebook posts. It was October, ADHD Awareness month, and after years of being referred to as 'clever but absent-minded', being exceptionally untidy and regularly arriving late, suddenly numerous pennies began to drop as I saw myself reflected in a variety of memes and posts about ADHD. The full story of my realisations and early journey in making sense of this can be found here, [Realising I Have ADHD During My PhD: A Hidden Battle - The PhD Place](#).

In sharing my experiences, I realised the power of being open and honest about some of my struggles in the way that I approach learning. By speaking out, it allowed other people to acknowledge they learned slightly differently to the perceived norm of how we plan, prepare, and execute our studies in Higher Education. I became motivated to try and understand my own needs better and, as a designer of online learning, to create learning opportunities that might be more inclusive and reduce challenges for other ADHD learners.

It must be noted that I am just one person who identifies as having an ADHD brain and when you have met one person with ADHD... you have met one person with ADHD! I share my self-reflections here, in the hopes that the perspective of a neurodivergent student might encourage others working in Higher Education to consider alternative and/or additional approaches to study skills and tutor support to create a more inclusive learning environment.

This paper highlights three specific personal struggles; the challenge of time, the medley of 'distraction, procrastination and hyperfocus' and the difficulties with reading online. My reflections are structured in such a way that they present my challenge, my own solutions to date and my musings for how Higher Education colleagues might think differently, to better support ADHD learners who struggle with similar issues to myself.

2. The challenge of time

It is important to reiterate that everyone is different. It is unlikely that you would walk into a room and spot that I had ADHD, making the hidden struggles sometimes even harder, because the need for support is less obvious. I can be lively and move around a lot, but mostly the extreme busyness remains in my head and the struggles I face are when I am at home and on my own trying to navigate the demands of being a student.

I have a very difficult relationship with time making judging the amount of time something might take or planning my work in time to meet a deadline extraordinarily difficult. I imagine that might be difficult for others to understand. I have a bright mind and yes, I do understand how time works and I can read a watch and a calendar! However, unless a deadline is imminent, I really struggle to see it and prepare for it. This absolutely does not mean I don't care – it means exactly the opposite. From the moment I know I have a deadline to work towards, I am on a heightened alert that I might not meet it, could forget it or won't have done enough by the time that the deadline comes around. It leads to high levels of stress in the run-up to handing work in and ongoing negative self-talk regarding how this always happens, and I don't seem to improve with this, ever.

The results over the years have been underperformance due to the misjudgement of time. Lost marks for poor referencing, comments like 'that's not a conclusion', even being awarded a 2:1 degree instead of a first-class degree because 'you needed just a bit more time on your research project', all as a result of this challenge of time. Because I am often in a heightened state of stress by the time it comes to submitting, I can also be the student where something goes wrong at the time of submission – I upload the wrong version (admin, labelling and saving documents are a further challenge), hit the wrong button or panic and then an issue occurs just ahead of a deadline meaning my work might be submitted just moments late, but could then be subject to a penalty. No one would like it more than me if I could manage time better! But I have had to concede that time will always feel tricky and therefore I need help to manage things.

Some of my own solutions are as follows:

Pretend, earlier deadlines. I agree these with my supervisors a couple of weeks before my actual deadline for submission. I can't visualise a 'complete draft' (in my head it is either done or not done) so I send in 'everything I have done so far' which is now usually nearly the whole piece of work. It allows me to get some feedback and check I am on track (another challenge being that I can creatively interpret guidance, rather than complete the task as set) and still gives me time ahead of the actual deadline. I will still work right up to the deadline, but by that point I have a lot already written so it becomes more doable. I did the same thing with this presentation. I offered to deliver a presentation in September and put time aside to write the presentation on the morning, ahead of presenting in the afternoon. By doing so, it gave me a solid draft to work from, ahead of the conference in October 2024.

Embracing my 'all or nothing' approach. Reluctantly, I have accepted this is how I work. I can spend weeks thinking about topics in my head but do very little reading and absolutely no writing. I now acknowledge that this is still hours spent learning and try not to give myself a hard time about 'not studying enough'. I am unlikely to start writing until nearer a deadline and when I do it will be intensive. I now try to work out how I can plan for intensive periods of study, which often mean writing through the night. I then try to plan quiet days after

a deadline so that I can catch-up on the sleep that I have missed. I am moving away from joking about being 'lastminute.com' and trying to be more positive that this is just the way that I learn and study. The difficulty is that a large part of study skills advice seems to suggest a planned, consistent, and linear approach to study which logically does make sense. Unless of course you can't learn and plan in that way. Too easily I can feel like a failure because timers, reminders, planners, and calendars are not solutions that work for me. I do need visuals, but they need to be obvious so a large wallchart with colours is more likely to be effective than an electronic diary that I will only see when I log-on. There is not space here to explain the challenges of memory recall and how easy it is for me to forget or mis-remember a deadline, but this is a further challenge for students with ADHD.

My questions to colleagues in Higher Education are as follows. Given the realities of what I have described above,

- Do deadlines need to be used as punitive?
- How can we help some students to meet deadlines?
- How can we show empathy and support to students who find time tricky?
- How can we normalise the diverse way in which humans learn?

As much as I find it hard, I need structure in my life and in my studies, so I appreciate clear deadlines – I am not advocating for the removal of these! Without a structured approach I would not be in the final year of my Professional Doctorate! However, I have always seen getting work in on time as a professional requirement that students ought to be able to learn to achieve. (I am a social worker by background and as educators we would often give the example of 'court won't wait for a report, so our students need to learn to meet deadlines'). Whilst that is true, there is usually a team of people helping you to meet a deadline in practice – I write lengthy assessments of foster carers and there are many earlier deadlines to ensure that a report is well-written and complete before the final deadline. So, if we know some students need help with timing and deadlines, how can we help them, rather than just punishing them with a zero score because they were a few minutes late, or refusing to offer a short extension when they were brave enough to admit they needed more time?

Empathy and support for those students who do experience challenges around time, for many different reasons, would make a big difference. They know that some tutors will judge them for not planning better, leaving things too late, asking for an extension at the last minute and that knowing can create internalised negative self-talk that can impinge their self-belief and self-confidence as a student. Perhaps I am more generous with extensions during a module than others because of my own experiences. I work within the requirements of my university but from the outset I show empathy to the busy lives all students are juggling,

and I now share my experiences as a learner to show anyone who learns in a similar way to me, that there is personal experience and understanding within the staff team.

One way of normalising diverse experiences of learning is for staff with different approaches to learning to be visible within the modules. It isn't easy because there is vulnerability in sharing struggles, but for me, if it helps just a few students to recognise they can learn different ways to manage time and that it is Ok to ask for help, it seems worthwhile. Encouraging discussion around the purpose of deadlines and how we use them to help students stay on track with the content they are learning about, rather than penalise them for failing to manage time also seems an important starting point. More varied ways to study skills will hopefully follow as we understand more about how challenges of time, linked to the traits of ADHD, can impact studying in Higher Education.

3. The medley of distraction, procrastination and hyperfocus

Linked to the above discussion of time, 'traditional' time management is difficult. For all the planning in the world, I cannot be confident that I will be focused on study and productive in the way that I hoped, at the time that I have created space in my diary. Whilst I benefit from structure, I struggle with both structure and routine. Meaning that nothing is ever uniform, consistent, or even. If the deadline for work is too far into the distance, I can be easily distracted by other tasks at home or work, always believing that there is time to get those done first. I have, in the past, wasted lots of time procrastinating on other things and not getting my studies done as planned. This leads to an experience that is close to self-loathing because when there is then not sufficient time to do a good enough job on the piece of work I know I am capable of, it further fuels negative self-talk about how I ought to have planned better and how I have now let myself down.

Hyperfocus is a wonderful state to be in – complete and utter engrossment in the subject area, writing and reading. Yet I can't know when this might come, I can't 'turn on the switch' and it has negatives (in the sense that everything else is forgotten and can lead to burnt toast or meals, forgetting to even eat or not remembering to collect one of my children). Consequently, unconsciously sometimes avoidance of hyperfocus creeps in, even though it is a very helpful state for studying. Hyperfocus for me, is also more likely to occur once the deadline is imminent. It is perhaps successful because of the hours spent thinking in my head, such that I have rehearsed many times over what I will say before I sit down to finally start writing.

Some of my own solutions to this tricky and unpredictable landscape to navigate have been as follows:

Learning to pivot. When I get caught in procrastination and distraction I have learned that doesn't really help to try and push on through. Instead, I try to have a list of different tasks that I could select from. So, if I can't focus on reading, I might be able to do the meticulous task of tidying up my references. Or if I am not able to read, I might try the internet for a short video that is about the topic I am studying. This links to the realisation

that I need *variety and choice* in my studies. Different locations can make a difference - a library that is very quiet, a coffee shop that has lots of bustle, but I go into hyperfocus, or somewhere new that is a change of scene – by the seaside or out in the countryside. It is worth a little extra thought and travel-time regarding what location might match where my head is at if, ultimately, I can then settle into studying. I now try to *plan for the likely trajectory* of the way that I personally study and *trust the process and my chaos*. I know to an outsider it looks extremely disorganised and at times it really is! Somehow, I always get there, and I produce good quality work. Increasingly I am allowing the positive feedback to give me confidence in my achievements and my ways of working. I can still wobble when I see other students who have lengthy drafts and who I know have put in more hours than me on reading and writing. However, a learning support member of staff also encouraged me to embrace and appreciate my ability to skim read and find the key information I need as a positive study skill. Prior to that discussion I had tended to think of my approach as cheating or taking shortcuts, because I only read minimal text to gain understanding of a topic and once I have grasped it, I move onto the next thing.

As a learning designer there has been tension between what I have learned about myself and now acknowledge as my ‘norm’ for learning and how I am designing learning for others. I am committed to creating logical and well-scaffolded learning journeys for other students, but what does that mean if the carefully crafted linear journey I have created, is never going to be followed by students like me? I am like a Tigger or a magpie. If something seems boring or not interesting at that moment in time, I probably won’t do it. I would be more likely to look right the way through a module and pick out what seems interesting, rather than follow it step-by-step. I also pick things up quickly and once I have understood something I don’t really enjoy repeating content to consolidate the learning, something that as learning designer I would probably incorporate into my learning design. This has led me to ponder alternative approaches to module design,

- Does online learning have to be linear, or could there be alternative routes to the same destination?
- Can variety and choice of *how* students receive the information and *how* students demonstrate their learning become the norm?

I recognise this could sound controversial, but could we design different routes through a module, so that we highlight different types of activity for different learners? Or perhaps it is possible to pay more attention to the wording of guidance. Could we avoid saying ‘this activity *should* take 10 minutes’ because it will take some students longer and some students less time. Or could we acknowledge that although learning has been designed in a specific order to help students, it is also OK for some students to choose a different sequence through the module, depending on their own interests and approaches? Key theory and content could be highlighted as a ‘must read’ to ensure essential topics are not missed.

Finally, although there is movement towards authentic assessment and AI is also driving discussion forward, currently much of the online content and the assessment tasks rely on reading and writing. Is it possible to offer content in both written and audio/visual formats, thus meeting the needs of more learners? Is it possible to offer students the choice to either submit a written assignment or a recorded PowerPoint presentation for the same assessment task? I don't have answers, but as noted, these are questions I have pondered.

4. The challenge of reading online

It is this final point that has been particularly difficult to acknowledge and accept. In recent years I have been an advocate for embracing new technology to enhance learning. However, I had not realised quite how difficult I find it to remain focused when reading information online. I am not dyslexic and had not realised that I too could be helped by changing the background colour, such that my eyes and brain do not become lost in a 'sea of black and white text'. I can compute information better when there are visual pictures and short blocks of writing, so mostly I can manage the activities presented on a VLE. However, lengthy written guidance about a module or an assessment task or a journal article are difficult for me to retain focus online. I have more chance of focus if I print the document and now, still somewhat reluctantly, I will download and print key documents. I am also finding that writing with a pen, rather than just typing, helps me formulate my thoughts and ideas.

It is possibly the combination of lack of focus and poor memory that means that I don't or won't read dense module guidance. I need a brief 'to the point' overview that I can return to several times and make sense of the information from one look, on one page. Associated with this has been a mix of difficult emotions – feeling guilty for not taking the time to read what others have created to help me, feeling ashamed that I can't access the information online and embarrassed to admit that I can't read online easily, which seems like such a big omission as a student signed up for an online degree course. This unhelpful negative self-talk can take its toll and it is only in speaking out honestly that I am beginning to find ways forward in self-kindness and self-acceptance.

In summary the solutions I have found for myself thus far are as follows:

- I print key documents and use a highlighter. I will print drafts of my work and use scissors and tape to re-order, before returning to the screen to make the changes.
- I go to the local university library and find real books to scan through.
- I use the search function on ebooks to go direct to keywords that I am looking for, rather than reading full texts or chapters. When I find something really of interest and relevant, then I will read that section.
- I am a work in progress, but becoming more honest, kinder and accepting of who I am and how I learn.

Again, I am not advocating to get rid of online learning! It provides accessibility for so many learners. Particularly for students who are neurodivergent it can offer different opportunities that perhaps have not been possible or successful in other experiences of education. It is therefore, in my mind, about thinking about inclusive practice to better support some students if, like me, reading online presents some barriers. My questions are as follows;

- Could suggestions be made to students regarding what to print?
- Could alternative study skill sessions be developed for different learners?
- Could there be more videos – demos of the online learning environment and/or recorded PowerPoints with the presenter speaking?
- Could there be more opportunities for spoken interaction between tutors and students, to check information has been correctly understood?
- Could the amount of lengthy written instruction be significantly reduced so that it is clear and straightforward? Less is sometimes more.

5. Conclusions

As noted, I am just one person, and these are personal reflections of my experiences as a student and how my brain has begun to muse about possibilities of how we might better support the needs of students who learn in similar ways to me. The Professional Doctorate route means I have regular online supervision with my tutors which is incredibly supportive and provides an excellent learning space for me. Yet too often students on larger undergraduate courses may not have this experience. Instead, they are often 'referred back to the written guidance' which they scabble around with, wondering if they have interpreted it correctly. I have found the amount of solo reading required on a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) hard going and I would have preferred more opportunities to discuss ideas in breakout rooms, watch videos and have more interaction with others during my learning journey. The poem below depicts my feeling of being a learner who needs interaction, enrolled in an online course that presents several challenges to me as a learner. I will leave you with the Lost Juggling Clown... and thank you for allowing me to bring lived experience and a student perspective to this important Higher Education conference about how the future of online learning might develop in the coming years.

The Lost Juggling Clown

by Jo Strang

I am a juggler, bright as can be,

Juggling balls for all to see!

A smile on my face, a glint in my eye

'Chuck me another', you hear me cry!

Excitement of learning, new ventures afoot

But oops...

WHAT ON EARTH?!

Something is caput...

I stumble, I turn, I blink and I wonder,

The colour is gone and I realise my blunder.

This excitable clown with ideas galore

Has stumbled on set of times long before.

I watch from the wings and observe from afar.

This black and white movie footage seems so bizarre.

The colour has drained, the silence is deafening

Fixated I try to focus and tune-in.

The actors are moving, they have stories to tell,

I try to interpret but find that I dwell...

Have I interpreted the miming as meant?

Have I decoded the info with correct intent?

I blink and I gaze as the movie flickers on.

But the effort is real and my patience is gone.

I **so** want to know that I **have** understood

But monochrome silence is really not good.

I have an idea! I will tip-toe on set!

With a wave and a smile and see what I get!

I will ask them to talk, to explain what they mean,

And gratefully confirm that their movie has been seen.

But still no one greets me. They smile but they turn.

They scribble a note from which I must learn.

The guidance is all there, the film just needs watched.

My request for a dialogue, politely is quashed.

Dejected I wander back home to my screen.

Thinking and thinking what all this must mean.

It is 2024 and I can't be alone?

Or is it that really, I just should have known?

The majestic history of written text lives on.

It is heralded and worshipped, our voices forgone.

Neatly presented in careful typeset,

A structure, an order that a juggler could upset.

But language is rich, it is fluid and flamboyant.

It can shout, it can swirl it can break with the norm.

And now we have mics, we have webcams and more

So really we all know that so much more is in store.

Arial size 12 will of course live on

But just maybe a light on that set could be shon.

Us jugglers need sound, we need inter-action!

A simple request for a minor adaption.

As a juggler to standstill for me is a chore,

And to read every line my retention is poor.

Five minutes of your time can make so much difference,

A video recording or short chat my preference.

And please let me cartwheel and dance and explore,

The ideas that fill my head with such furore.

Yes I can write them uniformly in a row,

But I think you would learn if I put on a show!

So let's embrace choice and reflect on what works,

Accept that us jugglers have a few quirks.

Communication is key, on that we all agree

But for some, dense written guidance is no guarantee.

6. References

Strang, J. (2024) *Realising I have ADHD during my PhD; a hidden battle*. Accessed at: <https://thephdplace.com/realising-i-have-adhd-during-my-phd-a-hidden-battle/>

STEM decolonisation in practice

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Abstract

Decolonisation challenges the Eurocentric dominance of what and how we teach and demands individuals consider their own world view and find strength to challenge and create a reimagined curriculum; a call to social justice (Costa *et al.*, 2023). As decolonising work is set to question and ultimately disrupt what we know to be true, then we need to start that transformation now; we need to be thinking differently about ‘facts’ (de Santos, 2014) and this includes all discipline areas including Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths (STEM).

One initial challenge is the lack of singular definition of what does it mean to decolonise a university or a curriculum, with sector efforts ordinarily emphasising the marginalised perspective and challenging existing power dynamics within the umbrella of equality, diversity, and inclusion activity. Yet decolonising can be argued to be more than this and as such it is not a simple task, as it requires different approaches to rethink and reframe knowledge creation. Efforts are underway in some UK universities, but these are criticised for being ‘piecemeal’ with only 20% claiming moves to decolonise (Mason, 2022), or even superficial, with Tuck and Yang (2012) regarding decolonising discourse as another ‘form of settler appropriation’.

This project acknowledges that there is still confusion on what decolonising academia means and more importantly what it practically implies, both at university level and within subject disciplines and even more so within STEM. It is Ali (2016) who asked, “does computing need to be decolonised?” and some Computing undergraduate students such as those at the Open University suggest that decolonising is irrelevant as there is “nothing to be decolonised” (Tompkins *et al.*, 2024). Yet without change we continue to embed the legacy of colonialism. But this is not the only option and as Battiste (2013: 175) suggests; “education can be liberating, or it can domesticate and maintain domination” and this is where our research is positioned as we help inform curriculum transformation within our discipline area.

The aim of this research is therefore to showcase a comprehensive audit of current STEM decolonisation activity within UK Higher Education Institutions (HEI’s). This data was collected through an extensive desk top survey of over 40 public facing HEI websites. The audit considered decolonising activity at both Russell Group and Athena Swan HEI’s and following thematic analysis identified eight emerging groups or themes of decolonising activity within STEM. This paper provides an overview of those themes by illustrating examples across the sector so that educators can learn from others how to adapt their own teaching and learning if they wish to decolonise their STEM curriculum.

Keywords: decolonising, STEM, computing, curriculum, transformation

1.0 Introduction

Decolonisation challenges the Eurocentric dominance of what and how we teach and demands individuals consider their own world view and in doing so find strength to challenge and create a reimagined curriculum; a call to social justice (Costa *et al.*, 2023). In recognising that today’s education institutions continue to uphold ideologies and systems which marginalise alternative wisdom and perspectives, the purpose of decolonising could be argued as action that seeks to redress these injustices to ensure meaningful change. By framing this change through a decolonised curriculum there is the opportunity to challenge and to interrupt the ways of knowing that have dominated education for centuries. Yet activity in the decolonising space is at best sporadic or ‘piecemeal’ as

only 20% of UK Universities claim moves to decolonise themselves or their curriculum (Mason, 2022). Yet even these efforts tend to be situated in the arts and social science, whilst STEM and explicitly the discipline of computing are less well represented. However STEM is not immune to the influence of colonialism and this in turn has fed into the curriculum and so also needs to move to a more inclusive and welcoming space for diverse voices and alternative ways of knowing. But why is computing and less so STEM so challenged by this way of thinking. Is it because as Professor Melken said 'people speak about decolonisation, but few people know what it is' (Vanzie, 2023). Or is it because there is still the belief that science, and we include computing in this discipline, is built on consensus of established norms and this continues to uphold a common belief that scientific knowledge is objective. Regardless of what view you take STEM needs to be decolonised and this paper will help inform that curriculum transformation.

This project is therefore attempting to map or chart the terrain of decolonising activity within the discipline of computing so as to identify the HE sector approach to knowledge disruption in STEM. There is evidence of sector transformation through university wide initiatives to decolonise the curriculum, but there is a noticeable gap in efforts to undertake decolonising of computing. In an effort to encourage and support computer science educators we have undertaken an extensive audit of existing STEM decolonising activity within the Higher Education sector looking at over 40 HEI's external websites. The identified activities have undergone thematic analysis leading to eight broad sets of categories. These examples of decolonising activity showcase that decolonising is possible and that there are many different approaches, which in turn reflect that there is no one, or right way, instead there are many ways to decolonise the STEM curriculum, including the field of computing. These initial findings are the preliminary outputs prior to the next stage of case study production and a decolonising STEM guide.

1.2 What does decolonising mean?

Decolonising work is often framed through questioning and ultimately disrupting what we know to be true, a transformation that requires thinking differently about 'facts' (de Santos, 2014). This way of understanding the world requires a new way of thinking by dismantling the principles of what and how we teach so to ignite curriculum transformation through new knowledge production that is culturally sensitive and representative. Situating decolonisation within curriculum transformation is according to Narang, (nd) to re-think, to re-frame and to re-construct and some HEI's have made impressive gains, noticeably SOAS, University of London, who produced in 2018 one of the first open source decolonising toolkit for educators.

Enslin and Hedge (2023) acknowledge the limitations in curriculum transformation as 'mere tinkering at the edges' unless there is a cultural and material shift in the purpose of education. Yet scholars have been critically interrogating knowledge production in the humanities and social sciences for over half a century, as can be seen in Sanchez's writings (2018) who draws on Orientalism in 1978 through to Foucault's power and knowledge entanglement (2008). Indeed, there are many campaigns to decolonise the University and/or the curriculum. But these decolonising claims are not without criticism. One concern is that these actions are tokenistic, due to checklists or *how to* guides; certainly, our findings show this type of resource is one of the most likely outputs from decolonising work within the sector. Stronger criticism comes from Tuck & Yang (2012) who protest the easy adoption of decolonising discourse as another 'form of settler appropriation'.

The term decolonising is itself without a consensus of meaning and can have many interpretations as there is no simple definition. Gorski (2008) refers to a change in consciousness, which suggests the starting point is a personal reflection. As researchers we have reflected on (Merriam *et al.*, 2001) insider/outsider power dynamics and our own positionality. Further supported by Hanesworth (2015)

who suggests it is imperative that those involved in curriculum development (academic or otherwise) consider ‘our own identities, biases and backgrounds’ in the creation of curricula and teaching experiences in order to develop our understanding of how these impact on student learning experiences and how we should adapt our teaching appropriately. But decolonising is complex and requires consideration of more than just self but also the political landscape of colonial plunder, as Moncrieffe *et al* (2019) summarise it is also about ‘mitigating injustices through the curriculum’.

1.3 Does computing need to be decolonised?

It is Ali (2016) who asked, “does computing need to be decolonised?” and some undergraduate students such as those at the Open University suggest that decolonising is irrelevant as there is “nothing to be decolonised” (Tompkins *et al*, 2024). Yet decolonising the curriculum should be one of the most important conversations in universities today as HE in the West is built upon the power and privilege of the dominant white and continues to be at the expense of those on peripheral. Universities were founded on money from colonial plunder, and one cannot ignore the Rhodes Must Fall movement first in the University of Cape Town, South Africa, and then the University of Oxford, UK, where students demanded the removal of the Cecil Rhodes a white supremacist. Empire and whiteness are therefore multifaceted and intertwined, but without change we continue to embed the legacy of colonialism. Battiste (2013: 175) suggests; “education can be liberating, or it can domesticate and maintain domination” and this is where our research is situated as all those involved in education have a role to play in both dismantling dominant sources of power and creating space for non-dominant forms of knowledge.

2.0 Methodology

The initial project focus was a desk top based audit to identify decolonising activity within the discipline of Computing, at the 24 UK Russell Group universities (Russell Group, n.d). Following a Works in Progress peer review at the UKICER conference held at Swansea University in September 2023, the scope was expanded to include Universities who were Athena Swan award holders (Advance HE, 2020). The full list of audited HEI’s can be found in Appendix A.

Using an unstructured exploratory approach though key word search (decolonising and computing) at a university of our choice, the three project team members conducted individual research. This led to differences in how we navigated external websites and as to what data we felt met the criteria of decolonising within computing. The subsequent production and use of standardised template introduced consistency and facilitated the documentation of findings of potential interest outside of the search criteria to be captured. The template was tested on another three HEI’s, refined and then adopted for the remainder of the desk top audit.

At this preliminary stage of the audit, we sensed that either Universities could be decolonising computing but are not making these activities public on their web pages or that they are not decolonising computing, but that there is evidence of decolonising activity within the broader STEM field. Given that there was so little activity linked explicitly to computing, the project scope again increased so that the search included STEM on the premise that computing is part of Technology.

Recognising also that decolonising work is often in collaboration with students, the project lead decided to put into practice this approach via the recruitment of three student researchers who each were paid for 20 hours of work over a three-month period.

2.1 Student Researcher role

Each student researcher (SR) was given a pre interview task to familiarise themselves with the nature of the desk based task. Following appointment, a team briefing session explained the task and nature of the audit using a completed exemplar to illustrate the standard required and how to navigate the HEI external website through use of key word search and then following links. The HEI’s were subsequently allocated randomly, and each SR was responsible for auditing 12 HEI’s between the period October to December 2023. The researchers were encouraged to focus on decolonising activities firstly within the discipline of computing and then more widely within the context of STEM. There was a limited range of key words utilised including: decolonising, computing, STEM, and expanded to include inclusive. Individual SR’s were supported by a dedicated project team member via regular check in meetings. The SR’s were also encouraged to regularly meet together to share their approaches and findings and each produced a mini report summarising their outputs. A final all project team meeting was also held.

3.0 Findings

The lack of explicit evidence of decolonising computing has not limited the findings of this project as the scope widened to consider the wider STEM discipline where there is widespread decolonising activities underway. The audit has uncovered that these decolonising efforts are often student led with external facing websites illustrating a range of decolonising activity through multimedia podcasts and videos. HEI are keen to share examples of self-developed toolkits and guides as a tool to encourage educators to start the decolonising journey. When there are operational initiatives, these appear to come from the ground up, with the first step the setting up of a working group, followed by workshops and then a project to produce a resource such as a *how to guide*. Sadly, far too often these initiative seems to then fade away.

The following section discusses the eight themed activities discovered, with examples to illustrate the practice within the sector. The URL’s have also been included and at the time of writing were all active. As preliminary findings they do not claim to be the only or indeed the best examples of decolonising activities within STEM, but they go some way to illustrate what the project set out to do, which was to map or chart the terrain of the decolonising practice within STEM within the UK Higher Education sector.

3.1 Collaboration

When there is a university wide decolonisation policy this is often linked to educator working groups both within and across the STEM disciplines and with other disciplines noticeably in the social sciences. There are also many student-staff working groups as they were found to be a highly popular approach to decolonising activity. There was also evidence of a broad range of collaboration with internal professional services such as faculties joining up with library colleagues. There was also external collaboration with public bodies such as museums with projects such as archive reviews. There is also joined up decolonising efforts between UK universities and with professional computer associations.

Table 1: Collaboration

Topic	Who is involved	URL
Exploring language used in the development and sharing of knowledge in education	London School of Tropical Medicine Decolonising Education Working Group	https://www.lstmed.ac.uk/news-events/blogs/expression-of-interest-decolonising-language-at-lstm

	Education Department and students, chaired by Director of Studies for MSc Global Health and co-chair of BAME network	
Working to inspire change in the science education community	University of Bristol, Kingston, Keele, Exeter, Cambridge, Wolverhampton and Leeds The DSC Working Group	https://inclusive-and-anti-colonial-practice.wp.st-andrews.ac.uk/files/2022/04/Decolonising-the-science-curriculum-working-to-inspire-change-in-the-science-education-community.pdf
Informatics working group	University of Edinburgh Led by EDI Director	https://informatics.ed.ac.uk/about/work-with-us/equality-diversity-inclusion/decolonising-the-curriculum
Working Group e.g. case studies, workshops, guidance by discipline area, forum, monitoring of impact	Aston University staff and students	https://www.aston.ac.uk/about/mission/inclusive-aston/decolonising-curriculum-aston-university

Collaboration is not limited to within the UK HE as a large body of progressive work including a First Nations engineering studio at The Australian National University and a paper on indigenous protocols for AI evidenced collaboration beyond the UK. The University of Edinburgh also has a collaboration with universities in Spain and Belgium and are widely publishing practical advice as well as debate. The use of ‘yarning circles’ at Curtin University in Western Australia is promoting conversation in the decolonial space and confirms that there is decolonising practice worldwide extending beyond Europe to Africa and Oceania.

3.2 Research/Scholarship

The audit identified that those who are decolonising are also writing about their efforts or encouraging others to start the curriculum transformation through publishing their views on the reasons to start this change. For example at the University of Bristol, Dr Eichhorn (2019) wrote ‘How the West was Won: A Deconstruction of Politicised Colonial Engineering’ but from a lens that categorises computing as engineering. Similarly, there is a focus by Mitra *et al* (2023) from Edinburgh University on engineering in relation to how modern technology companies hold extreme power and wealth and that we as educators have responsibility to ‘decolonise engineering projects’ if we are to disrupt the ongoing influence of colonialism. Other more general articles of interest which are applicable to STEM include Schucan and Pitman (2019) who highlight the tendency for existing reading lists to only represent the white male voice and argue for review in order to ‘deconstruct disciplinary boundaries’. Whilst in the field of medicine we found scholarship outputs being used to promote decolonising frameworks and a self-assessment tool to support science educators start curriculum transformation (Mbaki *et al*, 2021).

3.3 Resource Curation

HEI's have produced web pages, blogs, podcasts, videos, guides and toolkits on decolonising the curriculum, but rarely a resource for only computing, although there is such activity at the OU. Encouragingly there is also evidence of new activities building on earlier actions. For example, the digitisation of archives at Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine was the theme for the 2024 Black History Month. The event included a panel discussion with external invited guests. Disseminating ongoing decolonising work within events that are designed to give visibility to those who are creating change is a fresh reminder of why this work is so important.

Table 2: Resource Curation

Format	Resource Purpose	Curated by	URL
Digitisation of archives	To illustrate unheralded Black African and Minority Ethnic scientific researchers	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (LSMT)	https://archive.lstmed.ac.uk/
Framework	Actions to make science curriculum more inclusive and relevant to all students	Times Higher Education with University of Bristol	https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/framework-decolonising-and-diversifying-science-curricula
Web page	Decolonising Medicine, part one: taking the first steps Part two: empowering students Part three: uncovering the full picture with silenced voices and histories	Times Higher Education with University of Exeter	https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/decolonising-medicine-part-one-taking-first-steps
Podcast via YouTube video	Decolonising and diversifying the Biomedical Science Curriculum	St George's London	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4qAQvUotaBs
Podcast via YouTube video	Decolonising STEM guide, student podcast on what decolonising science means to them	University of Leeds	https://studenteddev.leeds.ac.uk/developing-practice/decolonising-how-to-guides/decolonising-the-science-curriculum/
Toolkit	For educators, professional and research staff to help apply a decolonial lens	DeMontfort University, Leicester	https://www.dmu.ac.uk/community/decolonising/toolkit.aspx
Case Studies	Discipline specific case studies to cover workshops, tips to start decolonising,	University of Bristol	https://bilt.online/decolonisation/

	interviews, practical methods and a reading group		
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3.4 Events

HEI's are organising a variety of events which tend to be talks and discussions via panels, discussions, workshops, roundtables and lectures. The events vary in that they can be internal to the University or include invited external speakers or open to all. Events are a mix of being delivered online, in person or hybrid. Some events require tickets, others do not. One example at University of Glasgow (2023) within the College of Science & Engineering was to run two online workshops with the aim to bring together potential external voices to develop a stronger community of practice network. The facilitators used a Padlet to capture participant input and have since shared the recordings. Many events seem to focus on empowering those who attend with the tools to start curriculum transformation through challenging Eurocentricity and exploring practice beyond the status quo.

Table 3: Events

Event Type	Event Name	Hosted by	URL
Keynote Lecture	'Decolonising Mathematics, a case for their aestheticising'	Centre for Research in Education in STEM, Kings College London	https://www.kcl.ac.uk/decolonising-mathematics-a-case-for-their-aestheticising
Discussion	Let's Talk About: Decolonising Knowledge in Practice	Academy of Inclusivity and the Library, University of Swansea	https://events.swansea.ac.uk/talk/index/2379/
Competition	Ethical Hackathon	University of Cambridge as part of Unbias project hosted at University of Nottingham	https://www.cs.ox.ac.uk/news/1495-full.html

3.5 Awards

There was no specific award identified that celebrated decolonising activity within computing or STEM. Where there was celebration, this seemed to blend in with other EDI initiatives within the institution for example at Bristol University, a PhD chemistry student was awarded the STEM Learning Award (2022) for setting up the Creative Tuition Collective within the local community to improve inclusion and diversity within STEM. Although not yet in recognition of STEM module level efforts, Kent University celebrate course content where a diverse range of resources offer an inclusive learning experience by issuing a Diversity Mark. As this is a collaborative programme run with student specialists who work with the convenors, our SR's felt that this was an initiative that could and should be expanded to include STEM modules and so is worth a highlight because of its focus on evidence and so is not just another tokenistic toolkit.

3.6 Hub/physical space

This focus of this theme is on the physical or online presence of a dedicated hub or studio, such as a computing education research centre or a centre for academic inclusion in the STEM curriculum. Again difficult to pinpoint to decolonising Computing or even more widely within STEM, but there is evidence at the University level of creating such spaces. For example in an aim to transform education the University of Exeter (nd) have established an Education Incubator initiative under the direction of ‘to be fearless ...to reimagine education and the possibilities it can realise’. This includes a programme of activity to decolonise the curriculum with a range of student led projects relating to EDI within the University and beyond. Connected to this incubator there is a blog post on ‘Decolonising STEM – what is this all about?’ reviewing a project sharing decolonising ideas in a sandpit of academics and professional service staff, subsequently extended to student interns which culminated in a mini symposium targeted specifically to STEM colleagues. This bringing together of staff and students is replicated at the University of Durham (2024), by way of a Hub who are leading a Decolonise Durham Campaign to think critically about education and the university. Students including those in science, are represented giving their personal views on their role as decolonising agents of change.

3.7 Curriculum development

In recognising the need to share and nature decolonial teaching and research methods both across the University and within discipline areas, it is no surprise that curriculum development was a constant theme in all the activities that involve decolonisation. Therefore although there are examples to draw upon, one HEI that stood out is Nottingham Trent University. Navigating through the Library home, to a page called **Supporting Curricula Development**, there is an explainer of ‘what is meant by a decolonized education’ from the perspective of an academic from University of Cape Town in South Africa. Here you will find discipline specific resource lists (although you need to be a staff/student member to access). There are also a set of critical questions for discipline areas to consider and there are links to external resources, such as podcasts to look at decolonising in the sector. A similar whole university approach to decolonising is to be found at Aston University (nd), which through their working party have established a ‘process of revising the principles of curriculum design, content and delivery, toward a decolonised teaching and learning system’.

Table 4: Curriculum Development

Format	Topic	Audience	URL
Lecture (Live)	Inclusive content: Decolonising the curriculum	Lecture to all first year Biology students at University of St Andrews	https://inclusive-and-anti-colonial-practice.wp.st-andrews.ac.uk/2022/02/23/inclusive-content-decolonising-the-curriculum-lecture-school-of-biology/
1) Outreach activity 2) Manikins in different skin tones 3) Book - mind the gap handbook of clinical	Widening representation in the curricula	School of Medicine, University of St Andrews	https://inclusive-and-anti-colonial-practice.wp.st-andrews.ac.uk/2022/02/23/inclusive-

signs in Black and Brown skin			content-mind-the-gap-school-of-medicine/
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3.8 Strategy

Decolonising is a feature of many HEI’s strategic plans and can be found referenced in Annual EDI reports, Race Equality Charter (REC) taskforce aims, Access and Participation Plans and so forth. Often these plans discuss the institutional aim to reduce the awarding gap and to support specific groups of students e.g. from Ethnic minority groups, students with disabilities or from low social economic backgrounds. For example, at the University of Bath there is a bottom-up approach as they are working in partnership with their student bodies on implementing an inclusive curriculum. Part of this approach is to facilitate the establishment of ‘Decolonising curricula’ student groups in Engineering, Science and Humanities. Recognising that students are key to decolonise the curricula, groups of students and staff are working together to co-create projects and resources to ensure that all students are represented within the curriculum. At University of Brighton decolonising the curriculum is placed within their EDI plan of achieving the REC award and there are specific actions involving student collaboration to decolonise the science research and education practice.

4.0 Conclusions

On the one hand decolonising can be seen as a process that encourages educators to think about who produces knowledge, what counts as knowledge, and where and how that knowledge is produced. If this is a radical reform of what and how we teach, then where does one start this curriculum transformation? Taking an ethical position requires creating space for non-dominant forms of knowledge and to do this requires dismantling dominant sources of knowledge and control in historically white institutions. Yet engagement with decolonising is challenging work and this project set out to map the terrain of decolonising activity initially within computing and then more broadly within STEM. The insights of this audit have highlighted firstly what the researchers feared that decolonising computing is rare, but this under representation has been balanced by an encouraging array of activity in the wider STEM subjects. The reasons for this lack of activity in the discipline of computing is outside the scope of this project and instead we hope that by showcasing what STEM decolonising activities are underway, will either ignite practitioners to start this difficult work or facilitate the sharing of practice amongst those who are already developing decolonising communities.

Decolonisation in HEI is therefore clearly an ongoing learning process, but the projects that seem most promising and substantial are those where collaboration within STEM and across universities including professional staff and fundamentally the student body are underway. Through establishing working parties, there are a variety of outcomes including co-written papers, creatively held discussion events, and the sharing of each other’s resources in video, podcast and the written word. Multimedia helps support resource creation and dissemination. To this effect the next steps for this project will be to produce our guide to decolonising STEM which will be freely available via open source with the aim to support practitioners towards a decolonised teaching and learning experience.

Appendix A: Audit list of Higher Education Institutions

Aston University University of Bath University of Brighton	London School of Economics and Political Science University of Manchester
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University of Bristol
 University of Cambridge
 Cardiff University
 University College London
 Durham University
 University of East Anglia
 University of Edinburgh
 University of Exeter
 Glasgow Caledonian
 Imperial College London
 University of Kent
 Kings College London
 University of Leicester
 University of Leeds
 University of Liverpool
 Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine

Manchester Metropolitan
 Newcastle University
 Nottingham Trent University
 University of Nottingham
 University of Oxford
 Queen Mary University of London
 Queens University Belfast
 University of Reading
 St George's, University of London
 University of Sheffield
 University of Southampton
 University of Strathclyde
 University of Surrey
 SOAS, London
 Swansea University
 University of Warwick
 University of York
 Ulster University

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Teaching, Learning & Assessment

A Virtual Reality training experience with future psychologists studying online: is a hybrid model feasible?

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Abstract

The introduction of new technologies in the clinical field brought a clear paradigm shift for the psychologist professionals, increasing the demand for a systematic training in the implementation of tools based on Virtual Reality (VR). Though VR-based programs effectiveness in the clinical practice is well established, there is scarce evidence on the use and impact of training packages designed for future professionals. Therefore, the present study aimed at a) exploring the psychologist trainees' attitudes and intentions to use VR in their future work; b) implementing a hybrid training package on the use of VR for assessing neuropsychological functions (i.e. combining online and face-to-face training) and c) examining the feasibility of the training and its impact on the psychologist trainees' attitudes. First, 93 out of 778 students attending a professionalising MSc program (General Health Psychology) in an online Spanish university completed a questionnaire on the perceived utility of receiving training on VR tools, on the intentionality to use VR and on its perceived added value for their future practice, using a Yes/Perhaps/No format. In the second step, a hybrid VR training package was offered to the students consisting of an one-hour online training on the use of a VR software assessing neuropsychological functions (attention, memory, executive functions) and the interpretation of fictional patient reports provided by the software Nesplora, and a 3-hours face-to-face session where students took part in role-plays with fictional case studies implementing VR-based assessments. The same questionnaire was completed after the training, with additional questions on the training experience. From the initial sample (N=93), though 86% of students considered that receiving VR training would be useful and 83% considered VR-based tools to provide an added value for their professional routine, only 58.1% reported intentionality to use such tools in the future practice. Indeed, only 6 out of 93 students took part in the VR training, with only four completing the questionnaire after the face-to-face session. All four participants considered the training useful for approaching them to the clinical practices, with two of them showing intentionality to use such tools in the future. The training experience was considered useful, entertaining, realistic, clarifying, and original by all students, and all of them expressed the need for further experiential training with VR tools. The study findings indicate that although the training was well valued, hybrid training of VR tools is not feasible for students attending professionalising online programs, as cost-effectiveness is poor; therefore, given the existing need for training on the use of VR tools, fully online training options should be offered to these students, albeit the risk of missing the opportunity for experiential learning on site.

Keywords: virtual reality, hybrid training, psychologists, clinical practice, distance learning

1. Introduction

New technologies have received increased attention for implementation in the clinical and psychosocial professional practice. In the field of Psychology, Virtual Reality (RV) is a tool with a great potential for facilitating the use of objective assessments and for increasing the effectiveness of psychological interventions (Bouchard, & Rizzo, 2019). Its utility has been already established across various domains, such as neuropsychological evaluations, assessment and treatment of anxiety disorders and pain management, to name a few (Riva, 2022). Virtual Reality is defined as “a variety of Applications based on new technologies that include experiences of 3D visual immersion, where participants navigate through a world that simulates reality” (Lopreiato & Sawyer, 2015; p. 40).

Albeit its potential, the implementation of Virtual Reality tools in healthcare is still in its infancy, as there is a lack of common framework that can guide meaningful practice (Kouijzer, Kip, Bouman, & Kelders, 2023) and a need for specific support on learning how to effectively implement such tools (Halbig et al., 2022). Indeed, previous studies have showed the efficacy of Virtual Reality simulations for gaining knowledge and training skills in the field of healthcare (Harder et al., 2010; McGaghie et al., 2011; von Wendt et al., 2017).

Virtual Reality offers opportunities for hands on experiential learning in a protected environment, where mistakes cannot hurt people and can be used as great examples of distinguishing between good and bad practice. Students may be asked to design potential Virtual Reality scenes that can be used for instance with patients suffering from phobias, or to design intervention sessions where Virtual Reality assessments are implemented to complement the clinicians’ judgements of a person’s condition. In any case, Virtual Reality training implementations are a great method of simulated applications and active learning, enhancing the students’ theoretical knowledge and making them autonomous learners (Jiang, Zhi & Xiong, 2018).

To date, there are only few studies focusing on how to prepare future healthcare professionals for the use of Virtual Reality tools in their everyday routine (Jones, Jones, & Moro, 2021; Saab, Hegarty, Murphy, & Landers, 2021). As a result, proper guidelines for effective training are missing and its impact on the professionals’ perceived efficacy is understudied.

Based on the above, the present study examined the applicability and feasibility of a Virtual Reality training program implemented with future psychologist professionals. The aim was to explore whether the training could potentially be inserted in the formal curriculum of postgraduate education for such professionals or could alternatively be used as an extracurricular activity aiming at the enhancement of experiential learning.

Specifically, the aims were:

- To examine the students’ perception of utility of Virtual Reality tools and their intention to use them in their future clinical practice
- To examine whether the training on Virtual Reality tools will increase the students’ perceived occupational efficacy, as compared to their perception levels before receiving the training and the perception levels of students not participating in the training activity.
- To explore the usability and acceptability of the Virtual Reality tools
- To receive suggestions for improvement regarding the training activity (design, clinical case studies used, feedback session, etc.)

2. Methods

This was a pilot study with a pre-post design, employing quantitative and qualitative assessments before and after the Virtual Reality tools training activity.

2.1. Sample

The sample consisted of students attending a professionalising postgraduate program in General Health Psychology in a university operating fully online in Spain. Students were at the second term of their study taking the subject "Psychological Interventions for Adults". The training activity was offered to 778 students, out of which 93 completed the pre-training assessment. Only six of them took part in the training and only four (three female and one male) completed the final assessment.

2.2. Assessment

Before the training, students completed a questionnaire on the perceived utility of receiving training on VR tools, on the intentionality to use VR and on its perceived added value for their future practice, using a Yes/Perhaps/No format.

The same questionnaire was completed after the training, with additional questions on the training experience using a not at all/more or less/a lot format.

Students also completed the Perceived Occupational Self-efficacy scale (Rigotti et al., 2008) before and after the training. This self-report instrument consists of ten items assessing occupational self-efficacy using a 7-point Likert scale, which higher scores indicating higher self-efficacy.

An open-ended question explored suggestions for improving or modifying the training activity after the training implementation.

2.3. Procedure

Upon receiving approval by the Bioethics Committee of the Universidad Internacional de La Rioja (PI072/2023) the Virtual Reality training activity was offered to all participants by the research team through an announcement on the virtual campus of their subject. After completing the initial questionnaire, a hybrid Virtual Reality training package was offered to the students consisting of a) an 1-hour online training on the use of a VR software assessing neuropsychological functions (attention, memory, executive functions) and the interpretation of fictional patient reports provided by the software Nesplora; b) a 3-hours face-to-face session in the University's premises where students took part in role-plays with fictional case studies implementing VR-based assessments; and c) an 1-hour feedback session to provide further explanations of the activity, share observations on the experience and complete the questionnaires. No extra credit or other type of reward was offered to participants. The activity took place from March to April 2024.

3. Results

From the initial sample (N=93), though 86% of students considered that receiving Virtual Reality training would be useful and 83% considered Virtual Reality-based tools to provide an added value for their professional routine, only 58.1% reported intentionality to use such tools in the future practice.

All four participants considered the training useful for approaching them to the clinical practices, with two of them showing intentionality to use such tools in the future. The training experience was considered useful, entertaining, realistic, clarifying, and original by all students (see Figure 1). All of them expressed the need for further experiential training with Virtual Reality tools.

The activity was

Figure 1: Participants' perceptions of the training activity

When it comes to their perceived self-efficacy, students' levels did not differ before and after taking part in the activity. Likewise, students undertaking the activity did not report higher self-efficacy compared to those that did not participate in the training activity.

With regards to the qualitative findings based on the responses to the open question, three of the students coincided in suggesting the implementation of more extended training in terms of time and activities, whereas one of them proposed the planification and implementation of a complete intervention program, combining Virtual Reality activities with traditional practice.

4. Conclusions

The study findings indicate that although the training was well valued, hybrid training of Virtual Reality tools is not feasible for students attending professionalising online programs, as cost-effectiveness is poor. For instance, costs for purchasing Virtual Reality glasses and software, and teachers and students' transportation to the University's premises was not compensated by the number of students that participated to the training program.

Therefore, given the existing need for training on the use of VR tools, fully online training options should be offered to these students, albeit the risk of missing the opportunity for experiential learning on site. Also, we suggest the combination of such kind of training activities with other tools that offer the opportunity of real-world simulation. A potential candidate could be any tool based on Artificial Intelligence, such as the Educational Avatars. The use of Avatars enables students to express themselves and establish communication in ways they may have been incapable of doing otherwise (Falloon, 2009), which leads to an increase of their interpersonal skills and confidence levels. Indeed, the combination of Virtual Reality and Avatars that represent people with mental health and/or neuropsychological difficulties can offer a unique opportunity for clinical practice approximation in a secure and protected environment. Such endeavours can be an attractive proposal of immersive learning (Fink, Robinson, & Ertl, 2024) that enhances the teaching and learning processes of future psychologist professionals.

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Co-Design of Tutor Induction to Transform Student Experience, Aid Retention and Progression

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Abstract

Background

Prior research (Johnstone, 2023), coupled with feedback from tutors, reinforced the need for improved induction to help with tutor confidence, competence, and retention and to enhance the student experience. Research and feedback also highlighted that consideration of the learning elimination curve was an important part of induction planning and design, as was collaborating with and seeking stakeholder input. Thus, using a co-design methodology is effective in creating a robust induction process.

Co-design is an approach that puts people at the centre and aims to find practical solutions to a particular goal without focusing on what is wrong. It involves integrating various perspectives, experts, and disciplines to generate ideas based on diverse experiences. Co-design is characterised by the philosophy of participatory design, which emphasises the participation of all stakeholders in the design process. (Bate and Robert, 2007; Blomkamp, 2018; Lenihan and Briggs, 2011).

Using co-design, this project prioritised the expertise and experiences of the stakeholders involved. The initial design recommendations are tailored to meet the needs of both the employees and employers (Steen et al., 2011). This has proven to be more effective regarding its impact on practitioners than traditional academic-designed projects.

Co-Design Project

The project had three main objectives:

1. To establish a comprehensive, flexible, and consistent approach to the induction for tutors.
2. To test a methodology that could be adapted and implemented in other contexts.
3. To determine the most effective activities and timelines that would optimise the use of resources and facilitate efficient and meaningful learning experiences.

We enlisted a group of tutors with the experience and expertise to assess, improve and revamp our induction process. Employing a similar methodology to the one used by Jackman et al. (2021), we divided the process into four stages, enabling us to engage with the tutors and develop an initial framework for the induction. We followed an iterative process, collecting feedback and incorporating revisions into the structure based on the tutors' perspectives.

We have created a basic framework that outlines the different induction and training tasks that tutors must undertake to be competent and confident in supporting apprentices throughout their programme. This

framework remains agile to allow flexibility to take account of previous expertise. It also covers the complex requirements of the apprenticeship funding rules and university governance that tutors must comply with.

After completing this process, it can apply to other job roles or contexts within any organisation because it can be generically applied, collaborating with the relevant stakeholders' knowledge and expertise.

Keywords: co-design, tutor induction, participatory design, collaboration, student experience

1. Introduction

Since the UK government introduced the Apprenticeship Levy in 2017 (Finance Act 2016, 2022), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have faced growing pressure to deliver sustainable degree apprenticeships at scale, in line with government targets to increase the number of apprentices. One of the earliest management apprenticeships at Level 6 and above was approved in 2015 (Institute for Apprenticeships and Technical Education, 2022), following the recommendations of the Richard Review of Apprenticeships (Richard, 2012). These degree apprenticeships provided a pathway for individuals to access higher education while simultaneously engaging in vocational training (Education and Skills Funding Agency, 2017). A key element of these programmes is the close relationship between the apprentice, the employer, and the HEI provider. This mode of delivery was unfamiliar to many institutions, particularly those that had not previously offered apprenticeships. Even for those familiar with the apprenticeship framework, the requirements were notably different, leading many institutions to adapt existing degree programmes by integrating them into the apprenticeship model.

Delivering higher and degree apprenticeships demands more intricate considerations than traditional degree programmes. Accustomed to conventional degree structures, academic staff had to familiarise themselves with the new requirements and integrate them into existing operational frameworks. This shift also necessitated changes in teaching and support strategies. Although universities have long been subject to oversight by bodies such as the Office for Students, as of April 2021, they are now also inspected by Ofsted for their apprenticeship provision (Office for Students, 2022). In some cases, this results in the degree or master's component being evaluated by the Office for Students. At the same time, Ofsted assesses the apprenticeship element, which can create potential conflicts between differing regulatory requirements. The non-completion of apprenticeship programmes has far-reaching consequences for all stakeholders involved. For training providers, such outcomes affect their performance metrics and influence external evaluations by bodies like Ofsted. Moreover, the impact extends to apprentices and their employers, with serious implications for both. Historically, research has identified several factors contributing to apprenticeship withdrawals. These include inadequate information and inappropriate selection of programmes, strained relationships with supervisors (Gow et al., 2008; Harris and Simons, 2005; Smyth and Zimba, 2019), dissatisfaction with employers, and apprentices leaving for alternative employment opportunities (Bilginsoy, 2003). Additionally, dissatisfaction with both on-the-job and off-the-job training has also been reported (Smyth and Zimba, 2019; Snell and Hart, 2008), alongside perceptions of training irrelevance, inappropriate teaching styles (Harris and Simons, 2005; Smyth and Zimba, 2019; Snell and Hart, 2008), and issues related to the quantity and/or quality of skills delivered through the programme (Bilginsoy, 2003).

Anecdotal evidence and preliminary findings (Johnstone, 2022) suggest that tutor induction experiences vary significantly, especially when comparing the pre- and post-pandemic periods, where a lack of consistency has

become evident. This is likely due to individuals' diverse pathways into tutor roles, with some having prior tutoring experience or other roles within the organisation. For a successful tutor-apprentice relationship, tutors must draw upon their industry and commercial expertise.

Another critical insight from recent research (Johnstone, 2022) highlights the importance of a more extended and phased induction process. This approach would allow tutors to assimilate information more effectively and receive training when most relevant to their needs. For instance, while comprehensive training on assessment systems will eventually be necessary for grading purposes, it is not required during the first month. Conversely, familiarity with the e-portfolio system is essential earlier on, as it is used at the outset of the apprenticeship programme.

1.1 Objectives

This project has the following objectives:

1. To develop a comprehensive, flexible, and consistent approach to tutor induction.
2. To test a methodology that can be adapted and applied in various contexts.
3. To identify the most effective activities and timelines that optimise resource use and facilitate efficient, meaningful learning experiences.

The project will establish an induction and training framework designed to equip tutors better to support apprentices throughout their apprenticeship journey. The initial phase will focus on outlining the structure, including key timelines and content, with the potential for future projects to develop and implement the induction programme within the faculty.

Collaboration with other stakeholders will ensure alignment with broader tutor development initiatives across the university, promoting consistency. This consultation process will also help ensure that all mandatory and core training is incorporated into the structure, minimising confusion caused by redundant information or conflicting resource guidance. It will also clarify the distinction between organisation-wide induction (such as a 'Welcome' covering organisational culture, mission, mandatory training, and health and safety) and faculty- or programme-specific training and guidance.

2. Inductions

2.1 What is an Induction?

Successful staff recruitment is only the beginning of what can develop into a productive and harmonious working relationship, provided that the subsequent steps are well-planned, effective, and mutually beneficial. Various terms are used to describe the process of integrating a new employee into an organisation or job role, the most common being induction, onboarding, and orientation, which will be examined below.

Trowler and Knight (1999, p. 178) define induction as "professional practices designed to facilitate the entry of new recruits to an organization and to equip them to operate effectively within it.", a definition that aligns with the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD, 2021). An induction programme aims to help new employees gain a deeper understanding of the organisation, its culture, and their role within it. Typical components may include health and safety, data protection, equality and diversity, and training on any job-specific systems. These programmes can be formal, informal, or a combination of both. While there is no universal framework, CIPD (2021) provides general guidelines that can serve as a foundation.

In addition to "induction," the term "onboarding" is often used to describe the process of introducing new employees. Davila and Pina-Ramirez (2018, sec. 1) define onboarding as "the process through which companies engage new employees or new-to-role employees in the company's culture and with their role." They identify two parts to the onboarding process: "general onboarding" and "role-specific onboarding" (Davila and Pina-Ramirez, 2018, sec. 1). General onboarding applies to all employees and typically includes an introduction to the organisational culture and mandatory training. Role-specific onboarding is tailored to the employee's specific job, focusing on the necessary knowledge, skills, and behaviours to succeed in the role, emphasising organisational socialisation (Davila and Pina-Ramirez, 2018, sec. 1).

Another term commonly found in literature related to induction is "orientation." Mestre et al. (1997, p. 443) describe orientation as "the familiarization with, and adaptation to, a new work environment." Their research in Japan highlights that orientation generally does not include the socialisation aspects found in induction and onboarding processes in Western workplaces. Orientation is typically the first stage of the onboarding/induction process (Davila and Pina-Ramirez, 2018, sec. 1). It involves administrative tasks such as setting up payroll and providing access to organisational systems.

According to *Investors in People* (2019), these terms share similarities but are distinct and essential in staff retention. Induction is often a short-term, transactional process focusing on formalities, while onboarding is a more extended, holistic approach. This view aligns with Davila and Pina-Ramirez's (2018) perspective, particularly regarding role-specific onboarding. For this discussion, the term "induction" will be used to encompass activities that are part of the induction and onboarding processes.

2.2 Planning Inductions

Induction programmes within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should be designed to equip new staff with the skills and confidence necessary for delivering high-quality teaching (Huber et al., 2011), while also integrating them into the wider organisational community, its culture, and systems. Bush and Middlewood (2013, p. 167) identify three core objectives of induction: "socialization," "achieving competent performance," and "understanding the organizational culture." These principles are applicable across diverse types of organisations, not just educational ones. For new employees to make a meaningful contribution, they must first become integrated into the organisation (socialisation). This integration then enables them to perform competently, while demonstrating an understanding and appreciation of the organisation's values and beliefs (culture). However, achieving this in a national organisation with widespread operations, many of which are primarily online, can be challenging. A potential solution could involve a combination of online modules and face-to-face sessions, akin to the programme developed by the Faculty of Business and Economics at Macquarie University (Huber et al., 2011).

In 2017, a CIPD survey revealed that over 80% of organisations faced challenges with staff retention. Given that replacing a staff member costs an average of £30,000 (HRreview, 2014), a robust induction programme could help mitigate this issue. In addition to financial savings, effective induction can prevent reputational damage, improve employee relations (by reducing high turnover), and preserve employee goodwill, which may otherwise be strained by the need to cover vacant positions. According to the Advisory, Conciliation, and Arbitration Service (ACAS), a "good induction programme" leads to "a more settled employee, improved response to training, lower turnover, and better employment relations" (ACAS, 2014, p. 30). Inductions must be carefully planned and balanced, as they are complex and should not be limited to new hires on permanent contracts (Bush and Middlewood, 2013, p. 170; Marchington et al., 2020, sec. 8.2). Even employees transitioning to new roles within the same organisation require role-specific inductions, though they may not

need the broader organisational induction. They still need time to understand what is expected of them in that role.

Johnstone (2022) found that much of the information given to tutors during induction does not consider the learning elimination curve (Shackleton-Jones, 2019, p. 109). The further away the need for the information, the greater the cost and time investment in training. Training should be delivered when it is most relevant, rather than frontloading all the information at once. The current induction model follows a "push" learning approach, as described by Shackleton-Jones (2019), which aims to raise awareness but often introduces topics that are not immediately relevant. This can overwhelm new tutors with information that would not be necessary until later in the programme. Ultimately, refining the induction process aims to enhance retention, job satisfaction, performance, and progression. This directly contributes to student experience and successful outcomes in an educational setting.

3. Methodology

3.1 Approach

This action research was conducted following the principles of a co-design approach, actively involving tutors as key stakeholders to capture their perspectives and collaboratively develop the content for the induction process (Blomkamp, 2018, p. 731). By incorporating tutors' insights, the research embraced the philosophy of participatory design (Sanoff, 2006, p. 140), ensuring that the professional expertise and experiences of the stakeholders were respected (O'Leary, 2021, p. 197). As a result, the recommendations generated were tailored to meet the needs of both employees and employers (Steen et al., 2011, pp. 57–58). This collaborative method will likely result in a more positive reception of the recommendations compared to a traditional top-down approach.

The decision to adopt a co-design methodology stemmed from a desire to hear directly from those performing the tutor role, leveraging the experiential learning gained throughout the tutor journey, from programme initiation to completion. This participatory design approach (Blomkamp, 2018) maximised tutor involvement, allowing solutions to be developed from their firsthand perspectives.

The tutors participating in the project brought a wealth of experience from other organisations, roles, and careers, enriching discussions and providing practical suggestions. Their willingness to engage was motivated by a desire to improve the induction process for future tutors, aiming to enhance job satisfaction and reduce stress. Moreover, their participation reflected the recognition of their valued contributions, which positively influenced tutor confidence and, consequently, the student experience through improved training and guidance.

An interpretivist approach was applied throughout the research, emphasising participants' experiences with the induction process. These experiences provided the foundation for creating a new induction and training structure that is more meaningful, incorporating a variety of perspectives (Saunders et al., 2019, pp. 148–149) while considering the appropriate timing of activities. Although the research does not influence the organisation's general induction programme, the improvements made to the role-specific induction will allow for more effective use of the induction period. This will better prepare tutors to support students, ultimately contributing to enhanced student experiences, aiding retention, and supporting progression.

3.2 Method

Focus groups were employed to explore a group of individuals' perceptions, understandings, and experiences (Davies and Hughes, 2014, pp. 206–207; Kumar, 2019, p. 239; Thomas, 2017, p. 213). In this case, the focus group were all tutors participating in the project, enabling open and honest discussions about their views and experiences. Focus group discussions allow participants to interact with one another, ask questions, and delve deeper into the topic (Morgan, 1996, p. 149). This approach yields richer data and is more time-efficient than conducting individual interviews with each participant.

The first focus group session was conducted face-to-face, but subsequent sessions were conducted online. The online sessions were recorded and transcribed for analysis, which allowed the facilitator to focus entirely on the discussion and helped to explore the topic further (Thomas, 2017, p. 213). The tutors were grouped into two groups with their peers from the same programme. This setup ensured no barriers to open discussion, as all participants held the same role but had varied experiences and perspectives regarding their induction (Acocella, 2012, p. 1129). The focus groups aimed to capture the participants' experiences, views and opinions at each stage of the co-design framework.

3.3 Co-Design Framework

The co-design framework used in this project was adapted from the approach developed by Jackman et al. (2021) and was based on the research conducted by Johnstone (2022). The adapted framework, illustrated in Figure 1 below, employs an iterative process where feedback and analysis are continuously gathered to refine the final output. This approach ensures that tutors are involved at every stage and play a crucial role in shaping the final decisions.

Figure 1: Co-Design Framework

Stage 1 (Face to Face Focus Group)

At the outset of the project, a group of tutors was recruited as participants. These tutors were chosen because of their diverse experiences with the induction process and their extensive experience within their respective

programmes, having completed all relevant activities from start to finish at least once. Their insights and expertise were crucial for identifying the necessary induction and training activities to equip tutors for their roles properly.

The first focus group was conducted as a full-day, in-person session. The tutors were divided into two groups based on the programmes they delivered. Throughout the day, they discussed the various tasks and responsibilities involved in working with apprentices and the training and CPD activities they found necessary or beneficial. Each group shared their discussions, which revealed gaps and differences between the programmes. Afterwards, each group created a timeline outlining when specific training or CPD activities were required to ensure tutors could effectively support apprentices. Figure 2 below illustrates an example of one of the timelines developed during the session.

Figure 2: One of the timelines created by the tutors.

Throughout the discussions, the facilitators took detailed notes and asked questions to clarify points and fully capture the tutors' perspectives. After the session, the notes and timelines were analysed, leading to the development of an initial induction structure for each programme, covering the entire duration. These preliminary structures were then shared with the tutors ahead of the next focus group, allowing them time to review and prepare for further discussion at the next focus group session.

Stage 2 – 4 (Online Focus Groups)

After the initial face-to-face focus group, three more focus groups were conducted online. These sessions allowed tutors to review and offer feedback on the draft induction structure created after the first meeting. During the first online session, it became evident that including indicative content for each training and CPD activity would help tutors better understand what each session would entail. This led to discussions about the potential content for each activity, with some suggestions for adjustments to the initial timeline.

The feedback and recommendations from this session were thoroughly analysed, further refining the induction structure. An indicative content document outlining the main areas to be covered in each training and CPD session was also developed. In addition to the tutors' input, tutor line managers and the core learning and development team were consulted to ensure that essential and mandatory training elements were included in the induction structure. This broadened the perspective, incorporating insights from different stakeholders beyond just the tutors.

Before each subsequent online focus group, tutors received updated versions of the induction structure and indicative content. This allowed them to review the revisions in advance and provide more targeted feedback during the sessions. Each round of feedback further enhanced the structure and content. By the end of Stage 4, a final induction structure and indicative content document had been agreed upon, reflecting all participants' collective input in the process.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

Before commencing the research, the researchers reviewed the ethical guidelines provided by the British Educational Research Association (2018) and the British Psychological Society (Oates et al., 2021) and the organisation's own research ethics policies and procedures. In line with these guidelines, participant consent was obtained, and the purpose of the research and how the information would be used and securely stored were clearly communicated to participants. The researchers also ensured that participants were informed of their anonymity and the secure storage of data (British Educational Research Association, 2018; Oates et al., 2021).

One ethical concern stemmed from the researchers' relationship with the organisation and participants, as some researchers also held line management roles. Small positive changes had recently been introduced within the team, and as relationships were still being formed, this was expected to reduce the influence of power dynamics and promote honest, open responses during focus groups. Using a co-design approach further helped balance power by considering all participants' voices and opinions equally. Additionally, the researchers consulted the organisation's internal research policy to confirm that no further ethical steps were required. Due to the limited number of participants, no additional actions were deemed necessary. This policy also safeguards participants from research overload, which could affect their workload, but as there were no concurrent research projects, this was not a concern.

Ethical considerations specific to the focus groups included maintaining confidentiality and minimising potential harm. The researchers acknowledged that complete confidentiality could not be guaranteed, as participants might share information outside the group (Smith, 1995, p. 482). To mitigate this, participants were asked not to discuss the content outside of the focus group. Additionally, the researchers assured that recordings would remain confidential and securely stored, while transcripts and findings would be anonymised. Although the subject matter was not considered particularly sensitive, the sharing of individual experiences could still affect participants emotionally. Therefore, the researchers had an ethical obligation to monitor participants' well-being and willingness to continue, which was considered when formulating the initial set of questions (British Educational Research Association, 2018, para. 24; Oates et al., 2021, p. 9).

4. Project output

4.1 Induction design

The induction design was developed by identifying similar activities across programmes while recognising the need for different timelines to suit the specific requirements of each programme. A structured outline of the necessary training for each programme was created, along with a corresponding timeline. This process acknowledged the complex and demanding nature of the tutor role within apprenticeship programmes, a challenge highlighted during initial discussions. Additionally, the variety of systems and processes, along with their individual nuances, contributes to this complexity. Recognising that this can be overwhelming for new tutors, the induction design incorporates a paced delivery approach with clear signposting, offering opportunities to revisit essential learning tools and access refresher training. A welcome pack will also be provided, outlining what needs to be completed to help tutors manage their time efficiently.

A recurring theme throughout the process was the need for a more structured and enhanced mentoring approach, with guidance and training for both mentors and mentees. This area will be explored further in a follow-up project, where we will dedicate the necessary time and focus to developing recommendations for improvement.

4.2 Good Practice

The iterative co-design approach (see Figure 1 above) allowed for continuous progress, with opportunities to revisit and amend the induction design as new discussions and ideas emerged. As a result, the design is grounded in a philosophy of continual improvement, with the ability to be refined even after implementation. This flexible approach ensures it can be applied to any programme or job role, as long as the necessary activities are clearly defined. It also clarifies when individuals need to access and complete training, build their knowledge in specific areas and include a guide to the time required for each activity.

Discussions with participants revealed significant variations in the induction experiences and the quality of induction for the tutor role, which became a key focus for improvement. Providing a structured and documented induction process with clear timelines and expectations allows for consistency across the board. This consistency directly contributes to tutor job satisfaction, proficiency, and performance. In addition, aligning the induction process with recruitment cycles, as dictated by programme start dates, ensures that all new tutors receive the same quality of induction. This consistency is crucial for fostering a competent and engaged tutor community. These principles were integrated into the design and are considered good practice for implementation and ongoing success, particularly as they impact the overall quality of the student experience.

Attention was also given to managing the volume of materials, resources, and time demands within the induction process. The goal was to allocate time realistically, avoiding overwhelming new tutors and recognising the learning elimination curve (Shackleton-Jones, 2019, p. 109). This ensures that training is delivered at the right time, avoiding unnecessary repetition, and making the best use of everyone's time. Additionally, providing context and background for the tasks and activities required for the apprenticeship will help tutors better understand their purpose and relevance.

4.3 Impact

Reed's (2018) framework of ten types of impact was used to evaluate the project's impact. While some impacts have already been realised, others are anticipated and will only become evident after the induction programme has been fully developed, launched, and trialled.

The project enabled a thorough exploration of the tutor's role and activities, emphasising the complex and nuanced responsibilities of supporting apprentices in completing their qualifications. It also highlighted the various systems, processes, and stakeholders that tutors in management apprenticeship programmes engage with, differentiating their role from others. This reinforces the need for a more structured, detailed and consistent approach to inducting and training new tutors.

The new induction structure shows a perceived shift in working practices. Tutors are expected to become more confident in navigating the processes and systems that support apprentices, leading to a more consistent approach across tutors while preserving individual teaching styles. This change is expected to improve apprenticeship outcomes, as tutors will better understand how to collaborate with other departments to support timely apprentice completion. Increased tutor confidence may also help retain staff, reducing the need for frequent recruitment and training, thereby lowering associated costs. The project's process allowed for a detailed examination of the tutor's role and the various systems used to support apprentices throughout their programme. This methodology can also be applied to other organisational areas and roles.

The induction timelines were developed based on the apprentice journey, identifying the departments and relationships required to provide effective support. Understanding the interdependencies among these parties helped identify areas for tutor development, which will be integrated into the induction programme. This will enable tutors to build and utilise these relationships, ensuring apprentices receive the best possible experience and support. The potential economic impact is considerable: as the student experience improves, the organisation's reputation for delivering quality apprenticeships will also strengthen, benefiting apprentices and their employers and potentially leading to repeat or new business opportunities.

5. Conclusion

The project has highlighted the complex and nuanced nature of the tutor role within apprenticeships. This has enabled a greater understanding of what training is required and when to ensure the tutor has the tools and information to give them confidence and enhance their ability to support the apprentice through their journey. The project has produced a wireframe to use to create the induction programme.

The induction timelines showcase when the activities should be completed, consistently delivering the same information to every tutor. This leads to increased confidence and competence in supporting the apprentices, improving their experience and, in turn, the reputation of the organisation's apprenticeship delivery.

5.1 Recommendations

The project's outcomes have identified additional areas for development and further investigation. The following recommendations have been made:

- Utilise the established timelines to develop online induction materials for new tutors that support both synchronous and asynchronous delivery.
- Collaborate with the learning and development teams to integrate organisation-wide tutor induction materials, reducing redundant training.
- Develop welcome materials to guide new staff through the induction process. These materials should include clear instructions on what to complete and the time commitment involved.
- Initiate a project to define the role and responsibilities of a mentor who can support new tutors, ensuring adequate time, resources, and training are provided.
- Investigate other areas or job roles where this co-design approach can be applied to improve processes and training.

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Distance Learning: A Vector for Hybridization in Education?

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Abstract

The required transition to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic prompted teachers to rapidly change their teaching methods and be proficient in digital technologies that were often unfamiliar to them. Between adapting the in-person courses to videoconferencing and reflecting on the necessary changes, teachers implemented a variety of digital teaching practices. However, despite using many new tools, it remains unclear whether they fully embraced them and adapted to their newly explored teaching methods.

Thus, more than two years after the end of the health measures, to what extent has the transition to distance learning transformed teachers' practices and representations?

To answer this question, we conducted an exploratory study using a survey and interviews with teachers from higher education and other levels of education who enrolled in the *I teach at a distance* training program during the pandemic. A total of 505 teachers completed the survey in 2023, and 10 were interviewed in 2024.

We were specifically interested in changes to the following dimensions: Teaching content or resources, teaching practices, learner support practices, learning activities, assignments, or exams to assess learning, and ways of correcting and providing feedback to learners.

As we will discuss, the survey results reveal diverse transformations across different dimensions of teaching practice, the extent of change and the type of individuals involved. Our research shows that while most actors implemented changes to their teaching practices, fewer changes were made to learning assessments and course content compared to the other dimensions in this study. The diverse results of our research enabled us to propose a typology highlighting three main ideal types reflecting the influence of the transition to distance learning during the health crisis on current teaching practices.

Keywords: blended learning, transformation, education, practices, teachers.

1. Introduction

As the United Nations noted (2020, p.2): “The COVID-19 pandemic has created the largest disruption of education systems in history, affecting nearly 1.6 billion learners in more than 190 countries and all continents. Closures of schools and other learning spaces have impacted 94 per cent of the world’s student population, up to 99 per cent in low and lower-middle income countries.” Regardless of the differences between societies or educational systems, most of the schools and universities around the world were impacted by the pandemic. The context leads teachers and students to adopt distance education or blended learning depending on the sanitary measures in place. It also facilitates everyone to access courses given in different countries according to their interests (Papi & Dugré, 2024), potentially contributing to the development of internationalization of education, a trend that has long been associated with the development of digitalization (Bruhn-Zass, 2022).

The abrupt transition to distance education (DE) during the Covid-19 pandemic required both teachers and students to familiarize themselves with a teaching and learning practice that was often new to them (Dobrica-Tudor & Coutlée, 2021). Despite the challenges and the stress associated with this transition, some individuals discovered the flexibility and time-saving benefits of distance learning. This is consistent with pre-pandemic findings that indicates students in higher education particularly appreciated blended learning (McLaughlin et al., 2015; Papi, 2015). Moreover, in the context of internationalization of education, blended learning appears as an appropriate practice for accommodating cultural diversity of learners and promoting the development of communities (Lacaste, Cheng & Chuang, 2022).

Transitioning from face-to-face to distance education or blended learning necessitates a redesign of the courses. However, it is uncertain whether teachers are willing or able to undertake this redesign (Lee & Martin, 2020). Consequently, it is pertinent to examine the extent to which teachers have or have not maintained certain distance learning practices or resources. In other words, although interest in hybrid teaching peaked during the pandemic (Bozkurt, 2022), to what extent in more than two years after the end of the health measures, can we see a development of blended learning in education?

The terminology and definitions of blended learning are numerous and varied across languages. Following an extensive effort to define the term, Fernandes, Costa and Perez (2016, p.12) propose the following definition: “mixed learning model that integrates online learning with face-to-face learning theories and practices, materialized in a flexible, multimodal and multilinear redesign.” This definition is adopted here, as it emphasizes that blended learning is not simply a succession of face-to-face and distance learning; it broadly represents a thoughtful articulation of different theories, practices and modes of teaching.

To explore this question, I carried out an exploratory survey using polls and interviews with participants from various levels of education and training backgrounds. The gathered diverse results will enable us to propose a typology highlighting three main ideal types regarding the influence of navigating distance education during the health crisis on current teaching practices.

2. Circumscription of blended learning

Hybridization lies at the crossroads of two modes of training and includes different variations ranging from the flipped classroom to co-modal teaching (Johnson, Seaman and Poulin, 2022). Blended learning is thus a spatio-temporal mix in the sense that hybridization makes it possible to combine presence and distance, synchrony and

asynchrony. The blended mode is often described as an ideal in the sense that it makes it possible to benefit from the advantages inherent in systems involving defined learning times or spaces that are likely to encourage socialization and interaction, and those of systems involving neither a specific time nor place for learning, which therefore favoring flexibility and accessibility. To propose our vision of blended learning, we present the following diagram.

Figure 1: Status of blended learning in relation to other educational modes

For more than a decade, a great deal of research has presented blended learning as a holy grail in that it leads to fewer dropouts compared to fully distance education and enhances learner performance more than in fully face-to-face education (Moskal et al., 2013; Vo et al., 2017; Vallée et al., 2020). In addition, students tend to prefer this mode of education (Papi, 2015) and the pandemic has at times provided an opportunity to discover the co-modal mode, offering students the choice of taking courses face-to-face or at a distance (Beatty, 2019). However, the attraction or interest in distance learning for students varies according to their educational level (Ostown et al., 2013; Vo et al., 2017; Papi et al., 2023) and its relevance may depend on the discipline (Vo et al., 2017; Breault and Papi, 2023). Furthermore, hybridization requires skills that teachers may not always have the opportunity to develop, as these skills differ from those required for face-to-face and distance education. Consequently, the influence of the pandemic on the development of blending learning and, more broadly, on pedagogical changes is highly uncertain. The articles published to date address the effects of the pandemic on education and focus mainly on the upheavals and challenges raised by emergency distance education (Hodges et al., 2020) with less focus on the changes that remain afterwards.

On one hand, teachers sought to change their practices to adapt to the required transition to distance learning, in particular by discussing and exchanging resources and practices with their colleagues (Buckley-Marudas & Rose, 2021). Communication and collaboration with and between learners seem to have been central to these changes. Hargreaves (2021) stresses the importance of discussion forums for exchanges between students and teachers, while Hardman (2021) promotes collaborative learning as a dialogic practice for motivating human relationships

and acquiring shared knowledge through interaction. Moreover, several studies indicate that teachers experimented with flipped classrooms during or after the pandemic. By offering learners a mix of pre-recorded lessons, links to articles and reading resources via an online platform, teachers seemed to be able to allocate more time in the classroom to support learners and carry out collaborative and constructive learning activities such as debates, problem-solving, and project completion (Al-Naabi, 2022; Divjak et al., 2022; Pakpahan, 2020). The development of active teaching practices (Flaherty et al., 2023) and even experiential learning (particularly in medicine) seems to be in order (Chaturvedi et al., 2021; McGowan, 2021). Beckmann (2023) indicates that 85% of mammalogy teachers surveyed at the end of the pandemic planned to continue using digital technologies beyond health measures. Some teachers even proposed innovative ideas on how they planned to use them in the future (Callaghan et al., 2023). Thus, the experience of distance education could therefore pave the way to a greater degree of hybridization, with the latter offering greater flexibility in terms of both the education mode and its location and scheduling, as noted by Augeri and Kajita (2023).

However, the development of fully or partially distance education seems to be constrained by digital divides related to access to digital equipment and literacy (Granjon, 2011; Plantard, 2021). Both practitioners and researchers have highlighted the fact that some learners and at times, some teachers - generally those living in countries with limited internet infrastructure (Simen et al., 2021), as well as those in Western countries from modest economic backgrounds or living in remote areas - lacked computer equipment or internet access, rendering them more severely affected than others by the health crisis (Kerres & Buchner, 2022). Additionally, it has been observed that the technical difficulties encountered by students and teachers hindered online teaching and learning, particularly by increasing the time needed to prepare teaching resources (Marmolejo & Groccia, 2022). Beyond the mandatory adoption of different tools, teachers' sense of personal effectiveness regarding the use of digital technologies in their teaching practices remains limited (Black et al., 2023; Callimaci & Fortin, 2022). Although educational establishments at times provided training to teachers to familiarize themselves with digital platforms and environments implemented in the institution (Black et al., 2023), such training did not meet all their needs (Foreman-Brown et al., 2023; Trevisan & Rossi, 2023).

Post-pandemic, institutions may at times press for a return to fully face-to-face learning, with their policies and technological investments potentially limiting the possibilities of hybridization (Muniz et al., 2023), in some cases despite national policies in favor of blended learning (Lison and Verchier, 2023). In addition, some lecturers noted the exhaustion caused by distance communication and admit that they struggle to maintain a presence or to keep students engaged and motivated and that they prefer face-to-face interaction (Michelot, 2023). Many continue to favor traditional lectures and in-person assessment methods (Pierrot et al., 2022). Carreras and Couturier (2022) thus show that not all teachers have developed new pedagogical practices; instead, during the pandemic, some have intensified their content-focused practices by increasing and varying the resources made available. As the last-mentioned authors indicate, teacher training and support still seem to be necessary, and other researchers note that not all teachers are prepared to follow training courses designated to facilitate them to implement a hybridization approach (Sautelet et al., 2022). This raises the question: to what extent have those involved in education who have undergone distance education, successfully integrated blended learning into their courses?

3. Field of enquiry and research methodology

We propose to study this subject in light of the survey results sent to individuals who registered for the *J'enseigne à distance* (I teach at a distance) course, along with interviews conducted with those who had expressed interest

in participating in the survey. The *J'enseigne à distance* course, developed at the request of Quebec's Ministère de l'éducation et de l'enseignement supérieur, was launched online at the start of the pandemic with modules that were created during the spring and summer of 2020 (Papi et al., 2021). The course is accessible online and without the need for registration. Although it was only advertised in Quebec, the course has attracted over 300,000 Francophone participants globally. Additionally, a free registration option is available for those seeking to obtain a certificate of completion. At the conclusion of the course, a survey was distributed to the 21,849 enrolled participants, with 2,249 responses received between 2020 and 2023. Of these respondents, only 16% reported having prior experience with distance education. While a quarter viewed the course as an obligation they could forgo, the remaining three-quarters perceived it as an interesting challenge and as an opportunity to develop or deepen their skills and teaching practices.

A subsequent survey was sent to registrants in the spring of 2023, resulting in responses from 928 individuals, of whom 739 were teachers. Among these respondents, 61 expressed an interest in participating in interviews, however only 12 (including 10 teachers) were available when contacted in winter 2024. This notably low participation rate in the survey may be partly explained by the significant gap of time between the training period (generally during the pandemic, i.e. in 2020 or 2021) and the distribution of the survey in 2023. Additionally, the gap between the distribution of the survey and the interviews in 2024, as well as the reluctance to revisit a difficult period likely contributed to this outcome.

The survey covered the period of the pandemic and sought to identify the changes that had taken place since, as well as to assess the appreciation and usefulness of the *J'enseigne à distance* course. It included both closed-ended and open-ended questions and was administered online via Limesurvey. The collected responses were subjected to descriptive analysis and cross-tabulations, including Chi-2 and analysis of variance (e.g. ANOVA). Of the 739 respondents who identified themselves as teachers, 505 completed all the closed-ended questions and the analyses are based on their answers. Of the respondents, 85% live in Canada, mainly Quebec, and nearly three-quarters are women. Additionally, 8% of the respondents live in African countries (including Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria, Cameroun, Ivory Coast, Burkina Faso, Senegal, Gabon, Nigeria), 4% in American countries (Mexico, Haiti, Brazil), 2% in European countries (France, Switzerland, Belgium, Spain, Italia, Romania). These 505 teachers work at various levels of education: 5% in preschool, 28% in primary school, 27% in secondary school, 24% in higher education, and 16% in adult training. Notably, only 3% of teachers reportedly have been teaching for three years or less, suggesting they may not have been teaching before the pandemic. Overall, seniority in the profession varies but is significant, where over 85% have been teaching for at least 10 years.

The interviews also covered training in DE, the adaptation of practices and experiences in DE, and the changes in practices kept or not kept since the end of the health measures. The semi-directive interviews were conducted by videoconference using Teams and were transcribed and recorded. Two types of analyses were carried out (Blanchet & Gotman, 2001): one focused on individual interviews aimed to understand the logic of the players, while the other was more thematic, aimed to highlight the similarities and differences between the practices and logic among the different players. Our sample consisted of twelve individuals living in five countries: Canada, Haiti, Algeria, Brazil and Belgium.

Table 1: Sample of interviewees

Code	Country province	Level	Profession	Seniority	Gender
UT1	Haiti	University	Teacher	20 years	Woman
CT1	Canada (New Brunswick)	College	Teacher	17 years	Men
UT2	Haiti	University	Teacher et director of Continuing Education Director	10 years	Woman
UT3	Brazil	University	Teacher	30 years	Woman
PT1	Canada (Quebec)	Primary	Teacher	22 years	Woman
UT4	Algeria	University	Teacher	26 years	Men
TT1	Belgium	Professional training	Teacher	3 years	Men
ST1	Canada (Quebec)	Secondary	Teacher	20 years	Men
ST2	Canada (Quebec)	Secondary	Teacher	17 years	Men
UT5	Algeria	Secondary and University	Teacher	18 years	Men
CE1	Canada (Quebec)	College	Continuing Education Advisor	21 years	Woman
CM1	Canada (Quebec)	Company	Training Manager	3 years	Woman

4. Main findings

We will sequentially present the main findings of the survey and interviews.

4.1 Results of survey data

One-third of the 505 teachers who responded to the survey stated that they were not at all familiar with DE before the pandemic. In 2023, only 10% said they were teaching in blended learning mode, where most of their courses were conducted face-to-face; 3% taught in blended learning mode with the majority of courses being distance learning and 2% in co-modal learning. This indicates adoption of blended learning is limited, with 79% of teachers primarily conducting classes in the classroom and only 6% by distance learning. In fact, approximately three-quarters of teachers have returned to the mode of education they were accustomed to before the pandemic, which for the majority of them is face-to-face teaching. In addition, one-way ANOVA tests show that the 50-60 age group is more likely to report teaching in blended learning mode than other age groups ($F(4, 471) = 4.198, p = 0.002$). Furthermore, men are more likely than women to teach in blended learning mode ($p = 0.012$). However, since men in our sample are older than women, it is difficult to clearly understand whether this trend is attributable to age or gender. It is also interesting to observe that some differences appear depending on the level of education, distance and blended learning being more prevalent in higher education and adult training.

Figure 2: Teaching mode according to level of education

Moreover, when teachers were asked whether the transition to distance education had led them to make changes that they would have kept after the pandemic, the majority said that they had changed certain resources or ways of doing things, as shown in the graph below.

Figure 3: Changes maintained by teachers since the pandemic

While most teachers implemented changes to their teaching practices that they maintained after the pandemic, an average of 16% said they had returned to their previous practices and resources. Among those who did make modifications, the extent of these adjustments varied. Only 4% said they had completely adjusted their resources or practices. Moreover, the changes or modifications made vary not only from one teacher to another but also

based on the adjustments it was related to. For example, the largest proportion of teachers (89%) said they had made changes to teaching resources, and the fewest (74%) noted changes in the assessment of learning. It seems relevant here to indicate that, as far as assessments are concerned, it's the men who reported having made the most changes, both in terms of learning assessment activities ($F(2, 391) 4.32 p= 0.037$) and ways of giving feedback ($F(2, 351) 4.1 p= 0.012$). Additionally, the teachers who answered the open-ended questions all pointed to increased use of digital resources or platforms, as this example shows:

Teams has remained an important work tool. I encourage students to contact me as soon as they are absent and I send them instructions for resuming the subject. My course documents are also available in Teams. I encourage students to ask me questions between lessons and I correct certain elements using photos sent by students. (Teacher, secondary school, Quebec)

Furthermore, some teachers mentioned doing more group work or offering oral assessments. The integration of technology and the various education modalities thus seem to have sometimes fostered hybridization, as illustrated by the following comments:

I have kept asynchronous lessons in the form of interactive presentations for the theoretical part of the course. Students can view the content asynchronously whenever they like. They can validate their learning via optional questionnaires linked to the course. During face-to-face meetings (once a week), I encourage teamwork, discussion and exchange. (Teacher, university, Quebec)

However, opportunities are limited in some institutions, as this teacher explained:

In our institution, we are not allowed to offer distance education. I'd like to make more use of this potential, but unfortunately union pressure has made that impossible. As a result, I only offer one-to-one distance coaching when it suits the student. (Teacher, college, Quebec)

More than two-thirds of teachers (64%) said that these changes have had a positive impact on learners. Their comments effectively highlight the enhanced structure and accessibility of learning resources, which encouraged students to work independently, as well as the diversification of activities and communication practices that supported their motivation and commitment, as highlighted by this quotation:

These changes allow for better organisation of time, teaching and learning. It also means better follow-up for parents, pupils and teachers (family-school collaboration). What's more, it helps develop autonomy, because pupils who are absent, for example, can get everything they need from Teams or ask questions directly in the conversation section. (Teacher, primary, secondary and college, Quebec)

However, one-third said they didn't know to what extent the changes in teaching were affecting learners, in the sense that they were still experiencing the after-effects of the pandemic: *'It's difficult to assess the impact of the changes because students are experiencing more learning difficulties and doing less well since the pandemic. They are much more anxious and less independent.'* (Teacher, college, Quebec)

Although most of the participants did not answer the open-ended questions, and the details gathered were limited, we aimed to explore these different aspects in greater depth through interviews.

4.2 Results of interview data

During the interviews, we discussed both the adaptations made as well as those not made during the transition to remote education during the pandemic, along with what practices were maintained afterwards. We will now highlight the main points that emerged from these two contexts.

The transition to remote education

Some participants were already familiar with distance learning, while others had no prior experience. Although all participants had completed some or all of the *J'enseigne à distance* course, it was not available during the initial two months of the pandemic. Five of the ten teachers had, nevertheless, taken other education courses before or at the start of the pandemic. Several challenges were nonetheless common to almost all the teachers interviewed.

Among them, those relating to technical constraints were frequently mentioned, such as the lack of equipment and connection, which proved to be particularly disabling in contexts characterized by material precariousness or remoteness from major urban centres, as mentioned by a university professor in Haiti where, in addition to Internet connection worries, 'the problem of electricity remains a major problem' (UT1). Moreover, the adoption of new technologies posed a challenge. One teacher (CT1), for example, recounts how sharing difficulties with colleagues helped him to overcome feelings of incompetence that had initially affected him to the point of considering resigning.

Institutional challenges were also mentioned, such as the lack of support, education and resources. For example, a teacher from Quebec reported: '*Before the government provided online education at TÉLUQ, [...] it was a lot of improvisation, trial and error, etc.*' (ST2). Similarly, a Belgian teacher (TT1), who had to run a new course without support in 2020-2021 said that he had 'tested things out' and observed that strategies that worked remotely also worked in person, while those that failed to work remotely didn't work in person either. More broadly, some individuals explained that the challenges they encountered were intertwined with socio-political issues such as the political crises in Haiti, for example.

Finally, the most frequently raised type of challenge involved learners' participation and classroom management: keeping learners' attention and getting them to participate while they often keep their cameras off, or even playing games, chatting or disconnecting during the class, presented as a frustration for all the teachers. Some participants attributed these inappropriate behaviours and lack of motivation to the effects of the health crisis and social isolation on their mental health or job opportunities, which were distracting them from their studies.

Several teachers shared the effect that this type of behaviour had in turn, impacted their mood and their motivation to teach, describing the fatigue resulting from the extra effort required to be made, in particular, to try to keep the class's attention: '*they would log on, but not put the camera on, [...] they would leave and not care... So, in fact, I felt like I was working more and for nothing.*' (ST2) More generally, a number of teachers at secondary, college and university level said that their workload had increased significantly during this period: '*Preparing an online teaching session took me a lot more time than face-to-face. Because you have to do the script, you have to select the information, you have to record yourself..*' (ST2) Whether or not they had taken education courses does not seem to have had a significant impact on how easily the teachers adapted to the transition to remote education or on the challenges they encountered. In this regard, practical experience of distance teaching before the pandemic seems to have been much more decisive.

The development of a certain hybridity

Most of the changes reported can be divided along two lines: the first reflects the importance of the role played by digital technologies in facilitating the changes. The second reflects the nature or depth of the change.

Teachers noted that the ability to upload and make all course content and resources such as lesson plans, documents, and photocopies accessible on a platform like Teams provides their learners with more opportunities to review the material. This accessibility in particular presented as beneficial for those with learning difficulties or those who have been absent. For young students, this approach seemed to encourage better collaboration between family and school:

Because parents have access to everything I do in the classroom. So there's no excuse: you can follow everything from all sides. I write my notes on the blackboard [... but they] stay in the notepad. So students who have difficulty listening and writing at the same time, well they can take their notes home... (PT1)

Similarly, some teachers emphasized that the digital applications and platforms they used made it easier for them to support students by making them 'more contactable' (UT2) to enable more frequent feedback and smoother communication with their students. One primary school teacher noted that the opportunity students had to communicate with her outside class time had a positive effect on them: *'at a distance, I can give feedback more often. So, the more often we give feedback, the more often we give pupils the opportunity to achieve small successes, so they stay motivated'*. (PT1)

In some cases, teachers leveraged the skills they have developed to encourage their learners to create audiovisual content themselves. For example, a secondary school teacher (ST2) suggested that his students create a podcast. In other more frequent cases, teachers noted that the adoption of technology had opened up new possibilities that extend beyond the shift to distance learning. This has enabled them to develop new practices or tackle challenges in a different way from how they were even before the pandemic, such as helping learners with disabilities.

Sometimes the changes cited are simply transpositions of course content or assignments into digital form. Examples include interactive online exercises, exams taken on Forms rather than on paper, and the submission of homework or assignments on teaching platforms such as Teams and Moodle. The videos created during the pandemic, which many teachers kept, have changed in purpose upon their return to the classroom. For example, one teacher now uses the videos more as supplementary resources, in the event of substitution, as a revision tool or to support certain students who had to be absent and could not attend the face-to-face session. However, beyond the product itself, the skills acquired during the process of creating these videos and the teaching practices have at times been retained. Teachers have enhanced their ability to synthesize the material or present it differently, which can be leveraged to even greater advantage in various educational contexts.

Some changes therefore have a more substantive effect, occasionally without even resorting to digital technologies. Several teachers reported that they have adopted and maintained practices that rely more on active and participatory approaches, particularly to overcome the challenges related to student attention, participation, and motivation. For example, they implemented flipped classrooms, collaborative activities and peer assessment; they are more inclined to challenge students and award them points for participation, as well as shortening the length of reading materials or offering alternative practices of resuming their studies.

5. Development of blended learning limited to one type of players

Analysis of the questionnaires and interviews reveals a wide variety of practices and perspectives on the changes that took place during and after the pandemic. However, similarities are discernible in the interviews and tend to be align with the survey results and existing research in the field. This allows us to propose the distinction of three ideal types: the overwhelmed, the converted and the experienced.

5.1 The overwhelmed

This group includes teachers who made minimal adaptations to their practices during and after the pandemic (corresponding in Table 4 to moderate, minor or no changes). For example, they did not create any audio-visual content, but instead shared videos relevant to the subject they were teaching; they prepared their lessons in more detail, but did not change them significantly; they changed their way of teaching and supporting their students slightly, in particular by challenging them to try to maintain their focus, but without proposing any new forms of support.

As highlighted in other research (Callimaci & Fortin, 2022; Marmolejo & Groccia, 2022), they often explicitly report a feeling of fatigue, or even exhaustion, which stems from the heavier workload and the efforts required to maintain students' attention (CT1, UT1). They noted that they spent more time on the same tasks compared to before the pandemic such as needing to rehearse more often in class, spending more time with students, and marking more on the computer than by hand, thus requiring longer times. These teachers described persistent difficulties in keeping students focused, mentioning unsuccessful attempts in this regard (TT1, ST1). Although they identified many challenges, only few concrete adaptations seem to be implemented in practice.

The difficulties and perceived failures were mainly attributed to external factors. In addition to the unstable socio-political context and the lack of equipment or connection (Augeri & Kajita, 2023; Kerres & Buchner, 2022; Simen et al., 2021), the following factors are mentioned: DE not adapted to the type of course given, inadequate technological resources available, unsuitable teaching resources, etc. These teachers insist that learners' behaviour is beyond their control: younger students "lack self-control and discipline" (ST1), others are perceived as hating the subject being taught (TT1). As a result, they are unlikely to question their own practices or their power to act on the factors complained of and, consequently, to experiment.

After the pandemic, teachers of this ideal type tended to revert to their old, less time-consuming practices, often based on a more behaviourist stance that waved the stick (punishment) and the carrot (participation points). The changes adopted during the pandemic and maintained since then, where they exist, mainly concern relations and interactions with students or the utilization of certain technologies which are now institutionalized, such as platforms for submitting and marking learners' work.

5.2 The converted

This type brings together teachers who actively renewed and adapted their practices during the shift to distance education imposed by the pandemic. The changes cited are more numerous, multidimensional, and lasting than in the other two ideal types. To cope with the transition to distance learning, the teachers mentioned an active process of research, self-taught learning, and reflective experimentation, which led them to develop new digital teaching practices.

One teacher (ST2), for example, reported doing a great deal of research, seeking out information, testing various tools, enrolling in training courses and drawing inspiration from these experiences to rethink about his course. Another teacher (UT3), who developed an interest in pedagogy since the pandemic, is now pursuing a degree in the field. In addition to the use of technology, teaching practices and the overall structure of their courses are being re-examined. The training courses taken and exchanged with colleagues serve as a source of inspiration (Buckley-Marudas & Rose, 2021; Foreman-Brown et al., 2023; Trevisan & Rossi, 2023), as does having already taken distance learning courses as a learner, as underlined by this account from a Quebec teacher who used a Teluq University course as a model: 'I said to myself, 'But why should I go and reinvent the wheel? I'm going to reuse the same model! So what did I do? I took Google Meet and started recording myself. (ST2)

These teachers noted that their new practices seemed to have positive effects on learner participation, motivation and even academic results, so much so that they tended to maintain these practices when they returned to the classroom. As a result, they tend to maintain what they have learnt (Black et al., 2023) to use active teaching practices more than they did before the pandemic (Al-Naabi, 2022; Divjak et al., 2022; Hardman, 2021) and to develop blended learning.

5.3 The experienced

These were teachers, educational advisers or trainers who had prior experience with distance education or various digital technologies in their practices before the pandemic, which gave them a certain familiarity and digital pedagogical skills that they could use in the context of distance education, whether fully or partially. Participants PT1, CE1 and CM1 claimed to have encountered a few challenges and to implement only minor to moderate changes. The approach they described appeared to be more pragmatic, relying less on experimentation and trial and error compared to the other ideal types. When they were already teaching entirely at a distance before the pandemic, their courses were not modified, but they may have had to share their know-how with colleagues who needed it (Papi et al., 2021).

Players of this type are more confident about what to do and appear to be better equipped. For example, UT5 described the actions taken to transition to distance learning in a precise and structured manner, highlighting the stages of needs assessment and analysis, planning of courses and activities, communication with students and parents, etc. Similarly, PT1 explained that she had first provided activities, links, and procedures to parents before describing what she had done to transition to distance learning.

Consequently, the changes and, above all, the challenges caused by the switch to distance education were few, given their pre-existing practices in hybrid or distance learning before the pandemic. As a result, they tended to maintain most of their practices, both during and after the pandemic. Notably, players in this ideal type considered dimensions overlooked by those in the other two ideal types, such as the importance of communicating with parents and offering them resources to support their children.

6. Conclusion

We looked at the potential development of blended learning by studying the changes made in the following areas: teaching content or resources, teaching practices, ways of supporting learners, learning activities, assignments or examinations to assess learning and ways of correcting and giving feedback to learners. Thus, we have been able to show that the majority of players have made changes to their teaching in these different areas, with the least

changes being made to learning assessment and course content. The results of this research thus make it possible to highlight the diversity of transformations in terms of dimensions of teaching practice, degree of change and type of player. They tend to show that neither a 'simple parenthesis' nor a 'mutation of the education system', the obligatory transition to distance education has favoured certain changes in teaching practices (Wagnon, 2020).

It is evident that for any changes in pedagogy to be maintained after the end of the health measures, they must have been made beforehand. However, not all teachers responded in the same way. Even though they had all taken the *J'enseigne à distance* course - and at times taken other courses as well - not all benefited from it in the same way - especially as the transition to distance learning had begun before the first course content had been put online. Nevertheless, they noted that the course has enabled them to diversify their teaching repertoire. The three ideal types proposed in this study reflect the different trends identified among the individuals interviewed in terms of pedagogical and digital transformation. Those who felt overwhelmed found the transition to distance education more challenging and were content to make the changes that would at least enable them to offer distance education courses. Since then, they have mostly returned to their previous practices, but tend to spend more time preparing their courses and supporting their learners. Those who embraced the changes devoted a great deal of time to experimentation, training and collaboration during the pandemic, and became more reflective about their practices. The modifications made to their teaching during the pandemic generally affected all the aspects mentioned, and some of them continue to be adapted today for in-person or blended learning. Experienced teachers, however, reported few changes, as they were already familiar with integrating digital technologies into their teaching, and had already been implementing distance education practices. As they had little need to review their practices, their current teaching practices remained largely the same as they were before the health crisis. This third type is often omitted from the literature on the subject, while the other two frequently emerge from other research.

Eventually, his typology could be further refined by focusing more on the different dimensions of teaching that have been modified. Additional analyses of practices or explanatory interviews could provide more insights into the changes and the rationale behind them. Moreover, our sample presented two notable biases: a bias of interest, since it only includes players who have registered for the *J'enseigne à distance* course, and a bias of origin, since most of the teachers who have taken this course are in Quebec. Nevertheless, the interviews made it possible to gather the teachers' testimonies in different contexts and, in so doing, highlight the importance of institutional and societal support or constraints. Furthermore, other recently published research tends to highlight similar elements, in particular the fact that, despite the development of digital skills that has taken place, the need to support teachers who have not yet succeeded in developing in-depth digital pedagogical instrumentation still remain (Lison and Verchier, 2023; Michelot, 2023). Despite limitations in terms of the representativeness of the situations and the depth of the analysis, these results provide valuable insights to take into account when considering the development of blended learning.

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Teaching Social Work Knowledge, Skills and Values online

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Abstract

The Open University (The OU), based in the UK, produces world-class research, scholarship, and knowledge exchange across a wide range of subject areas. Since its launch in 1969, more than 2.3 million people worldwide have achieved their learning goals by studying with the OU.

This presentation, delivered by Jo Strang (Lecturer in Health and Social Care and Mick McCormick (Senior Lecturer in Social Work), outlined the innovative design of a new module, 'Foundations for Social Care and Social Work Practice'. The module was created with input from various stakeholders, including academics, people with lived experience of using services, employers, and students. Through innovative activities and online teaching tools, students engage with peers and instructors online to practice skills, discuss linking theory and practice, and working towards demonstrating their readiness for practice in social work and social care.

This was a new venture to bring first-year social care and social work students together and teach a skills module fully online. Mick and Jo led the team, and in this presentation, they discussed the challenges they faced and how they overcame them through considered learning design. They outlined the various elements that contributed to a successful learning experience that has been reviewed positively by students, tutors, employers, and external examiners alike.

During this presentation, Jo and Mick linked to pedagogical theory to explain why the design was structured and created as it was, with evaluative quotes from all stakeholders. There is much to be learned from the design and success of this module that will be of interest to others seeking to improve online delivery of skills in module design. The module is reviewed on an ongoing basis. Jo and Mick completed their presentation summarising recent changes to assist student engagement with this innovative module.

Keywords: social work skills, social work education, social work training, online learning, interactive online learning, practice skills, innovation.

1. Introduction

Module K123, Foundations for Social Care and Social Work Practice, has been designed to meet the needs of Level 1 social care and social work students across all four UK nations, in addition to preparing other students to further their knowledge and practice skills in the field of health and social care. The regulatory bodies across the UK share their commitment to ensuring that in this first year of study, students are prepared with the necessary skills, knowledge and value base to be adequately prepared for working directly with individuals and families in complex situations. At the same time, the OU is committed to ensuring that all students completing their first year and progressing to a second year of social work study are deemed ready for practice and have begun to develop strong communication skills. This value base appreciates diversity and inclusion, professional curiosity and leadership skills that will equip them moving forward. The intention is to support students in their journey to become compassionate and confident social care and social work practitioners, recognising the importance of understanding people’s lived experience, the remit of organizational provision and the national context in which they will practice.

In planning and designing this module the authors reviewed the predecessor module and found that it did not achieve sufficient depth and detail in skills development at this level or a convincing sense of constructive alignment regarding module design. Detailed analysis of the predecessor module identified three overarching areas of concern which were having a significant impact on student retention and success on the module, and this was reflected in the falling student retention figures for module. It can be seen in Figure 1 that student retention on the module was regularly falling below 75%.

Figure 1. Retention on the predecessor module

The three overarching areas of concern are captured in Table 1 and were identified as:

- Compulsory attendance at seven workshops – alongside associated compulsory compensatory activities for non-attendance.
- Mechanism for handling the required, regulatory practice requirements.
- The module’s blended learning strategy.

Aspect of Module	Challenge	Solution
Mandatory attendance at 7 workshops	<p>Attendance rates can be poor and yet these count as Skills Days.</p> <p>A 500-word reflection as a compensatory activity does not equate to workshop learning activities, but it is counted as such.</p> <p>The three face-to-face modules were poorly attended and discriminated against students who were time poor, had work and caring commitments, or who lived considerable distances away from the tutorial venue.</p> <p>The four online workshops are scheduled as 2-hour slots, which are appropriate for an online experience but are not situated with a clear sense of pre- and post-workshop learning activities.</p>	<p>Assess, monitor and record engagement, participation and process of learning.</p> <p>Remove face-to-face workshops Offer active learning opportunities linked to assessment and portfolio requirements to create a learning journey for independent adult learners.</p> <p>Thus, the process of active learning can be accounted for as skills days.</p>
Readiness to Practice requirements	<p>This is a clunky, paper-based process that feels more like a tick-box exercise than a supportive and reflective skills development opportunity.</p> <p>There is no detailed consideration of the student’s practice, and it provides minimal feed-forward in preparation for placements.</p> <p>Not all students are familiar with the framework under which they are being assessed for their nation.</p> <p>Detailed feedback is only given to some students to help them further develop their skills.</p>	<p>Students are expected to confirm prior to the start of the module that they are involved in paid or voluntary work.</p> <p>The e-portfolio will include reflections on direct practice, a brief assessment of conduct and participation, and confirmation of practice.</p> <p>Closer alignment with each nation’s regulatory requirements.</p>
Blended learning strategy	<p>There is poor linkage to the sequence of module materials, attendance is not always high, and active participation in online workshops is variable. (Some will use mics, but often, there is a high reliance on written correspondence in the chat box.)</p>	<p>Establish a clear pedagogical underpinning for the delivery of workshop content.</p> <p>Expectations from the outset are that students use mics and webcams and are visible online.</p>

	<p>Tutors currently deliver in pairs. Independent learning tasks and opportunities for skills rehearsal are minimal.</p>	<p>One tutor dedicated to their own tutor group – to establish trust, ensure consistency and development of supportive community of practice.</p> <p>The platform must be sufficiently stable to enable interactive learning opportunities.</p>
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Table 1. Summary of overarching concerns.

The nature of the skills workshops' delivery had led to an inequitable and inaccessible student experience, which effectively tripped up and failed otherwise able practitioners. This was compounded by the formative and cumbersome practice portfolio. The new module was designed with a focus on a more equitable, accessible, intuitive, and supportive delivery of skills workshops, as described in the following section.

2. The design features of module (K123)

Research shows that to develop professional identity, students require active engagement with their peers, supervisors and role models, in addition to acquiring knowledge regarding the multiple areas of practice and the attributes and skills of these professional roles (Wiles 2017). As noted by Fry (2014, p144) *‘the content-led info-transmission model needn’t be the template for online teaching and learning today’*. Provided the platform for delivery is reliable, online delivery offers more freedom and scope such that *‘rich student-student interaction, experiential learning, peer feedback and small group learning can all be achieved’* (Fry et al. 2014, p.142). Online and simulated learning is now firmly embedded within the methodology of teaching in higher education in social and health care and should form part of the learning design of Higher Education content. This is of particular significance to health and social care education and training, in that online and simulated learning offers a way in which to tackle the perennial issue of teaching across the practice-theory gap. It has been found that it increases skill and knowledge levels (Dodds et al 2018, Ferguson & Driver, 2019) because learning by doing is realistic and safe - free from consequences of mistakes (Kourgiantakis & Lee, 2020).

Figure 2. Infographic showing incorporated elements to ensure a positive student experience

With the above pedagogical understanding in mind, providing a high-quality student experience was at the heart of the module design (see Figure 2). The module team made the active choice to design a fully online module and to move away from lengthy face-face workshops which were disadvantaging time-poor students, and particularly those with caring responsibilities, health needs or with limited budget to spend on travel to tutorial venues. Consideration was given to how best to structure and scaffold the learning, such that it would be both accessible and inclusive for students.

Key design features were as follows:

- Tutor/student ratio of 1:15 with one tutor always teaching their own group
- Approximately fortnightly workshops, to offer ongoing support
- 2 x 2-hour workshops per block of learning (aligned with the content of 5 blocks)
- A 1-hour consolidation session positioned at the end of each block of learning
- A variety of learning activities within each online workshop
- Appropriate compensatory tasks in place of missed workshops
- The completion of an e-portfolio in addition to Tutor-marked assessments (TMAs)

The decision to create smaller tutor groups was based on evidence that larger group sizes tend towards a didactic style, limiting the use of audio and often becoming reliant on written contributions by text (Mallon et al. 2023). The regularity of sessions, with attention to scaffolding of tasks, aimed to create a sense of community and, as the module progressed, provide opportunities for interactive learning tasks in breakout rooms. A wide variety of learning activities were included in the workshops for students, for example topic discussions, skills rehearsal and role play practice, applying theory to practice, developing confidence in critical reflection skills, inquiry-based learning tasks with peers and analysis of practice scenarios. Peer feedback gathered during role play in one workshop was a requirement for the e-portfolio. At the end of each block of learning, a consolidation session was positioned, allowing tutors to respond to their individual group and enhance learning in a needs-led tailored way.

Module workshops are facilitated by experienced social work educators who recognize the power of effective role-modelling and can demonstrate high levels of skill in their interactions with students regarding communication, empathy and anti-oppressive practice, such that students experience firsthand from their tutor's interactions what these professional skills can look like. Tutors demonstrate effective communication skills in building rapport and creating the safety needed for sensitive conversations as far as learning about identity, oppression and lived experiences of themselves and others. Workshop attendance and pre and post workshop activities and self-reflections constitute required regulatory skills days and if attendance is missed, an aligned compensatory task is set for the student, not as punishment but to ensure the student has not missed a key aspect of learning.

Students enrolling for module are informed of the expectations of them as learners. Before commencing the module, they know that the expectation is that they use both microphones and video technology to enable active engagement in discussions and tasks and that attendance at the online workshops is mandatory. Early in the module they are introduced to the e-portfolio and a full attendance record is required.

OU students are in a unique position in that they are already working or volunteering in health and social care roles. Again, they are told before enrolling that they will need to evidence a minimum number of days in

relevant social care or social work practice. The premise of action Learning is that people ‘*start to learn with and from each other only when they discover that no-one knows the answer, but all are obliged to find it*’ (Jarvis 2010, p.138). In this vein, the module aimed to provide small group work opportunities which includes some simulated learning, combined with independent and paired tasks to encourage and enables the development of professional curiosity and the sharing of practice experiences between student peers. Whilst the students are already engaged in direct work with their employers and voluntary organisations, and therefore practicing their skills in-situ, the remit of the module workshops is to help the student recognize the detail of the skills behind their practice, build confidence prior to more advanced direct-practice, and reflect on ways that their practice could be developed and enhanced further as they continue to build on the basic foundations of quality practice.

There are assessment tasks throughout the module and notably, an e-portfolio which runs alongside. This e-portfolio records progression of communication and self-reflection skills and collates feedback from the student’s tutor and employer. The voice of people with lived experience of using services is woven throughout the module with each block of learning beginning with original video footage which shares their experiences of accessing social care and social work services. In addition, students are required to gather feedback regarding their communication skills from a service user they have worked with, to include in their e-portfolio.

The contents page of the module's e-portfolio is shared below in Figure 3. It is completed online by students and is their responsibility to gather the evidence together that demonstrates the development of their practice across the timespan of the module. It requires ongoing self-reflective tasks, feedback from service users, peers, tutor and employer, a fully attendance record and an opportunity to think about personal and professional development beyond this module. Students in Wales are required to provide one further reflection from their practice and map their evidence to the standards for practice in their nation.

Figure 3. Contents page of K123 e-portfolio

The learning experience of K123 students is multi-layered. Knowledge, skills and values are ordered carefully to build in complexity as the module evolves, and with the intention that student's confidence and understanding of their own practice develops throughout the course of the module.

3. The results of the re-design

Student performance has significantly improved from performance in the predecessor module, and Figure 3 demonstrates the positive impact the design changes (outlined in Section 2) have had on student retention:

Figure 4. Retention figures comparing re-designed and predecessor modules.

The Student Retention Comparator (Figure 3) indicates the positive impact of these design changes on student retention – with retention increasing from around 75% to 92% in the first year the redesigned module was presented to students. In addition, feedback from all stakeholders involved (students, tutors, external examiners) has been overwhelmingly positive and supports the improvements in the module design, which in turn is seen in increased student satisfaction and success.

The following stakeholder observations are offered here which bring to life the positive nature of the student experience on the redesigned module.

Student feedback

Students have been overwhelmingly positive about the nature of the online skills workshops – reflecting not only on the workshops themselves:

- *The workshops were really good, it was helpful to have some of the concepts explained in a different way so I could understand them more than just through reading the module material.*

Students have also taken time to reflect on the ways in which the skills workshops have supported personal and professional development:

- *I feel that my confidence has grown through understanding the reasons why things are done rather than just knowing how to do them.*
- *Thank you, I've really enjoyed this module and have learnt skills which have improved my practice.*

These students offer a holistic take on the module, and it has been pleasing to note that students appreciate and have benefitted from the holistic approach taken to the redesign of the module:

- *[The module] has provided me with beneficial and effective learning; I feel that the workshops, module materials and peer groups have developed my learning and practice greatly. I reflect on materials that have become embedded within my learning and share pieces of information that I have found useful. I reflect on my learning journey, I have become more aware that development within practice and academic learning is a long one, and requires continuous development, awareness of areas to develop and a willingness to do so. Reflecting often on practice frequently and recognising where I can improve as a professional with social care.*
- *Engaging in workshops and supervised practice has allowed me to develop a varied skill set that enhances my ability to support the diverse and complex needs of the individuals. Academic coursework deepened my understanding of the theory and values that underpin social work practice, and I realised the importance of strong evidence-based practice. Learning about various theories, models and interventions equipped me to critically analyse situations, and to provide appropriate strategies whilst understanding the potential impacts of my actions.*

Tutor feedback

Most tutors transitioned from the predecessor module to the redesigned module, with only a few new tutors joining the team. It has been pleasing to receive feedback from tutors about just how much they have enjoyed, engaged with and learned from the new online nature of module delivery:

- *Overall, I found tutorials lively and interesting - though as the tutor I found the time went very quickly. I would have preferred longer - though I'm not sure how this would have worked for the students.*

Feedback from tutors indicates that they have enjoyed the more facilitative role in the redesigned module and have found teaching and supporting students on this module a very positive experience. A few, after the first presentation, have chosen not to continue and it may be that this more interactive learning experience does not best meet their skillset. In contrast, the module team have had other tutors offering to take second groups of this module:

- *I thought the content of the compulsory workshops was excellent. I thoroughly enjoyed working with the students through these. The greater their involvement, the more they seemed to enjoy the sessions, so the workshop on inquiry-based learning and the one that involved giving peer feedback worked really well. Most of my students had good connectivity and working in the breakout rooms worked well. Most students were happy to use webcams and mics which helped the group to gel.*

Tutors (like the students quoted above) also commented positively on the holistic nature of the redesigned module:

- *The tutorials provided an opportunity for active learning which I think worked well for students as it promoted engagement and helped develop learning and understanding of the module materials.*

External Examiner feedback

The External Examiner for the module has provided equally positive feedback on the module design and delivery and had also observed that the module was being recognised by employers as and having a positive impact on the development of professional practice (highlighted below):

- *The module provided an excellent introduction to Social Care and Social Work practice. The module is extremely well thought out in terms of content and the students' development throughout the module ...and the students developed fundamental knowledge and skills in this module around communication, working with other professionals, being a professional and developing professional practice. **I noted that students have reported that their managers have recognised improvements in student practice, critical thinking, confidence and self-reflection – this is an excellent reflection of the module and its content.***

It is also noteworthy that the students confirmed their positive experience of the module with the External Examiner:

- *...the module content and structure was excellent and... it provided a good foundation to develop his knowledge further. He has found this module beneficial when undertaking further modules. He commented that the teaching materials were clearly set out and structured and easy to follow.*

Stakeholder feedback and improved student retention and completion figures indicate the positive nature of online skills workshop delivery, particularly when combined and integrated into holistic module delivery. All stakeholders have reflected on the ways in which the module offers a highly effective opportunity to engage with, reflect on and develop social work skills online and apply these to practice. Personal and professional confidence seems to grow as a result and, in concrete terms, lays the foundation for ongoing academic and professional development.

The final section of this paper takes a reflective look at what the authors have learned from the experience of developing online skills workshops and implications for the module and for wider academic practice.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

This paper has described the redesigning of a practice learning module that was struggling to retain students and yet was a key foundational module for social work practice. The module redesign aimed to bring first-year social care and social work students together and teach a skills module fully online. The authors have discussed the challenges they faced and how they overcame them through considered learning design. They have also outlined the various elements that have contributed to a successful learning experience that has been reviewed positively by students, tutors, employers, and external examiners alike.

A substantial volume of research discusses or describes the function of simulated learning as a technique of online learning that can replicate real situations and experiences that enhance study (Bay et al., 2021). In preparing students for practice, simulated learning facilitated online has been found to 'connect intellectual knowledge to the spontaneous application of professional skills' (Lee et al., 2021. p.273), which facilitates learning of complex skills through scaffolding (Chernikova et al, 2020). Feedback from various stakeholders, as

shared above, suggests that the design of the module achieves this and allows students to develop a breadth of skills relevant to professional practice in health and social care.

Facilitation is key to the delivery of these online learning experiences. With little exception, research highlights that online facilitation of simulated education is essential (Aul et al, 2021, Blakeman 2019, Brewer & Barr, 2016). The group of tutors who migrated from the predecessor module to the new K123 module have demonstrated both skill and motivation to take up this facilitative role to support learning. Their willingness to embrace a new approach has been much appreciated and students have undoubtedly benefited from the guidance and support of experienced tutors who know social care and social work practice.

There is much to be learned from the design and success of this module that will be of interest to others seeking to improve online module design. Options for consideration are more creative use of AI and extended reality to enable skills practice in safe learning environments. The authors have recently secured additional funding to undertake more forensic scholarship focused on the online interactive workshops to gain insight from both the student and tutor perspectives regarding their experiences. The results of this will be available in Autumn 2025, and the hope is that these will provide evidence of what works and why, such that they might inform further module design at The Open University and might contribute more broadly to the evidence base for the effective pedagogical design of interactive online learning opportunities.

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The Cultivation of Critical Thinking in the Postgraduate Program: "Education Sciences" of the Hellenic Open University: A Case Study

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a significant debate about the importance of critical thinking in education, particularly in higher education and distance learning for adult learners. Important theorists and researchers in the field point out that the process of critical thinking is, perhaps, the most important learning experience of adult learners, who are required to live in a world that becomes more and more complicated and demanding (Pollard, 1987· Ritchhart, 2002· Brookfield, 2004, 2017, et al.). Only specific contexts can facilitate the acquisition and evaluation of critical thinking. In an educational environment, critical thinking skills require self-correction, monitoring to judge the reasonableness of thinking, and reflexivity (Behar-Horenstein & Niu, 2011). This means that studying the dimension of how critically learners support what they say and do in a classroom is a vital element for effective learning. Towards this direction, the evaluation of critical thinking should allow learners to document, prove, and justify their own involvement in critical thinking (Ojha, 2019). In the context of this reflection, the aim of this paper is to investigate how students in the Master program at HOU perceive critical thinking, as well as how this program cultivates critical thinking through specific educational activities. The research was carried out in the MEd "Education Sciences" of the Hellenic Open University and more specifically in the Thematic Unit EKP65: Open and Distance Education. The specific thematic module was chosen because, in its context, students are asked to design distance learning materials that aim to cultivate critical thinking, among other things. Teaching distance education students about its definition and operation is crucial, not only for their own learning but also for their future students. Exploring their perceptions of critical thinking and the application of those skills through the creation of educational materials is very important for the quality of distance education. The research questions posed were: "How do students in this particular module perceive critical thinking?" How do they understand the cultivation of critical thinking within the specific Med module? Finally, how can they evaluate and formulate activities that cultivate critical thinking in the distance learning material? ' The research is a case study of an exploratory nature with a small number of students and aiming at designing a larger scale research based on the results (Gering, 2004). The participants were 63 students (3 departments of the subject area), who were asked to evaluate an activity of distance learning

material in terms of its critical dimension. Distance learning material performs extremely important processes in distance education as it teaches, guides, supports, interprets, activates and organises the learners. The results of the research showed that the students' processing of the concept of critical thinking needs further deepening and reflection in order to make it more concrete and clear. Students appreciate that they cultivate critical thinking through appropriately designed writing tasks. The design of activities that cultivate critical thinking needs considerable training and practice among students.

Keywords: Critical thinking, distance education, educational material, Hellenic Open University

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the debate about the importance of critical thinking in education has taken on a major dimension, especially in higher education and adult education. Prominent theorists and researchers in the field suggest that the process of critical thinking is perhaps the most important learning experience for young and adult learners (Brookfield, 2000, 2012; Freire & Shor, 1987; Schon, 1987; Brookfield, 2000, 2012; Ritchhart, 2002, et al.). As a process, critical thinking involves adults in identifying and examining the assumptions that underpin their thoughts and actions. Only specific contexts can assess critical thinking. This means that the study of the action dimension—what learners do as well as what they say—is crucial. The cultivation of critical thinking should enable learners to document, demonstrate, and justify their own engagement with critical thinking. The Foundation for Critical Thinking (2007) identifies eight critical elements that characterise critical thinking and provide a framework for its approach. These elements include:

- clarity,
- accuracy,
- relevance,
- depth,
- breadth,
- logic,
- significance, and
- importance

(Foundation for Critical Thinking, 2007, as cited in Manousou, 2017).

The objective of this paper is to examine the perceptions of Hellenic Open University (HOU) Master's students regarding critical thinking, as well as the cultivation of critical thinking, through the lens of specific educational activities within the program. The research was conducted in the Master's program in Educational Sciences (EKP) at the Hellenic Open University, with a particular focus on the EKP65 module. The field of study is Open and Distance Education. The specific module was selected for investigation as it requires students to design distance Learning Materials (LM), which are intended to cultivate critical thinking. In this context, it was deemed essential to investigate the following research questions. In the context of the theory of open and distance education (EKP65), the creation of the LM represents a critical and pivotal process, as it constitutes the core of distance education. Distance learning engages in numerous crucial processes, including teaching, guidance, support, interpretation, activation, and organization for learners. Consequently, it is imperative to incorporate activities that cultivate critical thinking.

2. The Critical Thinking

The ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, along with his midwifery method, is a seminal figure in the history of critical thinking. The pre-Socratics also sought truth through the formulation of arguments for the meaningful and in-depth study of opinions, ideas and information. Plato and Aristotle continued and developed this path, leaving a decisive and lasting influence on Western philosophical and scientific thought. This is evident in the works of Erasmus, Francis Bacon, Descartes, Isaac Newton, Montesquieu, Voltaire, Diderot, Sumner, Dewey, Piaget, Mezirow, and others (Kokkos, 2010; Manousou, (2017); Matsangouras (2005, 2007); Mezirow et al. (2006); Paul (1990); Paul, Elder, & Bartell (1997); Russell (1995, pp. 419–25); Trillianos (1997); A common thread runs through all studies on critical thinking: the cultivation of a different way of thinking, the systematic search for arguments, the study and analysis of information, and constant questioning, checking, and reconsideration (Kokkos, 2010; Lipman, 2006:235-242; Matsangouras, 200). 7:77; Mezirow et al. (1990); Paul (1990); Paul, Elder, & Bartell (1997); Russell (1995:419–25); Scriven & Paul (1996); Trillianos (1997), as cited. Manousou (2017) posits that critical thinking ultimately leads to the creation of evidence-based arguments. There is no universally accepted definition of critical thinking. This is due to the fact that many different theorists and researchers have formulated their own definitions of critical thinking. These definitions focus on specific aspects or different contexts where critical thinking is cultivated. As Brookfield (2000) notes, there is no consensus on what it means to learn in a critical way. The term 'critical' is open to interpretation and subject to contestation. The way in which the terms 'critical' or 'criticality' are used reflects the ideologies of the users.

3. Cultivating critical thinking in education

One of the earliest educational theorists to emphasise the importance of critical thinking in education was John Dewey. He defined critical reflection as an active, persistent and careful evaluation of concepts or forms of knowledge based on the arguments that support them and the final results or consequences that they may lead to (Dewey, 1933). Many theorists in adult education have used Dewey's definition of critical thinking as a point of departure for further study of the concept and its adaptation to their own field of inquiry. In the modern era, prominent theorists in the field of adult education have acknowledged critical thinking as a process. This process engages adults in the identification and investigation of the underlying assumptions that shape their thoughts and actions (Mezirow, 1981; Brookfield, 1987, 1995, 2012, et al.). Fundamental beliefs about the world and our place within it, commonly taken for granted and not explicitly stated, are known as assumptions. Assumptions imbue our identity and actions with meaning and purpose. In many ways, our assumptions inform our identity. Our cognitive processes, verbal expressions, and actions heavily rely on assumptions about the world's functioning and the standards that define appropriate and moral actions. However, we often fail to acknowledge these assumptions as provisional understandings. Uncritically accepted assumptions often form the basis of ideas and actions considered commonsense and conventional wisdom. In some cases, individuals may accept the judgement of a person, institution, or authority that they either trust or fear, without questioning it. When we think critically, we begin to investigate these assumptions for the evidence and experiences that inform them. Nevertheless, the assessment of critical thinking is dependent upon the specific context under consideration. This therefore suggests that the examination of this theme in higher education as a dimension of action—encompassing both the actions and the discourse of students—is of the utmost importance. In the context of such a study, critical thinking is defined as the capacity of an individual to comprehend a range of perspectives and to assess the information received in a logical manner. The capacity to solve problems and to process, evaluate and source information is considered a requisite element

of the educational process (Ennis, 1993). Specifically, the following skills are crucial in modern education and are linked to the development of critical thinking:

1. Information Analysis
2. Problem solving
3. Developing critical communication
4. Dealing with different views.
5. Promoting improvisation
6. Processing and interacting with parts of a problem (Behar-Horenstein & Niu, 2011).

4. The cultivation of critical thinking in higher education

The cultivation of critical thinking in education, and especially in higher education, is an important and long-standing issue. However, as the data are constantly changing at the socio-educational level, it seems that a study of all or many of the factors is difficult to carry out in a comprehensive manner (Behar-Horenstein and Niu, 2011, Huber, & Kuncel, 2016). There are several studies of different types of interventions with varying durations that show evidence of improving critical thinking in education; this is not a generalized approach (Huber & Kuncel, 2016). Morris (2017) argues that critical dialogue is perhaps the most critical survival skill. Not only is critical dialogue a communication skill, but it also serves as a group-collaborative process necessary for civilized conversations in a world characterized by diversity, and it is crucial that values like respect guide this process. It's worth noting his point: "If we teach students how to participate in diverse groups and how to consider "big ideas" and difficult issues in college, they will have skills when they graduate that will remain long after the skills they learned for their first job have aged; they will be leaders in political discourse. Our communities and workplaces need nothing less." This view is in line with Behar-Horenstein and Niu (2011), who argue that cultivating critical thinking skills to form responsible citizens is essential in today's complex society and should be a goal of higher education. The cultivation of critical thinking and critical dialogue requires a shift in the educational process that emphasises mainly on content matter rather than the skills required. As Horenstein and Niu (2011) state, a shift "from what to think to how to think" is required and consequently a shift in thinking about teaching paradigms. This perspective aligns with the argument put forth by Behar-Horenstein and Niu (2011), who posit that the cultivation of critical thinking skills is crucial for the formation of responsible citizens in the context of today's complex society. They further contend that this should be a fundamental objective of higher education. The cultivation of critical thinking and critical dialogue necessitates a transformation in the educational process—one that prioritizes the development of skills over the transmission of content. As Horenstein and Niu (2011) posit, a shift "from what to think to how to think" is imperative, thereby necessitating a shift in the very paradigm of teaching. In their study, Behar-Horenstein and Niu (2011) reviewed 42 studies that employed three published protocols to assess critical thinking skills: the Cornell Critical Thinking Test (CCTT), the Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal (WGCTA), and the California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST). The researchers found these instruments to be highly challenging to measure. They emphasize the importance of using a range of tools to assess critical thinking skills, including open-ended questions, essays, interviews, and observations. etc. These protocols, or others created by researchers for the same purpose, are designed to enhance the possibility of identifying the factors influencing the development of critical thinking. Nevertheless, it was found that surveys of longer duration demonstrate a higher probability of detecting evident or even statistically significant development of critical thinking in trainees. In each case, it is of extreme importance to consider and control for potential threats to the validity of the results, such as maturation, context, background, and their impact or influence. Behar-

Horenstein and Niu (2011) In a broader study of critical thinking skills, we note that according to Matsangoura (2007, p. 138). "Critical teaching is any form of teaching which, in a context of active student participation, develops activities of data collection and processing that mobilise students' higher cognitive functions and lead to the formation of concepts, judgements, generalisations, processes, and patterns of interpretation of the world". The cultivation of critical thinking skills is directly linked to the educational teaching process, whether it is face-to-face-conventional or distance and is an important and timeless goal that is both linked to the purpose of education and even in the Greek constitution (Manousou, 2017). In addition, in higher education, students more often write scientific papers, where they analyze, evaluate the methodology, findings and conclusions of research papers, which they use as bibliographic sources. Assessment of critical thinking should allow learners to document, demonstrate, and justify their own engagement in critical thinking. In viewing learning from the outside, instructors may miss entirely the critical dimensions of students' thought and practice. Critical thinking can often be best assessed by one's peers, who function as critical mirrors.

5. Cultivating critical thinking in adult education and distance higher education

One of the ways to cultivate critical thinking in adult education is to train learners in critical analysis of texts. According to Brookfield (1996), the goal of critical textual analysis is to identify, in the analyzed text, the dominant cultural values and hegemonic processes that are embedded in practice and reflected in adult education. The variables particularly examined are social class, gender and race. The critical analysis of the texts raises questions of methodology (e.g. to what extent the central ideas of the text - the key assumptions - are based on documented empirical evidence), experience-based questions (e.g. what kind of connections and inconsistencies do you observe between the descriptions of adult education processes and practices contained in the text under review and our own experiences as adult educators or learners), communicative questions (e.g. which voices are most audible in the text under examination / to what extent does the text use a specialised vocabulary that is at a distance from the usual language of trainers and learners), and political questions (e.g. whose social and political interests seem to be served by the text or does the text contribute to the cultivation of conditions for taking initiatives for collective action to change and improve reality)? (Brookfield, 1996). The critical analysis of texts is linked to the critical approach to the educational material as well as its construction. One method of cultivating critical thinking in adult education is to provide learners with training in the critical analysis of texts. As Brookfield (1996) posits, the objective of critical textual analysis is to discern the prevailing cultural values and hegemonic processes that are intrinsic to practice and reflected in adult education. The variables under examination are social class, gender and race. The critical analysis of the texts raises questions of methodology; for example, to what extent are the central ideas of the text, that is to say the key assumptions, based on documented empirical evidence? It also raises experience-based questions, for example, what kind of connections and inconsistencies do you observe between the descriptions of adult education processes and practices contained in the text under review and our own experiences as adult educators or learners? Finally, it raises communicative questions. Such questions may include: which voices are most audible in the text under examination, to what extent the text employs a specialized vocabulary that is distant from the typical language of trainers and learners, and whether the text serves the interests of any particular social or political group. (Brookfield, 1996). The critical analysis of texts is linked to the critical approach to the educational material

as well as its construction. In distance education (modern and asynchronous), the cultivation of critical thinking is contingent upon a number of factors, with overall pedagogical planning and the formation of educational material representing two of the most significant. In distance education, the effectiveness of the educational process is contingent upon the design of appropriate educational material. The creation of digital and printed educational material is subject to specific pedagogical standards, which demand considerable preparation, knowledge and experience. Distance learning material is designed in accordance with the principles of clarity, explanation, interest, learner support, active participation, action, feedback, self-regulation and self-evaluation. The educational material includes a teacher who is available to instruct students and assist them in developing skills and acquiring knowledge. In other words, the material addresses the "what," "how" and "why" of learning in an engaging and interesting manner (Lionarakis, 2010; Manousou & Lionarakis, 2011). Distance learning material refers to any medium, resource or content used to deliver/support distance learning. This may include e-learning materials, multimedia, online platforms, electronics, educational games, interactive courses, and other educational tools that enable distance learning. Characteristics of Distance Learning Materials are (Manousou, 2008 & Hartofilika, 2011):

- User friendly: Learning Material is essential to be user-friendly.
- Clarity: Be characterized by the clarity of language in all its parts, especially in the instructions to learners.
- Interactivity: Should include elements that contribute to and enhance interaction with users e.g. activities, self-assessment exercises, etc.
- Flexibility: It is important that the LM is not linear but provides alternative routes that help learners to follow their own path.
- The polymorphism: LM should include various forms of content presentation and utilize pedagogically appropriate selected forms, media.
- The well structure: The LM must be well structured, in discrete sections whose structure is understandable to users.
- The aesthetics: The LM is necessary to be designed with aesthetic standards that are appropriate for the target group, with characteristics of simplicity, attractiveness, to attract the interest of the learners in order to engage them more in the process pleasantly without exaggeration.
- Accessibility: LM is extremely important to provide accessibility opportunities for all learners regardless of their particular learning or physical characteristics, e.g. visual impairment, dyslexia, etc.

The application of critical thinking in Distance Education and especially in educational material is effective when appropriate activities, case studies, etc. are designed, which include in their objectives scenarios that support the cultivation of critical thinking individually and collaboratively (Rahayu & Sapriati, 2018; Tourkohoriti, & Manousou, 2012). Research by Xu et al (2023 regarding a meta-analysis based on empirical literature, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications indicated that collaborative problem solving is the most commonly used strategy for teaching critical thinking as well as the most effective. As far as distance education is concerned, one of the most important elements is the development of appropriate educational materials that promote critical thinking.

6. Method

The purpose of this study was to investigate the students' views on critical thinking and the ways of cultivating critical thinking through specific educational activities related to the educational material.

The research was carried out in the Postgraduate Program «Education Sciences" of the Hellenic Open University and more specifically in the Module EKP65: Open and Distance Education. The specific subject was chosen, as in the context of this module students are asked to design distance learning materials, which aims, among other things, to cultivate critical thinking. In this context, it was considered interesting and crucial to find out how the students of this particular subject area perceive critical thinking? How do they assess that it is cultivated in the context of the Postgraduate Program "Education Sciences" and of this particular THE and finally how can they evaluate and formulate activities that cultivate critical thinking in the Distance Learning Materials (DLM). The creation of LM is a critical and extremely important process, as it is the heart of distance education. Distance LM performs many and extremely important processes as it teaches, guides, supports, interprets, activates and organizes the learner(s) (Manousou, 2008). For all these reasons, it is necessary to include activities that foster critical thinking.

The way distance learning students are taught what it is and how it works is crucial, both for themselves as students and for their future students. Exploring their perceptions of critical thinking and the application of critical thinking skills through EY is crucial for the quality of distance education. The students in our sample were well-versed in activity evaluation, having already completed a third written assignment where they assessed a student's LM. Additionally, the subject of critical thinking held significance for them, as they were required to prepare the Fourth (4th) Written Work, which focused on the creation of educational material and the formulation of related activities. In this context, the objectives of the research were: to capture students' perceptions of the cultivation of critical thinking.

- To find out how the students perceive that critical thinking is cultivated in the context of the specific postgraduate program (HOU/EKP).
- Evaluate an activity in terms of the development of critical thinking
- Collaboratively transform in an online environment (Webex breakout sessions) an activity to contribute to the cultivation of critical thinking

The research questions were the following:

- How do students on this particular module perceive critical thinking?
- How do they perceive that it is cultivated in the context of the specific module of the Med?
- How can they evaluate and formulate or transform activities that cultivate critical thinking in the distance learning material?

The research is a case study of an exploratory nature with a small number of students and aims at designing larger scale research based on the results (Gering, 2004). Out of a total of 96 students, 64 students from four departments within the subject area participated in the research. It is known that participation in the SCOM is not compulsory. Specifically, students from the following departments participated: HLE 41: 9. HLE 42: 18. HLE45: 18. HLE48: 19.

7. The Results

1st Question: The definition of critical thinking

In the first question, students were asked to answer the question of how they themselves define critical thinking. The answers provided are indicative and are categorized by department. -In the first section (HLE41) all 9 students defined critical thinking as a process of evaluating and deepening information, knowledge and experiences. Indicative responses are:

"Critical thinking is the ability of a person to examine information with filters based on their experience and existing knowledge."

"Critical thinking is a cognitive skill that requires a deeper understanding and prioritization of knowledge and experience."

The second section (HLE42) was answered by 18 students. These students also define critical thinking as a process of evaluating information, but they also mention the involvement of emotion and experience in drawing conclusions on a critically examined topic. Indicative responses are:

"Critical thinking is the evaluation and deepening of information and stimuli we receive."

"Critical thinking is the ability of an individual to process the information received and evaluate it to create their own opinion. It is the most basic way of removing stereotypes."

"Critical thinking is the evaluation of information through thought. It filters logical and emotional stimuli and comes to a conclusion."

The third section (HLE 45) was also answered by 18 students. In all responses, the definition of critical thinking mentioned the evaluation of information, while 12 also mentioned data analysis and free expression based on experiences and emotions.

"Critical thinking is the process of evaluating a piece of knowledge, an information that is offered to us."

"Critical thinking is the function by which we judge and evaluate the information we receive, accept, modify or reject by formulating our reasoning."

"Critical thinking is the free expression of my opinions and reasoning based on my experiences and feelings."

The fourth section (HLE 48) was answered by 19 students. In their answers, in addition to defining critical thinking as a process of evaluating information, there are references to the connection of this process with the wider socio-political context. The answers indicate that critical thinking equips us with the ability to analyze, understand, and evaluate the ideas presented.

"An individual uses critical thinking to evaluate the information they receive."

"Critical thinking pertains to the ability to differentiate between essential and unnecessary aspects of our lives, especially during a period when we are forming fictitious needs."

2nd Question: The cultivation of critical thinking in the Postgraduate Programme "Educational Science (EKP-Module EKP65)"

In the second phase of the survey, we asked students to respond in four groups to the following question: *"In your opinion, does your postgraduate program cultivate critical thinking, and if so, how?"*

-In the first part (HLE 41) the students answered that critical thinking is cultivated, especially in EKP65 and EKP64, through literature review and searching for sources, through the preparation of written assignments, but also in the process of Student Consultation Online Meetings (SCOM), through discussions and activities. Students particularly emphasized the role of the Faculty Advisor in the SCOM process. Indicative

responses are: "Cultivated, especially in the last 2 assignments of EKP65 with key questions that are of concern, such as the integration of AI in education and in EKP64 regarding the integration of art in educational programs for vulnerable groups."

"It is cultivated through the various themes and through the exchange of views between students and teachers."

"Critical thinking is developed through module work and dialogue in the CSDs".

"It is cultivated in different ways. Discussion in the forum, participation in workshops, activities within the SCOM and in the assignments".

-In the second section (HLE42) the students replied

"Critical thinking is cultivated in the Module EKP65. Specifically, through assignments that require critical analysis and synthesis of information. Still, through discussions and collaborative activities".

"Critical thinking is cultivated through assigned tasks, feedback and fruitful dialogue, activities and collaboration with fellow students and the Tutor".

"Cultivated when given the right stimulus mainly by the Tutor". "Through the process of assignments, discussion, knowledge seeking and SCOM, critical thinking is cultivated to a certain extent".

-In the third section (HLE45) students agreed that critical thinking in the master's is cultivated through written assignments, searching and evaluating sources, and educational material. Furthermore, they acknowledged that not all modules cultivate critical thinking in the same manner. Indicative responses are:

"Critical thinking is cultivated through the written assignments, where theory is applied in practice."

"Critical thinking is cultivated through the assignments and discussions in the SCOM. "We believe that it is also cultivated through searching for appropriate literature references, but also through the written assignments, which also require our own perspective on the topics under consideration".

-The fourth section (HLE48) students answered that critical thinking in the Master is cultivated through written assignments, searching and evaluating sources, and educational material. In addition, they indicated that it is not cultivated in all modules the same way. Indicative responses are:

"Critical thinking is cultivated in the Master through a variety of sources, approaches and stimuli. It is up to each individual to make use of this opportunity'.

"Our critical thinking is promoted through the teaching material and cultivated through discussions with tutors in SCOM ".

"Critical thinking is cultivated in the postgraduate program through practices such as writing assignments."

"In some modules yes to a satisfactory degree, in other modules to a lesser degree. There is a search for many scientific articles, writing many papers with many parameters and criteria".

3rd Question: The Evaluation of Learning Material in Distance Education

In the third phase of the survey, students were asked to evaluate an activity from educational material and make suggestions for its improvement. The activity was - Comment - as far as the cultivation of critical thinking is concerned - on the following research concerning the use of social networks in young people "How social media affect the mental health of young people" "Social media and its use have been linked to depression, particularly among teenage girls.

Figure 1: Man at the centre of the modern world

However, a new study suggests the issue may be more complex than experts believe. The research, published last Tuesday in the journal *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, involved interviews with around 10,000 teenagers aged 13 to 16 in England. Researchers found that social media can harm girls' mental health by increasing their exposure to bullying and reducing their sleep and physical activity. Our results suggest that Social media itself does not cause harm, but that frequent use can disrupt activities that have a positive impact on mental health, such as sleep and exercise, while increasing young people's exposure to harmful content, particularly the negative experience of cyber-bullying," study co-author Russell Viner, of the UCL Great Ormond Street

Institute of Child Health" said in a statement. Source : <https://www.cnn.gr/focus/story/187538/pos-ta-social-media-epirezoy-n-tin-psyxiki-ygeia-ton-neo>

The text was accompanied by the image below, with no comment or link to the text

Students worked in groups by section to answer the following questions

- In your opinion, does the above activity foster critical thinking?
- Is it comprehensive? What are the positive and negative aspects of it?
- What changes would you suggest?

The groups presented their work to the plenary after having synthesized their views into short, concise texts. For example Group 1 of HLE41 reported:

"The activity fosters critical thinking by distinguishing the existence of social media from the way it is used. In order for the activity to be considered complete, the sample would need to be larger and with different theoretical approaches. Negatives: few questions, general question. Positive elements: targeted research on mental health. Deepen research into how we choose to use Social Media." In the 2nd Group of HLE45 & HLE48 it was reported: "Cultivates critical thinking partially and not in depth.

The presentation of the activity is incomplete and brief and does not provide guidance to students on where to focus. Furthermore, there are no individual questions. Positive: it asks for the student's opinion and is not a literature search; It is familiar and familiar to the student. Negatives: There are limitations to the research and the findings are not presented in detail. Changes: Specific questions, more information and data" The 3rd group HLE42 records: "Critical thinking is only cultivated to a certain extent. Time of attendance and content factors are mentioned which determine poor or no use. Short text, not comprehensive. Why do this activity. Promote the use of social media for information and expression of emotions. *Only one impact is described and mainly on girls*".

Summarizing from the students' responses, it can be seen that several of them approached the training material in a uniform way. The evaluation criteria differ from group to group; however, there are similarities.

The first group of HLE41 students believe this activity cultivates critical thinking by distinguishing the existence of social media from their use. However, they feel that the activity is not comprehensive because the research sample is small and does not present different theoretical approaches to this topic.

Students in the first group of HLE42 believe the activity lacks critical thinking and is overly broad, yet it contains elements that could benefit from additional research.

Students in the first group of HLE45 and HLE48 consider that it fosters critical thinking, does not delve deeper, and does not identify further problems.

Students in the second group of HLE41 feel that this activity cultivates critical thinking because it brings to the forefront the negative use of digital media and social media. However, they believe that the activity only skims the surface, failing to delve into the underlying causes and consequences of the phenomenon. Also, these students also consider that the activity is not comprehensive because it does not have an estimated time of implementation, does not mention its usefulness and does not have an indicative answer.

Students in the second group of HLE42, quite rightly identify major flaws in the framing of the activity that it is generic and missing important elements in its distance framing. They do not identify that the picture is disjointed. They do not suggest an alternative. Students in the second group of HLE45 & HLE48, appreciate that it fosters critical thinking partially and not in depth, analyses the activity more systematically, identifies significant errors in the formulation and suggests improvements such as more questions and analysis.

The third group of HLE41 considers that this activity does not foster critical thinking, as it does not present a variety of opinions and results in order to have a dialogue leading to a conclusion. They also believe that the activity lacks comprehensiveness, as it does not provide students with the chance to develop and articulate their own opinions in a thorough manner. Students in the third group of HLE45 and HLE48 acknowledge that the activity partially fosters critical thinking, but they also recognize its lack of comprehensiveness, prefer to focus and comment on the topic rather than the activity, and do not offer suggestions for improvement. The fourth group of HLE41 believes that this activity fails to foster critical thinking because it doesn't equip students with the necessary information to exercise their critical thinking. The groups offer limited suggestions for enhancing this activity to foster more comprehensive critical thinking. They primarily concentrate on presenting additional research with divergent results, aiming to foster critical thinking via discussion and interaction. Students in the fourth group of HLE42 identify that the verb is generic, that there are missing elements and very importantly, that the picture is not relevant to the topic of the activity. Students in the fourth group of HLE45 & HLE48 identify shortcomings but focus on the content of the activity, i.e., social media rather than the broader elements of the content of the research and not the comments in terms of critical thinking (metacognition). We find that 3 out of 4 groups focus on the content of the text and not on the issues it raises, the questions it asks, the concerns it highlights. Only extremely general questions are the focus of the activity. 50% of the participating students found the question to be general, but they did not proceed to transform it into something more qualitative and meaningful. They also did not use metacognitive skills to evaluate the quality of the activity itself.

8. Conclusion

This paper presented a small, exploratory study on the cultivation of critical thinking at the graduate level at HOU. The survey involved 64 students out of a total of 96 from four departments of the Open and Distance Education Module (EKP65). The results of the survey are not representative; however, they are important for the design of a larger study on such

a crucial topic as the development of critical thinking by students who will mainly work in education and teach future citizens. In this specific TC, the quality of distance education heavily depends on students' understanding of it, its functioning, the cultivation of critical thinking, and its application through LM. Distance learning performs many and extremely important processes as it teaches, guides, supports, interprets, activates and organises learners. For all these reasons, it is essential to include activities that foster critical thinking. We will present the key findings from the survey, broken down by question, in the following section. Regarding the definition of the concept of critical thinking, the majority of students answered that critical thinking is about evaluating information and knowledge, analysing and comparing them objectively, without mentioning any criteria of objectivity. Individual responses referred to comparing different sources and analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information. In three cases, students link the cultivation of critical thinking to the wider socio-political context (Brookfield, 2012), referring to critical thinking as a tool for combating stereotypes and for dealing with the fictitious needs created by the current times. Student reports also shed light on the role of emotions in the development of critical thinking, emphasizing that emotions, not just reason, shape opinion formation. In conclusion, **the students in our study define critical thinking as a process of evaluating information without referring to evaluation criteria, and the majority also do not expand on linking the concept to the broader socio-political context in which they live.** In response to the second question, "In your opinion, is critical thinking cultivated in your postgraduate program, and if so, in what ways?" each student responded individually. **Most of their responses highlight that the Master's program primarily fosters critical thinking through the composition of scientific essays, necessitating a critical analysis of literature. Additionally, they mention other methods, such as engaging in group discussions and studying educational materials. However, they report that it is not cultivated the same in all modules and two responded that it is not cultivated. Some students point out the important role that the Tutor has in cultivating the critical thinking of the learners through his feedback on the written assignments and the topics he raises for discussion (e.g., AI), provoking dialogue.** Regarding the third question, does the activity provided by the training material foster critical thinking? While it offers some benefits, such as an engaging topic and a contemporary article, it also presents **several drawbacks. These include a general question that only requests a comment, a lack of depth, and the absence of essential elements such as purpose, indicative time, deeper questions, and comparisons. Generally, the groups express a divided view of the students. Students in the first two groups consider that this activity fosters critical thinking while students in the other two groups have a negative attitude. Those who believe that this particular educational material activity fosters critical thinking justify their beliefs by separating the existence of social media from its use and highlighting its negative aspects. Those who consider that this particular educational material activity does not foster critical thinking justify it on the grounds that it does not present results from other research, different opinions, etc., in order to generate critical dialogue. However, all the students in the four groups make critical remarks on this activity concerning the sample of the survey, the type of questions, the lack of reference to the time of its implementation, the lack of deepening of the causes and consequences of the phenomenon. Finally, on the crucial question of what changes they would suggest, we find that very few groups of students had suggestions. In particular only 2 groups mentioned that there could have been comparisons between different articles and more questions. In general, suggestions for changes to this activity to make it more comprehensive in terms of cultivating critical thinking are limited and focused on providing a second survey with contrasting findings so that through debate and dialogue critical thinking can be cultivated. It is worth noting that many groups focused on the content of**

the article rather than the type of activities. Also, there was only 1 comment on the accompanying image, the editing and use of which were not included in the activity's delivery. The processing of the above material could be linked to a lack of metacognitive skills; however, the limited time in the groups should be taken into account. At the end, the results of the research showed that the students' processing of the concept of critical thinking needs further deepening and reflection in order to make it more concrete and clearer for them. What needs to be pointed out here is that the teaching of critical thinking in education is necessary to start from the beginning of formal education, horizontally in all curricular subjects and not to be transferred to the level of postgraduate studies. In other words, a culture of critical thinking needs to be cultivated throughout education (Ritchhart, 2002). In terms of the cultivation of critical thinking in this postgraduate program, students appreciate that this is mainly through the written assignments and less through the activities implemented in the SCOMs and the collaboration with the tutors. From the evaluation of the activity of the teaching material, which in essence meant putting critical thinking into practice, it was found that the design as well as the evaluation of EM activities that foster critical thinking remains an area where students still need significant training and practical applications.

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Leadership, Strategy & Future Trends

Mapping the current landscape of digital competences

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Abstract

The efforts to implement digital competences in higher education (HE) continue. But what digital competences should be in focus for implementation efforts? The picture is more muddled than ever with a multitude of concepts competing for attention, e.g., computational thinking (CT), generative AI and data literacy. Is it possible to map current concepts, thus providing stakeholders with an overview that makes it easier to navigate the field? This paper presents and discusses the results of the initial phases of a design-based implementation research (Fishman et al., 2013) study. The original purpose was to integrate CT into subjects and study programmes in the humanities and social sciences at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) to support student employability. When applying for funding, CT was in focus, however, conversations with stakeholders revealed that several other projects were being launched. One concerns the integration of generative AI and another the integration of domain-specific digital competences. To avoid a situation in which projects would compete for stakeholder attention, it was agreed to engage in a mapping exercise to find synergies and connect the projects to enhance implementation. Based on these considerations and using digital competences as the generic term, the following research questions were formulated for the initial phases:

- *What digital competences should we support students in the humanities and social sciences in developing?*
- *How can we provide stakeholders with a meaningful overview of these competences?*

The mapping exercise is based on literature studies of existing frameworks (e.g. Binkley et al., 2012; Vuorikari et al., 2022) and conceptualisations (diSessa, 2001; Ng et al., 2021), and on conversations with stakeholders taking a co-design approach (Cumbo & Selwyn, 2022). Initially, three overall categories of digital competences were identified: digital mindset, digital study practices and digital domain-specific practices. The latter building on actual tools used in relevant professions and actual digital competences needed. These three categories were column headings in the first draft of the tool and served the purpose of facilitating discussions on the context for implementation. The five competence areas from the DigComp 2.2 framework (Vuorikari et al., 2022) were added later as rows in the tool to facilitate discussion on specific competences within each context.

The mapping tool was developed through three iterations with feedback from stakeholders and serves several important functions as a boundary object. It provides an overview of the digital competences that stakeholders must focus on, and it connects specific digital competences with meaningful overall categories. Hopefully this will make the process of working with digital competences more concrete and manageable. With the mapping tool, digital competences that are already integrated in subjects and study programmes can be identified. This can then form the starting point for locating the digital competences that should be the focus for future implementation efforts.

Developing a mapping tool is neither simple, nor straightforward. To build ownership, stakeholders must be involved, but this also means being respectful of and attempting to reconcile divergent views. However, it is a worthwhile effort since the exercise helps match expectations.

Keywords: digital competences, humanities, social sciences, design-based implementation research, codesign, institutional leadership, digital transformation

1. Introduction

Advances in digital technology are not only making an impact on job tasks, processes and roles in organisations, they are also setting the agenda for strategy development in HE (Jørgensen, 2019). Today the agenda is driven by generative AI (see e.g. Chiu, 2024) in particular. Initially banning the use of generative AI due to concerns that it will compromise academic integrity (see e.g. Wang, 2023), many universities are now rolling out plans for its implementation (McDonald et al., 2024). The main purpose is to stay relevant and ensure that students have the digital competences needed to be employable upon graduation (Chiu, 2024; Jørgensen, 2019). The focus on implementing digital competences is not new, but generative AI presents a burning platform (Kurtz et al., 2024) that has led some universities to switch strategies from implementation via funding of pilot projects and experiments undertaken by enthusiasts to broad implementation via formal strategies backed up by quality assurance measures to follow up on progress.

However, it is a challenge to decide what digital competences to focus on when developing strategies. The picture is more muddled than ever with a multitude of concepts competing for attention, e.g., computational thinking (CT) (Grover & Pea, 2018), AI literacy (Ng et al., 2021) and data literacy (Walker et al., 2019) to name a few. On the one hand, if narrowly planning for the implementation of generative AI, we overlook the need to build capacity in organisations to take in new technologies, and we will continue struggling to keep up. It is therefore an overriding concern to conceive of digital competences in broad terms that do not get outdated overnight. On the other hand, the notion of digital competences must be made concrete for stakeholders to set direction and clearly communicate the goals of implementation. A clear conception of digital competences is needed to provide stakeholders with an overview that makes it easier to navigate the field.

This paper presents and discusses the results of the initial phases of a design-based implementation research (Fishman et al., 2013) study. The original purpose was to integrate CT into subjects and study programmes in the humanities and social sciences at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) to support student employability. When applying for funding, CT was in focus, however, conversations with stakeholders at the outset of the study revealed that several other projects were being launched. One concerns the integration of generative AI and another the integration of domain-specific digital competences. To avoid a situation in which projects would compete for stakeholder attention and potentially create confusion, it was agreed to engage in a mapping exercise to find synergies and connect the projects to enhance implementation. Based on these considerations and using digital competences as the generic term, the following research questions were formulated for the initial phases of the study:

- *What digital competences should we support students in the humanities and social sciences in developing?*
- *How can we provide stakeholders with a meaningful overview of these competences?*

To be transparent about my own role and positioning in this project, I will provide a brief account of my background. I'm employed as an Assistant Professor at the Department of Design, Media and Educational Science at The Faculty of Humanities at SDU and affiliated with the university's Centre for Learning Computational Thinking. Besides conducting the research described in this paper, I teach subjects such as IT Pedagogy and IT Didactics in Organisations at the department's humanistic IT study programs. Before, my present position, I worked as an e-learning consultant at the SDU Centre for Teaching and Learning (SDU CTL)

for 12 years, undertaking competence development of teachers and supporting them in developing and delivering blended, flipped and online learning.

1.1 Outline of the paper

First the key concepts employed in this paper will be presented and discussed in the Theoretical framework section. This concerns the conceptualisation of digital competences and the notion of mapping exercise and mapping tool. Following that the research approach and the methods applied will be accounted for in the Materials and methods section. The Findings section will report on the mapping exercise and present the different versions of the mapping tool that was developed. The research approach, as well as the methods applied, will be the object of reflection in the Discussion and concluding remarks section that will also touch upon lessons learned. The paper ends with considerations regarding limitations and implications. First, the components of the theoretical framework will be outlined and discussed.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Conceptualising digital competences

There are many frameworks and conceptualisations of the type of competences that students, teachers, citizens and employees need in today's digitised society. Some conceptualisations are narrow in scope, e.g. computational literacy (diSessa, 2001) and AI literacy (Ng et al., 2021) and thus might be less helpful with respects to identifying a conceptualisation of digital competences that is broad enough to be applicable in the long-term as new technologies are developed and become available. Furthermore, the notion of literacy, defined by diSessa (2001) as "*a socially widespread patterned deployment of skills and capabilities in a context of material support (that is, an exercise of material intelligence) to achieve valued intellectual ends*" (p. 19) seems less helpful with respects to mapping specific digital competences that students should develop to be employable. Instead, this paper will turn to more concrete frameworks that outline specific skills or competences that are seen as necessary today.

Below, two examples of such frameworks are outlined to illustrate different approaches and foci. One framework is Binkley et al.'s (2012) *Twenty-first century skills* that encompass four groups of skills labelled Ways of thinking, Ways of working, Tools for working and Living in the world. In the Tools for working category, we find information literacy and ICT literacy. Binkley et al. (2012) have analysed 12 frameworks, that they deemed relevant, to arrive at their four groups of skills with the end goal of transforming assessment methods in education by proposing a 'next generation' model for assessing twenty-first century skills. To explain the concept of skills, the so-called KSAVE model is used. It covers *Knowledge, Skills*, i.e. abilities, skills and processes and *Attitudes, Values and Ethics* that include behaviours and aptitude (Binkley et al., 2012, p. 37).

Binkley et al.'s (2012) framework draws attention to the fact that other skills than simply mastering digital technologies are needed, since some tasks that are today performed by people will be taken over by technology. These other skills are creativity, innovation, critical thinking and problem solving, e.g. However, a critique that can be levied against Binkley et al.'s framework is that digital competences in the form of information literacy and ICT literacy are isolated in a category of their own, obscuring the fact that digital technologies have an impact on the other three categories in the framework. Thus, this seems to be a less helpful way of conceptualising digital competences.

Another framework is the well-known EU framework *Digital competence framework for citizens*, also called DigComp (Vuorikari et al., 2022). Digital competence is described as one of the key competences for lifelong learning (European Commission, 2019), and the framework consists of the five competence areas: Information

and data literacy, Communication and collaboration, Digital content creation, Safety and Problem solving. Digital competence is defined as “the confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for learning, at work, and for participation in society” (European Commission, 2019, p. 10). Further the notion of competence is described as a combination of *knowledge*, i.e. concepts and facts, of *skills* and of *attitudes* which is interpreted as a disposition or a mindset to act (Vuorikari et al., 2022). DigComp describes different levels of competence for each competence area and details knowledge, skills and attitudes for each of these levels. It is thus quite comprehensive. Furthermore, it has been used and evaluated in many contexts which has resulted in the extended second version, DigComp 2.2 which is described here.

Whereas the Binkley et al. (2012) framework is concerned with assessing competences in an educational context, DigComp 2.2 has an outward looking perspective that encompasses learning and work as well as participation in society. Thus, it overcomes the weakness found in the Binkley et al. (2012) framework because it considers digital competences in areas of application instead of compartmentalising them. However, both frameworks agree that competence is concerned with knowledge and skills as well as attitudes. It can be challenging, though, to apply DigComp 2.2 in a HE context. The framework can be unwieldy because of its comprehensiveness and level of detail that all point towards becoming a competent citizen in today’s digitized world. The framework must thus be translated and adapted to appear relevant and useful in a HE context.

As the two frameworks outlined above illustrate, both *skills* as well as *competences* are used in the literature on digital competences or 21st century skills. According to Voogt et al. (2013), skills is the more common term in American research, whereas the term competences or competencies is used in Europe. In the present paper, the term competence is used to denominate a person’s “realisation of her skills and knowledge in response to the demands of the given situation” (Dohn, 2018, p. 11) which is in line with the European Commission’s (2019) definition of digital competence, cf. above, which is also adopted here.

2.2 The concept of mapping tools and their functions

A mapping tool is understood as a boundary object (Leigh Star, 2010) that can serve different purposes in the different phases of a study and an implementation project. The word *boundary* denotes “a shared space” and boundary objects “form the boundaries between groups through flexibility and shared structure – they are the stuff of action” (Leigh Star, 2010, p. 603). Boundary objects can take different forms and need not appear as tangible things. However, in this paper, a boundary object is understood as an external representation, a shareable object of thought, that provides a persistent referent (Kirsh, 2010) to the issue being discussed, in this case digital competences. Boundary objects can provide a shared language and support the matching of expectations: what digital competences are we talking about? They can provide an overview that makes it easier to navigate the issue and makes coordination and shared sense-making possible. Ideally, mapping tools should be developed in collaboration with stakeholders in iterations where prototypes are discussed, negotiated and revised based on feedback and input. Such a process will allow for the incorporation of perspectives from diverse stakeholder groups which will support ownership and implementation. A mapping tool can thus function as implementation support, cf. the Materials and methods section below.

A mapping tool should be sufficiently concrete to frame implementation efforts and set direction, but it should also be open enough to allow for local interpretation to fit the very diverse subject domains typically found at a university and to build local ownership. This is a matter of granularity, interpretive flexibility and the dynamics of translating back and forth between global and local levels of an organisation (Leigh Star, 2010).

The concept of ‘mapping exercise’ is used in this paper to describe the initial, collaborative development of a mapping tool to provide a joint overview of digital competences. However, the mapping tool is also envisaged

as a tool for mapping the digital competences already integrated in subjects and study programs with a view to identifying gaps that can be the object of future implementation efforts. Thus, mapping exercises as well as mapping tools as boundary objects can play important roles throughout an implementation process. Next, the research approach and the methods applied in this study will be described and discussed.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Design-based implementation research

Top-down models for implementation of new strategies and policies often do not support sustained change of practice; an approach that involves stakeholders from early on and create ownership of solutions are needed (LeMahieu et al., 2017; Penuel et al., 2011). Design-based implementation research (DBIR) is one such approach. It shares similarities with other design research approaches, such as design-based research, namely the endeavour to bridge theory and practice, to iteratively develop, empirically test and improve designs, and to build theory to inform future efforts. However, DBIR has a broader scope and transgresses the classroom, which is typically the level of focus in design-based research, to encompass other system levels (Penuel et al., 2011).

DBIR studies adhere to four principles that frame tasks, processes and participation, outlining the mode of operation, which again sets it apart from design-based research where the researcher is not bound by such framing principles. The four principles of DBIR are listed below based on Fishman et al. (2013, pp. 142-143).

1. Focus on persistent problems of practice from multiple stakeholders' perspectives.
2. Commit to iterative, collaborative design.
3. Develop theory related to both classroom learning and implementation through systematic inquiry.
4. Develop organisational capacity for sustaining change in systems.

In design-based research, the researcher might approach practice to test a design she developed with the intention of investigating a hypothesis. However, in DBIR, the point of departure is the "important problems of practice" (Penuel et al., 2011, p. 332) as these are voiced by stakeholders. DBIR is therefore a strategy for involving practitioners (Koren et al., 2023) not only in the empirical testing of designs, but also in the formulation of important problems (principle 1) and in the iterative development, evaluation and refinement of designs (principle 2). Therefore, when planning a DBIR study, a significant methodologically-oriented task is to identify effective strategies to engage practitioners as pointed out by Koren et al. (2023). In the present study, co-design approaches (Cumbo & Selwyn, 2022) are used to support the involvement of stakeholders.

DBIR resolves common problems in design-based research studies, e.g. whose problem is the object of investigation: the researcher's or practitioner's? Likewise, regarding whose design is tested. In design-based research, the researcher's questions and designs are often in focus (LeMahieu et al., 2017; Odgaard, 2025), whereas DBIR specifies collaboration with stakeholders around the design, iterative testing and refinement of solutions, as mentioned above. DBIR thus positions researchers and stakeholders/practitioners as equal partners throughout the study (LeMahieu et al., 2017). In addition, whereas design-based research is preoccupied with designs that enhance learning and building theory to explain the nature of the phenomena discovered (diSessa & Cobb, 2004), DBIR has a dual focus seeking to build theory both on learning but also on implementation (principle 3). Finally, working at different system levels, DBIR focuses on building capacity for sustained change as part of the research endeavour (principle 4). The design, testing and refinement of implementation supports are part of this work (Fishman et al., 2013). The mapping tool that is discussed in this paper is seen as one such implementation support.

Design-based research has well-defined steps. Reeves’ (2006), e.g., proposes a four-phase model: Analysis, Design, Intervention and Reflection. DBIR on the other hand has yet to identify, formulate and consolidate such steps for conducting research (LeMahieu et al., 2017). Instead, the overarching goal of “enact[ing] change through a commitment to the four design principles” (LeMahieu et al., 2017, p. 27) is what guides researchers undertaking DBIR studies. However, to secure systematic inquiry, I translated the four DBIR principles into a research plan. The result was the following five-phase model (see figure 1) that should not be understood as linear but as a *back-and-forth process* where discoveries in one phase informs and shapes other phases.

Figure 1. The five phases of the reported DBIR study.

The study commenced in January 2024 when I set out to build partnerships across the organisation with a view to investigating stakeholder perspectives and uncovering “important problems of practice” (Penuel et al., 2011, p. 332). My collaboration with stakeholders also served the purpose of negotiating my research agenda to match the identified problems (LeMahieu et al., 2017). Simultaneously, having become aware of the many different projects that were underway as described above, I sought to map the landscape of digital competences to find synergies and relationships that could help stakeholders navigate and ease implementation. The results of this mapping exercise are described in the Findings section. Next follows an outline of methods used in the initial phases to build partnerships, investigate stakeholder perspectives, uncover important problems of practice and map digital competences.

3.2 Methods

In the initial phases of this project, I conducted both theoretical and empirical studies. The purpose of the empirical study was to gain insight into stakeholder perspectives, thus engaging with the first principle of the DBIR approach, cf. above. I involved different stakeholder groups, forums and units at the university, as well as external experts from other universities, that I identified as relevant with respects to contributing both important problems pertaining to the issue of implementing digital competences as well as opportunities in relation to the actual implementation. Here my 12 years of experience as an E-learning Consultant at the SDU CTL proved useful with respects to identifying relevant stakeholder groups, forums and units both internally and externally. Table 1 below provides an overview of the different stakeholder groups, forums and units that I involved. Below the table follows an account of the nature of the theoretical study, an outline of data collection methods employed and a description of the different roles, I played in the different contexts.

In the first column in table 1 below, the many different stakeholder groups, forums and units that have fed into the present work is listed. Column 2 explains the nature of my engagement with each group, forum and unit, and column 3 presents some of the stakeholder perspectives identified. As table 1 explains, I also used some of the stakeholder groups, forums and units to engage with principle 2 of the DBIR approach: commit to iterative, collaborative design. This process involved the mapping exercise and development of a mapping tool

and was undertaken in parallel with my gaining insight into stakeholder perspectives as described in table 1. So, the two initial phases of the study informed each other.

Table 1. Stakeholder groups, forums and units engaged in the present study

Stakeholder groups, forums and units	Nature of engagement (sample)	Stakeholder perspectives identified (sample)
The SDU Centre for Teaching and Learning (SDU CTL): unit in charge of competence development of teachers. Provides input for strategy development	I have had regular meetings with the centre to present and discuss the mapping tool which has been revised based on their feedback to secure alignment with competence development efforts.	Opportunity identified: joining forces and aligning my work with the SDU CTL will help stakeholders navigate the landscape of digital competences and strengthen implementation efforts. It will set a clear, uniform direction backed up by the organisation.
SDU Rio: unit that supports students with regards to employability and career development, among other things	I had a meeting with consultants from the unit on 14 March 2024 to uncover any overlaps between their and my work. The unit, among other things, supports student-company contact and thus have a large database of organisations that are interested in working with students and the university.	Opportunities identified: Develop company cases that illustrate digital practices in relevant professions – let students investigate these digital practices. Use the transfer model to help students connect digital competences to future job situations.
Conferences, webinars, seminars etc. on digital competences, generative AI etc.	On 19 March, I participated in a seminar on literacy and AI at SDU with students' presenting their perspectives.	Problem identified: fear of being accused of plagiarism. One student reported that she would like to know in which study/work processes it would be ok and relevant to use generative AI.
Education committee for heads of study at the Faculty of Humanities	I presented my study on 11 April 2024 followed by discussion.	Problem identified: "what digital competences are we to integrate?", asked one head of study. "What are we not already doing that we should start doing?"
Center for Learning Computational Thinking at SDU – interdisciplinary centre at SDU	On April 16, I facilitated a workshop for researchers who all teach on our humanistic IT study programs and a consultant from SDU CTL. I called the workshop <i>mapping the current landscape of digital competences</i> .	Contribution: overview of concepts and conceptualisations and a first mapping of hierarchy and relationships seen from a research point of view.
Sparring sessions with teacher teams and individual teachers on the development of digital activities and subjects	Spring 2024: I was included in a team of four teachers from the Faculty of Humanities who were developing the elective 'Digital mindset' for bachelor students.	Problem identified: "We can talk to students about the kind of investigations we can undertake using digital data and tools in our subjects, but who will help the students get started using the tools and give them technical support if they get stuck?"
Consultants in charge of mapping digital competences at the Faculty	I have had regular meetings with the consultants to present and discuss my efforts to map digital	Conflict identified: the concepts used by researchers and consultants to conceptualise categories of

of Business and Social Science	competences and to give and receive feedback that can secure progress. Conversations also include the purpose and function of mapping tools.	digital competences are not necessarily meaningful to teachers. Should we continue using these concepts? They can help us match expectations and introduce relevant ways of thinking about digital competences going forward.
Implementation task force at the Faculty of Humanities consisting of teachers who have been part of one or more digital experiments. The task force is led by the vice dean of the faculty	I am a member of the task force that had the first meeting in June 2024. I have used this forum to inform the development of the mapping tool. I have presented my prototypes, the teachers have critiqued them, and I have revised the prototypes based on their feedback.	Perspective identified: conceptualisations of digital competences should be simple and easy to understand. Conflict identified: the implementation of digital competences is seen as a practical matter and not necessarily as an area that should be theorised and systematically researched.
Knowledge exchange sessions with two Danish universities who have been through similar implementation projects	September-October 2024: Online knowledge exchange sessions with consultants from two universities. The consultants shared their models of digital competences and explained how they support implementation.	Opportunities identified: support the creation of a common language for talking about digital competences. Allow room for local interpretation and offer implementation support and tools.

3.3 The theoretical study

The theoretical study involved the investigation of concepts that were connected to the current and coming projects at SDU described in the introduction. Through the study of literature on, e.g., CT (e.g. Grover & Pea, 2018), computational literacy (diSessa, 2001) and AI literacy (Ng et al., 2021) as well as complete frameworks on twenty-first century skills (Binkley et al., 2012) and digital competences (Vuorikari et al., 2022), I attempted to get an overview of the different concepts and conceptualisations. This work was further informed through a workshop with researchers in the context of the Centre for Learning Computational Thinking. Together, we engaged in a mapping exercise to identify relevant digital competences, as well as hierarchies and relationships. In this way, I engaged the researcher perspective. The theoretical study resulted in version 1 of the mapping tool, cf. the Findings section below.

3.4 Data collection methods and researcher roles

To find synergies between the study described in this paper and other, similar projects at SDU, strategy documents and action plans describing these projects were retrieved for document analysis. The new strategy launched by The Faculty of Humanities in March 2024 proved especially useful and was therefore analysed in detail, cf. the Findings section. This analysis informed the design of the mapping tool and provided several opportunities that can be pursued in the actual implementation of digital competences. In addition, data were collected using ethnographic inspired approaches in connection with my engagement with the different stakeholder groups, forums and units described above. In these situations, I undertook participant observation as described by Spradley (1980). I produced field notes both during sessions and after sessions to record as many details as I could recall. The focus of my observations was problems as formulated by stakeholders, barriers to the implementation of digital competences as well as opportunities.

In addition, I sought to incorporate stakeholder voices into my work by listening to and recording how they discussed digital competences and the specific terms they used.

Overview of researcher roles

As explained by McKenney (2016), the type of educational design research conducted in this study involves the researcher taking on different roles in different phases. Table 2 below provides a brief account of the roles I have taken on so far in the project and shows the complexity of this type of study:

Table 2. Researcher roles in the present study

Role	Tasks
Theoretician and researcher	How can we conceptualise digital competences? What are useful theoretical lenses and underpinnings? How can we investigate the issue in a systematic manner? Documenting, evaluating, discussing and reflecting on approaches, findings etc.
Curator	Collecting and synthesising knowledge from literature, fellow researchers, external experts, stakeholder groups etc. Bringing knowledge into relevant forums at SDU, such as the implementation task force and the consultant group at the Faculty of Business and Social Sciences
Participant observer	Listening, observing, recording stakeholder perspectives and voices
(Co)-designer	Filtering and engaging with the data collected and the knowledge produced to inform the design of implementation processes and tools. Developing mapping tool and helping teachers develop digital activities for their students.

Below, the findings of the initial phases of this study are outlined.

4. Findings

First the results of the document analysis will be presented. Then follows an overview of some of the important problems of practice that have been identified. The section ends with a presentation and evaluation of the three versions of the mapping tool that has been developed.

4.1 Results of the document analysis

The analysis of the ‘Strategy for study programs at the Faculty of Humanities 2030’ (The Faculty of Humanities, 2024) helped establish the context for implementation of digital competences by describing these as:

- Up to date, digital humanistic competences adapted to students’ subject domains (e.g., history, philosophy, literature studies and media studies)
- Both specific skills related to digital tools as well as broad technology comprehension

In addition to this contextualisation, the following opportunities were identified in the document analysis in relation to the implementation of digital competences:

Opportunity 1: The strategy calls for new teaching formats and methods of working with the purpose of supporting students’ active engagement. This presents an opportunity in relation to the ways in which digital competences are implemented in subjects and study programs. This feeds into opportunities 2 and 3 below.

Opportunity 2: The strategy also calls for a strengthened dialogue and collaboration with the community. Specifically, SDU wants to increase collaboration with potential employers around teaching, project-oriented forms of study as well as students’ theses. This is an opportunity to integrate digital competences in teaching

in an authentic way. Through projects, e.g., students can investigate what digital competences are needed in specific, relevant professions, what digital tools are used and how this changes tasks, processes and roles.

Opportunity 3: In addition to the above, the strategy calls for enhanced integration of research and teaching to invite students into the faculty’s research environment and grow their academic talent. Such research integration can be combined with opportunity 2 above, so that student-teacher-researcher partnerships are formed around the investigation of digital competences in relevant professions.

The section below summaries the stakeholder perspectives that shaped the second phase of the study.

4.2 Problems raised by stakeholders

Table 1 above outlines some of the stakeholder perspectives identified. Three perspectives in particular fed into as well as shaped phase two, the exercise to map digital competences. They are as follows:

- Teacher perspective: Which digital competences are we to support students’ in developing? What should we do that we are not already doing today?
- Student perspective: I’m afraid of being accused of plagiarism if I use generative AI, e.g. I would like to know in which study/work processes it is ok and relevant to use generative AI.
- Researcher perspective: How can we give stakeholders a meaningful overview of digital competences?

Other perspectives were recorded as relevant for later phases, such as these teacher perspectives: “Who can teach the chosen digital competences? Who will support the students in relation to the use of digital tools?” Such perspectives were discussed with the vice dean to create awareness about potential barriers to the implementation of digital competences and encourage the management level to start working on solutions.

In the following, the three iterations of the mapping exercise are described, and the resulting versions of the mapping tool are presented and evaluated.

4.3 A mapping tool in three iterations

Prototype 1

In the theoretical study described above, an ambitious categorisation of competences was undertaken, and the concepts and conceptualisations studied were mapped against the identified categories. This resulted in the first prototype (see table 3 below for an extract).

Table 3. Extract from prototype 1 of the mapping tool

Competence category Concept	Digital citizen/digital mindset/digital Bildung	Digital study practices	Digital domain-specific practices
AI literacy	Understanding and critiquing LLMs Reflecting on the consequences of using generative AI	Learning to learn with AI Use of AI as co-operation between human-machine Prompt engineering – in general	Prompt engineering - customisation: Building own local models of relevance to subject domain / profession
Computational thinking	Understanding and critiquing algorithms, e.g. Reflecting on the impact of algorithms	Engaging with algorithms in connection with using digital tools for studying: use, modify, design	Algorithmic problem solving in subject domain
...	...	...	...

The competence categories of prototype 1 was also informed by student perspectives and the document analysis:

1. Digital citizen, inspired by the notion of attitudes in the DigComp 2.2 (Vuorikari et al., 2022).
2. Digital study practices, inspired by student perspectives (cf. table 1 above).
3. Digital domain-specific practices (cf. the document analysis).

Category 3 refers to actual tools used in relevant professions and actual digital competences needed. Specific competences such as AI literacy and CT were mapped against the three overall categories. The first category of digital citizen has several labels in table 3 above. This both communicates insecurity regarding what terms to use to support stakeholders' sense making and openness with regards to negotiating terms.

Evaluation

To proof test the prototype and get feedback that could further inform my work to develop a mapping tool, I met with the SDU CTL. The consultants at the centre are close to teachers who are their primary target group. Furthermore, it was essential that the consultants develop ownership of the mapping tool to support broad implementation of digital competences in the organisation. The consultants could relate to the three competence categories but found the use of concepts, AI literacy and CT, too narrow in scope. They suggested to move AI literacy and CT to the level of learning objectives and instead employ the five competence areas of DigComp 2.2 to signify specific clusters of digital competences. Based on this feedback, I revised the mapping tool and arrived at the second prototype presented below.

Prototype 2

The second prototype (see table 4 below) was developed for the first meeting in the implementation task force that was established at The Faculty of Humanities as described in table 1 above.

Table 4. Version 2 of the mapping tool

Competence category		Digital mindset/ Technology comprehension	Digital study practices	Digital domain-specific practices
Competence area				
Information & data literacy	Safety	Problem solving	Knowledge, skills and competences in relation to learning via digital tools – aimed at study practices: teaching and learning	Knowledge, skills and competences in relation to using digital tools within the subject domain – aimed at future profession and work life
Communication & collaboration				
Digital content production				
		Open and curious approach Willing to experiment Critical and reflected Transparent re. own practice Reflexive in relation to roles and identity		

The purpose of the mapping tool was to facilitate discussion around the context for implementation of digital competences and build a common language. Therefore, the second prototype contained a definition of the three competence categories and included the five competence areas from DigComp 2.2 to represent the voice of the SDU CTL. The intention was to build on this overall framework to formulate learning objectives for each competence area in relation to each competence category.

Evaluation

The second prototype served its purpose of facilitating discussion between the members of the implementation task force. However, it quickly became clear that the labels and language used was too far removed from the teachers. They found the tool too complex and convoluted and did not understand the idea

of a mapping tool. They also found it difficult to distinguish between digital study practices and digital domain-specific practices. Fortunately, the task force members provided suggestions for alternative formulations from a practitioner perspective, and it was possible to arrive at a shared understanding of both the context for implementation and specific clusters of competences that should be in focus. The latter was supported by some members of the task force who had participated in a digital curriculum project that made use of the DigComp 2.2 framework. Thus, they had prior knowledge of the five competence areas and felt confident discussing digital competences within this framework. This feedback fed into prototype 3 described below.

Prototype 3

Having found the DigComp 2.2 framework somewhat unwieldy and irrelevant in a HE context, I was now forced to work with it more in-depth to adapt it to a HE context. The University of Copenhagen and Aarhus University were also in the process of implementing digital competences, and therefore I arranged knowledge exchange sessions with consultants at the two universities to learn how they had handled the process. Aarhus University has also made use of DigComp 2.2 and could provide insight into the implementation supports they had developed. The University of Copenhagen, on the other hand, had developed their own model. This model is centred around students’ digital Bildung and is thus narrower in scope than the project reported here. However, the University of Copenhagen has formulated reflection questions for each of the elements in their model of students’ digital Bildung to support conversations with stakeholders. These reflection questions have inspired my work to adapt the DigComp 2.2 competence areas to a HE context.

Prototype 3 shown below (figure 2) is a more polished vision of the mapping tool. It was created for a summer seminar for heads of study at The Faculty of Humanities that took place in August 2024. This was a further and final proof testing of the tool to receive feedback from a larger stakeholder group with the purpose of arriving at a mapping tool that could be used for the subsequent implementation of digital competences in subjects and study programs.

Figure 2. Version 3 of the mapping tool

The three competence categories in prototype 2 (table 4) that the implementation task force found complex and incomprehensible have been replaced in prototype 3 (figure 2) with a description of the shared

understanding of the context for implementation that was arrived at during the first meeting in the task force. This shared understanding is represented in the mapping tool as 'generic academic digital competences' and 'domain-specific digital competences'. The first category concerns the competent use of digital tools for generic academic tasks such as information search, writing, data collection and analysis, presentation of findings etc. The latter category concerns the competent use of digital tools to solve problems and undertake inquiries that are relevant and meaningful for the subject domain in question, i.e. the subject domain drives inquiries rather than the digital tools. The task force also found the concept of 'mindset' incomprehensible. However, this concept is vital for a mapping tool to be future proof and relevant in the long-term since it concerns the way one engages with any technology. Thus, 'mindset' was preserved but 'approach' was added as well as key words to provide explanations and ease sense making. The first meeting in the task force revealed that nobody objected to the key words included in the explanation of 'mindset'.

The last element of prototype 3 is the five competence areas of DigComp 2.2. The idea is that specific learning objectives be formulated for subjects and study programmes within each area. To adapt the five competence areas to a HE context and ease stakeholder sense making, a table has been made for each competence area exemplifying relevant learning objectives. In addition, a second implementation support has been developed based on these tables, namely competence cards with reflection questions that are to spark conversations on the relevance of each competence area for specific subjects and study programmes. For the area *Problem solving*, e.g., the following sample learning objective was formulated: *Analyse and formulate problems within a subject-domain, so that these can be investigated using digital tools and methods*. The corresponding competence card includes these reflection questions: *What can digital technologies be used for in my subject-domain? What new, relevant and meaningful inquiries can I now undertake? How can I use digital technologies to innovate subject-specific processes and products?*

Evaluation

Prototype 3, as well as the tables and competence cards have been accepted by the implementation task force and the heads of study at the summer seminar as the model and tools to proceed with in relation to the actual implementation. Below follows discussion and reflections on findings, research approach and methods.

5. Discussion and concluding remarks

This paper reports on the initial phases of a DBIR study, the purpose of which is to implement digital competences in subjects and study programmes in the humanities and social sciences at SDU. Through engagement with different stakeholder groups, forums and units at SDU, insight into different stakeholder perspectives were obtained and recorded with a view to mirroring these in implementation processes and tools. Such a process, no doubt, informs implementation plans and helps create ownership at a local level. However, it is a difficult task to reconcile perspectives from multiple stakeholders. It takes perseverance and inclusion, but it paves the way for successful implementation. The lesson learnt here is to engage in open discussions not fixing concepts and conceptualisations beforehand. This is not an easy job for a researcher who is focused on rigour and the establishment of concepts and conceptualisations at the outset of inquiries.

The main objectives of the initial phases of the project were to create a common language and understanding around digital competences. Mapping exercises and the development of a mapping tool were employed as strategies to achieve this. As the Findings section illustrates, it can be difficult to build bridges between stakeholder groups and between theory and practice. However, boundary objects, such as the mapping tools described above, can facilitate discussions, negotiation and sense making. It is important to note that it took several iterations to arrive at a mapping tool that mirrored stakeholder perspectives satisfactorily.

As a researcher, I have sometimes felt at odds with this project. I have a clear vision of the end goal, but as I pursue principle 1 in the DBIR approach, I am negotiating research agendas with stakeholders to focus on the persistent problems they experience. Often, I found that practitioners, though being researchers themselves, just wanted to act when it comes to the integration of digital competences. They do not necessarily feel a need to theorise and undertake systematic inquiries. On a positive note, I have experienced that a dedicated resource like me, who has been allocated the time to investigate digital competences in HE can set the agenda and fill a knowledge gap concerning how to conceptualise and create a shared understanding of digital competences and how to go about implementation. I have disseminated prototype 3 with accompanying tables and competence cards to other faculties at SDU and these tools have been received with enthusiasm.

As the Findings section illustrates, it is imperative to involve different stakeholder groups from the outset of a project. Clearly, as I moved from prototype 1 to 3, I integrated stakeholder perspectives to a higher degree and found ways to bridge theory and practice to facilitate sense making. In a DBIR study, this is essential since the focus is to uncover and work with persistent problems of practice to support successful implementation.

6. Limitations and implications of the study

This paper illustrates participatory approaches to the integration of digital competences in subjects and study programmes. As such, readers gain insight into iterative processes that solicit and incorporate stakeholder perspectives and voices. It should be noted, however, that the final version of the mapping tool, prototype 3, does not represent a universally true conceptualisation of digital competences. Instead, it represents a shared understanding of digital competences and supports the creation of a common language locally at SDU. This in turn sets a direction for and facilitates implementation at the university. The methods reported in this paper can be adopted by other universities, but it might not be possible to adopt the implementation supports developed since these would have to be negotiated in and adapted to a new context to be of use.

7. Acknowledgements

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Research on Distance Education in Greece during 2019-2023, as published in the “Open Education” journal

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to present the research activity in the field of distance education (DE) in Greece during 2019-2023, through the examination of the research papers that have been published in the scientific journal “Open Education: the Journal for Open and Distance education and Educational Technology”. The study examines four main pillars: the thematic fields of the research papers and their classification, the research methodology, the theoretical framework, in which the articles were based, and the writers’ profile, as well as the cooperative forms that can be tracked among researchers.

Six regular and two special issues have been examined, to highlight the research field of distance education in Greece during the specific timeframe. The examination plan was based on the approaches and findings of similar research papers in other contexts and different time periods. The following characteristics were recorded for each research paper: title of the paper, indicated keywords, research theme, research level and areas (following the Zawacki-Richter classification), theoretical/conceptual background, research methodology, targeted population, researchers' profile, and number of writers per paper.

The paper begins with the review of important research studies in the field, published in international literature, for the period from 1980 until now -and few recent research papers that were conducted specifically in the Greek context. Then, the methodology that was used is presented in detail, and finally, the study presents the data that was collected and the relevant discussion. The paper concludes with the research limitations and the suggestions for further research in the field.

Keywords: research, distance education, research classification, research methodology, profile of the researchers.

1. Introduction

A review of research in a particular field of knowledge within a selected period of time is an approach that aims to understand the “big picture” by studying many individual research “snapshots”. Through it, it is

possible to highlight the topics of greatest research interest, the purpose, objectives and methodology of the preferred research, the theories on which the research is based, the type of problems posed and how they are classified, as well as to identify potential gaps for future research. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2020) state in this regard that systematic reviews provide, not just a summary of published research on a particular topic or research question - but more importantly clear and convincing answers to questions about who, why and when, while drawing the attention of researchers to consider the wider context of the research they are studying.

The present research seeks to identify the research areas in distance education that the researchers prefer, as well as those that are under-represented, covering the period 2019-2023; In addition, it seeks to describe the methodological preferences of the researchers, as well as their profile and the cooperative schemes that occurred. The articles that were used in this review, were published in the journal "Open Education: the journal for Open and Distance Education and Educational Technology", a scientific journal that has been published continuously since 2005.

Through the study of 6 regular and 2 special issues, the aim is to outline the field of research on distance education in Greece in the specific period, and to examine it based on the findings of previous related research and draw conclusions that will shed light on the current state of research activity. The objectives are focused on highlighting and categorizing the topics on which the researchers work, and the methodology followed, as well as linking those findings to the authors' profile.

The paper begins with a review of similar studies, conducted globally and -more limited- in Greece, presenting them through four main pillars: the research topics and their classification, the research method, the theoretical framework that supports their research, and the authors' profile. It continues with the description of the methodology followed, the presentation of the results and the discussion around them. The paper concludes with the limitations of the research and suggestions for further research in the field.

2. Brief overview of studies on research in distance education internationally

With the development of distance education and the increasing research interest it has gradually attracted, there has inevitably been an interest in reviewing the research conducted in the field. As early as the 1990s, as reported in Kaul et al. (2018, pp.50-51), a significant number of researchers emerge to undertake the task of reviewing previous research (Panda, 1992; Rekkedal, 1993; Calvert, 1995; Koble & Bunker, 1997; Holmberg, 2003). The interest in reviewing previous research continued in the 2000-2010s (Berge & Mrozowski, 2001; Rourke & Szabo, 2002; Parhar, 2003; Zawacki-Richter, 2009) and onwards (Richter & Naidu, 2016; Wong et al., 2016). These studies, despite their differences in terms of purpose, objectives and methodology, as well as the results they extracted, have some common points worth noting:

- The research was mainly carried out in internationally renowned scientific journals.
- A classification of the topics and the thematic areas of the research was carried out.
- The methodological approach of the researchers was examined and in some cases the profile of the researchers was also studied.

Several different methodological approaches were used to study the surveys. Thus, some of them are content analysis studies, others are literature reviews, and there is the pivotal study by Zawacki-Richter (2009), which applied the Delphi method with the participation of experts in the field from many parts of the world. It is worth noting the different perspectives in this category of research. Thus, we distinguish publications that the research focuses:

- in specific countries (Walker, 1997), which documented research in distance education in Australia, New Zealand and the Pacific countries,
- in specific time intervals and phases, such as Koble and Bunker's (1997) review of 8 years of the American Journal of Distance Education and Rourke and Szabo's (2002) review of 15 years of issues (1986-2001) of the Journal of Distance Education,
- in the delineation of thematic areas, such as that of Holmberg (1987), who proposed 8 categories for the inclusion of research in distance education (Schosser & Anderson, 1994),
- in different sources, such as Berge and Mrozowski's (2001) study examining the contents of four flagship journals in the field of distance education from 1990-1999,
- in trend formation, such as the research of Wong et al. (2016), which looks at trends in research in distance education in 288 research articles from 7 journals published between 2005-2015 and Zawacki-Richter and Naidu (2016), which looks at key research topics and the changes they show over time.

An important study, which formed the basis for a number of subsequent studies (Bozkurt et al., 2015), including this one, is that of Zawacki-Richter (2009), which resulted in a categorization of 15 research areas, which in turn are classified into 3 distinct levels (micro, meso and macro). Wong et al. (2016) describe this research as influential as it inspired many subsequent studies.

Some of the reviews have the specific aim of identifying the under-researched research areas and those that are popular among researchers (Berge & Mrozowski, 2001; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2009; Wong et al., 2016; Mustaira et al., 2019).

According to Kaul et al. (2018), as early as the 1980s, researchers have been pointing out the “neglected” areas of research, such as the policies and management of an open university.

Berge and Mrozowski (2001) point out that in the 1990-1999s, topics related to pedagogy were much more researched than topics related to organisation, administration and policy. In their research they comment that the focus of study is within the distance “classroom” and is mainly concerned with the distance learner and the tutor-consultant. However, the wider design, administration and management of an institution, accreditation and costs are areas that have a significant impact on the success or failure of a DE programme.

The following decade followed a similar logic. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2009), after studying 695 articles from 5 journals over the eight-year period 2000-2008, concluded that research in distance education “classroom” is largely focused on issues related to instructional design and personalised learning processes, while other important areas, such as the management of innovation and change or the intercultural aspects of DE, are completely ignored.

Wong et al. (2016) analysed the trends in research on distance education in 288 research articles from 7 journals published between 2005-2015. The results showed that research that falls into the macro level category, in areas such as globalisation or cultural aspects of DE, remains relatively rare. On the contrary, micro-level research, especially educational design, dominates research in both 2005 and 2015.

3. Classification of Research Areas in Distance Education (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2009)

Before we proceed to the presentation of the research methodology, the following table of the classification of research areas in distance education by Zawacki-Richter et al., as extracted from Bozkurt et al. (2015) will help to better understand the results of the current research.

Levels of classification	Research areas
Macro: Distance education systems and theories	Access, equity and ethics Globalization of education and cross-cultural aspects Distance teaching systems and institutions Theories and models Research methods in distance education and knowledge transfer
Meso: Management, organization and technology	Management & organization Costs & benefits Educational technology Innovation & change Professional development & faculty support Learner support services Quality assurance
Micro: Teaching and learning in distance education	Instructional design Interaction and communication in learning communities Learner characteristics

4. Research methodology

This research aims to outline the current landscape of domestic research activity in distance education, seeking to answer the following research questions:

1. How are the three levels represented among the selected papers?
2. How are the papers classified according to the research methodology that has been selected?
3. What are the theoretical frameworks that authors rely on to design their research?
4. What are the authors' and the authoring teams' profiles?

In order to address the above questions, the current research follows the method of literature review, examining the research studies published in the journal "Open Education: the journal for Open and Distance Education and Educational Technology" during the last five years (2019-2023). The journal "Open Education" is the first scientific journal in the field of Open and Distance Education and educational technology in Greece, published by the Hellenic Network for Open and Distance Education, with the first publication date in 2005 (Giosos et al, 2008).

The issues published in 2019-2023 are six regular and two special issues. A total of 111 articles were published. The research team decided to examine the Editorials separately, since they set the trend of each issue; In addition, descriptive texts which belong to section B of the journal (practical considerations and opinions) were excluded. The total number of texts that were used for the purpose of this research is 72.

An Excel file was created to collect and classify the data, in which the following columns were entered:

- Name of article
- Keywords
- Level according to Zawacki-Richter
- Subcategory according to Zawacki-Richter
- Research topic (summary record)
- Level of education
- Theoretical background
- Research methodology
- Authors' profession, institution
- Number of authors per article

In order to determine the themes, the content of the texts was studied, the keywords and the topic were recorded, and the level of education to which they belonged was also noted. To determine the methodology, the method followed was noted. Broad categorisation into quantitative, qualitative, mixed methods and literature review was chosen, as in previous review studies (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2009). To record the theoretical framework, the existence or otherwise of the framework was first noted, followed by the theoretical framework as mentioned by the authors.

No attempt was made to examine the time span between years, as the 5-year interval is relatively short and has common characteristics. All results are presented in aggregate for the five-year period.

The researchers took over specific issues and, after selecting the texts according to the criteria set, they filled in the above columns. They then carried out a review of the remaining issues and where there was disagreement on the classification, it was discussed until a final decision was made.

Different classifications were found in the literature review. The team selected the Zawacki-Richter's (2009) classification, for the following reasons mainly:

- Unlike similar studies that relied exclusively on literature review and content analysis, this particular classification was derived through the Delphi method with the participation of a number of experts in the field.
- Moreover, many studies (Bozkurt et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016) and conferences (EDEN Annual Conference, 2018) have adopted this approach to categorize the subject areas, which enhances its reliability.
- Finally, the classification into levels (micro, meso and macro) gives a structured orientation to the directions of the research, and the possibility to draw broader conclusions.

5. Results

The most popular keywords

In this study, 376 keywords were collected from a total of 72 articles, which were sorted according to their frequency. Figure 1 highlights the 12 most predominant ones.

Figure 1: The most prevalent keywords in the 2019-2023 research activity.

The term “ODE” (Open and Distance Education) tops the list (27 references) followed by “pandemic” (or coronavirus) with 16. The terms “ICT” (Information and Communication Technologies) and “levels of education” appear with 7 mentions. Next in line is the term “platform” with 6 references -the authors decided to include all the different platform brands that were mentioned in one key-word. “Online learning”, “open university”, “adult education” and “school distance education” follow with 5 references. Finally, there were 4 references for “teachers” and 3 for the terms “autonomy” and “professional development”.

Classification at macro-meso-micro levels

The following chart shows the aggregate representation rates for each level for the period 2019-2023. The meso level leads with 51.4%, followed by the micro level with 40.3%, while the macro level is the least represented with only 8.3%.

Figure 2: Representation of macro-meso-micro levels in research activity 2019-2023.

By analysing each level in the respective categories, the following data are recorded.

The **macro-level** includes **6 articles** in the following categories:

1. Access, equity and ethics (3)
2. Distance teaching systems and institutions (2)
3. Theories and models (1)

At the **meso-level** the representation is significantly higher (**37 articles**). The articles are not ranked equally in the respective categories and there is a clear preference of the authors for topics that concern mainly the use of technology, professional development and quality assurance:

1. Educational technology (12)
2. Professional Development and Faculty Support (10)
3. Quality assurance (6)
4. Innovation and Change (4)
5. Learner support services (4)
6. Management and organisation (1)

Finally, at the **micro-level**, **29 articles** are included, distributed as follows:

1. Instructional design (15)
2. Interaction and communication in learning communities (11)
3. Learner characteristics (3)

Figure 3: Representation of areas of research in distance education, 2019-2023.

It is noteworthy that the categories “Globalisation of education”, “cross-cultural issues” and “research methods in distance education” at the macro-level, as well as the category “Costs and Benefits” at the meso-level are not represented at all. The category of “Instructional Design” at the micro-level is the most represented with 20.83%, followed by the categories of “Educational Technology” and “Professional Development and Faculty Support” at the meso-level with 16.67% and 15.28% respectively. It is important to note that these 3 categories constitute 52.75%, of all research areas.

Representation of education levels

In the period under review, the largest proportion of articles (32.2%) concerned higher education. This is followed by primary education with 30%, secondary education with 22.2%, and finally pre-school education with 13.3% (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Representation of education levels in research activity 2019-2023.

Editorial articles

Finally, the following keywords can be identified from the Editorials of the issues:

- Quality,
- Openness and Inclusion,
- New Roles and Skills,
- Leadership,
- Strategy,
- Informal Learning and Civil Society, and
- Sustainability Risks of Distance Education Institutions.

Methodological Approach

Figure 5 shows the authors' preference for quantitative research, with a percentage of 43.06%. This is followed by qualitative research with 27.78%, and by literature review with 18.06%; finally mixed research is present with 11%. Although the categorization of research by scope was not adopted in this approach, however, a very high percentage of evaluation researches were identified. Specifically, based on the research scope, 38 belong to the evaluation research category for the given years, reaching 52.78%.

Figure 5: Representation of research methods in research activity 2019-2023.

Theoretical framework

Following the pattern of previous related research (Bozkurt et al., 2015), the dominant theories were collected, which were then classified according to their frequency. The theories, as mentioned by the authors themselves in the reviewed texts, are the following:

1. E-learning (17)
2. Online Learning Communities and collaborative learning (4)
3. Social constructivism (4)
4. Feedback Intervention Theory (3)
5. Theory of Transactional Distance (2)
6. Self-Regulated Learning (2)
7. Community of Inquiry (2)

It is noted that of the total number of studies, 11 did not present a clear theoretical framework.

Authors' profiles and cooperation schemes

176 authors are identified, of which 59 are recurring authors, so they are presented only once in the table below, resulting in a total of 117 authors. In terms of the professional status of the authors, the majority are higher education professors from almost all universities in Greece and Cyprus, primary and secondary school teachers, tutors at the Open University and postgraduate students.

Table 1: Professional status of the authors.

Professional status of authors		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Primary and Secondary Teachers	33	28,2
	Higher Education Professors	41	35,0
	Tutors HOU	15	12,8

Phd Candidates	4	3,4
Master's Degree Students	15	12,8
University Phd's	3	2,6
Postdoctoral Researchers	1	,9
Research Teams	1	,9
Other Specialties	4	3,4
Total	117	100,0

Also, in terms of the number of authors per article, the picture is as follows, with the majority of articles having 2 or 3 authors:

Figure 6: Authors by article in research activity 2019-2023.

Specifically, 14 individual papers and 58 group papers are recorded, of which 30 consist of 2 authors and the remaining 28 of a group of 3 or more authors. Of the total number of articles, 19 are from HOU theses. Finally, 57 of the 72 articles are in Greek and the remaining 15 are in English.

6. Discussion

As far as the classification of papers **based on the research topic** is concerned, the findings agree with the literature review in terms of the disparity in the representation of levels and individual categories (Schosser & Anderson, 1994; Berge & Mrozowski, 2001; Kaul et al., 2018). Specifically, the micro and meso levels gather the majority of researchers' interest while the macro level is underrepresented, although it includes key categories such as that of accessibility and openness in education, cross-cultural issues in education, theories, the operation of distance teaching systems and institutions, and research issues in distance education. At the meso level, the researchers' preference for the use of technology and online education in the contemporary educational environment is evident. Although representation is high at this level, it is not equally distributed across the sub-categories, with the majority of researchers focusing on the use of technology, professional

development and faculty support, and quality assurance. The persistence in issues such as teleconferencing, flipped classroom, introduction of ICT, use of mobile devices and integration of micro-applications in the educational process, demonstrates the need to adapt the educational system to the digital age and at the same time the need to evaluate the relevant applications. Topics related to management and organisation seem to be very low on the list of interests, while issues of financial management, program performance, etc., are not explored at all. Finally, the micro category is also in complete agreement with earlier studies (Berge & Mrozowski, 2001; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2009; Zawacki-Richter et al. Bozkurt et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2016), according to which it is adequately represented, with the two sub-categories, that of instructional design and that of interaction and communication in learning communities, occupying most of the research attention. Through the research area of learner interaction and communication, the effort of teachers to enhance interaction and collaboration, the need for the creation of online communities, and more generally the approaches that will contribute to a learner-centred educational environment emerge, while through the category of instructional design, the value of educational materials in distance education environments and the necessity of their evaluation emerge. It seems, as Berge and Mrozowski (2001) had pointed out early on, that the focus of the study remains on the distance “classroom” and is mainly concerned with the distance learner and the tutor/consultant.

Regarding the keywords that characterize each article, the term “distance education” is the most frequent, as expected, followed by the term «pandemic», given that the research covers the whole period of the pandemic that significantly affected education and contributed to the daily use of distance education not only in Greece but also internationally. The term “ICT” that follows is consistent with the representation of the meso level and recalls the leading role of technology in distance education. In a relative contradiction is the reduced appearance of the term “online learning”, although as recorded, online learning is mentioned as a theoretical framework in a large number of studies.

In terms of education levels, higher education is the most represented. The status of researchers plays an important role in this. By making a correspondence between the education levels and the profile of the authors, it can be seen that higher education professors cover 28.21% of all authors. If we add the other disciplines related to university institutions, such as tutors, PhD candidates, postdoctorate students, etc., we obtain a percentage of 60%, which obviously exceeds the total number of scholars belonging to primary and secondary education (28.21%).

Finally, it is worth noting that, based on the keywords extracted from the Editorials of the issues, these focus mainly on the macro and meso level, addressing key issues such as vision, strategy, quality assurance, but also the need to redefine the roles related to the distance education environments. We can see clearly here that there is a contradiction between the topics selected for the Editorials and the topics selected by the researchers.

Regarding the methodological approach of researchers, according to the literature review, there is a link between the method chosen and the categorisation of the studies. The under-representation of the macro-level, in which mainly theoretical texts and literature reviews are found, possibly explains the corresponding under-representation of literature reviews, while correspondingly the abundance of studies at the meso- and macro-level are in line with the high rates of quantitative and qualitative research (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2009) and the high rates of evaluation research.

Finally, the low percentage of mixed methods research is probably explained by the fact that this type of research is very demanding to implement, time-consuming and requires high skills from the researchers.

Regarding the theoretical framework, a lack of a clear theoretical framework was noted in a small number of studies, which mainly deal with recording teachers' views and perceptions on the implementation of DE, especially during the pandemic period. However, the majority of the studies are based on a sound theoretical

background, which is considered one of the most important aspects of a research study (Grant & Osanloo, 2014). The broader use of the term “online learning” does not give a clear picture of the direction of the texts, such as the frameworks Social Constructivism, Collaborative Learning, Theory of Transactional Distance, etc., yet it is highlighted in the majority of the texts. Also, theories related to collaboration (Collaborative Learning, Online Communities, Community of Inquiry) are strongly present.

The profile of the authors is consistent with the choice of topics. It should be noted that many of the university professors are also working as tutors at the Hellenic Open University (HOU), which partly explains the involvement of many different universities in research on distance education in higher education. It is also worth noting the predominance of research groups over individual authors (58 group papers, 14 individual papers), which has been noted in previous research (Wung et al., 2016). Finally, 19 of the 72 papers are from HOU dissertations, indicating the significant contribution of the HOU and its related curricula to the broader research field.

7. Limitations and suggestions for further research

This research is limited to a specific period of time (2019-2023), which it studies from a contemporary perspective as a single period, without considering the possible differences between years. The review revealed interesting points, such as the under and over representation of research areas. It would be very interesting to extend this research in other publications in the same country, such as PhD dissertations and selected conferences.

The historical research of the same topics in the same scientific journal would be also extremely interesting, possibly in relation to the main events and developments that took place in the field during each period.

8. Conclusions

In this paper, we examined the research activity in the field of distance education in Greece during 2019-2023, through the classification of selected research papers that have been published in the scientific journal “Open Education”. The examination was based on four pillars: the research topics, the research methodology, the theoretical framework and the writers’ profile. Most research papers are based on a solid theoretical framework. Nevertheless, the findings show that there is an unequal representation of research areas, with a clear focus on the teaching and learning aspects of distance education that belong to the micro and the meso level (use of ICT in education, interaction and communication in learning communities and instructional design). Macro areas of research, such as accessibility issues, theories and models are missing; The same applies for management and leadership issues of the meso level.

The preferred research methods fit to the selected research topics, as was previously noted in the literature. The authors’ profile is also consistent with the choice of topics. Most writers are professors or teachers while there is no participation from other positions within the universities or other institutions (managers, leaders, economic departments, technical teams etc.). This is a reasonable explanation of why certain topics are missing from the research, although important, and an opportunity for the Journal to address to a more diverse group of writers. On the other hand, the editorials persist on highlighting issues of the macro level perspective; this, in combination with the tendency for the creation of larger teams of writers, may bring a balance in the representation of research areas in the future.

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Open Education & Skill Development

Designing educational & training activities for skills development in Public Administration. Case study on the results from training programs' evaluation from the National Center For Public Administration & Local Government (EKDDA)

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Abstract

The contemporary national and global landscape is characterized by intense competition and demands, driven by globalization, the pervasive use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and the emergence of the Knowledge Society, fundamentally reshaping societal dynamics (Komseli & Bourbouli, 2022). Consequently, nations face escalating challenges as citizens' expectations rise and societies advocate for increased investments in education, healthcare, and social welfare, all while maintaining tax levels (OECD, 2005). To facilitate the swift adaptation of Public Organizations to this dynamic environment, structural, procedural, functional, and cultural transformations are imperative (Tolici, 2021). Human resources emerge as pivotal in enhancing organizational performance (Tolici, 2021), necessitating strategic initiatives such as cultivating a conducive culture, effective leadership, a supportive work environment, continuous employee training, and fostering change and innovation (OECD, 2005).

Education and lifelong learning serve as pivotal tools for nurturing both leadership and human resources, fostering skill acquisition and professional development (OECD, 2005). Based on these premises, Greece's public administration implemented a novel institutional evaluation framework centered on nine key skills, with corresponding Training Programs (TPs) designed by EKDDA's scientific teams.

Recognizing the complexity of adult learning, the design and organization of TPs aim to address the specific needs of adult trainees (Pavli-Korres & Leftheriotou, 2020). Adult training programs, as highlighted by Cervero and Wilson (1994), have far-reaching impacts, influencing individuals, their supervisors, their educational units, and ultimately, the broader public sector and citizens.

The design of these programs hinges on analyzing the educational requirements of the target audience and aligning them with program objectives (Rogers, 1999). For skills-focused TPs, design considerations include identifying skill gaps based on established standards (Vergidis, 2008). This paper emphasizes the anthropocentric dimension of the system, outlining the fundamental principles of adult education guiding program design, as well as proposing training methodologies and techniques aimed at enhancing experiential learning to bolster skill development (Leftheriotou, 2014). Additionally, preliminary results from trainees' evaluations are presented.

The research inquiries are centered on the approach of the new evaluation system, the foundational principles of design, the methodologies employed, and the reception of TPs by civil servants. This study underscores the significance of an anthropocentric approach, evaluation, program design, and adult education in fostering skill development within the public sector. Our research questions will be focused on:

- ✓ What is the approach of the new evaluation system?
- ✓ On what principles is the designing of TPs based?
- ✓ Which training methodology is followed?
- ✓ What was the civil servants' acceptance of the TPs?

Key words: anthropocentric, evaluation, training program design, adult education.

Introduction

Learning is a complex process and its duration is related to the duration of a person's entire life. Over the centuries it has become increasingly important, as "the speed of change in society has increased so much that its members are almost obliged to continue learning in order to remain members... However, learning and education are fundamentally different concepts" (Jarvis P., 2003: 25). Adult education has been influenced by two main approaches: Paulo Freire's "critical awareness" view and Jack Mezirow's "transformative learning" (Kokkos in Vergidis 2010: 65-93). Freire's

approach to "critical awareness" "consists in making people aware of the social, cultural and political conditions that determine their lives, re-examining them and forming new perceptions corresponding to their vital interests" (Kokkos in Vergidis 2010:75). The "theory of transformative learning" could be called the set of theoretical approaches that consider the main purpose of adult education being to enhance the process of critical reflection, rational examination, emotional evaluation, awareness and change of dysfunctional epistemological, socio-cultural and psychological assumptions that lead to problematic perceptions and ineffective behaviors. In other words, it constitutes a significant modification of the image we have of ourselves, others and the world that surrounds us" (Lintzeris in Vergidis, 2010: 95). These theories have a significant influence on the design of training programs by the bodies in charge of this task.

Particularly in the field of training and education of civil servants, the National Centre for Public Administration and Local Government (EKDDA), through its two educational structures, the Training Institute (INEP) and the National School of Public Administration and Local Government (ESDDA), has a key role as the strategic body for the development of human resources in the public sector. Through successive operational programs with the assistance of the European Union, training in public administration has gradually shifted from the model of "supply based policy" to the model of "demand based policy". On the basis of the supply model, an agenda of training programs offered to civil servants is formulated. This process leaves little space to meet the real training needs of public organizations and is mainly due to the absence of a human resources development plan by the organizations that is in line with the strategic and operational objectives of the public organization. This leaves little scope for putting into practice the knowledge and skills acquired by participating in training programs. On the contrary, the model of "demand policy", to the extent that a human resources development policy is developed by public organizations, can serve the real training needs of the civil servants of the organization that will be harmonized with its strategy and business objectives. Since the previous decade, attempts have been made to develop Education Plans in public bodies in application of the corresponding institutional framework (article 35A, Law 3966/2011), but this

effort did not yield the expected results. However, there was a sensitization of civil servants and institutions for the development of relevant policy and this was expressed through their participation in relevant training programs related to the formulation of training plans and the design of on-the-job training programs, so that the organizations cover their educational needs on issues that could not be covered by the training programs of INEP. The adoption of a policy of human resource development and utilization of human resources in the policy of training civil servants, in our view, is an imperative need and a central condition for the effectiveness and efficiency of the training provided, mainly for three reasons: a. because the mission, role and operation of Public Administration services are based on policy objectives, b. because the work of public organizations and their needs are affected by the speed of developments, unexpected events and challenges and c. because adapting the operation of public administration to e-government requires continuous adaptation of the knowledge and skills of human resources in order to be able to respond effectively to these challenges (Komseli, Bourbouli, 2022).

In this context, the paper first analyzes the key points of the institutional framework for the evaluation of civil servants and its anthropocentric dimension. Secondly, it refers to the basic principles of the designing of training activities for the development of civil servants' skills, the composition of the working groups and the training techniques included in the design. Thirdly, the training activities designed for the integrated implementation of the evaluation of civil servants are presented. Finally, the paper presents the first evaluation remarks on the training of civil servants.

1. Key points of the anthropocentric orientation of the institutional framework for the evaluation of civil servants

The administrative reform in the Hellenic Public Sector having as main purpose the operation of an efficient state that ensures the public interest and provides quality of services to the citizen has always been a field of major interest for every government (Karkatsoulis, 2004, Michalopoulos, 2003). The economic crisis, the Covid-19 pandemic with all the structural changes it brought about in the organization and operation of Public Administration structures (e.g. distance working), brought forward the necessity of a comprehensive reform of the Public Sector, aiming at the

exploitation of human resources' skills in order to create an efficient and effective state mechanism taking into account the financial cost. In addition, the malfunctions, problems and delays found during the implementation of the existing evaluation law 4369/2016 as amended and in force, were considered for the designing of the new law 4940/2022 (Government Gazette A 112 /14.6.2022).

The main objective of the new legislative framework and the long-term objective of the regulations is to improve the functioning of public administration through the development of an integrated approach to the development and empowerment of human resources, which is achieved by identifying the necessary skills for the performance of staff duties (Explanatory Report 2022: 54). The main points of the process are the following:

- Establishment of a Common Skills Framework (Article 4) for the entire human resources of the public administration, which delimits the content of those skills that constitute the reference point of all human resources processes of the public sector The Common Skills Framework (Article 4) consists of the following general categories:
 - a) citizenship orientation,
 - b) teamwork,
 - c) adaptability,
 - d) result orientation,
 - e) organization and planning,
 - f) problem solving and creativity,
 - g) professionalism and integrity,
 - h) knowledge management and
 - i) leadership.
- Establishment of a skill development plan in which the civil servant, in consultation with his/her supervisor, identifies the skills that need development. The relevant forms are described in the Ministerial Decision no. No. DAPDEP/F.5/23/oik. 18708 (Government Gazette 6176/T.B' /5.12.22).
- Introduction of the concepts of Mentoring and Coaching as methods of developing the skills of civil servants.

- Establishment of mandatory meetings between the Evaluator and the assessed (check-ins) three times a year for a progress review and possible revision of the Development Plan and for the evaluation of the year's performance and the formulation of the next year's Development Plan.
- Utilization of focused training activities for the formulation of skills development plans in the direction of improving the individual and, by extension, the organizational performance of the civil servant and the effectiveness of the team.

Taking into account all the above, we understand that a human-centered direction of the Public Administration is being attempted since the focus is on the civil servant as a human being on the one hand and the skills needed ensuring meritocracy. The new law on evaluation is a decisive tool for the Administration to be able to determine not only "which person in which position" but also "the right person in the right position". The selection of the right person is a decisive factor in strengthening the much-desired meritocracy and efficiency in the Greek Public Administration.

2. Training programs' design in accordance to the Common Skills

Framework

EKDDA is the National strategic body for the education and training of civil servants as well as the key advisor to the state for the reforming of PA. Having as main mission the upskilling and reskilling of the human resources of PA through continuous education and accredited training, modernizing the public sector, through research, documentation and dissemination of innovation, best practices and know-how, contributes to an effective and efficient implementation of the public policies. Therefore, the new law 4940/2022 seems to be a great challenge. Adult education, a the main project of the Institute of training (INEP) of EKDDA, focuses on the development of the adult learner's personality (Rogers, 1999) and is governed by an anthropocentric approach, placing the learner civil servant at its center. Based on this approach, the new law emerged as a learning need that should be covered following the corresponding educational activities of INEP.

According to Silva (2009) "21st century skills is one of the most ubiquitous terms in today's education debates". They host a number of occupational skills, non-cognitive skills, interpersonal skills, life skills, and application skills, which presuppose that the

most important is what they can practically 'do' with the knowledge they get during their studies for integrated individual, community, and socio-economic development. The European Qualifications Framework (EQF), in the context of skills in training, distinguished specifically among knowledge (learning), skill (application for a task), and competence (use of common abilities for professional and personal developments). Andrews and Higson (2008) identified as core skills for employee – civil servants: professionalism, reliability, ability to cope with uncertainty, ability to work under pressure, ability to plan and think strategically, ability to communicate and interact, creativity and self-confidence, self-management and time-management, and willingness to learn and accept responsibility.

2.1 Design of training activities for skills development

As mentioned above, new training activities were designed by scientific teams to develop the skills of civil servants and the head of units. "Every adult education program is like a stone thrown into the water and follows concentric circles, since it affects more or less, directly or indirectly, the lives of many people (learners and their surroundings, trainers, designers, wider social environment" (Cervero & Wilson 1994: 5, op. cit. in Pavli-Korres & Leftheriotou 2020: 68). In the case of the design of these training programs in particular, their impact concerns: civil servants as individuals, to their superiors, to their unit, to their institution and especially to the public sector and those who deal with it, i.e. all citizens.

The actions focused on:

- Targeted training aimed at meeting the training needs of civil servants that have been identified based on the strategy and priorities and objectives of the institution in which the civil servant belongs to.
- Deciding in consultation between the civil servant and his/her head of unit regarding the type of training required to improve the skills identified as needing to be improved in their meetings.
- Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the educational process and overall training to ensure its effectiveness and its alignment with the organizational objectives of the institution in which the civil servant serves.

The design of an adult program is mainly based on the investigation of the educational needs of the target population of the project. In order to meet these needs, it is important to link them to the objectives of the program (Rogers 1999). In the case of these educational activities, which focus on the development of the nine skills, there was no prior research to detect educational needs, but we could argue that their design was based on the awareness of a lack of skills in relation to a general rule or a standard (Vergidis 2008a: 28-31). The standard in this case is included in the institutional framework where each skill is identified and the civil servant discusses with his head of unit and jointly identifies the skills that he/she should develop. The training activities were designed at two levels, the first level concerns the development of civil servants' skills and second level concerns the development of supervisors' skills. The main distinction between levels relates to the responsibilities of the two categories of (civil servants and head of units) of officials. In the 1st level the main focus is on understanding the skill under development and its importance for the individual, while in the 2nd level the main focus is on understanding the importance of the skill under development for the individual and for the unit he leads. Training programs are mentioned in Table 1 as follows:

1	Common Skills Framework: Knowledge management in the public sector – 1 st level
2	Common Skills Framework: Knowledge management in the public sector – 2 nd level
3	Common Skills Framework: Professionalism and Integrity of Public Sector Personnel – 1 st level
4	Common Skills Framework: Professionalism and Integrity of Public Sector Personnel – 2 nd level
5	Common Skills Framework: Problem solving and creativity in the public sector – 1 st level
6	Common Skills Framework: Problem solving and creativity in the public sector – 2 nd level
7	Common Skills Framework: Public sector leadership – 1 st level
8	Common Skills Framework: Public sector leadership – 2 nd level

9	Common Skills Framework: Teamwork in the public sector – 1 st level
10	Common Skills Framework: Teamwork in the public sector – 2 nd level
11	Common Skills Framework: Public Sector Organization & Planning – 1 st level
12	Common Skills Framework: Public Sector Organization & Planning – 2 nd level
13	Common Skills Framework: Result-oriented - 1 st level
14	Common Skills Framework: Result-oriented – 2 nd level
15	Common Skills Framework: Citizen oriented – 1 st level
16	Common Skills Framework: Citizen oriented – 2 nd level
17	Common Skills Framework: Adaptability of the civil servant – 1 st level
18	Common Skills Framework: Adaptability of the civil servant – 2 nd level

Table 1. Skills’ development training programs

Field 2.4 in the template of the TP describes the purpose and educational objectives of the training following one of the basic principles of adult education program design (Karalis 2005a: 32). For example, in the training program for the development of leadership skills 1st level the aim is *“to improve the leadership skills of Public Administration employees in order to create the right climate of cooperation conducive to incitement/motivation, to achieve timely, effective, responsible and correct decision-making for conflict resolution and to develop the ability to manage, and guide team activity, in the implementation of the duties of officials, towards the achievement of the common objectives set in the team in which each official operates”*. Training program’s main goal *“is to adopt those characteristics and behaviors that will improve civil servants’ leadership in the workplace to achieve common goals of their team”* (TP Design, 2023: 4-5).

Regarding the training program for the development of leadership skills 2nd level the aim is *“to improve the leadership skills of the Heads of Departments / Directorates / General Directorates or equivalent levels of Public Administration in order to create the appropriate climate of cooperation based on motivation, mobilization of civil servants and cultivation of relationships of trust among them and their department to achieve the objectives of the team they lead, make timely, effective, responsible and correct decision-making to resolve conflicts, address every day and emergency issues and problems faced by the team in the workplace, develop the ability manage and*

direct the team's activity, in the context of implementing the duties of head of units, towards achieving the common goals set in the team headed by each head of unit". Training program's main goal is *"to adopt those characteristics and behaviors that will develop and/or improve the leadership of head of units in the workplace to achieve common goals of their team/department of unit and their service in general"* (TP Design, 2023: 5-6).

The duration of the training programs is 21 hours for the 1st level, while for the 2nd level the duration is 35 hours and in one case 28 hours. The design of almost all TPs lasted about 3 months per TP.

In parallel, there is the designing of a TP for the accreditation for the Human Resources Development Consultants under the title "Training & Accreditation of Human Resources Development Consultants".

It is a 70 hours TP, using blended (synchronous live & asynchronous distance) learning (depending on the topic), having as its main objective the framework for exercising the responsibilities of the Human Resources Development Consultant mainly being the:

- ✓ Provision of advisory assistance and support to staff mainly in matters of implementation of the evaluation system and development plans for civil servants and their head of units,
- ✓ Support and co-assistance to the organizational unit for matters of administrative support in human resources in matters of implementation of the evaluation system, in the planning of actions to staff development
- ✓ Data collection by the organizational unit responsible for administrative support and human resources regarding the implementation of the staff evaluation system of the relevant body and its supervised bodies
- ✓ Compilation of an annual report on its work, the effectiveness of the policies and individual human resources development actions implemented in the framework of the evaluation system, and
- ✓ Formulation of improvement proposals.

The expected learning outcomes after successfully attending the TP focus on knowing human resources development policies & the concept of Learning Organizations,

describing the concept of knowledge management, being acquainted with the institutional framework and especially the skills-based assessment system per civil servant category, knowing the European Qualifications Framework and the National Qualifications Framework, defining and distinguishing abilities, skills and knowledge, knowing issues related to organizational performance management & training methods, preparing individual and operational development plans, action plans, & training plans, preparing an Annual Report, developing or improving their counseling interview skills, coaching skills, communication skills (active listening, interviewing, empathy...) so that they respond effectively to their responsibilities as HR Development Consultants.

2.2 Synthesis of training programs' design groups & educational methods

For the designing of these TPs, an equal number of working groups (18 groups) were created based on the institutional and regulatory framework of EKDDA. The members of the working groups are members of the Registry of Main Teaching Staff of EKDDA. Regarding the composition of the working groups for TPs for skills development, indicatively are:

- EKDDA executives belonging to the scientific staff of the organization (with different scientific qualities) but also executives belonging to the administrative staff of the organization with experience either in the subject or in the coordination of working groups.
- Officials of the Ministry of Interior (advisors to the Minister and officials of the Ministry), scientific staff and executives who have extensive experience in human resources development issues of the public sector.
- Executives of the National Transparency Authority (NTA) with scientific experience in the legislative framework of the public sector for the design of actions mainly related to the skills of professionalism and integrity.
- Private sector executives who in this case were mainly coaches, psychologists, economists, executives with experience in human resources development in both the private and public sector.

- Executives from the administrative staff of INEP and EKDDA in charge of the coordination work, certification procedures, etc. contributed to the whole effort.

For the effective operation of the groups and for the meetings of their members, relevant technology tools such as webex, what's up, viber, etc. were used.

The proposed methodology is blended, i.e. synchronous distance education & asynchronous education depending on the program and according to the scientific documentation of the members of each working group. The design of the actions took into account the principles of Adult Education as is done in all the Institute's TPs (Rogers, 1999, Kokkos, 2005, Karalis & Papageorgiou, 2012). In the design of each training program, in addition to the detailed description of the thematic units of the program, the description of the educational techniques per thematic unit as well as proposed educational activities are provided.

The educational techniques described in the design of actions for synchronous education have an experiential character as experiential learning plays a central role in all theories about the adult learning process (Leftheriotou 2014:26). Jarvis considers that experiential learning is very important in the learning process of adults in response to a problem or need, but also values experience as a starting point for the process of reflection (Jarvis 2004). For the programs of the Common Evaluation Framework, the following activities are proposed indicatively by the designers both synchronous and asynchronous training:

- Exercises
- Role playing
- Simulations
- Video
- Brainstorming
- Case studies
- Collaborative work - Working and reflection groups

The Training Program's implementation followed the steps below:

- Training workshop for all trainers interested in teaching CSF training programs

- Communication of the program design to the trainers by the scientific coordinators of the program
- Contact of the scientific coordinator with the trainers for questions and highlighting the importance of using examples, case studies and practical applications – In many cases scientific coordinator sent to the trainers useful exercises or case studies to be implemented
- Implementation of the training program
- Monitoring the progress of the evaluation of the programs

At this stage it was deemed necessary to produce training material for each training program in order to facilitate trainers and enhance the participatory nature of the programs.

3. Evaluation remarks of the training offered during the 1st semester 2024

Training activities for the Common Skills Framework are implemented from the beginning of 2024. In this paper, we try to investigate how these TPs are accepted by civil servants and whether they helped them in the acquisition of the skills needed to be developed following their Personal Development Plan, i.e. if and to what extent the expected learning outcomes of the TP were achieved. As mentioned by Vergidis & Karalis (2008) the evaluation "*constitutes a necessary condition regarding the planning, organization and implementation of an educational program*". This means "*the effort to investigate the extent to which the planning of an education process, but also the procedures followed and the choices made during its implementation are considered appropriate and successful*" (Karalis & Papageorgiou, 2012). The study is based on the participants' evaluation for the training programs implemented from 1st of January 2024 till 31st of July 2024.

Data are collected by the writers from the Integrated Information System of INEP from the responses of the electronic evaluation questionnaire. While the results presented here are indicative, they have been derived from data with a high percentage of ratings (85%) relative to the participants (high sample in relation to the population). Limitations of the study are: a. the data collection is based on the INEP evaluation questionnaire and b. the short duration of TPs implementation, so further

monitoring of these evaluation indicators is required in the future as well as the data from the evaluation of the program (evaluation questionnaire) 3 months after participants' return to their working environment.

Regarding the ethics of the study, statistical data is available to INEP/EKDDA and is used only for the needs of this empirical part of the study, no personal data are used, nor is there any reference to the names and personal details of both the participants in the evaluations, as well as and to trainers evaluated by them.

As observed from the data study, the positive opinions, formulated on the basis of the eleven-point scale (from 0 to 10), approach values of the order of 9 (Excellent) for all the questions of the individual general indicators.

First of all Table 2. Presents the number of Training programs, certified persons and number of evaluation questionnaires.

Training program	No of trainin g progra ms	No of partici pants	No of certified civil servants	No of evaluations
Common Skills Framework: Knowledge management in the public sector – 1 st level	64	1.225	846 (69%)	851 (69,5%)
Common Skills Framework: Professionalism and Integrity of Public Sector Personnel – 1 st level	20	354	244 (73%)	260 (73,45)
Common Skills Framework: Problem solving and creativity in the public sector – 1 st level	75	1.515	1.135 (75%)	1.129 (74,5%)
Common Skills Framework: Public sector leadership – 1 st level	47	992	807 (81%)	761 (76,7%)
Common Skills Framework:	33	652	503 (77%)	498 (76%)

Teamwork in the public sector – 1 st level				
Common Skills Framework: Public Sector Organization & Planning – 1 st level	52	947	691 (73%)	686 (72,4%)
Common Skills Framework: Result-oriented - 1 st level	33	697	415 (59,5%)	510 (73%)
Common Skills Framework: Citizen oriented – 1 st level	23	489	355 (72,5%)	379 (77,5%)
Common Skills Framework: Adaptability of the civil servant – 1 st level	36	802	583 (72,6%)	596 (74,3%)
Total	383	7.673	5.579 (72,7%)	5.670 (73,9%)

Table 2. Number of Training programs, certified persons and number of evaluation questionnaires

First observation point: the number of training programs differs from title to title and depends on the applications registered in the system.

Second observation point: the number of certified civil servants is less to the participants' number because some civil servants don't pass the final test of the program.

Third observation point: the number of evaluations is usually less to the number of participants because all participants don't submit the evaluation questionnaire.

Fourth observation point: during the first semester of 2024 INEP has implemented training programs of the first level according to the applications recorded in the evaluation system of the Ministry of the Interior. The TPs of the 2nd level are addressed to heads of units so fewer applications were registered and far fewer TPs were implemented.

Regarding to the satisfaction of participants for the TP, this is recorded in Table 3 below. The degree of satisfaction can be found at the end of the questionnaire and

concerns the overall evaluation of the TP. The rating is based on the 10-point Likert scale where 0: not at all to 10: Too much satisfaction.

CSF Training program's title	Training Programs' overall evaluation
Common Skills Framework: Knowledge management in the public sector – 1st level	9,01
Common Skills Framework: Professionalism and Integrity of Public Sector Personnel – 1st level	9
Common Skills Framework: Problem solving and creativity in the public sector – 1st level	8,79
Common Skills Framework: Public sector leadership – 1st level	9,06
Common Skills Framework: Teamwork in the public sector – 1st level	9,12
Common Skills Framework: Public Sector Organization & Planning – 1st level	8,76
Common Skills Framework: Result-oriented - 1st level	8,92
Common Skills Framework: Citizen oriented – 1st level	8,63
Common Skills Framework: Adaptability of the civil servant – 1st level	8,86

Table 3. CSF Training programs' overall evaluation

We also studied the evaluation of a component that concerns the utilization of the trainer's methodology and techniques, i.e. the utilization of practical applications during the course. This assessment is reflected in Table 4 below.

CSF Training program’s title	Evaluation of “Trainers’ methodology & techniques (practical application)”
Common Skills Framework: Knowledge management in the public sector – 1st level	9,26
Common Skills Framework: Professionalism and Integrity of Public Sector Personnel – 1st level	9,32
Common Skills Framework: Problem solving and creativity in the public sector – 1st level	9,18
Common Skills Framework: Public sector leadership – 1st level	9,26
Common Skills Framework: Teamwork in the public sector – 1st level	9,25
Common Skills Framework: Public Sector Organization & Planning – 1st level	9,18
Common Skills Framework: Result-oriented - 1st level	9,28
Common Skills Framework: Citizen oriented – 1st level	9,11
Common Skills Framework: Adaptability of the civil servant – 1st level	9,16

Table 4. Evaluation of “Trainers’ methodology & techniques (practical applications)”

We note that the evaluation of this component is very high, which can be attributed to the training that took place for the trainers who were interested in teaching in these TPs but also to the fact that many members of the EKDDA Main Educational Registry have experience in adult education.

Concluding Remarks & Proposals

Law 4940/2022 brought dynamic changes for the human resources of the Greek Public Administration. Decoupling evaluation from performance and linking it to performance improvement, with the aim of increasing the efficiency of the public sector, is a first and essential innovation. The definition of the Common Skills Framework is an innovation of Law 4940/2022 and enables the development and improvement of Greek Public Administration's staff through training but also through on-the-job training, coaching and mentoring. In this way, the civil servant becomes a co-formulator of his own evaluation, through which he/she will develop his/her skills. In addition, the designing by expert groups of the respective TPs that takes into account the needs of the trainees and is appropriately designed (Pavli-Korre, Leftheriotou, 2020) seems: a. to enhance the effectiveness of the evaluation system to the extent that these actions have been decided by the civil servant himself and contribute to the creation of a Personal Development Plan and b. that they have been positively accepted by civil servants from a first study of evaluation results where a high degree of satisfaction is observed from their participation in training.

In conclusion, the anthropocentric dimension in the evaluation of civil servants gave the opportunity to design new training programs aiming at skills' development. Thus, the design of the TPs was based on the principles of adult education both in terms of content, methodology and training techniques. The training activities proposed by the TPs' designers and implemented enhanced the development and/or improvement of civil servants' skills taking into account the basic principles of adult education and have an experiential character (Rogers, 1999, Jarvis, 2003, Kokkos, 2005).

On the occasion of this extremely interesting experience we had and we still have in planning and implementing programs aimed at developing / improving skills, what we can suggest for the synthesis of design teams is:

- a) the greatest possible participation of individuals/experts with experience in the skills to be developed
- b) participation of experts in the design of adult education programs who have the relevant education or experience and

- c) participation of experts with knowledge of behavioral psychology or counseling / coaching for the best design of educational techniques and methods that will enhance effectiveness in skills development.

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Open educational practices with Wikipedia: a scoping review

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Abstract

Context: Over the last two decades, there has been a growing recognition of Wikipedia's role in education, transitioning from a debated information source to an accepted educational tool. The current study systematically examines the existing body of research on Wikipedia's role as an Open Educational Resource (OER) and an open educational practice (OEP) in higher education. **Method:** A scoping review methodology was adopted. A comprehensive search was conducted across English and French language databases, covering literature from 2006 to 2023. The review followed the PCC (Participants, Concept, Context) criteria and involved a two-stage iterative process of data extraction and analysis. A total of 322 publications were selected for detailed analysis. **Results:** More than three quarters (77.3%) of the corpus present empirical research, while 22.5% consist of theoretical or conceptual studies on the role of Wikipedia in higher education. Literature reviews account for only 2.2% of the total corpus. The main empirical approaches used are narrative research (23.7%) and surveys (23.3%). Other approaches include evaluation research (10.8%), development research (10%), case studies (9.2%) and qualitative description (9.2%). The analysis of the empirical papers revealed that research on Wikipedia's use as OEP has increased significantly since 2015, surpassing studies focused on its use as OER. Undergraduate students are the most frequent participants, with 55% of OEP-related research targeting this group. The study identified trends across academic disciplines, with Humanities and Social Sciences most frequently engaging with Wikipedia as OEP, while STEM fields showed lower engagement. **Conclusion:** This scoping review is the first to provide a comprehensive overview of peer-reviewed publications on the utilisation of Wikipedia as an (OER) and as (OEP) in higher education. It can serve as a foundation for more in-depth and specialised investigations into both aspects of Wikipedia as a tool for open pedagogy in higher education.

Keywords: Wikipedia, higher education, open educational resource, open educational practice, open pedagogy, scoping review.

1. Introduction

1.1. Open Education : from OER to OEP through open pedagogy.

The evolution of the contemporary Open Education movement commenced with an emphasis on Open Educational Resources (OER) and has since expanded to encompass Open Educational Practices (OEP). This is not a novel concept, as open education has its origins in open pedagogy, which places emphasis on fundamental values such as autonomy, freedom, democracy and participation (Paquette, 1979).

Educational Resources (OER) are teaching, learning, and research materials that are either in the public domain or made available under an intellectual property license, allowing for free use and modification by others. In line with Wiley's (Wiley, Bliss, & McEwen, 2014) 5R framework, UNESCO (2019) defines OER as "teaching, learning, and research materials in any format and medium that reside in the public domain or are under copyright but have been released under an open license, permitting no-cost access, re-use, re-purpose, adaptation, and redistribution by others."

The broad definition of OER as freely accessible resources for educational purposes is particularly valuable, as it encompasses any open resource that can be used for educational purposes, even if it was not originally created with the intent of teaching—such as Wikipedia. As the use of OER expanded, discussions shifted towards open practices, emphasizing the open sharing of not only content but also teaching and learning processes. This led to a revival of the concept of open pedagogy, now intertwined with ideas like open licenses, and focusing on knowledge as co-constructed and socially contextualized. This approach is inextricably linked to the social justice paradigm, with the objective of enhancing the accessibility of education and empowering students to assume the roles of both consumers and creators of knowledge.

Scholars such as Cronin (2017) posit that OEP includes the creation, utilisation and repurposing of OER, but extends beyond this to encompass the promotion of pedagogical practices that engage students in peer learning, knowledge creation and empowerment. This more expansive conceptualisation of OEP prioritises the process of learning, viewing openness as a means of fostering active learner participation and collaboration. The move towards OEP represents a shift from viewing openness as a property of resources to seeing it as a characteristic of educational processes. OEP is increasingly recognized as a key enabler of quality, access, and innovation in higher education, and part of a larger open education ecosystem, which also includes open access, open science, and open data.

1.2. Wikipedia : the largest open educational resource in the world.

In 2021, the collaborative encyclopedia Wikipedia, the flagship project of the Wikimedia Foundation, celebrated its 20th anniversary (Reagle & Koerner, 2020). The statistics available on the [Wikipedia Statistics page](#) demonstrate the remarkable success of this initiative, which aims to create "the sum of all knowledge" through open participation from anyone with internet access. With over 61 million pages available in 300 languages (and over 6.8 million articles in the English version alone), Wikipedia has become a key reference point for factual information. Wikipedia is frequently the first result returned by Google searches, and its content is also extracted for use in the Google knowledge panel, which provides summaries of searched topics. Furthermore, information from Wikipedia is used worldwide to power voice assistants such as Google Assistant, Apple's Siri, and Amazon's Alexa. It has also been used to train large language models, including ChatGPT. In light of the pervasive use of Wikipedia among students, it can be regarded as the preeminent open educational resource globally. Its content is published under an open license (CC-BY) that permits free access, utilization, adaptation, and redistribution without constraints. Indeed, since its inception in 2001, the

encyclopedia has played a pivotal role in the movement advocating for broad free access to information in the form of open resources for teaching, learning, and training, alongside initiatives such as Open Courseware.

1.3. Wikipedia, Open Pedagogy and Open Educational Practices.

The perception of Wikipedia in higher education has undergone a significant transformation over the past two decades. Following an initial period of scepticism regarding its value as a source of information, attitudes have undergone a significant transformation. Despite initial reluctance from higher education institutions (Ejikman, 2010), the potential of Wikipedia for OEP, within the paradigm of open pedagogy, has been increasingly acknowledged. McDowell and Vetter (2022) observe that educators and librarians are now actively incorporating Wikipedia into their OEP initiatives. This may entail using student contributions to improve encyclopaedia articles or organising community-led edit-a-thons to improve specific topics. In the context of higher education, the utilisation of Wikipedia as an OEP instrument encourages the collaborative construction of knowledge, empowering students to engage with content in a critical manner and contribute to the global knowledge base, thereby transforming their role from that of a consumer to that of a creator of knowledge. Recently, there has been a growing interest in utilising Wikipedia within OEP framework for critical, feminist and social justice initiatives (Bali, Cronin & Jhangiani, 2020). The participatory model of Wikipedia aligns with the core principles of open pedagogy, which encourage collaboration, agency and a commitment to the democratisation of access to education and information.

Nevertheless, there is a paucity of research examining the intersections between Wikipedia as an OER and its utilisation in OEP (McDowell & Vetter, 2022). Notwithstanding the recognition of OER as a multidimensional concept with fluid boundaries, recent comprehensive reviews of OER omit Wikipedia from their discussions (Cronin & MacLaren, 2018; Ehlers, 2011; Koseoglu & Bozkurt, 2018; Nascimbeni & Burgos, 2019). Furthermore, although there is a growing corpus of research on the utilisation of Wikipedia in higher education, few comprehensive reviews have been conducted to provide an overarching picture of the field (Konieczny, 2016; Maggio et al, 2020; Mesgari et al, 2015; Smith, 2020). The precise nature of the research being conducted on Wikipedia in higher education, particularly in relation to its role as both an OER and an OEP, remains unclear.

In light of Wikipedia's pivotal position within the open education ecosystem, it is imperative to gain a comprehensive understanding of how it is being utilised to implement the tenets of open pedagogy in higher education. Furthermore, given that Wikipedia is based on asynchronous and collaborative writing technologies, this knowledge is particularly relevant in the context of distance learning in higher education. This is especially true given that, like distance education, Wikipedia's ultimate aim is to democratise access to education and knowledge.

2. Research question and aims

The overarching research question guiding this study is to examine the extent and nature of existing research on Wikipedia, with a particular focus on identifying the key characteristics of studies examining its use in higher education. The overarching objective is to present a comprehensive overview of academic research examining the perceptions and applications of Wikipedia in higher education teaching and learning. In this paper, we concentrate on the perceptions and applications of Wikipedia as an OER and as an OEP. The specific aim is to delineate the principal characteristics of research on open pedagogy with Wikipedia in higher education.

3. Method

A scoping review was deemed the most appropriate methodology for providing a comprehensive overview of a potentially large and diverse body of literature, particularly given the complexity and heterogeneity of the

topic. The review was conducted in accordance with the framework set forth by Arksey and O'Malley (2005), refined by Levac et al. (2010), and further enhanced with recommendations from Tricco et al. (2016) to address specific challenges in ensuring systematic rigor and replicability within a collaborative process.

The research team comprised the principal investigator (BP) and five successive research assistants (DR, SC, GST and NEB). The review was conducted in accordance with the five of the six stages outlined by Levac et al. (2010). The process involved the following five stages: (1) identifying the research question, (2) identifying relevant studies, (3) screening and selecting studies, (4) mapping the data, and (5) collating, summarising and reporting the findings. The sixth stage, stakeholder consultation, will be conducted in collaboration with Wikimedia Canada in the future.

In order to enhance the scope and systematicity of the review, the process of searching (stage 2), selecting (stage 3) and mapping (stage 4) data was conducted in two iterations. The initial iteration was conducted between January 2018 and March 2021 and included iterative refinement loops at stages 1, 2 and 3 (BP, DR, NL, SC). The second iteration, which aimed to update the sources, took place between July 2021 and September 2023 (BP, GST, NEB). During this period, significant refinements were made to the analysis grid used in Stage 4, which resulted in the recoding of the entire corpus. The final mapping of the sources was completed in December 2023 by the principal investigator (BP), with assistance from GST and NEB.

Stage 1: Research question

The Principal Investigator (BP) formulated a broad research question as follows: "What is the extent and nature of research on the use of Wikipedia in higher education?" Following the initial exploratory screening in Stage 2, the research question was discussed with the research assistant (DR) in order to ascertain the scope of the term 'uses'. It was decided that the focus should be narrowed to encompass solely human uses and perceptions, specifically those of students, teachers and librarians, and that non-human factors such as algorithms or information systems should be excluded.

Stage 2: Database search

Due to linguistic considerations, the research was limited to articles published in English and French. In the English language, the following databases were utilised: Education Source (EBSCO), LearnTechLib, Psychology & Behavioral Sciences Collection (EBSCO), and Francis, in addition to the multidisciplinary database Academic Search Complete. In French, the databases CAIRN.info, Érudit, Francis and JSTOR were searched.

A comparable list of keywords was devised for both languages, and the search was executed using Boolean formulas. In English, the search string employed was as follows: The search terms "Wikipedia" and one of the following terms, "Teach*," "Learn*," "Student*," "Academic*," "Pedagog*," "Education," or "Higher Education," were used in combination with one another in the abstract or title of articles. In French, the search string was as follows: "Wikipédia (in abstract or title) AND (Enseign* OR Apprenant* OR Apprentissage OR Étudiant* OR Académique* OR Pédagog* OR Éducation OR Enseignement supérieur) (in text).

To address potential limitations of this strategy, we employed a 'snowballing' technique, whereby reference lists were screened and the 'cited by' function of Google Scholar was utilised to examine the first 50 references. This approach enabled a balance to be struck between breadth and depth of search.

The initial search was conducted using the search terms outlined above and included papers published up to December 2020. Updated search using the same search terms, included publications up to August 2023. At this second iteration, the Medline database was consulted in order to identify studies on the utilization of

Wikipedia in the fields of medical education and health sciences. Furthermore, additional studies that had not been identified previously were incorporated during this phase.

All citations were imported into the web-based bibliographic manager EndNote, which was accessible to the research team. Duplicate citations were removed manually and iteratively.

Stage 3: Screening and Selecting Studies

The studies were evaluated according to the PCC framework (Tricco et al., 2016), which established the following eligibility criteria: the studies must focus on the uses and perceptions of Wikipedia (concept), by faculty, students, and library professionals (participants), within the context of higher education (context).

The title and abstract of each citation were independently screened by two reviewers (DR and NL), and any discrepancies were resolved by the third reviewer (BP) during online meetings. In the absence of an abstract, the title was read in full.

Studies that did not align with the conceptual framework and focused on human uses and perceptions were excluded. For example, studies evaluating the quality of Wikipedia articles using information systems and algorithms, as well as those analyzing political, sociological, anthropological, linguistic, or psychological aspects of Wikipedia in contexts broader than higher education, were excluded. Due to practical limitations, the review was restricted to peer-reviewed articles and book chapters, excluding monographs, dissertations, theses, preprints, newsletters, and presentations from Wikimedia Foundation events.

In total, the process yielded 322 papers published between 2006 and August 2023.

Figure 1 presents the PRISMA flowchart of the study selection and screening process.

Figure 1: PRISMA flowchart of study selection process.

Stage 4: Data Extraction and Charting

In the first iteration phase, the analytical grid was developed, discussed, and tested by the principal investigator (BP) and two research assistants (DR, SC). The grid was designed to identify the key variables related to the three themes of the PCC framework : participants, context, and concept.

In the second iteration phase, the analytical grid was refined and finalised, and this version was employed to recode the entire dataset. The data extraction and charting were completed in December 2023 by the principal investigator and two other research assistants (GST, NEB).

The final version of the analytical grid incorporated elements from the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) (Hong et al., 2018) to facilitate the extraction and categorization of empirical research types. Countries were coded using the International Standard for Country Codes (ISO 3166), while educational levels and scientific fields were coded in accordance with the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) (UNESCO, 2011; 2013). For each record, we extracted the following information: 1. Year of publication, 2. Country where the study was conducted (or the country of residence of the corresponding author if the study was international or the country of conduct was unavailable). 3. Type of paper: theoretical, literature review, or empirical. For empirical studies, additional details were extracted: 4. Type of empirical method. 5. Educational level. 6. Academic field and Academic discipline. 8. Type of learning or teaching activity involving Wikipedia, categorized as either OER or OEP. 9. Perceptions and use of Wikipedia by students, teachers, or librarians.

4. Results

4.1. Overall view

The corpus under examination comprises 322 articles published between 2006 and August 2023. During the initial six-year period following the inception of Wikipedia, the volume of research output exhibited a gradual and consistent growth, increasing from four publications in 2006 to seventeen in 2011. Since 2012, the number of annual publications has remained relatively stable, with an average of 17 to 23 articles per year. Notably, there was a slight increase in 2020, with 35 publications, many of which were empirical studies from North American projects linked to the Wikimedia Education initiative.

In terms of geographical distribution, 163 publications (50%) were authored by researchers based in the United States. Four other countries contributed 10 or more publications, including Canada (22), Australia (19), France (11) and the United Kingdom (10), for a total of 62 publications (19.2%). The remaining 97 publications (30%) were produced by researchers from 38 different countries.

In terms of research focus, more than three quarters (77.3%) of the publications present empirical research, while 22.5% consist of theoretical or conceptual studies on the role of Wikipedia in higher education. Literature reviews account for only 2.2% of the total corpus.

The main empirical approaches used are narrative research (23.7%) and surveys (23.3%). Other approaches include evaluation research (10.8%), development research (10%), case studies (9.2%) and qualitative description (9.2%). Less common methods include mixed methods research (5%), experimental studies (randomised or non-randomised controlled trials, 4.8%) and cohort studies (before and after design, 3.2%).

Regarding academic fields, nearly one-third of the publications (31.3%) were categorized as covering multiple fields or unspecified fields. The Humanities and Arts (23.3%) and Health and Welfare (17.7%) together accounted for approximately 40% of the corpus. These are followed by the Social Sciences (13.7%) and the Sciences (including natural, physical, and computer sciences), which represented 8.4% of the empirical studies. Research was far less prevalent in the fields of Education (4%), Agriculture, Forestry, and Veterinary Science (1.2%), and Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction (0.4%).

In terms of educational level, almost half of the publications (49.8%) focused on the bachelor or equivalent level. Approximately one-third (37.3%) of the studies were categorized as focusing on multiple fields or an unspecified level of higher education. Research addressing the master's level comprised just 6.8% of empirical studies, while those on short-cycle tertiary education and the doctoral level were scarce, representing 1.2% and 0.8% respectively. Additionally, 4.2% of the publications primarily concerned faculty members engaged in postgraduate or doctoral education.

Of the empirical publications analysed, 52.6% examine how students perceive and use Wikipedia, while 42.8% focus on the perceptions and use of Wikipedia by teachers. Only 3.6% of the studies explore the perceptions and use of Wikipedia by library professionals.

In terms of the type of educational practice under consideration, 40 % of the studies (n=100) describe and analyse the use of Wikipedia as OER, while 60 % (n=149) focus on OEP. Table 1 provides an overview of the results obtained from the analysis of the corpus.

Table 1: General characteristics of included publications.

Characteristics (All records)	Number (n=322)	Percentage (100%)
Publication year		
2006-2008	22	6,8
2009-2011	47	14,6
2012-2014	64	19,9
2015-2017	58	18,0
2018-2020	74	23,0
2021-2023	57	17,7
Type of research		
Theoretical	66	20,5
Lit. review	7	2,2
Empirical	249	77,3
Characteristics (Empirical studies)	Number (n=249)	Percentage (100%)
Method		
Narrative research	59	23,7
Qualitative description	23	9,2
Case study	23	9,2
Survey	58	23,3
Experiment (RTC, NRCT)	12	4,8
Cohort study (Before-After)	8	3,2
Evaluation research	27	10,8
Development research	25	10,0
Mixed methods	14	5,6
Academic field		
General (covering multiple fields or unspecified field)	78	31,3
Agriculture, forestry, veterinary science	3	1,2
Education	10	4,0
Engineering, manufacturing and construction	1	0,4
Humanities and Arts	58	23,3
Health and Welfare	44	17,7
Sciences (natural, physical, mathematical, computer science)	21	8,4
Social Sciences	34	13,7
Educational Level		
General (covering multiple levels or unspecified level)	93	37,3
Short-cycle tertiary education	3	1,2
Bachelor's or equivalent level	124	49,8
Master's or equivalent level	17	6,8
Doctoral or equivalent level	2	0,8
Postgraduate or doctoral education (typically for faculty members)	10	4,0
Perceptions and use of Wikipedia by		
Students	131	52,6
Teachers	109	43,8
Librarians	9	3,6
Perceptions and uses of Wikipedia as		
OER	100	40
OEP	149	60

4.2. Detailed analysis of empirical research on Wikipedia as OER vs OEP.

Evolution of research over time.

The results demonstrate a gradual increase in research on the use of Wikipedia in higher education until 2020, with the exception of a decline in 2014. The year 2020 represents a peak in the number of publications, after which a decline was observed. It is important to note, however, that the data for 2023 is incomplete, as it only includes articles published up to August 2023.

It is worthy of note that research on the utilisation of Wikipedia as OEP has been a prominent feature from the outset. The only years in which research on Wikipedia as OER surpassed that on OEP were 2010, 2011, and 2013. Since 2015, publications focusing on Wikipedia as OEP have consistently outnumbered those on its use as OER, with the exception of 2023, for which the data are incomplete.

Figure 2 presents data on the evolution of research over time regarding the use of Wikipedia as OER versus OEP.

Figure 2: Evolution of research over time regarding the use of Wikipedia as OER versus OEP.

Methods used in research on Wikipedia as OER versus OEP.

Two research methods are used in almost half of the publications on the use of Wikipedia in higher education: narrative research (n = 59) and survey research (n = 58), which account for 23.6% and 23.2% of all empirical publications respectively.

However, the methods used differ depending on whether researchers are interested in Wikipedia as OER or as OEP.

The data show that research on Wikipedia as OER primarily uses the survey method (n = 43), which is the basis for 43% of research on the perception and use of Wikipedia as a information resource. The second method is evaluative research (n = 23, or 23%), which mainly involves assessing the quality of Wikipedia articles,

sometimes by comparing them with other academic sources of information in a given field. These two methods account for 66% of research on Wikipedia as OER.

The picture is different for research on Wikipedia as OEP. The dominant research methods here are narrative research (n = 53 or 35,5%), development research (n = 22 or 14,7%), case studies (n = 21 or 14%), qualitative description (n = 15 or 10%) and surveys (n = 15 or 10%). These five methods are used as OEP in 84,2% of research publications on Wikipedia.

Figure 3 presents data on the methods used in research on Wikipedia as OER compared to OEP.

Figure 3: Methods used in research on Wikipedia as an OER compared to OEP.

Educational levels in research on Wikipedia as an OER versus OEP.

Among empirical studies on Wikipedia as OER, 47% (n=47) cover multiple educational levels or do not specify the level. When specified, the majority of research—42% (n=42) focuses on undergraduate students.

In contrast, research on Wikipedia as OEP is predominantly conducted at the undergraduate level, with 55% (n=82) of publications involving undergraduate student projects. Studies that address multiple educational levels or do not specify the level constitute 30.9% (n=46) of these publications.

Very little research has been conducted on OER or OEP with Master’s or equivalent level students, accounting for only 5% (n=5) and 8.1% (n=12) of studies, respectively. Even fewer studies focus on doctoral students: only 1.2% (n=2) of OEP-related publications, and none for OER-related research, explore the perceptions and uses of Wikipedia at the doctoral level.

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of educational levels addressed in research on Wikipedia as OER compared to OEP.

Figure 4: Distribution of educational levels addressed in research on Wikipedia as OER compared to OEP.

Academic fields in research on Wikipedia as an OER versus OEP.

With regard to the academic disciplines represented in the empirical studies, 37% (n=37) of publications on Wikipedia as OER and 27.5% (n=41) of publications on OEP cover multiple academic fields or do not provide sufficient information to specify the academic domain. When this information is available, the humanities and arts lead the way in research on the perceptions and uses of Wikipedia as OEP, accounting for 28.8% (n=43) of all OEP studies. Both the social sciences and health and welfare have an equal representation, with 14.7% (n=22) of OEP-related publications each. The remaining 14.3% of OEP studies are distributed as follows: The remaining fields represented in the empirical studies are Sciences (7.3%, n=11), Education (4.6%, n=7), Agriculture, Forestry, Veterinary Science (1.3%, n=2), and Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction (0.7%, n=1).

With regard to Wikipedia as OER, the field of Health and Welfare is the most represented, comprising 22% (n=22) of the studies, followed by the Humanities and Arts at 15% (n=15) and the Social Sciences at 12% (n=12). The representation of other academic fields in OER studies is analogous to that observed in OEP: Sciences 10% (n=10), Education 3% (n=3), Agriculture, Forestry, Veterinary Science 2% (n=2), with no research identified on Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction.

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of academic fields in research on Wikipedia as OER in comparison to OEP.

Figure 5: Distribution of academic fields in research on Wikipedia as OER in comparison to OEP.

5. Discussion

The results of this scoping review illustrate that academic research on the utilisation of Wikipedia as OER and as OEP in higher education is both extensive and varied. Furthermore, the findings indicate that studies on Wikipedia as OEP have increased significantly since 2015, exceeding those examining its role as OER. This shift suggests that educators are increasingly aware of the value of engaging students in the process of knowledge co-construction, thereby enabling them to contribute to a public knowledge base rather than merely consuming information. It also demonstrates that over the past two decades, Wikipedia has transitioned from a debated information source to an accepted educational tool.

It is worthy of note that the majority of research in both the OER and OEP contexts is conducted at the undergraduate level. This trend appears to reflect an increasing emphasis on the development of essential academic skills, such as critical thinking and digital literacy, at the outset of students' higher education journeys. However, the paucity of research focused on graduate students, particularly at the Master's and doctoral levels, is surprising, given the expectation that advanced students would have much to contribute to and learn from the knowledge-building process on Wikipedia. Similarly, it may be assumed that, given the rapid evolution of knowledge in all academic fields, advanced students continue to rely on Wikipedia as an OER, albeit in different ways than undergraduate students. It would be beneficial to investigate this matter further and to gain a deeper understanding of the social, institutional, or economic factors that may explain why researchers and educators appear less inclined to promote participation of advanced students in the creation and public sharing of knowledge on Wikipedia.

With regard to the academic disciplines in which Wikipedia is the subject of study, the review findings indicate that it is most frequently used as OEP in the humanities and arts, followed by the social sciences and health and welfare. Conversely, there is a notable dearth of research examining the utilisation and perceptions of Wikipedia in the context of STEM fields and professional disciplines such as agriculture and engineering. These findings may be surprising, given that Wikipedia's editorial guidelines encourages objectivity and a neutral point of view. Consequently, one might have expected these disciplines to be ideal for the sharing of well-established scientific knowledge. This appears to be the case in medical disciplines within the field of health

and welfare, where research tends to focus on both the quality of medical information available on Wikipedia and the dissemination of high-quality information.

6. Conclusions

This scoping review is the first to provide a comprehensive overview of peer-reviewed publications on the utilisation of Wikipedia as OER and as a OEP in higher education. The present systematic overview of research conducted over the past 20 years can now serve as a foundation for more in-depth and specialised investigations into both aspects of Wikipedia as a tool for open pedagogy in higher education, focusing on its role as both a resource and a process for knowledge construction, sharing and learning.

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Relating Study Courses with Open educational Resources using hierarchical controlled vocabularies and advanced subject classification tools

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Abstract

This paper aims to present methods and tools for relating study courses to appropriate (Open) Educational Resources. After a reference to the general categories of document search and retrieval methods, emphasis is placed on the use of hierarchical control vocabularies in the form of subject taxonomies. It is shown with concrete examples how a subject taxonomy is linked to a repository of resources (textbooks, in particular) in order to help users find the desired resources for a topic of interest.

For repositories lacking a subject classification functionality or for unclassified material of any source, a new method for automatic hierarchical classification is presented. It builds on previous work that leverages a specific controlled vocabulary of subjects (the KALLIPOS thematic taxonomy) and extensive metadata of books and courses [e.g., Table of Contents (ToC) or extended abstract] to classify them into a closed set of subject categories. This approach is extended here to hierarchical classification, so that courses and learning materials are placed as deep as possible in the nodes of the thematic hierarchy. This co-placement can give the desired relationship between them: similar educational entities share the same node or neighbouring nodes in the taxonomy.

Keywords: educational resources, hierarchical classification, KALLIPOS, subject taxonomy textbook repositories

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1. Introduction and background

Searching for and finding learning material suitable for a specific educational activity (university course, blended intensive program-BIP, lifelong learning study, etc.) is of paramount importance, both for the teacher and for the student/learner. Using general-purpose search tools, such as Google and Yahoo search engines, or AI tools, such as ChatGPT, one can discover appropriate material from the Cloud. However, it is often necessary to limit the search within specific scholarly collections of textbooks or other learning objects (e.g. the Springer e-book collection), where general web search tools do not easily penetrate and/or focus. In such cases, specialized tools and book recommender systems are needed, with specifications “tailored” to the available Collection of educational material. Over the course of the last two decades a multitude of such methods and tools have been developed and proposed, roughly categorised as follows:

(i) Keyword-based search. It is the traditional technique that relies on users giving words or phrases related to the content they are looking for. The search engine then retrieves documents or books that contain those specific terms, either in the title, abstract, metadata, or in the full text, according to specific priorities. Advanced functioning allows the use of logical operators (AND, OR, NOT, e.g., *history AND mathematics*) and wildcards (symbols like * or ? to represent one or more unknown characters) (Baeza-Yates & Ribeiro-Neto, 2011; Manning et al., 2008).

(ii) Subject-based search. It relies on structured metadata, particularly **subject headings** or classification systems, like the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) or the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) used by librarians. Books are categorized on the basis of subjects or topics, allowing users to find material by navigating through the defined subject hierarchies (Svenonius, 2000; Taylor & Joudrey, 2009).

(iii) Citation-based Search. It uses bibliographic references to find related books or articles, in two modes of operation: Backward Citation Search (find sources that a book cites) or Forward Citation Search (find works that cite a specific book) (Bornmann & Daniel, 2008).

(iv) Machine Learning (ML) methods. Nowadays we are witnessing an explosion of ML-based information retrieval, following the general trend of using AI in almost all fields of human activity. Combined with Natural Language Processing - NLP (Jurafsky & Martin, 2024), such techniques can enhance document search by “understanding” the meaning behind queries and making predictions based on past search behavior, content similarity, or contextual information. Three main categories of ML methods for document searching may be distinguished:

- (a) Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI): Uses mathematical techniques (like Singular Value Decomposition - SVD) to discover the hidden relationships between terms in large collections, improving the matching of documents to queries even when exact words do not match.
- (b) Word Embeddings, e.g., Word2Vec (Mikolov et al., 2013), Bidirectional Encoder representations from transformers -BERT (Devlin et al., 2019): Used to represent words in high-dimensional vectors based on context and meaning, enabling finer-grained understanding of relationships between terms.
- (c) Neural Networks (Deep Learning): Models that learn from large amounts of data to infer patterns in user queries and content, allowing for complex, dynamic searches.

Despite the great advances in Machine Learning and other AI-based techniques, the use of keywords remains the most straightforward and convenient method of searching. All Document Repositories are equipped with relevant tools to locate search-words either in the metadata (title, abstract, set of assigned keywords) or in the full text. There may be problems, however, related to the precision and recall of the derived results, especially when the search is made in large collections of voluminous texts (e.g. books) without appropriate metadata or when the keywords are freely chosen by the archivist or the user of the material attempting the search.

An improvement in the accuracy of the results of keyword-based search can be obtained by limiting the keywords within a set of standardized terms called *controlled vocabulary*. **Subject Taxonomies (ST)**, in particular, are hierarchical vocabularies of thematic terms, offering a stable reference to concepts and scholarly resources in a structured and consistent manner and allowing semantic classification and search

methods to be applied on them. Sound examples of STs are the already mentioned Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH, <https://www.loc.gov/aba/publications/FreeLCSH/freelcsh.html>), Medical Subject Headings (MeSH, <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>), UNESCO Thesaurus (<https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/>) and FAO/AGROVOC (<https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>). Relating a subject taxonomy with a repository of resources and creating links/indexes (through off-line processing) from subjects to resources provides an efficient and friendly resource recommender system.

In a recent work (Makris & Mitrou, 2023), we introduced a new method for the analysis and application of multi-subject book classification. The proposed methodology uses a bilingual subject taxonomy, the KALLIPOS vocabulary (<http://dx.doi.org/10.57713/kallipos-356>, <http://skosmos.cn.ntua.gr/Skosmos/kallipos/en/page/0>), to automatically assign subjects to individual books and collections of books. An important advantage of the proposed method, in contrast to other previous multi-label classifications, is its ability to assign accurate weights to each subject contributing to a specific book or book collection. Additionally, by focusing on the ToC rather than the entire book, one can save time and eliminate unnecessary words that do not significantly contribute to the book subject matter. By analogy and for the same reasons, experienced librarians do not need to read the entire book in order to classify it; only the ToC is enough for them to make their choice. The multi-subject classification method was systematically applied and tested on two different book collections: the Springer e-book collection (in the English language) and the KALLIPOS open textbook collection (in the Greek language), thanks to the bilingualism of the KALLIPOS vocabulary (Makris et al., 2024).

In the present paper, we extend the work presented in Makris & Mitrou (2023) to a hierarchical setting. At every node of the subject taxonomy the vocabulary is updated by filtering out those terms that have low **discriminating ability** for the child subjects of the node. This filtering is performed by applying an entropy threshold (terms with a rather flat distribution over the subjects do not have a discriminating power and exhibit high entropy). Then, the dominate subjects (one or two) are retained and indicate the path(s) towards the next lower level. We stop at the nodes where only few terms remain active in the vocabulary. At the end of this process, every term of the vocabulary is assigned a set of paths in the taxonomy, with specific subject weights (distribution) at each node of the path. A simple summation of the subject weights for the terms appearing in a document gives the subject distribution of the document, again at every node of the hierarchy.

After this introduction, the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives concrete examples of searching for textbooks in open repositories by using controlled vocabularies (in the form of subject taxonomies) associated with them. Section 3 is devoted to the proposed algorithm for automatic hierarchical classification of books, based on their ToC and a specific thematic vocabulary. In section 4, the problem of relating study courses with resources (textbooks) by applying the proposed methods is addressed. In the final section, 5, the main results are summarized and some directions for further work are suggested.

2. Using Controlled Vocabularies for book classification and searching

As mentioned earlier, in the introduction, controlled vocabularies are standardized sets of terms or phrases that are used in building thesauri, subject taxonomies and other classification schemes. Using terms from a controlled vocabulary as keywords in tagging documents (books, articles) and, then, for searching and retrieving these documents out of large collections, can significantly increase the accuracy of the search results. Moreover, by classifying the collection items according to a subject taxonomy, one can find documents that match a subject of interest more easily by simply navigating through the taxonomy nodes. Two distinct use examples of subject taxonomies in connection to resource repositories are presented next.

2.1 Use example 1: KALLIPOS

The KALLIPOS repository (<https://repository.kallipos.gr/>) is a digital archive of academic content available to everyone, with open licensing (Creative Commons – CC licenses). It was developed on the open-source Dspace platform (current version 6.3). Today (October 2024), it includes more than one thousand (>1000) complete textbooks, with more than ten thousand (>10.000) independently annotated book chapters and other learning objects. This material has been created by members of the Academic and Research Community in Greece, in the framework of the KALLIPOS project [<https://kallipos.gr>, (Mitrou & Koutsileou, 2022)]. Most of the textbooks are written in the Greek language; the metadata, however (title, keywords, abstract, ...) is provided bilingual, in Greek and English.

Closely linked to the KALLIPOS repository is the KALLIPOS taxonomy of subject terms (<http://skosmos.cn.ntua.gr/Skosmos/kallipos/en/page/0>), provided in SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) format (<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>). The taxonomy was used by the authors in order to classify their books by affiliating specific subject nodes with them. The paths to the nodes for each book are archived to the repository and shown in the book page at the subject tag [see example in **Figure 1(a)**]. By inverse indexing this metadata, the Repository allows navigation through subjects and can show all documents relevant to a specific subject [**Figure 1(b)**]. To facilitate searching even more, appropriate links to the repository subjects were created for every single term (either a node or a leaf) in the SKOS interface of the vocabulary, as shown in **Figure 2**.

2.2 Use example 2: DESTATIS taxonomy in OERSI

The **Open Educational Resource Search Index** (OERSI, <https://oersi.org/resources>) is a central indexing system aiming at providing access to various open-resource repositories from a single entry-point. It harvests the necessary metadata periodically from the respective open-source platforms through available public APIs and organizes this metadata appropriately. Currently (October 2024) it provides links to more than 87.000 learning objects [more than 10.000 textbooks, from sixteen (16) different providers (KALLIPOS is included as the 3rd larger)]. OERSI is intended to be the main OER hub of the alliance EULIST (European Universities Linking Society and Technology, <https://eulist.university/>).

Subject is among the various filters provided by OERSI for resource search. It uses the subject taxonomy established by DESTATIS (the Federal Statistical Office of Germany), with nine (9) main categories at the first level, sixty-five (65) sub-categories at the second level and 274 leaf-subjects at the 3rd level (<https://skohub.io/dini-ag-kim/hochschulfachersystematik/heads/master/w3id.org/kim/hochschulfachersystematik/scheme.html>).

Figure 3 shows an instance of the DESTATIS subject filter at OERSI.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: The KALLIPOS repository. (a) Subjects assigned to a book. (b) Searching through the subject hierarchy.

Figure 2: The SKOS interface of the KALLIPOS vocabulary and links to the repository.

Figure 3: The DESTATIS subject taxonomy as a filter at the OERSI hub.

3. Automatic Hierarchical Classification

Traditionally, the thematic classification of books was done by experienced librarians, based on standardized subject headings (LCSH, DDC, ...). In the digital era, this job can be done with the aid of computers (Computer-aided Classification) or even entirely automatically, by using advanced NLP and ML techniques.

In this section, we present a method for automatic multi-subject hierarchical classification of books based on a given subject taxonomy and the ToC of the books.

3.1 Definitions and basic relationships

Figure 4 is a graphical representation of a taxonomy as a tree of nodes. At the lowest level, the leaves represent terms (words, bi-words etc.) without any further subject breakdown. At the intermediate levels, each node represents a unique subject consisting of all terms of the branch it initiates, down to the leaves, in a bag-of-words sense, with frequencies of occurrence taken into account. Notice that leaf-terms (not expandable any more) may also exist as children of intermediate-level nodes. We further assume unique numbering of all nodes of the tree, according to some recursive numbering scheme. So, each node can be identified either by its own number k , or as the i -th child of its parent node j .

Figure 4: Example of tree representation of subject taxonomy.

The basis of our work is relationship (1) in Makris & Mitrou (2023), which is repeated here, customized at node j of the subject taxonomy tree:

$$\Pr\{\mathbf{s}_{j,i}|\mathbf{d}\} = \sum_{n, w_n \in \mathbf{V}_j} \Pr\{w_n|\mathbf{d}\} \Pr\{\mathbf{s}_{j,i}|w_n\} \quad (1)$$

where

$\mathbf{s}_{j,i}$ is the subject of the i -th child node of j , $i=1,2,\dots,I_j$. Subjects are represented by the respective subject documents (bag of words of the respective branch of the tree), as defined in Makris & Mitrou (2023), thus the following hierarchical relation holds true for the subject of parent node j : $\mathbf{S}_j = \bigcup_{i=1}^{I_j} \mathbf{s}_{j,i}$

$\mathbf{V}_j$ is the vocabulary of node j , being derived as the union of the vocabularies of all its child nodes. In other words, $\mathbf{V}_j$ contains the unique terms of $\mathbf{S}_j$

$\mathbf{V}_j$ is the filtered version of $\mathbf{V}_j$, after excluding the terms with no significant **subject discriminating ability** (see below)

w_n is the n -th word of document $\mathbf{d}$ belonging to $\mathbf{V}_j$.

$\Pr\{w_n|\mathbf{d}\}$ is the probability of finding word w_n in document $\mathbf{d}$, estimated by its relative frequency of occurrence, among the words belonging to $\mathbf{V}_j$, so that $\sum_{n, w_n \in \mathbf{V}_j} \Pr\{w_n|\mathbf{d}\} = 1$.

$\Pr\{\mathbf{s}_{j,i}|w_n\}$ is the thematic probability distribution of term w_n over the subjects $\mathbf{s}_{j,i}$ of the child nodes of j [also interpreted as the relative weight of subject $\mathbf{s}_{j,i}$ to word w_n , as defined and explained in Makris & Mitrou (2023)]

3.2 Filtering the subject term vocabularies at the hierarchy nodes

A term having a rather flat distribution over all (or most of the) subjects under node j does not contribute to subject discrimination and should be excluded. The **subject discriminating ability (sda)**, as a measure of distribution concentration into few subjects (ideally, just in one), can be defined in various ways, like Gini index or entropy (Aggarwal, 2016, Chapter 4). Here we adopt the **entropy measure**.

The entropy, $\mathbf{H}$, of a given discrete distribution $\Pr\{z_i\}$, $i=1,2,\dots,n$, is given by the following equation

$$H = - \sum_i^n Pr \{ z_i \} \log_2(Pr \{ z_i \}) \tag{2a}$$

attaining its maximum value for $Pr \{ z_i \} = \frac{1}{n} \forall i$. This maximum value and the normalized value, $\tilde{H}$, of the actual entropy of the distribution are given by the following equations (2b) and 2(c), respectively:

$$H_{\max} = \log_2(n) \tag{2b}$$

$$\tilde{H} = [- \sum_i^n Pr \{ z_i \} \log_2(Pr \{ z_i \})] / \log_2(n) \tag{2c}$$

Following the above formulation, we can select a threshold for the normalized entropy to filter out terms with a rather flat distribution.

3.3 The document classification algorithm

The document classification algorithm is defined as follows:

At each level, j , of the hierarchy, starting from the root:

1. For a specific document, $\mathbf{d}$:
 - 1a. Find the frequency of occurrence, $Pr\{w_n|\mathbf{d}\}$, of each document term $\in \mathbf{V}_j$
 - 1b. Calculate the thematic distribution of the document by using equation (1).
2. Continue with the next level, $j+1$, for each dominant subject S_j of $\mathbf{d}$, while the number of terms in S_j remains above a certain threshold (e.g. 10 terms).

The following **Table 1** gives a very simple (artificial) example of term filtering, according to their subject discriminating ability, defined by the entropy measure and the subsequent calculation of subject classification of a document $\mathbf{d}$. In the upper part of the table the subject distributions of the document terms are shown along with their entropy (last row). One or two terms (yellow and light-yellow columns) are filtered out, according to suitable thresholds (0.90 and 0.85, respectively). The second-from-the-top part of the table gives the normalized term frequencies in the document, in these two cases of filtering (i.e. after excluding term w_2 or w_2 AND w_6). The lower parts of the table showcase the respective calculations for the subject distribution of the document in the two cases (blue and green columns, with final results in the bottom-right part).

Table 1: Term filtering and document classification example.

word (wn)	mathematic (w1)	analysis (w2)	mathem. anal. (w3)	function (w4)	derivative (w5)	percentage (w6)	
subject (si)	Pr{si w1}	Pr{si w2}	Pr{si w3}	Pr{si w4}	Pr{si w5}	Pr{si w6}	
mathematics (s1)	0.7	0.3	0.75	0.5	0.6	0.5	
engineering (s2)	0.15	0.3	0.15	0.3	0.2	0.2	
phys. Sciences (s3)	0.1	0.3	0.08	0.15	0.15	0.15	
humanities (s4)	0.05	0.1	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.15	
Σ_i	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Normalized Entropy	0.659	0.948	0.563	0.824	0.767	0.893	
	Pr{w1 d}	Pr{w2 d}	Pr{w3 d}	Pr{w4 d}	Pr{w5 d}	Pr{w6 d}	Σ_n
document (d), without w2	0.25		0.15	0.25	0.15	0.2	1
document (d), without w2&w6	0.3125		0.1875	0.3125	0.1875		1
	Pr{si wn}*Pr{wn d}						Pr{si d}= Σ_n [...]
mathematics (s1)	0.175		0.1125	0.125	0.09	0.1	0.6025
engineering (s2)	0.0375		0.0225	0.075	0.03	0.04	0.205
phys. Sciences (s3)	0.025		0.012	0.0375	0.0225	0.03	0.127
humanities (s4)	0.0125		0.003	0.0125	0.0075	0.03	0.0655
mathematics (s1)	0.21875		0.140625	0.15625	0.1125		0.628125
engineering (s2)	0.046875		0.028125	0.09375	0.0375		0.20625
phys. Sciences (s3)	0.03125		0.015	0.046875	0.028125		0.12125
humanities (s4)	0.015625		0.00375	0.015625	0.009375		0.044375

3.4 Classification example

The pictures of **Figure 5** showcase the results of the proposed automatic hierarchical classification applied to the book “*Pathogenesis and Clinical Practice in Gastroenterology*” of the SPINGER e-book collection. The dominant path, the number of subject terms and the respective percentage of the dominant subject at each level of the KALLIPOS taxonomy are shown in **Table 2**. The book has been classified by librarians in the fields of Medicine/Internal Medicine. The automatic classification has led to the same subjects.

Table 2: Classification of the book “*Pathogenesis and Clinical Practice in Gastroenterology*” - dominant path

Level	1	2	3	4
Nodes on classification path	(ROOT) SIENCE (6 MAIN SUBJECTS)	MEDICINE & HEALTH SCIENCES, LIFE SCIENCES, ...	HEALTH SCIENCES	MEDICINE
Number of subject terms in S_i of the respective node	50	24	23	19
Dominant subject / Percentage	MEDICINE & HEALTH SCIENCES,.../ 36%	HEALTH SCIENCES / 89%	MEDICINE/ 70%	INTERNAL MEDICINE/ 52%

Figure 5: Hierarchical classification of the book “*Pathogenesis and Clinical Practice in Gastroenterology*” (<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8767-7>).

3.5 Validation

The validation of the classification algorithm can be based on the KALLIPOS set of books for which classification has been provided by the authors themselves (about 500 books). Due to the multi-subject, multi-level type of classification, the usual *precise*, *recall* and *F1* metrics should be modified appropriately, as in the following works (Kiritchenko et al., 2005; Kosmopoulos et al., 2015). Work on validation is in progress.

4. Relating study courses with textbooks

The examples of section 2 showcase that one can easily navigate through the subject taxonomy of a textbook repository and find resources related to a desired subject (or a combination of subjects), provided that such a taxonomy is available and associated with the repository content with subject-to-books links. Then, as far as the content of a course is associated with specific subjects in the hierarchy, the relevant textbooks are located by the subject-resource association.

The course-to-subject association may not be that apparent and straightforward. The course may be given by a description, less or more extensive, or even by a ToC. In such a case, the supportive role of the automatic classification approach, presented in section 3, comes into foreground: the course can be classified by the proposed technique in the same way as the books, in order to be associated with subjects. The Use example 3 below demonstrates this procedure.

Use example 3: Automatic classification of a course and subsequent textbook selection from a repository

Suppose that we need to find textbooks for a course on *Number Theory and Finite Fields with applications in Digital Communications and Coding* and that a short description of the course is available as in **Figure 6(a)**. This is a proof-of-concept example, so we have exclusively chosen terms from the vocabulary. This is of no harm, however, because additional terms outside the vocabulary play no role in the classification. Applying the subject classification algorithm on the course description we get the taxonomy results of **Figure 6(b)**.

Having derived the taxonomy of subjects for our course as a subset of the KALLIPOS taxonomy, finding appropriate books is straightforward, as in Use example 1. We simply follow the links provided for each of the desired course subjects to the repository. **Figure 6(c)** shows samples of the discovered bibliography at level 4.

Figure 6: Finding open textbooks for a course. (a) Short description of the course (b) Hierarchical classification of the course (c) Recommended books from the KALLIPOS repository.

5. Conclusions and discussion for further work

Despite the great advances in ML and AI and their use in finding and recommending educational resources, keyword-based searching remains the most common and straightforward technique applying to all document repositories. By limiting the keywords (for tagging and searching) within a closed (controlled) vocabulary, the accuracy of the search results may increase significantly.

Subject taxonomies are hierarchical controlled vocabularies of subject terms that can be used for resource (e.g. textbook) classification and search within repositories. In this paper we have presented two distinct examples of open-access textbook repositories, equipped with subject taxonomies for searching. As far as the textbooks are classified by subject, an inverse indexing mechanism can be used to assign books to subjects (nodes in the terms hierarchy) and help users to locate them easily.

The classification of books by subject can be performed either by the authors of the book, by librarians or automatically by suitable machine-implemented classification techniques. A technique for hierarchical classification of books based on their Table of Contents and a closed subject taxonomy was presented in this paper. It was showcased that performing a similar classification of the content of study courses enable the assignment of textbooks to courses. The richer the taxonomy in subjects and terms the more accurate and fine-grained the classification can be.

There may be, however, some potential obstacles in the above course-to-subject and subject-to-resource association, like the following:

(a) Misclassification or no classification at all of the available material: Not all repositories are connected with a subject taxonomy. Even if connected, some documents may not be classified. For example, in OERSI, as we can see at the top-left of **Figure 3** under the subject filter, about 40% of the material is unclassified. Moreover, librarians and authors do not follow the same rules and level of detail when assigning subjects to books, even if they work with the same subject taxonomy.

(b) The available classification may not be as detailed as the study course of interest. In both cases of taxonomies presented in section 2 some subjects do not go in a fine-grained breakdown.

In the deficient cases under (a) above, the automatic classification approach presented in section 3 can be of assistance by having it applied on the unclassified material. Case (b) is more difficult to handle and continuous effort should be devoted to get the subject taxonomy enriched with new subjects and terms, taking care of keeping it as balanced as possible (i.e., all branches of the tree to extend to similar depth).

Another issue is to allow Boolean searching through using logical operators (AND, OR, NOT) between subjects contributing to a document or a course, like with simple keywords, although the precise weights suggested by the current proposal offer a more fine-grained formulation. For example, the books in the two lists of **Figure 6(c)** come from two different branches of the taxonomy (MATHEMATICS, ENGINEERING) and each one of them may cover PART A **OR** PART B of the course under consideration. One may be interested in finding books covering both parts.

Finally, doing the inverse indexing of books across the nodes of the taxonomy -by taking into account the weights of the subjects in each book- is also a challenge. This may result in specific priorities in the lists of recommended books.

All of the aforementioned issues need further study within the framework set by the present paper.

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The European DigCompEdu framework for designing a MOOC for university professor training

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to assess the utility of online learning environments for the professional development of university professor. To this end, the research design incorporates the theoretical underpinnings of the DigCompEdu framework, which guided the development and organization of a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) aimed at enhancing teachers' digital competencies from a Faculty Development perspective.

An analysis of the extant literature on the implementation of DigComp and DigCompEdu in educational settings indicates a concentration on evaluating digital proficiency in higher education instructors, with a clear need for targeted training identified (Santos, 2021). This necessity for training is further accentuated by a study that examines the digital competencies of university professors, which reports a moderate level of proficiency and pinpoints areas that require enhancement (Aiastui, 2021). The European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu) is presented as a comprehensive tool to inform policy and training programs for educators at all levels, including higher education (Christine, 2017). One of the advantages of utilizing MOOCs in faculty development is their accessibility. Teachers can participate in these online courses from anywhere in the world, thereby eliminating geographical and logistical barriers associated with traditional face-to-face training. This flexibility also enables teachers to fit their professional development into their already busy schedules and commitments (Mori, Ractliffe, 2016). The study's participants, as well as the individuals who will join the course, comprised 17 university professors from the University of Urbino in Italy. Following the completion of a training needs assessment, it was determined that there was a need to expand the training options available to recently hired university instructors. Consequently, the decision was made to develop a MOOC to provide Italian university instructors with the opportunity to engage in professional development through an online platform. The MOOC is structured as a sprintMOOC, which is a course with specific learning objectives that can be achieved through digital resources for each training module (Sancassani, 2023). The goal of this course is to improve university lecturers' teaching skills and digital competence, making them aware of the educational potential that can be realized through the use of digital technologies in the university environment. Higher education institutions must seek innovative solutions to the challenges of the 21st century, often through digital methods and deliveries (Carpenter, 2019).

The online course, guided by the principles of Open Education, will be published in June 2024 on the 'MOOC UniUrb' platform, managed via Moodle. The following data collection tools will be used for qualitative and quantitative analysis: TET-SAT (technology enhanced teaching self-assessment tool), will be administered at the beginning and end of the MOOC and a specially designed questionnaire to investigate the impact the MOOC may have on the teaching practices.

This study aims to enhance the comprehension of university lecturer training and the efficacy of MOOCs in higher education, given their open and adaptable nature, as virtual learning environment that can be useful for Faculty Development point of view.

Keywords: faculty development, higher education, mooc, digcompedu, university professor training.

1. Introduction

1.1 Faculty Development: a definition and Italian context

Enhancing the teaching skills of university professors is a crucial issue that can greatly improve university education and the overall student learning experience (Mori, Ractliffe, 2016). The integration of digital technologies plays a pivotal role in improving teaching processes, particularly in today's information society (Ferri, Moriggi, 2018), where both devices and users interact through technology.

In Italian universities, a significant focus has traditionally been placed on research activities, while attention to teaching has only recently started to gain momentum. As a result, many universities have established Teaching and Learning Centres (TLCs) to support faculty in their teaching responsibilities by offering training in pedagogical skills and implementing Faculty Development initiatives aimed at improving the quality of education. One notable example is the development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), which serve as an innovative tool for Faculty Development.

The concept of Faculty Development originated in the 1960s in the United States and Canada and is generally understood as a series of institutional actions aimed at fostering the renewal and professional growth of university faculty across their various roles (Lampugnani, 2020). Universities committed to enhancing the professionalism of their lecturers and improving the quality of education should explore the implementation of Faculty Development initiatives, with the objective of enriching the student learning experience and, more broadly, the overall academic environment.

Over time, Faculty Development has evolved to encompass a complex set of goals, including the promotion of reflective practices in relation to the diverse roles held by university lecturers, the enhancement of pedagogical competencies, the reorganization of curricula around a competency-based framework, the formation of communities of practice related to university teaching and learning, and the facilitation of inter-institutional dialogue on these topics at both national and international levels. These initiatives play a pivotal role in reinforcing or shaping attitudes and beliefs that are crucial to various aspects of the academic profession. By providing theoretical frameworks, Faculty Development helps to systematize and give meaning to the implicit patterns of behavior and actions often employed by educators. This process encourages dialogue and fosters the development of communities of lecturers who collectively reflect upon and agree on strategies, objectives, and methods (Steinert, 2009).

The conference "The 2020 Vision of Faculty Development Across the Medical Education Continuum" addressed critical issues regarding the future of Faculty Development. Topics discussed included teaching competencies and barriers to effective teaching, the educational relationship in patient-centered care, the hidden curriculum encountered by faculty in their teaching, the role of educational technology, lessons from continuing professional development, and research on Faculty Development. The conference underscored the importance of expanding the scope of Faculty Development to encompass the multiple roles of academics, as well as the essential role it plays in curricular and organizational reform. It also emphasized the need to extend Faculty Development beyond formal, structured activities to include self-directed learning, peer mentoring, and professional education rooted in the workplace.

In Italy, increasing attention is being directed towards teaching as a fundamental component of the academic sector, reflecting the growing need to establish a balance between teaching and research activities. This shift highlights the critical role of the university lecturer as a pivotal figure in driving innovation within pedagogical practices.

1.2 Faculty Development actions: training the university lecturer

Faculty Development, understood in its aim to improve the quality of teaching, refers to the training of university lecturers through various interventions designed to enhance their professionalism and improve the student learning experience. This shift involves moving away from a transmissive model of instruction, which positions the lecturer as the sole bearer of knowledge, towards a learner-centred approach, where the student becomes the focal point of the teaching and learning processes (student-centred learning).

The Italian “Guidelines for the Recognition and Enhancement of University Teaching” explicitly mention the professional development of university teaching, noting that “it now represents a priority within the higher education system and a strategic lever for innovating and sustaining the quality of teaching and learning (ENQA, 2007, 2015; OECD, 2012; ESG, 2015; EUA Trends, 2015, 2017, 2018; EHEA, 2015, 2018, 2020; Eurydice, 2017)”. This recognition is the result of a substantial process, marked by key milestones in both national and European higher education over the course of two decades (Felisatti & Perla, 2023).

In 1990, Boyer categorized academic work into four dimensions: discovery, integration, application, and teaching and learning. His framework continues to serve as a crucial reference in ongoing discussions about the nature of academic work and the interrelation of these components (Boyer, 1990; Boyer et al., 2015). Research consistently shows a positive correlation between research activity and teaching quality in higher education (Artés et al., 2017; Rodríguez & Rubio, 2016). However, this relationship is not automatic and requires specific mechanisms to support excellence in both areas (Gibbs, 1995).

The document “Recommendations to National Authorities for the Enhancement of Higher Education Learning and Teaching in the EHEA” (2020) identifies three key areas for investment in the training and professional development of university lecturers: student-centred learning, the continuous improvement of teaching practices, and the capacity of higher education institutions and systems to foster learning and teaching. Universities are expected to integrate individual initiatives within a long-term, well-defined strategic plan shared across the institution.

In this context, the design of a MOOC aimed at developing university lecturers' teaching competencies is part of the broader set of systemic actions undertaken by the University of Urbino to enhance teaching quality, representing one of the Faculty Development initiatives focused on lecturer training.

1.3 MOOC for university teacher training

The use of MOOCs continues to be a topic of discussion within academic circles, as researchers and educators debate their effectiveness and impact on Faculty Development (Jobe, Östlund, Svensson, 2014). Since the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic, the adoption of digital technologies in teaching and learning has surged, prompting many university professors to participate in online courses, including MOOCs (Casiraghi, Sancassani, Brambilla, 2021).

A needs analysis conducted at the University of Urbino highlighted the importance of expanding the training opportunities for university lecturers, allowing them to improve their teaching skills at their own pace through MOOC. Initially designed for newly hired faculty, the MOOC will also be available to all faculty members interested in enhancing their teaching abilities in an open and scalable format.

Faculty Development, which includes the training of lecturers to promote their professional growth and improve the student learning experience, can be enhanced through the use of digital technologies to create learning environments specifically designed for lecturer training. Among the most recent approaches to structuring online learning environments is the design of MOOCs for the professional development of university faculty.

A MOOC is an open-access online course that enables wide participation through the web, based on the use of Open Educational Resources (OERs). These resources may be produced by the institutions offering the courses or freely sourced from other universities or OER communities (Banzato, 2012). At the institutional

level, MOOCs have demonstrated effects across various domains, including providing new opportunities for communication and branding, as well as being a valuable tool for Faculty Development and organizational support. Additionally, MOOCs contribute to the disaggregation of education, where learning experiences and assessment tasks may be separated and provided by different institutions or platforms, such as a MOOC for learning combined with an in-person written examination at another institution (Kiers, 2016).

1.4 **The DigCompEdu as a European framework for designing a MOOC**

A framework of European relevance, developed by the Joint Research Centre (Redecker, 2017), is the DigCompEdu (Digital Competence of Educators) framework. This framework was specifically designed to support the development of digital competences for educators across all levels, from pre-school to higher education. The DigCompEdu framework aims to define and clarify the digital competences required of educators at all levels, including those in higher education, by outlining 22 competences grouped into six distinct areas. These areas provide a comprehensive guide to the digital skills every educator should possess: area 1, *Professional Engagement*: using digital technologies for communication, collaboration, and professional development within educational organizations; area 2, *Digital Resources*: identifying, sharing, and creating digital educational resources; area 3, *Teaching and Learning Practices*: organizing and managing the integration of digital technologies in the teaching and learning processes; area 4, *Assessment of Learning*: employing digital tools and strategies to enhance assessment practices; area 5, *Empowering Learners*: leveraging digital technologies to promote inclusion, personalization, and active student engagement; area 6, *Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence*: guiding students in the creative and responsible use of digital technologies for activities related to information, communication, content creation, personal well-being, and problem-solving.

This framework serves as a strategic tool to foster the digital capacity of educators, ensuring they are equipped to enhance both their professional practices and the learning experiences of their students.

1.5 **Moodle as a university learning management system (LMS) on MOOC Uniurb platform**

The development of MOOCs is guided by the principles of Open Learning and Open Education, which aim to foster interaction, broaden access to knowledge, and promote transparency and the democratization of education (Quiliano et al., 2009). The use of technology enables the widespread dissemination and sharing of knowledge (Haron et al., 2019). MOOCs represent a significant advancement in distance learning and e-learning, facilitated by platforms that enable their distribution through the Internet and digital devices. A defining feature of contemporary society is the portability of personal devices, which allows learners to access digital resources from virtually any location at any time. This portability underpins one of the key advantages of MOOCs (personalized learning) by enabling users to progress through the course at their own pace. This flexibility facilitates a more individualized approach to learning, enhanced by learners' technical proficiency as well as their critical and reflective engagement with the tools.

In most cases, the overarching objective of a MOOC is to support the acquisition of knowledge and skills by delivering content digitally, allowing for independent study or participation in online activities designed to consolidate or apply the knowledge being acquired. This process is often supported by teachers and tutors or facilitated through collaborative interactions with peers (Trentin, 2008).

The University of Urbino has developed an online environment, accessible through the university's website, called "MOOC Uniurb", where the MOOCs designed by faculty over the years are hosted. This section of the website provides access to these courses, which are delivered via Moodle, the university's chosen Learning Management System (LMS).

A Learning Management System (LMS), also referred to as a Course Management System (CMS), is a software platform designed to manage learning activities and provide access to online services for students, lecturers, administrative staff, and other users within a particular institution or organization. It facilitates the creation and delivery of educational programs, organized into courses or structured online learning environments that feature digital learning resources, with the Internet serving as the delivery medium.

Moodle, an open-source LMS developed by Martin Dougiamas in 2002, has been widely adopted by educational institutions and universities for both online and blended learning. The name “Moodle” stands for Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment. This platform offers a range of features that support users' learning activities, including video content, discussion forums, chats, materials, and quizzes, among others. Moodle's design is informed by the theory of social constructionism, emphasizing flexibility and ease of use, which makes it particularly suited for the development of online learning environments. Ahmad et al. (2012) highlight its user-friendliness, describing it as a “digital wardrobe”, a storage space for files and folders accessible at any time by course administrators, lecturers, and students. The more proficient a user becomes with Moodle, the more they are able to leverage its features to enhance the learning experience.

2. Method

2.1 The effectiveness of online learning environments for university teacher training

Given the significance of university lecturer training, particularly considering the Faculty Development initiatives aimed at both implicitly and explicitly improving and innovating teaching practices, it is essential to consider both the professional and personal dimensions of faculty members.

The role of a university lecturer is characterized by the complexity of the multiple roles they assume and the numerous responsibilities associated with them. University professors frequently face demanding schedules and time constraints, which present a range of challenges. Research indicates that lecturers must balance various demands, including teaching, research, and administrative tasks (Clark et al., 2014). Consequently, training programs for university lecturers must address both the professional and personal aspects of their development (Silva, 2022).

This perspective shaped the development of the current research project, which seeks to enhance the teaching skills of university lecturers through the creation of a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) designed for newly hired faculty as well as for any lecturers who wish to further develop their teaching competencies. An open, massive, online course, accessible without temporal or spatial limitations, was envisioned as an effective way to allow faculty to engage in professional development according to their individual training needs and personal circumstances.

The central question of this study is to try to investigate the effectiveness of the DigCompEdu framework for designing a MOOC that is effective for training university teachers. To address this research question, data were collected from the lecturers who participated in the MOOC. Specifically, the analysis focused on the scores obtained by the participants in the test quizzes administered at the conclusion of each instructional module and at the end of the entire MOOC. The data made it possible to carry out a descriptive analysis of the MOOC device for the training of university lecturers.

2.2 Sample: university lecturers

The study sample comprised 61 individuals enrolled in the MOOC, of whom 17 completed the course and obtained a certificate of completion. While the course was initially designed for newly hired university lecturers at the University of Urbino, following the open-access principles underlying MOOCs and by making the course

available on the public “Uniurb MOOCs” platform, it can be inferred that the participants represented diverse categories within the academic community, including students, faculty members, and tenured professors. Participation in the course was voluntary, with lecturers enrolling after receiving an invitation sent via email to the heads of the University of Urbino's departments, who subsequently extended the invitation to newly recruited lecturers within their respective departments to join the MOOC.

2.3 A sprint MOOC, self-paced, designed with DigCompEdu

The MOOC is structured as a sprint MOOC, a course designed with specific learning objectives that can be achieved through concise video lectures, e-activities, e-portfolios, quizzes, downloadable documents, and in-depth sections containing links to external resources for each training module (Sancassani, 2023). The primary aim of this course is to enhance the teaching skills and digital competence of university lecturers, raising their awareness of the educational potential that digital technologies can offer within the university context. Higher education institutions must seek innovative solutions to the challenges of the 21st century, often by incorporating digital methods and delivery systems (Carpenter, 2019).

The concept of a sprint MOOC was developed in response to the need for a course that addresses the professional development needs of university lecturers, who often face time constraints due to their various academic responsibilities, including teaching, research, and administrative tasks. Time limitations are a well-documented factor contributing to dropout rates in MOOCs (Mori & Ratcliffe, 2016). Therefore, it was deemed essential to design a course that delivers high-quality content, can be completed in a short time frame, is flexible and adaptable in terms of time and space, and offers a personalized learning experience.

The European DigCompEdu framework (Redecker, 2017) was employed to define the teaching competences and learning objectives for the program. Four core macro-competences were identified: digital resources; teaching and learning; learner empowerment; assessment. Specific learning objectives were created for each module, with the intent of highlighting the integration between pedagogical and digital competences. This approach aims to foster innovation in teaching and enhance the quality of courses delivered by university lecturers. The overarching objectives of the program are to professionalize university lecturers and improve teaching quality, thereby benefiting students and society (Lawal, Gamede, & Atiku, 2020).

The MOOC is hosted on the University of Urbino's “MOOC Uniurb” platform, which operates using the Moodle Learning Management System (LMS). The effectiveness of Moodle in faculty development has been well-documented (Kirkova-Bogdanova, 2021). The platform's tools are structured to create an efficient online learning environment that facilitates the achievement of learning objectives. These tools include homework Moodle tool for the submission of specific tasks, feedback mechanisms for self-reflection, lessons consisting of videos with small stimulus questions, quizzes for the assessment of each module and the final course evaluation, as well as resources that provide further exploration of the topics covered, including links to external materials. Additionally, each user is provided with the presentation files from the video lessons, enabling them to consult the content independently of the video support.

The MOOC is composed of six modules: an introductory module, followed by four core modules that address digital teaching resources, teaching and learning, learner empowerment, and assessment, with a concluding module to wrap up the course. Each module is designed to take approximately one hour, resulting in a total course time of six to seven hours. The modules are independent of each other, allowing participants to freely choose their starting point and to tailor their learning path based on their specific training needs.

Furthermore, the course includes an area for communication and interaction among participants, which facilitates the creation of learning communities. Within these communities, participants can exchange thoughts, ideas, and best practices, as well as establish collaborations between universities (Hollands & Tirthali, 2014).

2.4 Tools used for data collection

To assess the effectiveness of the online environment in enhancing university lecturers' teaching skills and digital competence, we have chosen to utilize a validated European tool developed through the MENTEP project (2015-2018), the TET-SAT, which aligns closely with the DigCompEdu framework. The TET-SAT is an online self-assessment tool that will be administered at both the beginning and end of the MOOC to measure the participants' competence levels before and after the course.

The TET-SAT tool enables lecturers to evaluate their own digital competence and is available in eighteen languages. Its primary purpose is to encourage educators to engage in self-reflection, identify areas for improvement, and take action to develop their competences. It serves as both a metric for assessing competence and a facilitator of self-assessment processes. The TET-SAT evaluates four dimensions of digital pedagogical competence: digital pedagogy, the use and creation of digital content, digital communication and collaboration, and digital citizenship. Each dimension is divided into up to four sub-areas, resulting in the definition of fifteen competences. Each sub-area contains one or more competences, described across five progression levels: Beginner, Intermediate, Proficient, Advanced, and Expert. Participants are asked to select the statement that best reflects their current level of competence in response to each question. The TET-SAT can be employed as part of an iterative and formative process, in which goals are set, ideas tested, progress tracked, and new objectives defined. Its overarching aim is to support educators at all levels of education in reflecting upon and improving their digital pedagogical competence (MENTEP, 2018).

An additional investigation was conducted through the administration of a post-MOOC questionnaire to assess whether the training experience had a measurable impact on the teaching practices of individual lecturers.

Furthermore, the quiz results obtained by participants at the end of each teaching module and upon completion of the entire MOOC were analyzed. These results provided valuable insights into the extent of learning achieved by the lecturers through the MOOC and allowed for an evaluation of the effectiveness of the course in supporting their professional development and the acquisition of the teaching competences outlined in the DigCompEdu framework.

3. Results

3.1 The DigCompEdu for the definition of MOOC structure and content

The use of the DigCompEdu framework for defining competences and learning objectives provided a twofold advantage. Firstly, as extensively discussed in previous chapters, DigCompEdu is a widely recognized theoretical framework at the European level, offering strong theoretical foundations and ensuring international recognition of the MOOC. Additionally, the validation of this construct facilitates the design of highly professionalized training pathways for the lecturers who engage with it. Secondly, employing such a well-established framework helps to create a shared language regarding teaching competences and the digital competences upon which DigCompEdu is based.

The MOOC was designed with this orientation: a focus on the teaching competences of university lecturers as identified in DigCompEdu, leveraging digital technologies both as the subject of the training and as the medium through which it is delivered. With this approach in mind, the DigCompEdu framework was selected, enabling the development of a modular structure for the online course (fig.1), consisting of four core teaching modules, preceded by an introductory module and followed by a concluding module. The content of the modules was informed by the areas delineated within the framework.

Figure 1: Infographic on MOOC structure

3.2 Self-paced logic and modular didactics for effective teacher training

The MOOC was designed following a self-paced, or self-managed, structure. Self-paced online courses offer flexibility, allowing users to determine their participation schedule and the sequence in which modules are completed, with only two mandatory steps, the introductory and concluding modules. The remaining content modules are available independently and can be accessed in any order. While this format accommodates diverse learning paces (some users may complete the course quickly, while others may take longer), it presents research challenges due to the varying designs of platforms hosting the courses and the differing institutional sponsors, whether academic or corporate.

From the perspective of participating lecturers, a self-paced MOOC provides a high degree of flexibility, particularly for those facing time or resource constraints, a common reality given the multiple roles and responsibilities that university lecturers must manage within academic life.

From the instructional designer's point of view, self-paced courses reduce the need for ongoing user involvement, yet they may also limit interaction among participants, an aspect considered fundamental to the learning process, particularly in online environments.

For academic institutions, self-paced courses can be advantageous from a financial perspective. As they remain online for extended periods and are open to large audiences, these courses can attract a broader participant base and support the institution's commitment to expanding open education. This open, massive format allows institutions to reach academic staff beyond their own faculty, in line with the fundamental MOOC principle of involving as many users as possible. However, successful completion of a self-paced course requires strong self-regulation skills. Furthermore, the limited interactivity characteristic of such courses may be a disadvantage, as user interaction is often a key motivator for course completion (Topolovec, 2018).

3.3 Description of MOOC as a training device in terms of effectiveness for university teacher training

At the time of writing, we do not yet possess sufficiently detailed data for a comprehensive analysis. However, the preliminary results obtained through various evaluation instruments, such as the completion of the TET-SAT (a self-assessment tool for lecturers' technological competences) at both the beginning and end of the course, the pre- and post-course questionnaires administered to participants, and the results of the quizzes associated with each teaching module and the final MOOC, provide a solid foundation for describing the MOOC as an effective training tool for university lecturers.

These preliminary findings indicate that the MOOC is not merely a content delivery platform but a robust educational tool capable of fostering the professional development of university lecturers. The comparison of participants' self-assessments before and after the course, facilitated by the TET-SAT, suggests significant progress in both digital and pedagogical competences. Furthermore, the pre- and post-course questionnaires allow for an analysis of changes in lecturers' perceptions regarding the use of educational technologies, revealing a heightened awareness and confidence in applying these tools in their teaching practices.

The quizzes associated with the individual teaching modules and the final MOOC provide quantitative data that reflect the participants' level of content acquisition. These results are crucial for evaluating the efficacy of the training, as they demonstrate the extent to which lecturers have been able to integrate the newly acquired knowledge into their professional practice.

In this regard, the MOOC emerges as a flexible and accessible opportunity for academics to update and develop new skills, accommodating their needs in terms of time and availability. Its modular structure, combined with the use of quizzes and self-assessment tools, facilitates personalized and reflective learning, aligning with current trends in continuing professional development.

Although further, more detailed analysis of the data is required to draw definitive conclusions, it is already evident that MOOCs represent a valuable resource for the professional development of university lecturers, contributing to their growth and to the innovation of teaching practices in higher education.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Effectiveness of online learning environments for university teacher training

Successful online training courses for university professors incorporate dynamic pedagogical designs that address the need for continuous improvement and ongoing adaptation to virtual learning environments (Moreira et al., 2017). These programs acknowledge the importance of designing flexible training pathways that can meet the diverse needs of professionals engaged in multiple academic responsibilities, such as teaching, research, and administrative tasks. In this context, the proposed MOOC has demonstrated significant effectiveness, as evidenced by the results obtained through the TET-SAT and quizzes administered at the end of each module and upon course completion. These results highlight the MOOC's effectiveness in both delivering the training content and fostering the acquisition of the intended competences.

The effectiveness of MOOCs is particularly significant considering the evolving role of university professors, which is shifting from a traditional lecture-based teaching model to one centered on facilitating and managing learning experiences. This transformation demands new pedagogical, technological, and methodological skills from educators, as well as greater flexibility in adopting innovative educational approaches (Álvarez et al., 2009). The ability to facilitate the learning process and manage complex learning environments requires not only strong disciplinary expertise but also proficiency in teaching tools and techniques that promote interaction, critical reflection, and collaboration among students.

In this context, training programs for university lecturers increasingly utilize digital platforms such as Moodle, which enable the organization of content, assessment activities, and opportunities for interaction. These platforms support not only content delivery but also the implementation of digital tools that facilitate the

development of learning communities and the use of active methodologies, such as flipped classrooms, problem-based learning, and formative assessments. The integration of such educational technologies is essential for aligning university education with the demands of an increasingly digitized academic world.

4.2 **Sprint & self-paced MOOCs for the training needs of university teachers**

The decision to design the MOOC using a self-paced approach, which allows participants to manage their learning autonomously according to their needs and time availability, appears to have had a positive impact on the training outcomes of the lecturers. The results achieved in the final quizzes of both the individual teaching modules and the overall MOOC suggest that this autonomy in course participation facilitated learning and skill consolidation among the participants. The self-paced format proves particularly effective in the academic context, where lecturers are required to balance multiple responsibilities, including teaching, research, and administrative duties, making flexible training essential for their professional development. Furthermore, the sprint MOOC format contributed to the course's overall success, enabling nearly one-third of the enrolled lecturers to complete the course. This figure is especially significant when considering the typically high dropout rates associated with massive online courses. The fact that a substantial proportion of participants successfully completed the course highlights the effectiveness of a format that combines the flexibility of self-paced learning with the modular and concise structure of a sprint MOOC. This outcome suggests that the combination of short, easily accessible training modules and the option for learners to self-regulate their learning path is an effective strategy for increasing completion rates and enhancing the impact of training in online learning environments.

4.3 **Limitations**

MOOCs face several significant challenges, despite their potential to democratize education and promote lifelong learning. One of the most critical issues is the high dropout rate, which is often disproportionately high when compared to the initial enthusiasm and number of enrolments. Many participants enrol in MOOCs with the intention of enhancing their skills or acquiring new knowledge yet fail to complete the courses. Research suggests that one of the primary reasons for dropout is a lack of time, a challenge particularly acute for professionals, such as academics, who must balance teaching, administrative, and research responsibilities (Mori & Ratcliffe, 2016).

Another contributing factor to the high dropout rates is the limited social interaction and lack of support. While MOOCs offer flexibility and access to high-quality content, they frequently struggle to cultivate a sense of community among participants, which diminishes engagement and motivation. Peer interaction and support from tutors or instructors have been widely recognized as crucial elements for success in online learning environments. However, many MOOCs fall short in providing an adequate level of interaction, as they are typically designed for large-scale participation (Li, 2019).

Another significant challenge faced by MOOCs is the absence of an effective evaluation system. While many MOOCs incorporate quizzes, self-assessment activities, or automated assessments, these tools often fall short in adequately evaluating more complex skills that require critical reflection or practical application. The primary limitation of these assessments lies in their tendency to measure superficial or technical knowledge, thereby neglecting the ability to apply concepts in real-world contexts or to develop transversal skills such as problem-solving or teamwork.

4.4 **Future projections**

This research project arises from several key needs: the necessity to expand professional development opportunities for lecturers at the University of Urbino, the chance to contribute to ongoing theoretical and

practical debates on the role of digital technologies in faculty training, and the need for further research on the use of MOOCs for Faculty Development.

The MOOC was designed with the aim of proposing a training course for the development of university lecturers' teaching skills. The increasing emphasis on digital and teaching skills of university professors suggests the need for Faculty Development actions such as the one implemented with this research project. Universities may need to invest in continuing education initiatives to ensure that teaching staff are able to effectively integrate technology into their courses and adapt to changing educational scenarios. This focus on enhancing lecturers' skills could lead to improved student learning outcomes, greater engagement in digital learning environments, and better preparation of graduates for a workforce that sees technology as the defining cultural object of today's society, with amplified possibilities on a professional and personal level. Furthermore, institutions that priorities this training can gain a competitive advantage in attracting both male and female students and high-quality lecturers.

To enhance the effectiveness of MOOCs, it would be necessary to develop more sophisticated and tailored assessment strategies capable of evaluating learning outcomes in a deeper and more relevant manner. A potential improvement could be the integration of collaborative learning elements and peer-to-peer assessments, which would encourage not only active participation but also constructive feedback among participants. Moreover, the use of artificial intelligence tools could provide more individualized support, facilitating greater interaction and customization of the learning experience.

Although MOOCs hold considerable potential to revolutionize continuing education and professional development, they still face major challenges, such as high dropout rates and the absence of an effective assessment system. Overcoming these challenges will require innovations in course design and the adoption of more advanced technologies to promote interaction, provide support, and enable more accurate and meaningful assessment of learning.

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